

The Relationship and Impact of Multidimensionality TQM and Innovation on Organisational Performance: In the context of the Bangladesh Garments Industry

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to seek the impact and relationship of TQM and Innovation techniques on organisational performance in Bangladesh garment manufacturing organisations. This paper presents a conceptual approach for investigating different research hypotheses where multiple models are tested under structural equation modelling (SEM). The survey data were obtained following purposive sample questionnaires from 25 garment manufacturing organisations with a response of 371 participants. In addition, fifteen 'face-to-face' semi-structured interviews were collected, and a thematic framework matrix approach was used to analyse. Therefore, the research was conducted using mixed-method concurrent triangulation.

The analysis of the qualitative research on the RMG indicates all aspects of TQM and innovation substantially impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. The quantitative data output demonstrated that administrative Innovation had no significant impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance, but technological Innovation significantly impacted. Conversely, the quantitative data output showed only mechanistic TQM significantly impacts on organisational performance. In addition, organic TQM uses mechanistic TQM as a mediator to significantly impact on organisational performance while having no direct impact on administrative or technological Innovation. The mechanistic TQM significantly impacts on administrative Innovation but is insignificant on technological innovation. In addition, organic TQM mediates mechanistic TQM to significantly impact on financial and non-financial performance. Therefore, quantitative analysis showed a complex relationship between quality management and Innovation. So, two different models have emerged following qualitative and quantitative data analysis, which may help the RMG organisation to identify how quality and innovation impacts on RMG organisations. Furthermore, from the perspective of RMG manufacturing, this study contributes a novel theoretical, managerial, and empirical contribution to the global subject of TQM and Innovation.

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Glossary of Terms

This research is specific to a particular sector. Therefore, some terms used by the researcher must be defined to ensure a proper understanding of the study.

The following terms are defined as follows:

TQM: a philosophy that seeks to integrate all organisational functions to meet customer needs and corporate objectives.

BGMEA: Bangladesh Garments Manufacturers and Exporters Association (BGMEA) is the apex trade body representing the country's export-oriented garment manufacturers and exporters.

RMG: Readymade Garment is the leading garments manufacturing sector of Bangladesh.

Quota policy: a temporary agreement to protect their domestic garment industries from the onslaught of cheap imports from low-wage countries.

Multi-Fiber Arrangement (MFA): MFA is an international trade agreement on textile and clothing that imposes quotas on the amount that developing countries can export in yarn, fabric, and apparel to developed countries.

EU Generalized System of Preferences (GSP): GSP is a formal system whereby a wide range of industrial and agricultural products originating, in particular, developing countries, are given preferential access to the markets of the developed country.

Total Quality Management (TQM) is a standardised quality management philosophy.

Organic/Soft QM (OGQ): Organic quality management elements are HRM dimensions concerned with TQM's social and behavioural aspects.

Mechanistic/Hard QM (MCQ): Mechanistic practices address the use of quality management systems and improvement technologies to enhance and support the application of soft techniques.

Balance Score Card (BSC): BSC is an organisational performance measurement system that includes a broad range of financial and non-financial performance indicators.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA): CFA is a multivariate statistical procedure used to test how well the measured variables represent the number of constructs.

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA): EFA is a statistical method used to uncover the underlying structure of a relatively large set of variables.

Average Variance Extracted (AVE): AVE measures the amount of variance captured by a construct concerning the amount of variance due to measurement error.

Composite Reliability (CR): CR is a measure of the internal consistency of scale items.

Comparative Fit Index (CFI): CFI analyses the model fit by examining the discrepancy between the data and the hypothesized model.

Normed Fit Index (NFI): NFI is an incremental measure of goodness of fit for the statistical model without affecting the number of variables in the model.

Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Background of the Bangladesh Garment Industry

Bangladesh accounts for around 20% of the industry's annual growth rate in the section of clothing. About 78% of export earnings are carried by Bangladesh Readymade Garments Management (RGM) sector (Ahmed, 2009). Meanwhile, 4.2 million people are employed in this sector, around 4,490 factories which capture 50% of the employment from the total of Bangladesh employment sectors (Seddiqe and Basak, 2014). According to Rahman (2001), the Bangladeshi labour cost is cheaper compared to the other competitors in the garments sector. Therefore, Bangladesh's garments industry is more labour intensive and does not employ the same levels of technology and quality. Although the garment sector is the country's largest revenue-earning sector, the labour cost is just 0.4 dollars per hour (Seddiqe and Basak, 2014). So, the Bangladeshi RMG organization prioritized cutting costs other than quality and innovative productivity. However, the growth rate of the Bangladesh garments industry is very significant because of some government privileges and opportunities to enter the market, such as Multi-Fiber Arrangement (MFA), quota-free, and EU Generalized System of Preferences (GSP). According to Seddiqe and Basak (2014), the Bangladesh garments industry is performing in the sectors of cutting, making, and trimming. However, in the apparel sector, Bangladesh is performing less well than its competitors in the market. According to Yunus and Yamagata (2012), the RMG industry of Bangladesh takes the maximum lead time to process an order which varies between 90 – 120 days. However, for similar products, Sri Lanka takes 19 – 40 days, China 40 – 50 days, and India 50 – 70 days. So, it shows that the delivery lead time is more than their competitors, and it negatively impacts on business. The country's economy relies heavily on the Ready Made Garment (RMG) industry. It generates almost four million direct jobs. This sector also contributes about 78.6% of the country's export revenues (Chowdhury and Quaddus, 2015). The RMG sector also contributes to lowering the country's high percentage of female unemployment, as 80 % of garment workers are female (Chowdhury and Quaddus, 2015). Bangladesh is also frequently scored as the world's second-largest garment exporter. Despite its enormous potential, the business is affected by many factors, one of which is supply chain disruption (Islam and Deegan, 2008; Haider, 2007). The costs of disruptions are enormous; for example, Bangladesh's RMG business loses millions of dollars daily due to issues in supply chain functions induced by political instability. Furthermore, preferential access to the US market has been revoked due to a lack of safety standards in manufacturing plants after the Rana-Plaza

garments factory collapsed in the capital city, Dhaka, which resulted in the deaths of over a thousand workers. These disruptions affect all members of the supply chain network, including worldwide customers (retail chains) and suppliers (Chowdhury and Quaddus, 2015). Bangladesh is a major exporter of readymade garments (RMG) globally. Bangladesh's RMG industry is a significant economic driver, with garment exports total of 19.90 billion US dollars in 2011, making the country the second-largest garment exporter. The convenient and efficient operation of supply chain operations is essential due to the tremendous economic relevance of RMG in Bangladesh's economy. However, several challenges, including labour unrest over human rights violations, low wages, a poor and hazardous working environment, political instability, disruptions in utility supply, particularly power shortages, inefficiency in customs and port management, exchange rate fluctuations, strict compliance code regarding social and environmental issues, and disruptions in timely supply of fabrics and other accessories, are causing the RMG to reach a breaking point said by Chowdhury and Quaddus (2015), and Islam and Deegan (2008). The smaller economy and external risks and dangers are a barrier to the RMG business, and these essential variables are hindering economic growth and business improvement for Bangladesh. According to Ansary and Barua (2015), Bangladesh has tremendous opportunities to capitalize despite barriers. Bangladesh can attract high-quality Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) for development and progress. Therefore, product variety, process, and service improvements are essential to meet client needs. With limited resources, Bangladesh has maintained an average annual GDP growth rate of 6%. The RMG business has become a prominent industry with the highest export earning capability. This sector accounted for 83 % of the country's overall export revenues In MY 2017/18, totaling approximately \$30.61 billion in 2017/18 fiscal year (Fibre2fashion.com, 2021).

The number of garment factories in the country is growing faster and steadily. Bangladesh had 4482 factories in MY 2016/17, which grew by 3.10 % to 4621 factories in May 2018/19. From May 2018/19 to May 2020/21, it is predicted to grow from 1.53 percent to the total number of 4764 factories. As a global supply hub, the country's garment industry emphasises compliance and environmental sustainability. The number of green factories in Bangladesh is steadily expanding and has surpassed 100. Between 2014 and 2018, the cost of producing garments in the country grew by 30%. In addition, from December 2018, the minimum pay for garment workers has increased by 51% (Fibre2fashion.com, 2021).

The total Bangladesh RMG exports were 28,149.84 million dollars in May 2016/17, with an increment of 26.90 percent to 35,724.33 million dollars in May 2018/19. Overall exports rose

16.69 percent year over year in May 2018/19 and are expected to reach 38,984.92 million dollars in May 2020/21 with a compound annual growth rate (CARG) of 12.65 percent from May 2018/19 (Fibre2fashion.com, 2021). Total exports rose 15.40 % year over year in May 2018/19, with a CAGR of 11.22 percent from May 2018/19 to 19,105.35 million dollars in May 2020/21. Total woven exports were 14,392.59 million dollars in May 2016/17, but they increased by 23.69 % to 17,801.89 million dollars in May 2018/19. Total knit garments exports grew 30.28 % to 17,922.44 million dollars in May 2018/19 from 13,757.25 million dollars in May 2016/17. Total exports rose 18 % year over year in May 2018/19 and are expected to reach 19,879.57 million dollars in May 2020/21 with a 14.14 % CAGR from May 2018/19 (Fibre2fashion.com, 2021). RMG exports in non-traditional markets declined in May 2019/20 due to trade tensions between China and the United States and the falling price trend of raw materials, mainly cotton and yarn. According to the Export Promotion Bureau (EPB), China began importing from Bangladesh in the early months of the current fiscal year 2021 after the Chinese government provided duty-free access to over 5,000 Bangladeshi items. Bangladeshi garment exports in India also grew (Fibre2fashion.com, 2021). This chapter gives an overview of the rationale and purpose of this study, research aims, objectives, and questions, a synopsis of the literature review, methodology, research originality, and a short description of all chapters.

1.2 Problem Statement and Purpose of the Study

It is recognised that business is a vital issue for the economic development of any country. Generally, manufacturing organisation plays an essential role in developing the economy. It was mentioned earlier that 78% of the export earnings of Bangladesh are carried by the RMG sector (Seddiqe and Basak, 2014). However, the RMG sector has frequently faced external and internal threats from regulatory bodies and stakeholders. There are about 1,200 employees died, and more than 3000 injured after the building collapsed (Rana Plaza) in the capital city, Dhaka. After the incident, Wal-Mart and H&M stopped doing business in Bangladesh. The western media published the news highlighting the issues of quality management, corporate social responsibility, employee rights, and health and safety violated in Bangladesh's garments sector (Ansary and Barua, 2015). There are additional issues such as the vulnerable supply chain management, political instability (Ahmed *et al.*, 2014), lack of social management capabilities to handle the stakeholders' pressure (Huq *et al.*, 2016), buyer's and supplier's responses, lack of skilled employees, employee's dissatisfaction for lower payment from the marginal level of wages (Zhang *et al.*, 2014), health and safety issues, improper building and place selection for factories, lack of technology, inequality among the employees, and lack of quality management are

affecting the progression for this business sector. According to Seddiqe and Basak (2014), Bangladesh is the cheapest labour country in the world, approximately equivalent to \$0.4 per hour. Hence, organisations follow a cost-cutting strategy while quality management practices and innovative strategies for sustainable growth in the world market are not being valued. The smaller economy and external threats are the challenges for Bangladesh. According to Hossan *et al.* (2012), organisations rely on products, processes, and formulation patents to safeguard their innovations as the competition becomes more patent-intensive. Therefore, being innovative for the organization is very important to cope with the flexible global business environment.

In developed countries, especially in the first world, TQM has been introduced and practiced early as a quality management tool. Business competition among organizations is raising because of technological advancement and innovation practices. Therefore, Bangladesh is getting in touch with globalized business completions due to technological advancement. Organizations are more aware of how to cope with global competition. The concept of TQM and innovation practices are not being practiced thoroughly for sustainable business development (Mamun and Islam, 2002). Bangladesh has dropped from its 2nd to 5th position in 2017 from its global garments exporting position. Studies have been carried out on a few Bangladeshi organizations that accepted TQM, but none of the research has been carried out on the multi-dimensional view of TQM practices and innovation performance in the RMG sector or any of the other industry sectors in Bangladesh (Mamun and Islam, 2002; Akhter, 2014). According to Sundbo *et al.* (2015), products, processes, services, and technological Innovation are strategically vital to make the organization competitive and sustainable in the competitive market. According to Salavou *et al.* (2004), organisational Innovation is a strategic direction and structure of competition for any organization. Therefore, the impact of TQM and innovation practices and their relationship is one of the unique factors for sustainable business performance. Considering the above issues, this study will focus on examining the impact of TQM and innovation practices and their relationship based on the performance of the RMG industry in Bangladesh.

1.3 Research Aim

This research project aims to examine the impact of multi-dimensionality TQM and innovation practices on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Finally, this study examines the relationship between TQM and Innovation on the organisational performance in Bangladesh Garments Industry.

1.4 Research Objectives

- To identify the impact of TQM (organic and mechanistic quality management) on organisational performance in the Bangladesh Garments industry.
- To examine the impact of Innovation (Administrative and Technological) on organisational performance in the Bangladesh Garments industry.
- To examine the relationship between TQM and Innovation on organisational performance.

1.5 Research Questions

- What is the impact of TQM (organic and mechanistic aspect) practices on organisational performance in the Bangladesh Garments industry?
- What is the impact of Innovation (Administrative and Technological aspect) practices on organisational performance in the Bangladesh Garments industry?
- What is the relationship between TQM and Innovation on organisational performance?

1.6 Indicative areas of Literature Review

The readymade garments sectors are the highest exporting business in Bangladesh. Therefore, the garments industry plays a significant role in the Bangladesh economy. However, the potential demand for Bangladeshi garment products is reducing in the global market due to not maintaining sustainable quality and innovativeness in products, processes, and services (Chowdhury and Quaddus, 2015). According to Terziovski and Samson (1999), a well-organized quality management concept helps an organization maintain continued growth and long-term business outcomes. Zeng *et al.* (2015) split TQM into two categories, such as the Total Quality Control (TQC) process, which concerns quality standards. In contrast, the Total Quality Learning (TQL) is workforce development oriented. As a multi-dimensional view, Burns and Stalker (1961), and Prajogo and Sohal (2004) identified that the TQM is divided into two perspectives: mechanistic and organic. According to Terziovski and Samson (1999), most organisations today are assessing their competitive skills and management practices intending to expand business outcomes and gain a favourable position by facing fierce competition in a dynamic business environment. Enterprises aim to create, implement, and manage TQM procedures, apart from a staffing shortage and the requirement to sustain performance. Prajogo and Sohal (2004) defined

organic quality management is based on staff skills growth, which fosters creativity, while mechanistic quality management emphasizes on quality performance on the task. In today's globalized and highly competitive marketplaces, evaluating organisational performance has become a critical component in the formulation of the organisation's strategies. The practice of quantifying the efficiency and effectiveness of production systems is known as performance evaluation. According to Fernandes *et al.* (2014), organisations are facing challenges in meeting the customers' demands because of the business environment, flexible economy, and technological changes across the globe. The changes are increasing customer's demand which forces the organisation to introduce new strategies coping up with the situation. Thus Fernandes *et al.* (2014) defined that the management quality and innovation strategy influence the organization to be competitive.

Innovation is essential for developing unique products and services, increasing core competencies, and establishing barriers to entry for new competitors. As a result, many scholars have been interested in identifying the variables that drive Innovation. One of the questions that have been considered is whether total quality management (TQM) practices may emerge as one of the requirements for developing innovation strategies. There is no consensus in the literature about whether Innovation generates conditions for implementing TQM practices or whether TQM helps to build an environment and a culture that supports Innovation (Antunes *et al.*, 2017). Innovation can substantially impact on the organisation's performance by providing a stronger position in the market resulting in a competitive advantage. As a result, this study aimed to investigate the relationship and impact of Innovation and TQM on organisational performance. Several writers, including Prajogo and Sohal (2001), and Martnez-Costa and Martnez-Lorente (2008), have studied this relationship and its impact on organisational performance. The importance of Innovation is enormous to achieve economic competitiveness over competitors (Terziovski and Samson, 1999). Innovation opens the path to generating new ideas and processes. It helps to accept the changes and grab opportunities quickly. Therefore, Innovation develops a competitive tendency to compete sooner against competitors (Prajogo and Sohal, 2003).

According to Prajogo and Sohal (2003), Innovation and TQM are some of the major developments in management practices where TQM is recognized as a competitive advantage across the globe, especially in western countries. Though TQM has been criticized for its failure, empirical studies have found a strong relationship between TQM and organization performance (Terziovski and Samson, 1999; Prajogo and Sohal, 2003). To get sustainable competitive

advantages, Innovation has a key impact on the organisation (Prajogo and Sohal, 2003). Therefore, organizations in developing countries should consider Innovation as an economic plan (Ooi *et al.*, 012). Thus, as a developing country, Bangladesh should consider innovation practices by the organization. One of the fundamental reasons for successful economic and social development is the operation of the manufacturing industries (Zeng *et al.*, 2015). Thus, Innovation secures sustainable competitive advantages by securing the problems from a flexible market environment (Antunes *et al.*, 2017). Several scholars such as Terziovski and Samson (1999), Prajogo and Sohal (2003), Feng *et al.* (2006), and Antunes *et al.* (2017) have investigated the relationship and impacts of TQM and Innovation on organisational performance across developed countries but not the substantial research has carried out on the context of developing countries (Ooi *et al.*, 2012). Hence, this study is focused on the need to identify the impact and relationship of TQM and innovation practices on the organisational financial and non-financial performance of the RMG industry in Bangladesh.

1.7 Indicative Research Design

According to Saunders *et al.* (2012), appropriate philosophical choices are necessary to accomplish successful entrepreneurship research. Therefore, the researcher needs to consider the right philosophical approaches to ensure the quality of management research (Gray, 2009; Kumar, 2014). According to Saunders *et al.* (2012), there is an inescapable discussion on ontology and epistemology for selecting between positivist and interpretivist philosophical assumptions or quantitative and qualitative approaches by the researchers. However, Teddlie and Tashakkori (2009) proposed a multi-dimensional data collection strategy for the impractical practice of philosophical methods where researchers' best option is to accept the pragmatist viewpoint. It is necessary to understand how managers manage, how organisational change occurs, how micro-politics work, and how staff relationships are formed and sustained to conduct an effective social scientific study (Watson, 2011). This study aims to identify the impact of TQM (soft and hard aspects) and Innovation on the business performance of the Bangladesh RMG industry. Simultaneously, the relationship between TQM and Innovation is examined on business performance by analyzing both subjective and objective complex issues. According to Tashakkori and Teddlie (2010), pragmatism under the epistemological philosophy deals with complex issues, and management employees' thoughts and beliefs are considered by the researcher to get a deeper insight into real-life experiences. This study uses qualitative and quantitative data collection simultaneously and independently. Hence, positivism and interpretivism are used under pragmatic philosophy. According to Creswell (2011), using

quantitative and qualitative methods in a single study is better for understanding the research problem. Similarly, Tashakkori and Teddlie (2010) defined that mixed method concurrent triangulation design consists of two distinct phases, which are quantitative and qualitative.

The data was collected from the Bangladesh RMG industries and analyzed separately. The data result was compared to bring the impact of TQM and innovations and their relationship on RMG business. So, Mixed method concurrent triangulation is the justified research method for this study. According to Saunders *et al.* (2018), moving from theory to data is the common characteristic of the deductive approach, and data to theory is the inductive approach, but an abductive approach moves back and more, as the abductive approach combines both deductive and inductive. According to Charmaz (2014), abduction begins with observing a surprising fact and then working out a possible theory on how this could have occurred. To find the actual facts and credible data, the researcher followed both quantitative and qualitative methods for data collection and analysis, which allowed the researcher to find and collect any credible data or information at any stage in the research process under the abductive approach. According to Saunders *et al.* (2012), abduction is the superior logic for testing credible theories at any stage of the research process. According to Saunders *et al.* (2012), the cross-sectional study is time-constrained and mostly prefers a survey strategy. Therefore, the quantitative data of the cross-sectional elements is applied. However, the research includes qualitative interviews to ensure that a deeper understanding of the research topics is explored. According to Saunders *et al.* (2012), cross-sectional could also be the choice for qualitative or multiple research strategies based on the short length of the period. Therefore, cross-sectional studies are employed for this research as the qualitative interview would be conducted alongside the quantitative survey. Structural equation modeling is used to analyses the quantitative data, and thematic framework matrix analysis are used to bring qualitative outcomes.

1.8 Theoretical development and time frame

The theoretical structure and time frame help the researcher to highlight a study notion because of the brief discussion of the entire research activity. The research is divided into six chapters. In chapter one, the researcher explained the research context, the study's purpose, the investigation's goal, the research methodology, and a portion of the literature review. Then numerous concepts and models related to the research issue are examined, such as Total Quality Management, Innovation, performance assessment, and the relationship between them. The hypotheses are created, and the conceptual foundation also has been developed in this

chapter two. In chapter three, the researcher discussed the research methodology, tools, and strategies used to conduct the study. This chapter also discusses quantitative and qualitative questionnaires. Then, the researcher obtained quantitative and qualitative data and analysed the findings and outcomes in this chapter four. In chapter five, qualitative and quantitative data discussions were carried out following the research objectives. In chapter six, a comparative discussion is carried out based on quantitative and qualitative outcomes. In addition, the research contribution, recommendations, limits, and conclusion are discussed in chapter six. This chapter also includes the researcher's reflections on the research project.

1.9 Originality and contribution to Knowledge

This section examines the thesis's originality and the contribution of this study to knowledge in the domain. Originality is a very valid and important criterion for evaluating academic scholarship. According to Guetzkow et al. (2004), to make the research original, the researcher might satisfy the following criteria: a new approach, a theory, and a method that can be used. Other requirements may include researching a new issue, conducting research in an understudied area, or presenting fresh discoveries. Phillips and Pugh (2010) outlined fifteen different parameters to make research original. From those, this research can be denoted as original based on providing single original technique and competent piece of research following the parameters iv. The parameter x defined that the research has conducted elsewhere but first in the context of any country. This research also used mixed method concurrent triangulation which not been significantly carried out before in this context. Parameter xiii defined that research can be original being cross-disciplinary and using different methodologies. Also, parameter xiv defined that research can be original looking at an area not previously explored in a particular discipline (Phillips and Pugh, 2010). To justify originality, the above points can be linked up as this research has not been conducted in the context of Bangladesh before. It should be noted that this research is performed in the specific context of the Bangladesh garment industry. Most similar types of research have been conducted using quantitative techniques, but this research has covered both questionnaire and interview techniques to understand the real phenomenon in this area. Hence, this research satisfies the criteria of an original piece of work, followed by the above statements of Phillips and Pugh (2010).

Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.0 Introduction

The industry is mostly using or planning to use total quality management (TQM) for better performance. However, having a high enthusiasm or passion for adopting TQM is not enough to assure the success of the TQM strategy in every organisational environment. Organisations must embed a quality culture in their key values and use quality to gain a competitive edge. Many businesses in a variety of sectors use or aim to employ Total Quality Management (TQM). However, having a strong desire to implement TQM is not enough to ensure the success of the TQM approach from every organisational perspective. Organizations must set a quality culture in their core principles and leverage quality to create a competitive advantage. Global competitiveness presents both obstacles and possibilities for the Bangladesh garments industry. As a result, Bangladeshi organisations must be able to develop circumstances conducive to meeting the difficulties. Therefore, innovative strategies must be employed to strengthen their position in the home and foreign markets. Research helps establish a guideline that can be employed in the organisation's strategy to achieve the desired outcome. A thorough review of research publications on TQM and innovation practices indicated that research studies examined soft and hard TQM, and administrative and technological innovation practices have relationships with organisational performance (Zeng *et al.*, 2015). Hence, the correlation between TQM and innovation practices and their impact on organisational performance in the Bangladesh Garments industry has been focused on in the literature review for this research task.

2.1 Total Quality Management

TQM is viewed as a business excellence model (Alanazi, 2021; Fonseca, 2021). Several models, including the Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award (MBNQA) model, were established in the US in 1987 to promote quality awareness and practices. The European Foundation for Quality Management (EFQM) model was founded in Europe in 1994 to recognise and promote sustainable success and offer guidance. Furthermore, the king Abdul Aziz Quality Award (KAQA) model was introduced in Saudi Arabia in 2007 to encourage organisations to adopt the principles of total quality and raise standards in tandem with international competition. Those models are acknowledged as global best practises despite displaying differences in terms of their criteria due to their respective representation of differing cultural, economic, or social dynamics, Leadership, strategic planning, people resources, suppliers and partners, operations

management, beneficiary focus, measurement analysis, knowledge management, social responsibilities, and business performance are just a few of the characteristics that have been used to compare the models (Alanazi, 2021). The models also cover the management direction, including the purpose, vision, and strategy; the execution of the creation, including sustainable value, the driving of performance and transformation, the participation of stakeholders; and the outcomes, including stakeholders' views, strategic and operational performance of TQM (Fonseca, 2021). TQM is a comprehensive management strategy that consists of a system of tools, practises, and training for continuous improvement. It is used to manage businesses in an environment that is constantly changing in order to ensure customer satisfaction, boost success, and decrease failure rates through quality and teamwork (Ali and Johl, 2021; Haffar *et al.*, 2021; Jevanesan *et al.*, 2021).

According to Mayo (2014), TQM has its roots in 1945. The modern TQM demonstrated that employee participation in decision-making improves productivity, igniting interest in continuous improvement. Shewhart (1931; cited in Mayo, 2014) developed statistical control charts in the 1930s as a mechanism for understanding variation and developing strategies for improvement on a larger scale. The philosophical foundations of Shewhart's continuous improvement process influenced the development of the plan-do-check-act (PDCA) cycle in the 1950s, also known as the Shewhart cycle or Deming (1986) and subsequently revised to the plan-do-study-act (PDSA) cycle because 'check' prioritised inspection over analysis. This had a significant impact on Japanese management practise, which resulted in the creation of a company-wide quality control philosophy referred to as total quality control (TQC) in the 1960s and propelling Japan into a world quality leader in the 1970s (Ishikawa, 1985). TQM, a term first used by the American company Navel Air Systems in the 1980s, was based on the TQC of the Japanese (McDaniel & Doherty, 1990). The literature search and study conducted by Martnez-Lorente *et al.* (1998) support the idea that the word TQM was first used in the 1980s and only later became widely accepted as a term and practice associated with quality in the 1990s. Nowadays, TQM and its offshoots like ISO, Kaizen, and Six Sigma are widely used and implemented throughout various nations, sectors of industry, and organisations worldwide (van Kemenade, 2021). According to de Permana *et al.* (2021), TQM evolved in the 1980s, following its predecessor's total quality control (TQC), which emerged in the 1960s, quality assurance (QA), which emerged in the 1950s, quality control (QC), which emerged in the 1920s, and quality inspection (QI), which appeared in the 1900s. Jasti *et al.* (2021a) stated that TQM could be licensed and approved. According to van Kemenade (2021), TQM is guided by four paradigms, such as empirical, which

is the conformance to requirements, values accountability, and accuracy; reflective, which is quality as an event, values professionalism, and wisdom; reference, which is fitness for use, values success and improvement; and emergence, which is quality in dynamic and unpredictable, values flexibility, and willingness to change. In today's competitive business environment, businesses depend on adopting a quality plan. Various authors have defined TQM in a variety of ways. TQM is a method for continually improving the quality of goods and services offered by involving employees at all levels and activities of an organisation. It mainly refers to striving for excellence, as well as developing the necessary approaches and controls to prevent defects or errors and improve customer satisfaction through enhanced efficiency and effectiveness. TQM is a company-wide initiative that all employees must implement. TQM has also been viewed as a collection of processes that represent an organisation's dynamic behaviour. A company is considered a socio-technological system if the operations took out meeting customer needs while maintaining efficiency and effectiveness. The company's viability is being tracked throughout the whole business cycle. The principles of TQM are based on the quest for advancement and ongoing development in terms of cost, dependability, quality, Innovation, efficiency, and commercial effectiveness. TQM has been defined by organisations as the fully integrated efforts of organisational members to gain a competitive edge by continuously improving all aspects of organisational culture (Lakhe and Mohanty, 1995). It is acknowledged that TQM was proposed as a plan for the next millennium as a corporate management philosophy. TQM's philosophy assists businesses in reforming their business operations in order to attain higher-quality productivity and competitiveness in the market (Mehra *et al.*, 2001; Samson and Terziovski, 1999; Zhang, 2000).

Increased levels of competition in the global marketplace have resulted that quality is being increasingly important to organisations, as a result, TQM has become a critical management issue at present. Many businesses use TQM, which has been the subject of several academic publications and studies. At the end of the 21st century, TQM became a widely recognised management philosophy for most successful organisations. However, the word was not used TQM two decades ago (Martinez-Lorente *et al.*, 1998). Therefore, before delving into the history of TQM, it is important to look at specific definitions of the word because practically every writer on the subject has an independent definition, which is usually tailored to their ideas, prejudices, and commercial and academic experiences. This is also the same in organisations that have used a TQM approach to business management. As a result, there is a profusion of distinct definitions, which confuses comparisons and complicates understanding and analysis. Even

though ISO 8402 published an international definition of TQM, there is enough evidence that authors and researchers do not adhere to this concept and instead build their unique offerings (Martinez-Lorente *et al.*, 1998). Hackman and Wageman (1995) point out, a wide range of actions unrelated to TQM are being included under the TQM umbrella, thus complicating definition and comprehension. Despite differing perspectives on what defines TQM, there are certain similar aspects that run across the numerous definitions, for example, top management support, customer and supplier relationships, and employee involvement. Several authors, including Ahire *et al.* (1996), Dale *et al.* (1994), Flynn *et al.* (1994), and Saraph *et al.* (1994), have attempted to identify the various characteristics that shape TQM. The researcher analyses the standard dimensions for TQM on both soft and hard elements. The two key contributions towards the Innovation in TQM are a comparative comparison of the Japanese approach to quality management and Feigenbaum's sixty-one idea of comprehensive quality control (Martinez-Lorente *et al.*, 1998). Notably, this perspective on TQM proposes that TQM consists of both soft and hard aspects. The soft aspects of TQM assessment elements are evaluation, reward, and recognition system; customer focus; employee empowerment; employee involvement; employee knowledge and education; employee recommendations; employee training and learning; environmental uncertainty; human resource management, recognition, and collaboration; knowledge management; leadership and top management commitment; operations and process emphasis; organisation trust; people management. Conversely, the hard criteria or practises of TQM are benchmarking, computer-based technologies, concurrent engineering, continuous improvement, cross-functional product design, feedback, housekeeping, just-in-time, partnership and resources, product and process management and control, product and service design, quality information, quality management tools and techniques, statistical process control, and technology utilisation (Ali and Johl, 2021). Other widely used methods for continuous improvement include ISO 9001, Kaizen, and Six Sigma (Fonseca, 2021; Jevanesan *et al.*, 2021); meanwhile, widely used performance metrics include benchmarking, balance scorecard, and service quality tools (Jasti *et al.*, 2021b). Noteworthy is the fact that TQM is a concept continuously developing in line with market realities like Industry 4.0, which is the fusion of technology, quality, and people management (de Souza *et al.*, 2021; Sader *et al.*, 2021).

A variety of factors influence TQM adoption and practice. On the one hand, its enablers include employee commitment and readiness for change (e.g., organizational members' self-efficacy, skills, and perceptions of change benefits, personal benefits, and management support),

leadership (e.g., top management commitment, strategy, style, support and vision), organizational culture (e.g., adhocracy, hierarchy, group, and market culture), staff engagement (e.g., motivation, participation, empowerment, and support), and technological advancement (e.g., Industry 4.0) (Haffar *et al.*, 2021; Jevanesan *et al.*, 2021). Similarly, in the approach to TQM implementation, its conceptual barriers include a lack of clarity for achieving objectives, the target customers, the interpretation of quality concepts, and a lack of knowledge and resources for evaluating, improving, and managing quality performance. Its organizational barriers include insufficient leadership, resources, and resistance to change. The operational barriers include customer diversity, a lack of formal processes, improper selection of TQM models or misuse of tools and techniques, inability to differentiate and adapt TQM models, and inadequate performance measurement (Jasti *et al.*, 2021a; Karamouz *et al.*, 2020; Permana *et al.*, 2021). TQM adoption and practise have been shown to produce a number of positive outcomes. First, TQM improves customer satisfaction which is consistent with TQM's primary goal (Jasti *et al.*, 2021b; Jevanesan *et al.*, 2021; Permana *et al.*, 2021). Second, TQM improves organisational performance in areas, such as cost reduction, engagement and communication, decision-making, procurement, and production. TQM also improves process efficiency (batch size, product quality, production time, and lead time), Innovation (research and development), profitability (profit margin and net profit), return on asset and investment (ratio and growth rate), sales (net sales and growth rate), resource management, safety, and service quality (Dieste *et al.*, 2021; Jevanesan *et al.*, 2021; Permana *et al.*, 2021; Sader *et al.*, 2021). Third, TQM improves employee productivity by improving motivation, empowerment, and work-satisfaction (Jasti *et al.*, 2021b; Jevanesan *et al.*, 2021; Permana *et al.*, 2021). Fourth, TQM can lead to scalability in organizational operations (e.g., logistics) and revenue (e.g., sales) when aligned with technological advancement, for example, industry 4.0 technologies (Sader *et al.*, 2021).

TQM is called a management philosophy that is customer and quality-focused, practices a set of Quality management tools developed in the USA and successfully implemented in Japan (Render and Heizer 1999; Slack 2016). There are fourteen points defined by quality expert Deming (1986) to follow the TQM approach. Later, modifications have gone through on all those points. Heizer and Render (2000) defined six elements of TQM tools: continuous improvement, employee empowerment, benchmarking, just-in-time, taguchi concepts, and knowledge of QM tools. Employee empowerment entails involving employees in all stages of the production process through the development of communication networks, open and supportive supervisors, and sharing responsibilities among all employees that contribute to the development of

organizational performance, including organising teamwork and managing the quality process. People, equipment, suppliers, materials, and process management are part of continuous improvement activities. Continuous improvement activities are also referred to as zero defects and six Sigma in the United States. Benchmarking is a series of actions that must be followed, such as the benchmarking team determining what and how to benchmark. It's also important to find benchmarking partners, gather and analyse benchmarking data, and take steps against the data outcomes to fill the gap and enhance organisational performance. Quality is linked to the Just-In-Time philosophy in three ways: JIT lowers quality costs by exposing poor quality, quickly identifying scrap, rework, inventory investment, and damage costs. JIT improves quality by reducing lead times, storing evidence of errors, and limiting the number of potential sources of errors, among other things. Lower inventory cost helps to improve quality products, ensure higher quality, and improve organisational performance. There are three aspects in the Taguchi concept, such as quality robustness, removal of the consequences, and lower cost than addressing the causes (Taguchi loss function). It states that minor differences in material and technique do not degrade the product quality of the final goods. Conversely, the quality loss function ensures high-quality products, whereas target-oriented quality is a philosophy of continual improvement that keeps the product on track. Lastly, the knowledge of TQM tools, including check sheets, scatter diagrams, Pareto charts, flow charts, and statistical process control, must be taught to all staff (Heizer and Render, 2000). Several researchers have defined that the Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award (MBNQA) has served as the basic model of TQM with six quality tools practices such as leadership, strategic planning, customer focus, information analysis, people management, and process management (Choi and Eboch, 1998; Prajogo and Sohal, 2003; Jung and Wang, 2006; Prajogo and Hong, 2008). In addition, Samson and Terziovski (1999) defined that performance management is also an important TQM element besides the six tools. Similarly, the Deming prize covers the following criteria such as corporate policy, organisation and administration, education, implementation in specific departments, the effect of total quality control of products quality, and others like profit, delivery, safety, costs, and finally, companies intend to carry the cost of Total Quality Control (TQC) programmes.

Heizer and Render (2000) defined that specific components need to be followed to make a successful TQM environment in the organisation, such as understanding the customer (internal and external), understanding the business (functional analysis, quality cost), knowing about quality management system (as BS5750, ISO900, AQAP), continuous quality improvement (as management commitment, employee involvement, education, teamwork, measurement, error

prevention) and understanding about quality tools (as statistical process control, benchmarking and problem-solving). According to Zhang (2000), authors such as Deming (1986), Juran and Gryna (1993), Feigenbaum (1991), Crosby (1979), and others have produced quality management concepts throughout the last few decades. So, quality management describes an improved understanding of the fundamentals of quality issues. The Deming Prize (1992) in Japan, the European Quality Award (Award, 1994), and the Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award (Award, 1997) in the United States are just a few examples of quality awards accepted and utilised in management around the world. Each prize is based on a TQM model, which has been perceived by considering a wide variety of management activities, behaviour, and procedures that influence the quality of the final offerings rather than focusing exclusively on product or service excellence. These award models serve as a valuable audit or evaluation framework for firms to evaluate their quality management procedures and end-to-end business outcomes to meet the customer's requirement, error-free performance (do it right and first time), continuously improving the quality, which is known as Kaizen (doing things better, little by little, all the time) in Japan. The TQM philosophy also relies upon a series of problem analysis tools related to statistical process control, such as diagrams, Pareto, histograms, and flowcharts (Zeng *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, following a detailed examination of the QM literature from quality gurus, the three quality award models, and other existing TQM literature, the following TQM performance measurement scales such as leadership, supplier quality management, customers quality management, strategic vision, quality planning process, evaluation, process control, process improvement, product design, quality system improvement, and employee participation are highlighted to be the most important (Zhang, 2000). The TQM activity model is also defined into ten aspects where quality management elements specified as supplier improvement, process control and improvement, internal customer focus, measurement and reporting, leadership, quality system, participation, recognition, education and training, and external customer focus (Mann and Kehoe, 1994).

In addition, Mahmood *et al.* (2014) identified various TQM dimensions for assessing an organization's quality profile with a extensive review on literature from several scholars and found that TQM have used 27 different essential quality management assessment elements or conceptions those are top management support, quality information availability, quality information usage, management benchmarking, strategic quality planning, employee training, employee involvement, process and product design, supplier quality management, corporate quality culture, strategic quality management, customer orientation, process management,

quality improvement system, the role of the quality department, internal quality results, external quality results, strategic project control usages, employee empowerment, product quality, supplier performance, operational quality planning, supervision or monitoring, external interface management, quality citizenship, quality policy, and technology utilization (Mahmood *et al.*, 2014). However, Mahmood *et al.* (2014) integrated all the twenty-seven elements and designed TQM as nine dimensions in line with the concept of Saraph *et al.* (1989). On this perspective, Flynn *et al.* (1994) identified seven TQM dimensions and twelve TQM dimensions identified by Ahire *et al.* (1996), ten TQM dimensions were determined by Black and Porter (1996), and seven TQM dimensions were determined by Zeitz *et al.* (1997). TQM has been defined with eleven dimensions by Joseph *et al.* (1999). Similarly, TQM can be measured following 13 different elements described by Rao *et al.* (1999). Based on the TQM practices by notable scholars, Kanapathy (2008) has selected the eight most common reasonable criteria, such as management support, availability of quality information, usage of data, staff training, employee involvement, product or process design, supplier quality, and customer orientation. Laszlo (1996) noted that the application of TQM varies by the type of organization and region. So, successful TQM instances cannot be copied and followed as permanent elements. The quality award concept, particularly those created for many countries and regions, can only be used as a suggestion rather than a model for dealing with problems (Laszlo, 1996). In the context of Bangladesh, the RMG Company is experiencing both soft and hard parts of quality management challenges. Health and safety concerns, inadequate infrastructure, a lack of employee expertise, a lack of negotiating abilities, lower productivity, lower product quality, a lack of teamwork, lack of market analysis and benchmarking are all obstacles for Bangladesh's RMG company (Zeng *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, corporate social responsibility is included as a TQM measurement element beside the other twelve measuring elements: top management commitment, employee suggestion, small group problem solving, task-related training for employees, supplier quality management, customer orientation, strategic quality planning, process management, preventive maintenance, housekeeping, quality Information, and benchmarking. So, altogether thirteen different elements are used to measure the TQM performance considering the quality management cultural context of Bangladesh and matching with the frequency of using the tools by the quality management scholars, such as Deming (1986), Crosby (1979), Juran, and Gryna (1993), Feigenbaum (1991), Kanapathy (2008), Mann and Kehoe (1994), Zhang (2000), Saraph *et al.* (1989), Ahire *et al.* (1996), Zeitz *et al.* (1997), Joseph *et al.* (1999), Laszlo (1996), and Heizer and Render (2000) in both organic and mechanistic aspects as it called multidimensional (Zeng *et al.*, 2015).

2.2 Multidimensional view of TQM

The multidimensionality of TQM has been presented as a theoretical foundation by several researchers (Sitkin *et al.*, 1994; Watson and Korukonda, 1995; Moreno-Luzon and Peris, 1998; Lau and Anderson, 1998). However, the presence of a multidimensional view of quality management in several terms is identified in the subject areas such as Quality control (QC), quality assurance (QA), total quality control (TQC), company-wide quality control, total quality management (TQM), and strategic quality management. Among those, TQM and QA (quality assurance) are the appropriate structures for evaluating the multidimensional nature of quality management from these many terminologies. The appropriateness of these terminologies is valued concerning the focus on management control systems and products to ensure predetermined requirements. In contrast, it focuses on human aspects such as management and employee involvement, training, learning, and internal cooperation or teamwork (Moreno-Luzon and Peris, 1998). Kekale and Kekale (1995) believed that the organic learning approach and the TQM technique are related. When contrasting a cognitive system that priorities soft qualitative attributes like organic management style, delegated responsibility, and autonomy with the behavioristic techniques of quality management practices, such as systematic measurement, work control, standards, and statistical methods. Watson and Korukonda (1995) reviewed the relative position of certain TQM aspects and identified the challenge of distinguishing between organic and mechanistic components. Watson and Korukonda (1995) also found complexity to allow theoretical discoveries and conceptual clarity of TQM. TQM proponents, on the other hand, are less enthused about explaining TQM's mechanistic elements than its organic ones. Critics made that the mechanistic aspect of TQM impacts passivity, subordination, and suppression of free will. Simultaneously, failing to acknowledge those would be equal to disobeying certain fundamental TQM principles.

In addition, Prajogo and Sohal (2001) assert that evaluating the TQM duality due to its mechanistic and organic aspect is essential to understand the scholar's debates about the relationship between Innovation and total quality management. In this instance, Sitkin *et al.* (1994) developed a theoretical foundation for establishing a correlation between multidimensional TQM and Innovation. Sitkin *et al.* (1994) argued that organisations could use two separate aims and methods following two different approaches, such as Total Quality Control (TQC) and Total Quality Learning (TQL) under the same fundamental of TQM aspects. In this aspect, TQM emphasizes quality by conformity when relating to a regulation-oriented or mechanistic paradigm and so seems to fulfill all negative objections about its connection with

Innovation. In contrast, TQM and an organic model are both more linked to Innovation. In the literature on Innovation, an organic component has long been identified as vital in developing Innovation. In comparison, total quality learning sets a focus on the development of new abilities, the appraisal of unique creative paths, and other creative activities (Burns and Stalker, 1961). The effects of each dimension of total quality management on performance were evaluated independently in empirical research that focused on the correlation between TQM and organisational performance. The output showed that the specific elements of organic TQM (i.e., "human factors" like employee commitment, teamwork, and motivation) support organisational success and organic TQM serves a positive impact on organisational performance (Dow *et al.*, 1999; Samson and Terziovski, 1999; Powell, 1995; Rahman, 2001). According to Ahire *et al.* (1996), in order to bring the TQM output, management first needs to establish an atmosphere in which hard TQM can be seamlessly diffused and implemented, and the second is to directly affect organisations' performance in the same way that standard human resource management (HRM) methods may impact the organisation. According to Rahman and Bullock (2005), past efforts to figure out the links between TQM indicators and organisational performance were insufficient. Hence, Rahman and Bullock (2005) provide a more logical strategy for studying these links in their research and found that soft and hard TQM both influence organisational performance, which is in line with the outcome found by Hart and Schlesinger (1991), Bowen and Lawler (1992), and Kochan *et al.* (1995).

Wilkinson (1992) was the first to recognize that TQM has both hard and soft aspects that correlate to various circumstances. Hard TQM is commonly associated with the tools and procedures required for quality improvement, which include a wide range of production technologies such as statistical process control, organisational activities, just-in-time delivery, and fundamental quality control tools (Thiagaragan *et al.*, 2001). The earlier studies focused on hard elements because the hard TQM analysis is more systematic and quantitative than soft TQM analysis. However, soft factors are critical and need time-consuming inputs and control on it (Habtoor, 2016). For the effective adoption of quality management systems, Powell (1995) stated that soft TQM is more beneficial than hard TQM. On the other hand, Lewis *et al.* (2006) used an analytic hierarchy process (AHP) to discover that hard TQM methods, such as systematic development for continuous improvement and process management, are increasingly prevalent in modern organizations. According to Rahman and Bullock (2005), both soft and hard TQM have a favourable influence on organisational performance. Thiagarajan and Zairi (1997) proposed that hard TQM can help soft TQM. Despite these significant contributions, there is a

general lack of understanding of the soft factor system's hierarchy and the significance of its many components. Quality was described as delighting a client by constantly satisfying and continually enhancing customers' expectations (Kriemadis *et al.*, 2021). Quality is the sustainable improvement of an organisational prolonged systematic process. Thus, TQM may be characterized as a system approach with the goal of increasing a company's value by continually improving its systems and processes. To truly adopt TQM, a corporation must employ both its mechanistic and organic parts. The mechanistic aspects of quality are the systems, tools, and processes used in its operations, while the organic elements are mostly linked with the firm's human attitudes and increased values. The following contexts are the categorization of quality factors into four broad perspectives such as top management dedication (organizational strategy), analyze the gaps (systems and techniques-QMS), system installation (appraisal and feedback), and Continuous enhancement (cultural changes) (Lewis *et al.*, 2006). Adopting and using soft and hard TQM elements may establish the groundwork for enhancing a company's operations and supporting total quality implementation. To achieve market sustainability, a firm must incorporate both hard and soft components, such as focusing on consumers and accurately assessing their satisfaction level, proper strategic guidance from senior management, negotiation and train up employees, customers, and supplier support (Gremyr *et al.*, 2021; Mas-Machuca *et al.*, 2021). The mechanistic aspect of TQM is broadly discussed in the following section.

2.3 Mechanistic aspects of TQM elements

TQM is concerned with analytical and technical issues and emphasises regulating processes and products using proper tools and techniques to meet optimum organisational standards (Zeng *et al.*, 2015). Hard TQM methods involve process management, error detection and prevention, housekeeping, and benchmarking (Hadid *et al.*, 2016). Also, it may include quality management and statistical process control improvement tools and systems (Alkhaldi and Abdallah, 2021). Hard aspects address the use of quality management systems and improvement technologies to enhance and support the application of soft practices (Abdallah, 2013; Lewis *et al.*, 2006). Similarly, according to Wilkinson (1992) and Ho *et al.* (2001), Hard TQM techniques are more technical and tool focused. These approaches include using tools like the design process, statistical process control (SPC), and quality function deployment. According to Zeng *et al.* (2014), the practice of managing processes and products via the use of tools and procedures in order to cover and comply with preset standards is known as the hard aspect of quality management. Hard elements are regarded as management tangible elements (Gadenne and

Sharma, 2009). There are six major hard TQM practices analyzed, such as continuous improvement and innovation, information and performance measures, process management, strategic planning, process control, and product and service design (Lewis *et al.*, 2006). Also, quality Information, product and service design, and process management as the hard TQM practices are consistent with the hard perspective of the seven standard practices that were looked at in empirical studies of quality management (Zeng *et al.*, 2015). The operations-related performance, such as productivity, product quality, and customer satisfaction are referred to as operational performance in enterprises (Feng *et al.*, 2006), where the operational performance was examined using quality and inventory management aspect (Alkhaldi and Abdallah, 2021; Terziovski, 1999). There are now ten constructs used to measure operational performance, including customer satisfaction, besides the six constructions used to evaluate quality performance. Better product or service quality, higher output, reduced defect and rework costs, quicker consumer delivery lead times, less customer complaints, higher customer satisfaction scores, and fewer warranty claims are all examples of quality performance. Similarly, Inventory management performance is measured by buying material turnover, total inventory turnover, and decreased inventory obsolescence costs (Terziovski, 1999; Alkhaldi and Abdallah, 2021). TQM is defined as an integrated strategy or philosophy that attempts to meet or exceed customer expectations by continually improving product and service quality (Prajogo and Sohal, 2006). Continuous improvement is the notion that progress ongoing process, so businesses must constantly work to improve all aspects of their operations to make performance a dynamic target that competitors find challenging to replicate or surpass (Abdallah, 2013). Management actions, such as customer focus increased quality knowledge, and management engagement helps to improve quality in all aspects (Adam *et al.*, 1997). Continuous process improvement may reduce scrap and rework costs, control waste and variance, and enhance productivity and lead time (Kaynak, 2003). The TQM strategy focuses on process control to guarantee that processes run as planned and are often accomplished using statistical instruments. It entails the use of a control chart, the expense of poor quality such as rework, scrap, and warranty charges, and the provision of information about areas that require improvement (Ho *et al.*, 1999). The term process refers to the mix of machinery, tools, procedures, materials, and the people involved in the manufacturing process (Montgomery *et al.*, 2000). Process management focuses on controlling the manufacturing process so that it runs as intended by the management to change and enhance the manufacturing processes, which would necessarily improve overall quality performance (Abdallah, 2013). It also focuses on developing almost error-free procedures, a steady production schedule, and work distribution (Flynn *et al.*, 1995).

Quality tools and processes were termed hard TQM aspects, including flow charts, correlation diagrams, scatter diagrams, control charts, Pareto analysis, quality function deployment, design of experiments, and so on (Fotopoulos and Psomas, 2009). Organisations of any size require excellent tools (either management or statistical), which help to improve organisational performance (Ahmed and Hassan, 2003). Quality tools and processes were seen as a means of enhancing quality, leading to continual process improvement, customer satisfaction, and the consolidation of market position through effective top management, staff management, and supplier support. Organisations try to identify all the requirements for the products and its design process before launching any new product (Fotopoulos and Psomas, 2009). According to the American Quality Foundation (AQF) findings, firms that succeed in quality spend their resources on the product designing process rather than product inspection. Manufacturability design favours finding a solution to the problem with the new product before producing it rather than rushing a problematic product to market. This may be done by creating straightforward and low-variable designs, doing a lot of prototyping and trial production runs, and promoting the involvement of design engineers, manufacturing engineers, customers and suppliers, marketing representatives, and staff members from other departments in the product development process. The interdisciplinary design team is made up of all the individuals mentioned above (Flynn *et al.*, 1995). These efforts refer to a solid understanding of the requirements needed to produce a good or service (Kim *et al.*, 2012).

Several academics, such as Saraph *et al.* (1989), Rao *et al.* (1999), Flynn *et al.* (1994), Ahire *et al.* (1996), and Joseph *et al.* (1999) have identified process design as an essential aspect of managing quality. The study suggested that process design is necessary for improved service and quality management. The product design process's consequences affect manufacturability, complexity, reliability, features, and product serviceability. The manufacturing process variance is reduced when product components are designed to be easy to make and assemble. The reduction in friction is then seen in several indicators of internal quality performance. Furthermore, designs that reduce the end product's complexity, improve its reliability as the fewer the pieces, the lower the failure rate. There are certain parts also make it easier to coordinate the manufacturing process, minimize manufacturing throughput time, and lower manufacturing costs. The design of items that ensures simplicity to use, improves the product's serviceability, which influences customer perception of the product's value (Hauser & Clausing, 1988). One of the critical activities influencing internal quality performance and competitive capacities is the design of a production process. Error-proofing strategies, such as Shingo's poka-yoke, contribute

to the design of production processes by reducing employee acted errors (Shetty, 1987; Agus and Hassan, 2011). Recognizing the role of suppliers in achieving quality excellence is one of the most significant contributions of quality management. According to Ho *et al.* (1999), defective entering supplies are a primary source of product or process quality concerns. The negative effects of faulty supplies on quality performance made management aware of the significance of incoming materials, components, and quality services, as well as the necessity of supplier relationships in gaining a competitive edge (Flynn *et al.*, 1994). Purchased materials and parts usually become the primary causes of quality issues (Flynn *et al.*, 1994). Defective or low-quality raw materials result in low-quality products being manufactured. As a result, supplier quality is an important aspect of quality assurance. Following researchers Zeitz *et al.* (1997), Rao *et al.* (1999), Saraph *et al.* (1989), Flynn *et al.* (1994), Ahire *et al.* (1996), and Rao *et al.* (1999) have highlighted supplier quality as an important dimension of quality management as defined that defective or low-quality raw materials result in low-quality products being manufactured. This dimension refers to several facts that management must follow to select the suppliers. Those dimensions are the quality of imported materials, supplier reliability, technical support for suppliers, long-term supplier relationships, and supplier engagement in the material specification (Mahmood *et al.*, 2014).

Through routine management, preventative maintenance attempts to ensure safe and quality work and prevent equipment breakdowns. The manufacturing success of an organisation depends on effective preventive maintenance and plant engineering processes (Flynn *et al.*, 1995). The goal of preventative maintenance is to prolong the life of equipment, structures, and machinery while also increasing efficiency and monitoring operating efficiency (Arauz *et al.*, 2009). However, an essential part of the technology is preventive maintenance because maximum activities in the business cycle have an impact by technology which might produce defect-free operation so that products or services can ensure quality to be competitive in the market (Zeng *et al.*, 2015). According to Feng *et al.* (2021), strategic quality planning has considerable effects on organisational performance. Customer satisfaction and organisational success may not be achieved if the resource and allocation of resources within the enterprises are not guided by strategic quality management and fail to ensure customer quality expectations. Improving quality is a long-term competitive strategy that necessitates a long-term management approach (Deming, 1986; Juran, 1986; Lascelles & Dale, 1989). Quality and customer satisfaction issues must be integrated into strategic and operational plans as a part of strategic quality planning. Organisations can use this combination to set clear goals, determine

development efforts for target areas, and distribute resources to the most key functions (Godfrey, 1993). Housekeeping is concerned with maintaining the cleanliness and structure of the workplace to eliminate clutter (Flynn *et al.*, 1994; Schonberger, 2007). Housekeeping is essential not only for production but also for consumer satisfaction. It is a collaborative and ongoing endeavour with a focus on training, routines, clear access, identification, cooperation, and the cleanliness of each cell. Many of these housekeeping activities are monitored by the audit services to ensure floor and storeroom quality standards which has the internal and external impact on the company (Zeng *et al.*, 2015). Total quality management is defined as an organisation's dedication to customer satisfaction via continuous improvement of all business processes related to the production, delivery, and maintenance of goods and services. As an element of TQM, Housekeeping also contributes to enhance the overall quality of corporate activities. It also attempts to maximise the organisational competitiveness, which might be considered an impact on the internal business perspective (Ahire and Dreyfus, 2000; Deming, 1986; Arauz *et al.*, 2009).

Benchmarking is an important quality management tool since it has the potential to drastically enhance a company's critical business processes. Benchmarking can be defined as the pursuit of organisation best practices that result in greater performance. The Malcolm Baldrige National Award winners organization Xerox and Motorola both produced substantial advances by borrowing from world-class benchmarks. Benchmarking allows businesses to enhance their internal systems by learning from outside sources. Companies that do not benchmark will have no idea where they stand concerning competitors and world-class performers, will miss out on new ways of thinking required to accomplish breakthrough advances, and will have no method of analysing the effectiveness of their processes (Rao *et al.*, 1999). Benchmarking is the study of and commitment to best competitive practices to give a guideline for rational performance goals and to assist in setting expectations for cost, product reliability, and other aspects. To serve as benchmarks, management can research their competition and discover the best practices in various functions. When a company's performance is measured and compared to the best globally, it accelerates improvement. As a result, productivity, performance, and effectiveness can all be improved (Kotler, 1994; Zairi, 2010). The common guiding principles of TQM, according to Sitkin *et al.* (1994), are divided into three categories: (a) concentrating on customer satisfaction, (b) emphasising continuous improvement, and (c) approaching organisations as entire systems. Clusters (b), such as emphasising continuous improvement, and clusters (c), like as approaching organisations as entire systems, strongly link with hard TQM. According to

Rahman and Bullock (2005), if Soft QM only impacts organisational performance, then what role do the aspects of hard QM play? The scholars such as Powell (1995), Dow *et al.* (1999), and Ahire *et al.* (1996) found that the usage of benchmarking, statistical process control, and flexible manufacturing systems were not connected to organisational performance. Despite this, several research outcomes defined that few elements of hard TQM significantly impact organisational financial and non-financial performance. Companies like DuPont, Ford, Motorola, Xerox, and General Motors, for example, have used product and process benchmarking to achieve optimal product design while lowering costs (Main and Jacob, 1992). Additional cases have included the effects of six sigma processes at Toyota's QFD (Sullivan, 1986), Honda's seven simple tools, Motorola's SPC (Kumar and Gupta, 1993), and Mazda and Ford's Taguchi approach has a significant impact on organisational performance (Rahman and Bullock, 2005). Therefore, the hypothesis can be made based on the above discussion:

Hypothesis H1: Hard QM has a significant direct impact on organisational financial performance.

Hypothesis H2: Hard QM has a significant direct impact on organisational non-financial performance.

2.4 Soft or Organic aspects of TQM elements

Soft TQM is concerned with the social and behavioural aspects of TQM, whereas hard TQM is concerned with the technical and technological aspects (Abdullah and Tari, 2012). Soft TQM approaches encourage the system's human and behavioural characteristics in order to increase employee participation, human resource management, and customer awareness (Zeng *et al.*, 2015). Examples of such techniques are management and employee interaction, cooperation, training and learning, and multifunctional integration (Abdallah, 2013). It is defined that organisational organic structure is more appropriate than mechanistic structure for successfully implementing the TQM approach. Leadership role motivates the employees and building trust among them where leaders provide motivation, improve staff engagement, and develop a clear vision in order to implement successful TQM approach (Mashi and Cooke, 2000; Hchaichi, 2021). Similarly, customer orientation and participative management ensure TQM's success (Black and Porter, 1996). This concept was later widely appreciated in the work of Damanpour and Schneider (2006) by aiming to satisfy employees and stakeholders, maintain good relationships, and build teamwork (Tata and Prasad, 1998; Hchaichi, 2021). A number of barriers are identified to implement TQM implementation, such as lax control and a lack of performance

standards in quality approaches which impede the implementation of TQM (Zeitz, 1996). Barriers such as a lack of a reward system, a lack of comparative analysis, insufficient training, and resistance to change are also focused on by Tamimi and Sebastianelli (1998). Aldrich (1979) and Dess and Beard (1984) emphasize the importance of resources in total quality management implementation. Many other studies concentrated on the connection between resource availability and total quality management implementation. West *et al.* (1993) emphasis the importance of providing adequate resources to ensure the success of the TQM establishment.

There are consistent definitions of mechanistic and organic TQM based on the sociotechnical systems (Appelbaum, 1997). It is defined that soft TQM is part of larger improvements in human resource practices, whereas hard TQM involves restricted sets of technological instruments (Rahman and Bullock, 2005). The soft TQM refers to philosophical aspects of management concepts and principles, whereas the hard TQM refers to technical aspects of management tools, techniques, and practices (Vouzaz and Psychogios, 2007). The organic components of TQM are concerned with organisational behavioural dimensions and its people, whereas the hard aspects are concerned with tools and processes (Gadene and Sharma, 2009). The soft TQM is concerned with social and behavioural variables, whereas the hard TQM is concerned with technological design, implementation, and improvement (Calvo-Mora *et al.*, 2014). The organic components of TQM employ organisational development approaches to support change, but the mechanistic aspects employ process and technical tactics to deal with design, implementation, and improvement (Kanapathy *et al.*, 2017). It is also defined that the soft components of TQM include behavioural traits, people, and corporate culture. Conversely, the hard aspects focus on scientific methodologies and statistical tools (Sciarelli *et al.*, 2020).

According to Deming (1986), senior management support is the most important aspect of TQM implementation. Most researchers in this field, such as Rao *et al.* (1999), Saraph *et al.* (1989), Flynn *et al.* (1994), Ahire *et al.* (1996), and Joseph *et al.* (1999), agree that top management support is the most essential element in quality management and to run this functions well, managers must provide adequate and timely support. According to Mahmood *et al.* (2014), top management support has a direct and positive impact on organisational performance. Top management is expected to recognise that quality is not something that can be delegated to realise the strategic function of quality. Management's responsibility is to establish and portray the company's quality values and vision in a transparent, visible, and systematic way (Puer and McCarthy, 1996). Top management's active and visible participation in quality management implementation is essential in supporting the actions and behaviours that drive the company's

internal and external quality performance to success. To promote quality standards and enhance efficiency, management must focus on and accept quality leadership as well as provide adequate and timely support (Zeng *et al.*, 2015). According to Hayes (1981; cited in Rao *et al.*, 1999), providing timely and correct information regarding the production process is essential for regulating the process and reducing defective goods. Employee awareness and the ability to make accurate and timely decisions depend on a consistent flow of high-quality information at all work locations. This has a positive impact on the organization's quality performance. Information systems are an important aspect of the quality management infrastructure (Godfrey, 1993). In order to implement successful quality management practices and create a solid foundation for developing powerful competitive capabilities, precise quality information must be easily accessible (Rao *et al.*, 1999). The continual flow of reliable information about the processes that produce the company's products is required for quality maintenance and improvement. For improving and maintaining product quality, information from diverse constituencies, such as workers, agents, vendors, and customers, is vital (Crosby, 1979; Deming, 1986; Ishikawa, 1985; Juran, 1986). Traditional methods of administering the quality information system at random with unclear, inadequate, erroneous, and outdated data are insufficient and create mountains of meaningless data. To make effective judgments on quality-related issues and tasks, senior management and employees must have access to appropriate quality information. To improve organisational quality performance, meaningful and critical process information must be used to facilitate evaluation and decision-making at all levels. Companies reach desired quality levels by utilising quality information rather than simply having it available (Rao *et al.*, 1999). There can be no effective quality improvement program unless the organization's staff are adequately taught by training. Multiple researchers have backed up this argument, such as Saraph *et al.* (1989), Ahire *et al.* (1996), Rao *et al.* (1999), and Joseph *et al.* (1999). According to Mahmood *et al.* (2014), employee training encompasses skill development, statistical approaches, and quality-related instruction. By giving enough resources, top management commitment is required for company-wide employee training considering its impact on organizational performance. One of the most significant components in a company's long-term success with quality management is human resources. Furthermore, training is essential for workers to reach their maximum potential. The usefulness of employing employees' expertise has risen to the extent that training is now required to achieve world-class manufacturing status. Training in quality-related concepts and methods is required to improve quality improvement actions, such as employee involvement and empowerment. Several case studies have shown a

link between training and productivity, product quality, process quality, prices, and the use of innovative manufacturing technology (Rao *et al.*, 1999; Ahire *et al.*, 1996).

Solving problems in groups and utilising collaborative activities are excellent ways to overcome quality difficulties and improve organisational performance (Flynn *et al.*, 1994). Several research studies have emphasised the necessity of employee collaboration for problem-solving and enhancing quality (Dow *et al.*, 1999; Abraham *et al.*, 1999). Employee involvement encourages them to boost the procedure by utilising their practical experience (Forza and Flippini, 1998). According to Stoner *et al.* (1995), empowerment is the act of giving people power, knowledge, and resources so they may accomplish their job objectives effectively. Employee participation programs should be implemented in firms to engage employees in quality decisions. As a result, it will be possible to gauge employee satisfaction, create a quality-conscious culture, and hold people accountable for the consequences of their work. Therefore, employee participation is an important factor in a whole quality management program. Companies must modify how they are organized and their management processes to achieve more involvement of all employees in problem-solving, decision-making, and the firm's financial success. The main principle behind employee engagement is that employees become more responsible, learn to control their work, and effectively participate in the business. Employee participation means giving employees more responsibility, knowledge, and training and rewarding top performers. Employee engagement refers to a set of guidelines that, on the one hand, provide employees the freedom to suggest changes and, on the other way, give everyone the skills, incentives, and power to continually enhance how the company operates (Oliver, 1990). The practice of environmental reporting is well-established, but businesses attempting to do away with social indicators in places like the community encounter extra challenges (Eriksson, 2004). The proper technique to evaluate CSR is to balance the benefits and costs involved. The ISO 14001 standard was developed but has not received as much attention as ISO 9001 (Sharma and Kodali, 2008). Deming (1986) spoke on the importance of the social contribution that would emerge from the use of quality tools and processes (Jacques, 1999). According to Sharma and Kodali (2008), while several quality gurus have emphasised social obligations, they have not received satisfactory attention in the existing TQM framework. Customer expectations are so important and considered the industry's driving force. Management should be committed to creating satisfied consumers to meet or surpass customer expectations. Customer suggestions should be incorporated into the product and process design by top management (Mahmood *et al.*, 2014). An organisation prioritizing its customers first differs from a regular organisation. While cost and efficiency are the main

corporate motivations in a traditional organisation, client satisfaction is the driving force behind everything the company does in a customer-oriented organisation. Therefore, the fundamental strategies for maintaining a competitive edge requires concentrating on the client. In a customer-focused organisation, customers determine and are the final judges of quality (Rao *et al.*, 1999). According to the findings of Powell (1995), Only three of the twelve soft TQM variables, such as management commitment, open organisation, and employee empowerment, were found to be strongly connected with overall financial and non-financial business performance. Dow *et al.* (1999) discovered that out of a total of nine criteria, only the three elements, such as shared vision, staff commitment, and customer focus, had a significant positive correlation with quality and performance in research on Australian manufacturing companies. In the study of automobile manufacturing and component firms in the United States, Ahire *et al.* (1996) found that performance based on product quality was strongly connected with soft TQM characteristics such as staff empowerment, training, and involvement. However, this research used different sets of indicators to measure organisational performance. In comparison, Dow *et al.* (1999) and Ahire *et al.* (1996) have used relatively limited quality-focused definitions of performance, whereas Powell (1995) included a variety of specific TQM performance indicators. Therefore, Kochan *et al.* (1995) defined that TQM can be seen in two ways. In the first approach, TQM is considered a small set of technical tools, such as Pareto analysis and statistical process control. In contrast, TQM is viewed as a component of more extensive reforms to human resource practices in the second approach. They discovered that organisations that use initiatives to strengthen stakeholder commitment and include employee input in decision-making processes are more likely to use hard TQM techniques. Soft TQM, in addition to having a direct impact on performance. Soft TQM elements are essentially HRM dimensions. The management literature covers soft TQM extensively, and the recommendations presented in the management and TQM books are highly similar. Three of the six criteria of the Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award (MBNQA) framework are widely addressed in the management literature (Dean and Bowen, 1994). Soft TQM encompasses three criteria: leadership, HRM, and strategic quality planning. According to Powell (1995), organisations adopting aspects of soft TQM can perform better than rivals without the corresponding. Therefore, the above literature suggests that:

Hypothesis H3: Soft QM has a significant direct impact on organisational financial performance.

Hypothesis H4: Soft QM has a significant direct impact on organisational non-financial performance.

2.5 Innovation Practices

According to Boeddrich (2004), innovation arises from ideas generated within and outside the company. As a result, to generate the greatest number of new products, services, and process concepts, a holistic view of the innovation process is required. Because of industrial breaches of CSR, the Bangladeshi RMG sector faced tremendous forces from external stakeholders. Around 1200 individuals were killed, and another 3000 employees were injured when the building (Rana Plaza) collapsed in the heart of the capital city Dhaka, Bangladesh. Following the incident, Wal-Mart and H&M ceased all operations in Bangladesh (Rubya, 2014). So, the country was looking forward to overcoming the issue. Process and service innovation are essential for avoiding external risks and ensuring sustainable business success. The management's new strategy and ideas could be the option to find a better solution to bring out the Bangladeshi organisation from that situation (Rubya, 2014). According to Burgelman *et al.* (2004), in the front-end innovation process, the idea acceptance phases by the management contain numerous stages through which the idea must pass and where it is developed. Once the preferred ideas have been identified, it is essential to use efficient procedures of saving resources. Reid and Brentani (2004) proposed "fuzzy front end" innovation, arguing that the concept generation and composition, as well as the time spent on the idea, should be prioritised to improve those ideas. The concept could come from both inside and outside the company. In this procedure, the new product and process must be taken into account. However, according to Koen *et al.* (2001), the front end is analogous to the introduced concept creation stage. The front end is primarily used for identifying and analysing opportunities. As a result, the acceptable area of the innovation process and its success is the front end (Brem and Voigt, 2009). According to Brem and Voigt (2009), there are two approaches important for obtaining ideas: collecting ideas from any individual or group's thinking or using creative methods to develop ideas through a well-thought-out procedure. According to Stenmark (2000), the important ingredients for boosting corporate creativity include a motivating compensation scheme, officially acknowledged creative efforts, the inspiration of self-initiated activities, and redundancy allowances. According to Boeddrich (2004), certain characteristics must be met to produce ideas that are successful in the marketplace. As a result, to exercise innovation, management's self-will must be concentrated in the organisation. Later, Koen *et al.* (2001) proposed a standard language for front-end activities, which became a widely accepted new concept development procedure. Because these stages contain a continuous process of multiple information improvement stages, such as market studies or scientific tests, opportunity identification and analysis come before an idea. Finally, a formal business strategy

or project proposal outlines the transition to new product and process development (Brem and Voigt, 2009). On the other hand, Boeddrich (2004) establishes company-specific preconditions for successful front-end management. However, Sandmeier *et al.* (2004) created a broad process model and discussed market pull vs. technology push in detail. In this 'integrated front-end process model,' the first phase focuses on a company's market and technological prospects. The strategy and aims of innovation are crucial and iterative tasks. Finally, there are one to two research fields and prospects for the next stage. The next step focuses on idea development and evaluation, which includes various sub-processes that lead to the generation of balanced business and production. The innovation process is very complicated, and it includes stages such as recognising opportunities, locating resources, constructing venture stages, and delivering value. As a result, the innovation process has its sequence that assists the company in becoming more innovative and competitive in the market (Tidd *et al.*, 2001). According to Utterback (1994), successful organizations are those that have accepted failure as a part of the process. According to Tidd *et al.* (2001), practicing innovation entails developing a dynamic competency. By assuring the quality of products, processes, and services, management innovation keeps the company competitive. According to Simpson *et al.* (2006), innovative businesses have higher operational efficiency and productivity. This is a result of intra-organizational process improvements. Employee satisfaction, good performance, and retention are common in innovative companies. A workplace that encourages creativity is more likely to increase happiness, self-fulfillment, and job satisfaction. Firms that are focused on innovation obtain a competitive advantage in the market because of their unique products or processes. As a result, the market share should potentially increase. On the other hand, Simpson *et al.* (2006) did not state that firms that focus on innovation have higher profit margins. However, according to Simpson *et al.* (2006), an innovation-oriented organisation may encounter unprofitable innovation if it introduces innovation outside its normal competencies. As a result, producing innovation outside of an organisation's core competencies may have detrimental consequences. The organisation may become enamored with developing creativity to create more innovations and lose sight of its fundamental competencies. Researchers defined administrative and technological innovation as the two main categories of innovation (Chuang *et al.*, 2010; Weerawardena, 2003; Yonghong *et al.*, 2005; Ling and Nasurdin, 2010; Maistry *et al.*, 2017). Santos-Vijande and Alvarez-González (2007) defined innovation as adopting new ideas that impact on organisational activities and efficiency from both technological and administrative perspectives.

2.5.1 Technological Innovation

The production procedure, goods or services offered, and service providers are all subject to technological advancement. Technology adoption is correlated with technological innovation, which affects on organisational efficacy (Yonghong *et al.*, 2005). Chuang *et al.* (2010) and Maistry *et al.* (2017) used three subscales to measure technological innovation those are namely, technological products or service innovation, technological technology, and technological process innovation. The technological product and service indicators are used to compare the products that are superior or first to market, advancement of technology, and R&D results for boosting efficiency and effectiveness. While the technological technology is assessed, followed by the organisational technological adoption, R&D competitiveness, implementation of the new technology for improving outcomes, and how the company is continuously on the lookout for new technology skills to help it stay ahead of the competition curve. Similarly, technological processes are assessed by the company's technological strategy or R&D activities, which are how quickly adjusted to meet market demands and how the organisation's technological process operations are carried out in such a way that more outputs are produced with fewer resources. To improve its technological process or R&D outputs, the organisation initiates to develop and implement new approaches on a regular basis. Technological processes are evaluated by the company's technological strategy or R&D activities, followed by how quickly the organisation adjusted to meet market demands (Chuang *et al.*, 2010; Maistry *et al.*, 2017).

An idea, behaviour, system, programme, device, policy, method, product, or service that is new to the firm is classified as innovation (Damanpour, 1992). While organisational innovation, according to Damanpour (1992), encompasses all aspects of the company by including all sorts of innovation that can be split into two categories: technological innovation and organisational innovation. Anzola-Román *et al.* (2018) differentiated between technologi-oriented and non-technology-oriented innovation, classifying the latter as new marketing strategies and changes in management approaches or organisational structures. Product and process innovation are frequently considered to be part of technological innovation. Product innovation is classified as introducing new or significantly enhanced goods or services in terms of their specifications or desired purposes. This includes substantial advancements in technological requirements, components and materials, software integration, user-friendliness, and desired functional aspects (OECD, 2018). A comprehensive set of corporate characteristics that promote and support the firm's technological innovation strategies is called TICs (Burgelman *et al.*, 2004). Several academics have created methods for evaluating a firm's TICs, including asset

approaches such as scientific research, product innovation, and esthetics design (Christensen, 1995). The process approach, in contrast, focuses on how a firm's skills, resources' availability and allocation, competitors' innovative marketing strategies, technology advancements, the structural and cultural environment, and dealing with internal creative activities (Burgelman *et al.*, 2004). Similar skills enable concept generation, process innovation, product creation, leadership, and efficient system and tool use (Chiesa *et al.*, 1996). Additionally, the functional model incorporates capabilities for strategic planning, resource allocation, manufacturing, marketing, and research and development (Christensen, 1995).

Traditionally, research on technological innovation has concentrated on firm-specific factors, including research and development activities and company size. Recent research has tended to include factors outside of organizations, particularly when it comes to external sources of innovation that firms use to generate or improve their products or processes. The source of innovation is significant because it determines what competencies a company must have to implement the necessary innovations on time and achieve market success (Yam *et al.*, 2004; Yam *et al.*, 2011). The efficiency and capacities generated from new product developments could provide a competitive advantage to a company (Lawless and Fisher, 1990). The accumulation of capabilities is responsible for a growth in product innovation, which leads to innovation outputs. In most cases, high-performance companies have more capabilities than low-performance companies. Improved technological innovation capabilities can benefit the company and increase its competitiveness (Yam *et al.*, 2004). According to Evangelista *et al.* (1997), research and development are vital in a firm's technological innovation activities and the most significant intangible form of innovation expenditure. The diversity in a firm's financial returns is due to its heterogeneous resource portfolios, including its people, capital, and technology resources. The company's particular competencies contribute significantly to improving profits and competitive advantage. There is a correlation between a company's resources and its ability to innovate technologically. Any innovation's success is always best measured in monetary terms. Financial indices measure whether a product or service has affected the market or has been financially successful. The sales figure attributable to technologically new or better products as a percentage of total sales over the last three years was used to determine sales performance. This metric is commonly used in research on innovation (Yam *et al.*, 2004). Extensive organizational innovation may emphasize strategic positive or negative consequences that impact the entire firm more than innovation metrics like rate and speed (Simpson *et al.*, 2006). Innovation can manifest itself in a variety of ways. The distinction between radical and gradual

innovations, product and process innovations, and administrative and technological innovations is frequently drawn (Maistry *et al.*, 2017). According to Nieto and Santamaria (2010), product innovation is appropriate when a company wants to enter a new market ahead of competitors and match customer needs, whereas process innovation directly affects the marketing position through increased productivity and cost reduction. According to Lyon and Ferrier (2002), introducing new and innovative items enhance market share and profit margin. As a result, according to Simpson *et al.* (2006), new goods improve a company's financial performance and competitive advantages. Process innovation, on the other hand, is often related to increased efficiency, productivity, and cost reduction (Krelle, 1987). Tether (2002) claims that sectors with high technological potential are linked to high-tech activities. Firms with higher levels of technology activity are likely to be more innovative in terms of its product and process development than those with lower levels of technology activity. Therefore, it can be assumed that:

Hypothesis H5: Technological innovation has a significant direct impact on organisational financial performance.

Hypothesis H6: Technological innovation has a significant direct impact on organisational non-financial performance.

2.5.2 Administrative Innovation

According to Tidd and Bessant (2014), there are several areas where innovation may happen, such as Sundbo *et al.* (2015) mentioned product and service innovation, conceptual innovation, Dolfisma (2004) said dedicated innovation, technological, and regulatory innovation. Innovation management and revenue model innovation are mentioned by Baba (2012). Most organizations are concerned about adopting those important areas around innovation. According to Pinho (2008), innovation influences to improve the products, processes, or procedures. Thus, innovation helps to enhance the value and performance of products, processes, or procedures by covering the TQM practicing elements such as leadership, strategic planning, customer focus, information analysis, product development, people management, and process management (Sila, 2007). Fernandes *et al.* (2014) stated that the TQM principles are Leadership, focus on customers, involvement and development of people, management by process, ongoing improvement, relations with suppliers, result measurement, and product design. Simultaneously, Fernandes *et al.* (2014) mentioned that the elements associated with innovation performance

are: continuous development and technological innovation, product innovation, process innovation, organizational innovation, management innovation, and marketing innovation. Innovation is the simple development and implementation of new ideas by people, which could be drastic (radical) or incremental (Tidd and Bessant, 2014). Innovation is a concept and could be multi-dimensional such as product, process, and services (Prajogo, 2016). Product innovation is defined as developing or implementing new components, structures, and technologies to develop unique products. Service innovation is the unique path to deliver support value to the customer. Process innovation is the improvement of production processes and technologies required to produce a product. Process innovation occurs within the internal operations of a firm (Ahuja and Lampert, 2001; Prajogo, 2016). According to Tether (2002), companies must implement modern techniques and ideologies to compete in both existing and emerging markets. Innovation is a task shared by all business divisions and departments, and its participation should always be determined accordingly. According to Zahra and George (2002), an organization's ability to identify, obtain, and implement (external) ideas is the most important component of its commercial success. Brem and Voigt (2009) term this the 'Front-End' of innovation, which is widely recognised as one of the most important aspects of corporate administration as a method for practicing innovation.

New technology and international rivals have sparked a business-friendly transformation to reinvent themselves in innovative ways. Organizational innovation is currently being given more attention. Indeed, innovation is one of the unique reasons behind a country's winning in international business rivalries (Stokey, 1995). The adoption of a novel concept or behaviour by the adopting organisation has been defined as organisational innovation (Damanpour & Evan, 1984). As a result, innovation could take the form of a new product or service, a new manufacturing process technology, a new organisational structure or administrative system, or a new strategy or programme for the members of the organisation (Damanpour, 1991). Administrative innovation is the adoption of new working methods to increase organisational performance, structures, systems, and processes (Weerawardena, 2003). Chuang *et al.* (2010) and Maistry *et al.* (2017) used three main subscales to measure administrative innovation those are namely, internal organisational innovation, marketing innovation, and strategic innovation. Following the previous study of Chuang *et al.* (2010), and Maistry *et al.* (2017), the indicators of administrative innovation and its assessment criteria are used based on internal organisational, marketing, and strategic perspective. The internal organisational innovation can be assessed by the organization that has a structure and culture to practice creative activities for desired

outcomes. Similarly, a participatory working environment that openly discusses new ideas and allows employees to develop their skills and abilities are the criteria to assess the internal organizational innovation. Marketing innovation leads to customer involvement in organisational innovation, boosts R&D outputs to break into new markets, and focuses on building creative activities and products of an organisation that contributes to its competitive advantages. Strategic innovation assessment criteria are used for its strategic operational actions, organisational external knowledge, trends, relevant policies that implemented by other companies, and to cope with a changing economic environment following how organisation encourages strategic alliances and partnership (Chuang *et al.*, 2010; Maistry *et al.*, 2017). Innovation can be categorised in many ways. Knight (1967) divided innovation into four categories: product or service, manufacturing process, organisational structure, and people. In a study on the relationship between organisational size and innovation, Damanpour (1992) looked at six forms of innovation: product, process, administrative, technical, radical, and incremental. In the same manner, six categories of innovation are highlighted by Johanessen *et al.* (2001), such as new products, new services, new methods of manufacturing, new markets, new sources of supply, and new ways of organising. Conversely, Mavondo *et al.* (2005) highlighted three types of organisational innovation, such as product, process, and administrative innovation. Similarly, Others such as Damanpour & Evan (1984) and Damanpour (1992) focused on two types of organisational innovation: technical or technological innovation and administrative innovation. Ravichandran (2000) found that administrative innovation has been shown to improve organisational performance among the various types of innovation. Administrative innovation encompasses basic job activities inside the organisation that are directly related to management, and it highlights performance generated from changes to organisational structure and administrative procedure, reward, and information system (Damanpour & Evan, 1984; Mavondo *et al.*, 2005). Administrative innovation can be viewed as a fundamental source of competitive advantage since manufacturing enterprises operate based on internal process efficiency (Ling and Nasurdin, 2010). Unlike product or process innovation, administrative innovation is not patentable (Zhu & Zhang, 2019). Furthermore, this form of innovation frequently entails substantial start-up expenditures as well as significant reorganisation of duties and responsibilities (Teece, 1980). As a result, administrative innovation is unique for its impact on organisational performance in many ways. In addition, research in the innovation field has concentrated on product and process aspects rather than administrative innovation (Wang and Ahmed, 2002). Similarly, Naveh *et al.* (2006) note that administrative process innovation can lead to cost reductions in the manufacturing environment. Thus, the

administrative process is one of the valuable predictors of innovation. Therefore, Administrative innovation has a financial and non-financial impact on organisational performance. Hence, the following hypothesis can be developed:

Hypothesis H7: Administrative innovation has a significant direct impact on organisational financial performance.

Hypothesis H8: Administrative innovation has a significant direct impact on organisational non-financial performance.

2.6 Relationship between TQM and innovation performance

Prajogo and Sohal (2001) argue that the relationship between quality management and innovation is contradictory. According to Imai (2007), and Oliver (2009), QM proponents believe in continuous improvement to simplify or streamline a process. Continuous improvement emphasises gradual change and calls for standardisation or formalisation in order to retain control and stability. According to Morgan *et al.* (2002), forcing people to concentrate on the details of the present quality process rather than a fresh concept to change the existing work procedure would result in rigidity and impede creativity. Process management techniques aim to reduce waste and boost efficiency, but this may be detrimental to creativity since it depletes stock assets, which are essential for encouraging innovation (Sadikohlu and Zehir, 2010). Oliver (2009) criticizes on it by claiming that consumer focus is a source of creativity. According to McAdam *et al.* (1998), quality management may be seen in many. There are three important subject areas for innovation pointed out by Pfeifer *et al.* (1998), such as customer and service-oriented, flexible organisational structures, and innovative employees, which align with quality management principles. In QM, consumers are prioritised, highlighting the importance of satisfying customers. As a result, focusing on customers might push businesses to look for new customer requirements and be more innovative than merely adhering to standards (Prajogo and Sohal, 2001; Prajogo and Sohal, 2003). Teamwork, worker autonomy, and information transfer are important factors in supporting creativity defined by Molina *et al.* (2007). The correlation between quality and innovation performance is also covered by opposing viewpoints which make the quality management and innovation relationship more ambiguous. It is defined that product innovation, and quality is mutually exclusive (Flynn *et al.*, 1994). Based on this concept, an increase in one measure of performance requires a drop in another. Hence, businesses cannot simultaneously reach high levels of performance for several competitive significances. However, based on the

Sandcone model, organisations can enhance many dimensions of performance at the same time since the improvements cumulatively reinforce each other (Ferdows and De Meyer, 1990; Lii and Kuo, 2016). According to Brown *et al.* (2007), the ultimate apex of the sandcone model's pyramid is innovation performance, which is constructed upon the cumulative influence of development on other types of manufacturing performance, including quality performance. McAdam *et al.* (1998) found a significant robust correlation between innovation and continuous improvement. In that research, McAdam *et al.* (1998) compared quality management to innovation in 15 Irish companies, and output stated a strong correlation suggesting a causal relationship with continuous improvement leading to innovation over time. However, according to Singh and Smith (2004), there is no substantial link between quality management and innovation performance. This decision was made by doing analyse on large numbers of data samples of Australian manufacturing companies. However, Prajogo and Sohal (2003) found a favourable correlation between quality management and innovation success in Australian organisations. From a managerial standpoint, quality improvement, particularly in the product, can be viewed as a means to meet strategic knowledge requirements rather than as a means to meet the demands of efficiency and effectiveness. Mazzola and Perrone (2013) define enlightening product quality as being closely tied to strategic requirements intended to increase knowledge. Kim *et al.* (2002) also discovered a positive link between the quality management process and all types of innovation. According to Abrunhosa and Moura (2008), the whole effect of quality management on innovation is difficult to generalise since QM is a challenging organisational philosophy that encompasses both mechanistic and organic aspects, which might lead to divergent outcomes in terms of innovation.

Michela *et al.* (1996) identify a series of reasons stating that quality management philosophy and standards are incompatible with innovation. The ideology of quality management emphasises sustainable growth intending to streamline or simplify a system. To maintain control and stability, continual improvement emphasises sustainable change and necessitates standardisation or systemisation. According to Zeng *et al.* (2015), quality management effects on innovation vary based on QM implementation's emphasis on the organic and mechanistic aspects of QM elements in a firm by focusing more on mechanistic aspects or more on organic aspects. According to Tidd *et al.* (2001), managing innovation is about building a dynamic capability. Tidd *et al.* (2005) also defined innovation strategies are the successful use of creative ideas within organisations, which represent value to customers. Under the Resource-Based Theory (RBT), Jung and wang (2006) defined that a Firm's innovation approaches can offer superior

performance because creativity offers value to customers and distinguishes them from others that are hard to imitate and cannot be replicated. According to Molina *et al.* (2007), teamwork, workers' autonomy, and knowledge transfer play a significant role in fostering innovation. McAdam *et al.* (1998) found a substantial and robust correlation between continuous improvement and innovation. McAdam *et al.* (1998) also indicate that continuous improvement would lead to innovation. However, Singh and Smith (2004) did not find any robust correlation between quality management and innovation performance based on the Australian manufacturing firm's research output. Furthermore, Prajogo and Sohal (2003) analysed on Australian firms, and output came as a positive relationship between quality management and innovation performance.

Business productivity and economic growth have been defined as major drivers of innovation (Schumpeter, 1934; Romer, 1990). According to Schumpeter (1934), innovation is the transfer of knowledge into new products, services, or business processes. There has been a lot of research into the relationship between innovation output and inputs (Crepon *et al.*, 1998; McCann and Simonen, 2005; Griffith *et al.*, 2006; Roper *et al.*, 2008). Several scholars have attempted to clarify why certain businesses are more innovative than competitors, with company attributes such as a firm's size, sector, strategic ownership, and geography identified as driving factors of innovation and performance (Jordan and O'Leary, 2008; McCann and Simonen, 2005; Audretsch and Feldman, 1996; Boschma, 2005; Gordon and McCann, 2005; Tether, 1998; Roper *et al.*, 2008; Romer, 1990). Authors also have emphasised the importance of research and development to corporate innovation (Roper *et al.*, 2008; Freel, 2003). Firms that invest in research and development expand their knowledge base, resulting in business profits from the implementation of new goods, processes, or corporate changes (Roper *et al.*, 2004). Similarly, managerial qualities have been identified as a key element of innovation in a firm. For businesses to successfully innovate, managers must constantly and effectively communicate the company's aims and objectives to employees (Barnes *et al.*, 2006). There's also a lot of evidence that external sources are important for innovation outcomes (Mansury and Love, 2008). Customers, suppliers, competitors, and research institutes could all be considered outsider sources of knowledge (Roper *et al.*, 2008). It has been acknowledged as process innovation is essential when a business seeks to increase productivity, emphasising a possible connection between innovation and quality management. As previously mentioned, the mechanical and organic aspects of quality management were discussed in the existing literature on the relationship between quality and innovation. However, it is noted that several of the research findings

empirically evaluate a particular quality investment management and its implications on innovation performance instead of considering the organic and mechanistic aspects of the strategy (Martnez-Costa and Martnez-Lorente, 2008). The study brought out by Zeng *et al.* (2015) is a significant recent example where a small number of studies look at the connection between quality certification and innovation, focusing primarily on mechanistic quality investment management and innovation. In the paint and photography industries, Benner and Tushman (2002) discovered that the breadth of a firm's process management activities is linked to an increase in exploitative inventions and exploitative innovation's percentage of overall innovations. Pekovic and Galia (2009) found that ISO 9000 certification is significantly and positively associated with seven of nine innovation variables using data from two French microeconomic surveys. Additionally, research shows that ISO9000 accreditation encourages process innovation but prevents product innovation (Terziovski and Guerrero, 2014). Zeng *et al.* (2015) also emphasized the necessity of hard quality management for innovation.

It is argued that many researchers are not aware of any quantitative research that particularly link quality circles to innovation when it comes to the relationship between soft quality management and innovation. Sitting in a small group and solving problems, employee suggestion systems, and employee training have been found to positively impact problem-solving abilities, provide workers the authority to offer process changes, and update employees' skills and knowledge. There is evidence of such soft techniques benefiting corporate innovation activity in HRM and quality management literature (Nakata and Im, 2010; Laursen and Foss, 2014; Leiponen, 2005; Zeng *et al.*, 2015). The majority of research so far has concentrated on the relationship between TQM and innovation, which has been proven to be favourable in most cases. In an analysis of the Portuguese footwear sector, Moura and Abrunhosa (2008) report a favourable association between TQM and innovation, though the relationship is relatively weak. In a research on 451 Spanish companies, Martnez-Costa and Martnez-Lorente (2008) found a strong and positive association between TQM and product and process innovation, while Prajogo and Hong (2008) discovered that TQM favourably promotes research and development in South Korean organizations.

Hung *et al.* (2011) recently investigated the impact of TQM and organisational learning on innovation performance in Taiwan's high-tech industry. TQM has a large and positive impact on organisational learning, and both TQM and organisational learning have a considerable and positive impact on innovation performance. While many of these studies do not clearly distinguish between the organic and mechanistic elements of TQM in terms of innovation results, and there

is evidence that certain aspects of TQM have an impact on innovation activity. According to Abrunhosa and Moura (2008), communication, supportive people management techniques, and cooperation have a significant positive impact on innovation performance, whereas autonomy and consultation do not. In a study of the impact of TQM on product innovation in Australian businesses, Prajogo and Sohal (2004) found that two aspects of TQM, such as leadership and people management, had a positive impact on innovation. On the other hand, Hoang *et al.* (2006) reveal that both soft and hard quality management practices have a significant effect on firm growth and demonstrate how three distinct TQM components, leadership and people management, process and strategic management, and transparent organization, have a direct influence on firm innovation in Vietnam. Studies conducted by Perdomo-Ortiz *et al.* (2009) and Perdomo-Ortiz *et al.* (2009) on Spanish industrial enterprises found that only the soft human resource management part of TQM is associated positively with innovation. They find that TQM encompasses a collection of human resource management best practices that encourage improved innovation performance. The researchers also looked at five other aspects of TQM like as management support, quality Information, process management, product design, and agent interactions, and found no evidence of a favourable correlation between innovation and any of them. Perdomo-Ortiz *et al.* (2006) examined the link between TQM and innovation in a previous study, using business innovation capacity as a moderating and mediating component. Its defined about TQM is a collection of human resource management best practices that promote better innovative performance. According to Maistry *et al.* (2017), technological innovation impacts effectiveness, which refers to embracing new technology and relates to production processes, products or services, and service delivery that satisfies the mechanistic TQM elements. However, administrative innovation improves organizational performance, organisational structures, systems, and processes by implementing a new working process that meets the organic TQM elements (Weerawardena 2003). Therefore, organic TQM elements are considered to measure administrative innovations. Conversely, to measure technological innovation, mechanistic TQM elements are considerable (Maistry *et al.*, 2017). In general, quality improvement and innovation are regarded as complementary roles inside organisations, and while quality management typically supports innovation, this connection is not always advantageous (Prajogo 2016). In addition, depending on the flexible aspects of quality management systems, different organisational or behavioural dynamics may impact differently on performance. The complementary relationship between hard and soft practices of TQM has a significant impact on organisational performance (Maistry *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, Zeng *et al.* (2015) looked at how organic quality management can support or mediate the interaction

between mechanistic quality management and innovation and discovered a significant correlation between both. Therefore, based on the above discussion following research hypothesis can be developed.

H9: Hard QM has a significant direct impact on administrative innovation.

H10: Hard QM has a significant direct impact on technological innovation.

H11: Soft QM has a significant direct impact on administrative innovation.

H12: Soft QM has a significant direct impact on technological innovation.

2.7 Organisational performance BSC

Business performance is widely acknowledged as a multidimensional phenomenon (Venkatraman and Ramanujam, 1987). Ruekert and Walker (1987) propose a simple yet broad framework for evaluating effectiveness, efficiency, and flexibility in corporate achievement. The success of a company's tactics in serving the specified markets in comparison to competitors is referred to as its effectiveness. Sales growth and market share are two metrics that represent the essence of this dimension. Efficiency implies the outcome of a company's strategy in terms of the resources utilized to achieve them, and it is calculated using financial measures such as return on investment. Operating efficiency is distinguished by a small scope of activities and a focus on cost reduction through the standardisation of operating procedures (Hambrick, 1983). The ability of an organisation to adapt successfully to changing external environmental conditions over time is referred to as adaptability. Flexibility is replaced by successful new products and services introduced in response to changing client needs and competitor offerings. Subsequent and more current research has confirmed the benefits of this "balanced" approach to performance monitoring (Morgan *et al.*, 2002). In keeping with the spirit of this multifaceted approach followed by the researcher Varadarajan and Jayachandran (1999), the effectiveness of marketing and financial performance is used to evaluate corporate performance, though marketing effectiveness is explained more broadly to include new product launches in keeping with the study's emphasis on innovation. As a result, marketing effectiveness measures revenue growth, market share gains, and successful product launches. Market share is regarded as a valuable performance statistic since it predicts cash flow and profitability. The organization's theory that benefits from scale effects can cut costs and achieve more significant profits than rivals with smaller market margins (Jacobson, 1988). Gaining market share is a suitable and

accurate metric since it indicates adaptation to fluctuating conditions. In some ways, it demonstrates the firm's ability to adapt (Mavondo *et al.*, 2005). The BSC system includes a broad range of financial and non-financial performance indicators that, when combined, can give managers continual signals about what is most essential in their everyday tasks and where initiatives should be addressed. TQM enterprises should use a BSC to find suitable multifunctional, non-financial, and financial indicators, so that, staff are both motivated and honoured for achieving objectives, as well as encouraged and compensated for sharing feedback on areas where advancements may be made. The feedback mechanism is the key success factor. TQM success is achieved by empowering people to contribute to attaining continual performance improvement (Hoque, 2003). Implementing management strategies in today's changing environment necessitates integrated performance measurement systems to detect changes in financial and non-financial parameters. Integrated performance management systems use performance drivers and result metrics to align the organisation's activities with management strategy. Integrated project management systems attempt to offer managers at all levels a more explicit definition of what activities they should do properly to implement strategy (Bremser and Barsky, 2004). According to Kaplan and Norton (2001), BSC outlines five essential principles for a strategy-focused organisation, which can be stated as translating strategy into work, aligning strategy in every part of the organisation, making strategy everyone's job, making strategy a continuous process, and activate leadership to check and support the process (Bremser and Barsky, 2004). Although the highest-level scorecard should be applied at the corporate level, the BSC can also be used at the division or department level. The BSC framework is used to implement strategy from four perspectives: customers, internal business processes, innovation and learning, and financial performance (Kaplan and Norton, 2005; Kaplan and Norton, 1996).

The BSC approach reflects operational distinction and the product's unique value propositions from the customer's perspective. Organisational sales and marketing departments can also have an impact on cause-and-effect relationships (Bremser and Barsky, 2004). The BSC requires management to define its overall customer service purpose statement into particular measures that represent the truly important variables to clients. Customers are often concerned about lead times, product and service quality, corporate performance, and cost-effectiveness. However, in the long run, and especially in the age of globalisation, every firm's competitiveness is determined by several customer-related criteria (Kaplan and Norton, 2000; Bhagwat and Sharma, 2007). From a financial standpoint, management mainly proposes to measure an

organisation's revenue growth and productivity (Bremser and Barsky, 2004). Financial performance measures show if a firm's strategy, implementation, and execution efficiently affect a firm's bottom-line development. Financial objectives include achieving profitability, sustaining liquidity and solvency in the short and long term, increasing sales turnover, and maximising shareholder wealth. So it can be said that the financial objectives' motive is to survive, achieve, and develop. Similarly, cash flow determines survival, success determines sales and operating income growth, and prosperity determines increasing market share, return on equity, and capital utilisation (Kaplan and Norton, 2000; Bhagwat and Sharma, 2007). Internal process metrics at the BSC are related to a few fundamental levels of processes, which are innovation, operations and logistics, customer management, regulatory, and environmental (Bremser and Barsky, 2004). What organizations must excel at: intrinsic BSC measurements are derived from operational processes that have a significant effect on customer satisfaction, such as processing times, quality, workforce competence, and performance. Enterprises must choose the systems and skills needed to thrive and set metrics for everyone (Kaplan and Norton, 2000; Bhagwat and Sharma, 2007). A firm's capability to innovate, learn and develop is significantly linked to the company's value. The innovation and continual learning process can lead to increase efficiency in the business's operating domain. Furthermore, it ensures cost minimisation and product variation to fulfill clients' diverse needs. As a result, it improves financial capability by maximising revenue and profit appropriation and maintaining a considerable proportion of revenues to fund the company's potential development of prospective projects under consideration (Kaplan and Norton, 2000; Bhagwat and Sharma, 2007). The balanced scorecard approach to evaluating the performance of organisations was used to evaluate organisational performance factors (Banwet and Deshmukh, 2006; Bremser and Barsky, 2004). Because acceptable performance measurements should include both financial and non-financial indicators to assess operational results and processes (Maisel, 1992), the evaluation of organisational performance was done from both a financial and non-financial aspect. The scales used for measuring organizational performance are well accepted for the previous studies by Maisel (1992) and Maistry *et al.* (2017), followed in this research context. Return on investment, profitability, shareholders' funds, loyalties, fund generation to build the capabilities are considered for financial assessment. To assess the internal organizational performance, inventory management, impact on profitability, management benchmarking, organisational initiatives to accept change are considered. Therefore, acceptable organisation performance measurement scales are shown in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: organisational performance measurement scales

Performance Scales	Used Assessment Criteria
Financial aspect	Return on investment, profitability, shareholders' funds, loyalties, and fund generation to build the capabilities are considered for financial assessment (Kaplan and Norton, 2000; Bhagwat and Sharma, 2007).
Internal organisational aspect	To assess the internal organizational performance, inventory management, impact on profitability, management benchmarking, and organisational initiatives to accept change are considered (Maisel, 1992; Maistry <i>et al.</i> , 2017).
Customer/(CSR) aspect	Considered the social-economic and environmental factors while operating the activities or agenda. Considered the aptitude to match the market's demands and ability to generate new market demands. In addition, it is considered the ability to gain customer and stakeholders satisfaction (Maisel, 1992).
Innovation and Learning aspect	Considered the innovative way of utilizing resources and business processes such as mergers, acquisitions, or licensing. Also, considered the ability to develop new ideas, technologies implementations in goods, services, communications, transportation, etc. The ability to publish research findings or advertisements in international business. In addition, task monitoring skills, abilities, and capacity to meet delivery deadlines or improve the delivery frequency have been considered (Maisel, 1992; Maistry <i>et al.</i> , 2017).
Human resource/employee aspect.	To assess employee performance, capacity-building and programmes' effectiveness are considered. Simultaneously, motivation to recruit and retain highly competent employees, job satisfaction, and health and safety issues are considered (Maistry <i>et al.</i> , 2017).

In addition, the four BSC dimensions contribute to the effectiveness of TQM programmes. It is important to discuss about the major TQM-related activities, performance indicators, and critical BSC factors for each TQM-related activity. It includes a list of eight major TQM-related measurement scales for quantitative and thirteen elements for qualitative analysis. It is worth noting that, by the literature, these eight parameters of TQM are vital to the performance of an organisation.

The TQM performance parameters: management leadership, quality information, and social responsibilities performance are measured following the performance measurement scales such as employee opinion, suggestions, techniques of introducing new products or services, and

practicing CSR in the organisation with the BSC dimension of innovation and Learning, and internal business perspective (Hoque, 2003; Mahmood *et al.*, 2014). Surveys on customer satisfaction, customer retention, market share rate, customer complaints, and warranty repair cost are used as performance matrices to measure the customer's performance in TQM, which matches the customer and financial perspective by BSC category. Supplier satisfaction and retention rate are used to measure the TQM performance; these elements are considered from the internal business perspective to measure the performance in the BSC category. Comparative labour cost, cost of quality, scrap rate, ROI, and market share is used for benchmarking. Employee satisfaction, employee capabilities, investment for training and development, and degree or decentralisation in corporate governance are used as TQM matrices to measure the performance of TQM elements of employee training, employee suggestions, and problem-solving. The BSC approach measures those performances in both internal business processes and financial perspectives. The number of defective products, material and labour efficiency variance, warranty repair cost, and shipment cancellation are used to measure the preventive maintenance and housekeeping performance. For measuring the performance of process management, investment in high technology, introducing the new management system, and sales growth are used as the TQM measure scales where internal business perspective, innovation and learning, and financial perspective are considered to measure the organisational performance using BSC approaches. The key performance measures are selected from quality management and performance measurement literature, and these metrics are then matched to the BSC category (Ahire *et al.*, 1996; Hoque, 2003; Mahmood *et al.*, 2014).

TQM and BSC converge on several dimensions. First, the strategic management accounting scholars addressed that traditional accounting methods do not assist quality drivers and quality driver analysis and that the administrative control process should be adjusted to enable TQM (Schiffauerova and Thomas, 2006; Langfield-Smith, 1997). Traditional accounting is useful for evaluating production and cost but not for evaluating the quality or solving problems because the quality rate is driven by non-financial elements such as product and process design, rework, and on-time delivery (Schiffauerova and Thomas, 2006; Johnson, 1994; Hoque and Alam, 1999). The non-financial performance measurements are stronger predictors of management effort and represent the several causes of future financial performance (Ittner & Larcker, 1995, Ittner & Larcker, 1997; Banker *et al.*, 2000). As a result, non-financial measures must augment financial efforts to provide TQM support. Non-financial elements can have goals and objectives, and metrics can deliver feedback and rewards. According to Ittner *et al.* (1997), establishing balance

necessitates managers doing well on several dimensions. To gain management objectives at the level of the strategic business unit and the level of the corporation, managers must focus on both financial and non-financial criteria. By focusing on the conventional financial indication, management cannot take a comprehensive perspective of how activities contribute to the achievement of the organization's strategic goals. According to Hogg and Hogg (1993), using BSC increases the likelihood of success for continuous improvement or quality management projects. According to Yamin and Gunasekaran (1999), the quest for constant quality development necessitates firms identifying employees' cognitive demands in order to improve a quality approach based on agreed values, as well as identifying customers' cognitive demands to understand their purchasing behaviours. As a result, to succeed, the corporation must align the cognitive needs of its consumers' values and resources. As a strategic management system, the BSC is a helpful tool for regulating individuals. Organisations must select a proper mix of BSC predictors to reduce cognitive friction between corporate and frontline management. As part of the total management package, TQM can also help in this context due to its multidimensional focus. As a result, both TQM and BSC techniques include information provisions, management reactions, communication, control and design, and the impact of these aspects is required to accomplish desired results (Hoque, 2003).

2.8 Hypothesis development and Framework

Based on the literature review, this study developed the following key hypothesis, which is tested using structural equational modeling.

Hypothesis H1: Hard QM has a significant direct impact on organisational financial performance.

Hypothesis H2: Hard QM has a significant direct impact on organisational non-financial performance.

Hypothesis H3: Soft QM has a significant direct impact on organisational financial performance.

Hypothesis H4: Soft QM has a significant direct impact on organisational non-financial performance.

Hypothesis H5: Technological innovation has a significant direct impact on organisational financial performance.

Hypothesis H6: Technological innovation has a significant direct impact on organisational non-financial performance.

Hypothesis H7: Administrative innovation has a significant direct impact on organisational financial performance.

Hypothesis H8: Administrative innovation has a significant direct impact on organisational non-financial performance.

H9: Hard QM has a significant direct impact on administrative innovation

H10: Hard QM has a significant direct impact on technological innovation

H11: Soft QM has a significant direct impact on administrative innovation

H12: Soft QM has a significant direct impact on technological innovation

2.9 Theoretical framework based on the hypothesis

The hypotheses have been developed to examine the impact of organic and mechanic aspects of TQM on organisational financial and nonfinancial performance in the first part of the literature review. Simultaneously, in the second part, the hypotheses have been developed to identify the impact of administrative and technological innovation on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Finally, in the third phase of the literature review, the hypotheses have been developed to identify the impact and relationship between quality management and innovation practices on organisational financial and nonfinancial performance. Therefore, based on the proposed hypotheses, the conceptual research framework is presented below in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Theoretical Conceptual Framework

2.10 Conclusion

TQM has mainly been regarded as a management approach that provides competitive success depending on the successful implementation. However, as market conditions change, it is projected that the competitiveness will change with quality becoming one of the qualifying requirements and flexibility, responsiveness, and, most importantly, innovation taking over as winning order criteria (Tidd *et al.*, 2005). From a TQM and innovation standpoint, this discussion reassesses the need for TQM and innovation implementation in businesses and their impact on organisational performance. This research examines the connection between TQM and innovation practice's impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance and the relationship between the organic and mechanistic aspects of TQM and innovation based on organisational performance. As a quality management philosophy, TQM is divided into soft and hard aspects (Prajogo and Sohal, 2001). This chapter discusses TQM's soft and hard aspects,

covering multiple elements. In addition, the impact of soft and hard elements on organisational financial and nonfinancial perspectives are discussed following the BSC approach under four criteria: internal organisational perspective, innovation and learning perspective, customer perspective, and financial perspective. Similarly, organisational innovation practices are discussed under administrative and technological aspects. The impact of innovation on organisational performance is also addressed following BSC approaches. All elements of TQM and innovation practices are pinned into the four perspectives of balance scorecard approaches to identify financial and non-financial performance.

There are many common aspects identified with TQM and innovation. Mainly the soft part of TQM supports the administrative innovation elements. Conversely, technological innovation is closely linked to the hard aspect of TQM. Both factors emerge to counter the intense competitive pressure that is the manufacturing organisation are facing recently. TQM and innovation share several characteristics, among them, continuous improvement is an important aspect of both TQM and innovation practices. Furthermore, the organisational structure is an important part of TQM and creativity. These similarities imply that organisations adopting TQM successfully may be more innovative than those not. In this sense, it can further be implied that TQM implementation may be a vehicle for organizations to become more innovative. Conversely, it can be discussed that innovation could improve the TQM performance or both combined influence on organisational performance (Singh and Smith, 2004).

The requirement for quality and innovation in service firms has become important for business excellence and competitive advantage. Therefore, many scholars have been compelled and inspired to perform a study on the link between TQM techniques and innovation (Karani & Bichanga, 2012). The current literature has offered new perspectives and techniques from many aspects of the TQM practice and innovation relationship (Bon and Mustafa, 2013). So, the complexity emerges from the range of TQM practices and aspects, as well as the diversity of innovation patterns. Hoang *et al.* (2006) researched on the influence of TQM on innovation and found that TQM has a favourable impact on the degree of newness as well as the number of new goods or services provided or produced. Similarly, Martinez-Costa and Martinez-Lorente (2008) discovered a positive relationship between TQM and innovation which defined that TQM has a favourable effect on both product and process innovations. As a result, it is argued that enterprises must apply TQM not only to improve performance, but also to enable and ease the innovation culture. Following the research questions, this study made a critical discussion in the literature review by covering TQM and innovation practices aspects and finding the link between

TQM and innovation in organisational performance. Furthermore, the conceptual research framework and a preliminary conceptual model were developed, followed by the hypothesis in the literature review. Studies on the link between TQM and innovation are still limited in the literature, while the role of service industries is growing and increasingly significant. Therefore, most of the research that explored the relationship between TQM and innovation was undertaken in manufacturing or both manufacturing and service businesses with the exception of no such study focusing just on service firms.

The paper hypothesised and conceptualised the relationship between TQM practices and innovation using a model that included top management leadership, employee suggestion, small group problem solving, task-related training, supplier quality management, customer relationship, and corporate social responsibilities as the independent variables under the dependent variable of Soft TQM. Similarly, the dependent variable of hard aspects of TQM is categorised by the elements of strategic quality planning, process management, preventive maintenance, housekeeping, quality information, and management benchmarking as the independent variables. Similarly, organisational innovation practices are discussed following the dependent variables of administrative and technological aspects where internal organisational innovation, marketing innovation, and strategic innovation are independent variables under the dependent variable of administrative and independent variables such as technological product, technological process, and technological technology innovation are included under the dependent variable of technological innovation. The impact of soft and hard TQM is directed to the dependent variables of financial and nonfinancial perspective, where internal organisational perspective, innovation and learning perspective, customer perspective, and financial perspective are included as independent variables.

In addition, the relationship between total quality management and innovation practices on organisational performance is discussed. Many experts believe, there is a substantial association between TQM and Innovation practices to increase organisational performance. Literature also defined that TQM and innovation both positively impact each other. In contrast, research outcomes found TQM and innovation have no significant relationship to impact on one another performance. Therefore, the outcome is controversial on this issue. In order to answer this controversy, a research framework is established, which is preceded by a theoretical explanation of TQM's multidimensionality when implemented in various organisational perspectives. Similarly, administrative and technological dimensionality has also been focused in various organisational aspects. Therefore, after the literature review, several hypotheses have been

developed, followed by the impact of the soft and hard aspects of TQM and administrative and technological aspects of innovation on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Based on the hypothesis, the conceptual framework has been developed (see Figure 2.1). Later, the primary data outcomes test the hypothesis to justify the impact and relationship between TQM and innovation on organisational financial and non-financial performance.

Chapter Three: Research Methodology

3.0 Introduction

Research is one of the ways of finding answers to research questions which must follow a specific process that is a framework of a set of philosophies, using procedures, methods, and techniques that need to be tested for their validity and reliability. It is also important that the process design be unbiased and objective (Kumar, 2014). The methodology chapter should explain how the researcher achieves the solution (Saunders *et al.*, 2012). As a result, the researcher must select the proper research philosophy, approach, and strategy to complete the research project and reach a conclusion (Gomm, 2008). The main subject of this chapter is to explain the study conducted for this research activity and how the data was obtained in the most appropriate way to assess and establish evidence for this project. This research followed six stages to formulate an effective methodology: research philosophy, approaches, methodological choices, strategies, time horizons, and techniques and procedures for data collection and analysis (Saunders *et al.*, 2012). Therefore, the above six steps are discussed in this chapter.

3.1 Research philosophy

For successful entrepreneurial research, it is necessary to have a good understanding of philosophical issues. As a result, the researcher needs to explore the appropriate philosophical issue to ensure the quality of management research (Gray, 2009; Kumar, 2014). According to Saunders *et al.* (2012), research philosophy varies depending on the research questions the researcher is attempting to answer, which also differs based on the circumstances. Furthermore, Saunders *et al.* (2012) have emphasised ontology and epistemology as two fundamental ways of thinking about research philosophy. In addition, management study has considered axiology's philosophical issue (Kumar, 2014; Bryman, 2016). According to Sanders *et al.* (2012), a dispute on ontology and epistemology is unavoidable when deciding between positivist and interpretivist research philosophies or quantitative and qualitative methods. However, Teddlie and Tshakkori (2009) proposed a multi-dimensional set of a continuum rather than discrete views for philosophical issues and unrealistic practice of continua. In this case, Teddlie and Tshakkori (2009) suggested the pragmatist perspective, where notions are meaningful to reflect the action. Ontological philosophy concerns the nature of reality and the presence of relationships between persons, society, and the world in general (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2008). On the other hand, epistemology concerns appropriate knowledge in a specific field. It mandates that the

investigator define appropriate understanding in the researcher's research area and what information is provided to be legitimate and related to facts due to thorough testing (Bryman and Bell, 2015; Saunders *et al.*, 2012). The positivist philosophy generates testable research questions and allows explanations to be compared against preferable knowledge of world. Interpretivism is a set of ideas that focuses on the significance of people's engagement in social and natural life. An interpretivist perspective is ideal for business and management study (Eriksson and Kovalainen, 2008). According to Saunders *et al.* (2012), axiology is a branch of philosophy that allows researchers to recognise and understand the function of their values and opinions in collecting and interpreting data rather than trying to eliminate or balance it. The axiology philosophical approach has also been considered in management research (Bryman, 2016; Kumar, 2014). Therefore, researchers need to understand ontology, epistemology, and axiological philosophies before embarking on a research design (Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2012). According to Teddlie and Tashakkori (2009), a multi-dimensional set of approaches rather than separate positions for philosophical approaches, researchers' right option is adopting a pragmatist position.

3.1.1 Justification for choosing the philosophy (Pragmatism)

An effective entrepreneurial study necessitates understanding how management and micro-politics operate, how corporate change comes about, and how staff understanding is shaped and maintained (Watson, 2011). This study aims to identify the positive impact of TQM (soft and hard aspects) and innovation (Technological and Administrative) on the Bangladesh RMG industry's business performance. The relationship between TQM and innovation would be identified by analysing both subjective and objective complex issues. According to Saunders *et al.* (2012), and Tashakkori and Teddlie (2010), pragmatism under the epistemological philosophy deals with complex management issues, and employee's thoughts and beliefs are highly considered by the researcher to get deeper into the fact for gaining the actual data from the real-life experiences. According to Creswell (2011), using quantitative and qualitative methods in a single study is better for understanding the research problem. Saunders *et al.* (2012) also defined pragmatism as an action-supported concept where one position may be more appropriate than another for answering a particular question. Therefore, pragmatists' view supports a different philosophical position which is also defined by Tashakkori and Teddlie (2010). According to Tashakkori and Teddlie (2010), pragmatism endorses using quantitative and qualitative research methods in the same research study. It does not support post-positivism or constructivism concerning logic and epistemology. However, it supports both points of view for making an efficient and applied

research philosophy. Therefore, pragmatism is the right choice of philosophy for practical and real research work based on field activities following mixed methods. In this research task, the mixed methods concurrent triangulation design is applied. According to Tashakkori and Teddlie (2010), mixed methods concurrent triangulation design consists of two distinct phases: quantitative and qualitative. The data would be collected and analyzed separately from the RMG industries in Bangladesh, and then the data result would be compared to bring the outcome of the research questions and objectives. According to Creswell (2011), this technique is justified because individual quantitative and quantitative data gathering and analysis provide a general grasp of the study subject. The qualitative data and analysis clarify and explain the statistical results by delving deeper into the participants' perspectives. Hence pragmatism philosophy would be the justified philosophy for this research work.

3.2 Research Approach

When performing a research project, the scholar must establish which theoretical approach is used. It is frequently described as three techniques based on the author's reasoning: deductive, inductive, and abductive (Saunders *et al.*, 2016; Tashakkori and Tiddle, 2010).

The deductive approach involves the construction of a theory, which is then put to the test through a sequence of propositions. It builds the hypothesis on top of an existing theory and then articulates the research strategy to test it (Saunders *et al.*, 2012; Gray, 2009). According to Bryman (2016), a top-down strategy is used in deductive reasoning because the result logically follows from theory, hypothesis, and observation to confirmation. The inductive approach is distinguished by shifting from the specific to the universal (Bryman and Bell, 2015). In the inductive approach, no framework informs data gathering at the outset, and the study focus is thus developed after the data has been collected (Flick, 2011). The investigation begins with observations, and patterns in the data are looked for. This method is often employed in qualitative research by interviewing on certain phenomena (Flick, 2011).

3.2.1 Justification for selection of research approach (Abduction)

According to Saunders *et al.* (2012), the selection of a research approach depends on the emphasis of the research and the nature of the research topics. According to Tashakkori and Tiddle (2010), the research topic has a wealth of literature for defining the theoretical framework, and the hypothesis tends to be deductive. Conversely, a new topic with little existing literature might be appropriate for an inductive approach by generating data and analysis and reflecting

upon the theoretical themes the data suggest. According to Saunders *et al.* (2012), moving from theory to data is a common characteristic of the deductive approach. Data to theory is inductive, but an abductive approach moves back and more, as the abductive approach combines deductive and inductive. According to Charmaz (2014), abduction begins with observing a surprising fact and then a possible theory on how this could have occurred. In this research, the researcher observed the impact of TQM and innovation practices on organisational performance. The researcher also will examine the relationship between TQM and innovation on business performance. To find the actual facts and credible data, the researcher follows both quantitative and qualitative methods for data collection and analysis, which enables the researcher to find and collect any credible data or information at any stage in the research process under the abductive approach. According to Easterby-Smith *et al.* (2008), for three reasons for abduction research approaches are important. First: the abductive approach enables the researcher to make more informed decisions about the research design (Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2008). Secondly, it helps pick up the fundamental research strategies and methodological choices. Thirdly, the knowledge of different research traditions enables the researcher to overcome the barrier in the research process to choosing the suitable form of research design (Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2008). The concurrent triangulation method supports collecting both quantitative and qualitative data concurrently. The method also supports analysing the collected information separately and then comparing them. Hence, an abductive approach is the choice for the research task (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2010). Similarly, the abductive approach is a platform with a wealth of information in one context but less in another, enabling the researcher to modify an existing theory (Saunders *et al.*, 2012). The research task has a wealth of knowledge and information in the context of a developed economy but has a real gap in Bangladesh as a growing economy. Hence, abduction is significant for this research task.

3.3 Overview of Research methodology: Mixed Method

In the literature, there are numerous definitions of mixed methods as defined by Tashakkori and Teddlie (2003), Saunders *et al.* (2010), and Green *et al.* (2007), mixed method research entails the combination of quantitative and qualitative methodologies for data gathering and analysis in a single study.

Quantitative research methodology focuses on fact measurement and entails the collecting of numerical data based on the assumption that reality is fixed and quantifiable (Creswell, 2011). The positivist research philosophy encompasses quantitative research methods (Saunders *et*

al., 2012). A hypothesis (e.g., impacts and relationships among variables) is formed based on a theory in the positivist philosophy to test its application in a specific circumstance via a deductive procedure (Bryman and Bell, 2015). It is defined by Balnaves and Caputi (2001), quantitative techniques are used because they:

- i. Relatively larger samples use to enable broader analysis.
- ii. Emphasize quantitative data from independent respondents.
- iii. Apply statistical tools to examine the relationship between variables, draw conclusions, and extrapolate findings to specific phenomena.
- iv. They make it easy to write a report and generalize findings.

However, qualitative research is frequently used to better understand human behaviour (Minichiello and Kottler, 2009) by posing simple, generally open-ended questions about what, why, and how to get insight into respondents' viewpoints (Molina-Azorin, 2016). Because qualitative research is subjective, it fits quite well with social constructivism (Neuman, 2014). In qualitative research, the theory is important because the researcher may either test it or establish and develop new theories through an inductive approach (Blumberg, 2014). According to Silverman (2011), qualitative research has the following advantages:

- i. It can undertake a detailed analysis with a small sample size.
- ii. Involves gathering non-numerical information based on social reality.
- iii. Enables thematic analysis of observations, which can reveal new aspects of the phenomenon, and
- iv. Concentrates on a specific issue.

This study engaged qualitative and quantitative methods at the same time independently to deeply identify the impact and relationship established among various hypotheses (chapter two) on the context of TQM practices and Innovation practices to the organisational performance. Therefore, after a careful review of this existing research, this study employed a mixed-method concurrent triangulation research methodology where quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis carried out independently without interfering each other. However, the data results are compared at the end. According to Flick (2011), an explanatory study helps to establish causal relationships between variables. The process mostly emphasises studying a situation or a problem to explain the relationship between variables. Similarly, it is explained that explanatory research is conducted to identify the extent and nature of the cause-and-effect relationships.

According to Creswell (2011), explanatory research can identify the impacts of specific changes or existing norms. Hence, from the research aim and questions, it is proved that the nature of the research design is practiced from exploratory as the research explored the impact of TQM and innovation practices then described. The research finally demands the relationship between TQM and Innovation on the performance of the Bangladesh RMG industry. Therefore, the explanatory approach is justified for this study.

A number of factors have been considered in this research project considering the appropriate research method. Very few research has been conducted on the Readymade Garments Industries of Bangladesh. Also, very little research has been carried out on innovation and TQM impacts and relationships on the RMG industry's performance in Bangladesh. Therefore, online resources may not be sufficient for this research based on the Bangladesh perspective, but the theories and practical work might be the right path for this research process. Therefore, one position might be better than others, or both might be equal to answer the research questions under the pragmatism philosophy that led to mixed or multiple methods design covering both qualitative and quantitative under the abduction approach (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2003). Based on the availability and access to both floor level and management level of employees, this research has taken the opportunity to cover both the quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis under the view of mixed methods. This research project aims to examine the impact of TQM and Innovation practices in the RMG industry in Bangladesh and the relationship between TQM and innovation under that context. Hence, the two vital parts of this research are TQM and innovation, which may or may not be familiar to all levels of employees equally. Therefore, to get into the depth of this research and bring out the rich data from all employees, it is important to equally emphasize quantitative and qualitative methods for data collection and analysis. So, the concurrent triangulation design under the mixed methods is the right choice of research method for this research task.

3.4 Research Ethics

Business research is expected to be done accurately and honestly when involving human participants. Therefore, it can be assumed that ethical issues are defined as complex and demanding for any researcher (Bryman and Bell, 2015). The research is conducted following the University Ethics Committee (2016) ethics guidelines based on the four major principles, which are: absence of maleficence (not harm), beneficence (do positive good), autonomy (show respect for rights of self-determination), and justice (treat people fairly). Research ethics are

concerned with procedural and practical phases (Guillemin and Gillam, 2004). Ethics are essential to research since they are rooted in the morality of a person's actions (Edwards and Mauthner, 2002). A framework of ethical conduct was prepared before the start of this research, followed by the University of the West of Scotland's publishing criteria (UWS). Before seeking formal clearance from the school's ethics committee, this ethical code of conduct was negotiated with the Director of Studies. The application was approved, and the committee gave the authorisation to begin collecting data (a copy of the ethical approval is attached in Appendix one). Throughout the data-gathering process, the UWS ethical code of conduct was observed.

A survey strategy was chosen to obtain primary data. In the first step, a questionnaire was handed over to the participants and selectively asked for an interview for depth discussion. Those who showed their interest in having interviews were conducted on the day of collecting the survey questionnaires. At all times, confidentiality, data security, and anonymity were maintained (Rowe *et al.*, 2012). The BGMEA head and garments administration was given a brief overview of the project, its nature, and its goals, as well as assurances that confidentiality and anonymity were preserved following the General Data Protection Regulation 2018 (GDPR) and the Data Protection Act 2018 (DPA). 371 participants answered survey questionnaires, 15 participated in the interview, but four did not participate in the interviews without justifying any reason. The willing participants were given the option of choosing the interview day, time, and location. Participants were told about the study and ensured their privacy and anonymity. So, consent has been signed by the participants where it is mentioned that participants are allowed to review their transcripts if desired. Therefore, an ethical approach was considered to gather the data where verbal and written consent was given to all participants. The participants were reminded that they had the right not to answer any questions if they were uncomfortable. They may withdraw from the study at any time and remove any information provided. It is also assured that all data gathered will be anonymized and stored securely to protect the respondents and the data sources (Saunders *et al.*, 2012).

3.5 Cross-Sectional Survey Method and respondents

The cross-sectional survey is recommended because of its accuracy, standardized method, scales' dependability, cost-effectiveness, ease of data collection, comparison, and capacity to accurately reflect the population (Saunders *et al.*, 2011; Osuagwu, 2020). Researchers can collect meaningful data at a single point in time using a cross-sectional research design (Ritchie *et al.*, 2003). Respondents have the option of selecting the best response from a selection of

options to record their thoughts on specific subjects (Blumberg *et al.*, 2011). According to Saunders *et al.* (2012), cross-sectional could also be the choice for qualitative or multiple research strategies based on the short length of the period. Therefore, cross-sectional studies are justified for this research work as the qualitative interview would be conducted alongside the quantitative survey. Additionally, 'handover and collect' and face-to-face survey procedures are time-consuming with moderate cost, though a high response rate makes them efficient. Mailing a questionnaire is very cost-effective but has a lower response rate. The educational background of respondents, the social development of the country, infrastructure development (e.g., internet facilities, access to IT services, academic qualification, etc.), available funds, and the size and efficiency of the mailing system in a country each affect the survey technique chosen. This study used a self-administered handover and collection survey technique to save time and cost, considering the lack of E-mailing facilities.

This study used a cross-sectional design to gather data, analyse it, and draw conclusions about the target population. Due to time and cost restrictions, a cross-sectional study approach was chosen over a longitudinal research strategy (Sekaran and Bougie, 2019; Saunders *et al.*, 2011). Longitudinal studies collect data over time and study the relationship between groups of variables or people (Collis and Hussey, 2013). The longitudinal design is useful for tracking and comprehending change trends over time (Kumar, 2014; Zikmund *et al.*, 2013). According to Kumar (2014), a cross-sectional study is ideal when dealing with any topic relating to a circumstance, specific issue, or understanding of a population's specific behaviour or attitude. Cross-sectional research is frequently used to generalise quantitative findings. The cross-sectional survey is especially beneficial for big sample sizes because it is the most reliable means of gathering responses to several questions (Babbie, 2007). The Likert scale 5 agreement rating type of questionnaire was applied by asking the opinion of strongly agreed, agreed, neutral, disagreed, and strongly disagreed to get the preference from the respondents. The semi-structured interview questions were used to obtain qualitative data from the respondents. Because of time constraints and available resources for data collection, this study used a cross-sectional survey research approach rather than a longitudinal strategy. The use of structured questionnaires to gather data for quantitative analyses and semi-structured interviews to collect data for qualitative studies has remained a popular choice among academics. Furthermore, researchers are compatible with the cross-sectional design (Bryman, 2016). As a result, structured questionnaires were administered throughout the survey to obtain primary data for testing the model's proposed hypothesis.

3.6 Sample size

A crucial part of survey research is selecting an acceptable sample size (Teddle and Tashakkori, 2009). To avoid sampling error, a presentable sample size is required (Saunders *et al.*, 2011). A key statistical tool for determining optimal sample size is called power analysis (Bruin, 2006). The G*Power 3.1 program (See Figure 3.1) was used to conduct a power analysis to estimate the minimum sample size for this study (Faul *et al.*, 2009). A priori analysis was performed using linear multiple regression to establish the required sample size for this investigation, with the target power level set at $(1-\beta)$ and a confidence level of 0.95 percent.

Figure 3.1: Power Analysis to calculate Sample Size

However, the significant acceptance level was established $\alpha = 0.05$ with a medium effect size of $f^2 = 0.15$ based on the model's six predictors. Using these criteria, the minimal sample size is 107, as demonstrated by the fact that 100 or fewer survey replies are commonly considered to

be a small sample size. A sample of 100 to 200 responses is regarded as a medium sample size, and more than 200 responses are called a large sample (Kline, 2015). Ding et al. (1995) suggested a sample size of 100-150 for quantitative analysis, and Raykov and Marcoulides (2006) advised using the rule of ratio to calculate a suitable sample size, which is calculated by multiplying the number of variables by 10. This study comprises six variables, so $6 \times 10 = 60$, indicating the minimum sample size of sixty is significant to run the SEM. This rule is also known as the $N: q \geq 10$ rule.

A large sample size, according to researchers, improves the accuracy and dependability of results (Creswell and Clark, 2011; Dawson, 2002; Saunders *et al.*, 2011). As a result, this study aimed for a bigger sample size and was administered at random in 25 readymade garments industries in Bangladesh on a random basis, with 371 respondents freely participating. The data screening procedure was completed with 350 responses.

3.7 Questionnaire Design

Questionnaires are one of the most often used data collection tools. As a result, the researcher is concerned about its validity and reliability. The phrasing of the questions can influence the validity of the questionnaire, but inadequate question sequencing, a confusing structure, or the design of the questionnaire can all undermine its validity. Hence, in this research task, those above issues are considered to avoid in the questionnaires. The researcher considered covering the topics TQM in both soft and hard aspects and Innovation thinking in the format of administrative and technological in terms of content and detail (Dawson, 2002). To ensure the generalisability and external validity of the findings, the researcher has avoided asking spurious, irrelevant questions that increase the length of a questionnaire, which may reduce the number of responses, as low response rates limit the generalizability and external validity of the findings. The researcher rechecked the questionnaires to ensure they linked with the research questions, aims, and objectives. If identified and dissimilarities, the correction was made based on the research objectives and questions to ensure the validity and generalizability of the questionnaires. The result was measured and did not find any change, so reliability was justified. All survey scales were pre-tested and used in previous research studies. Surveys were tested in pilot research from a garment factory to reduce mistakes and boost reliability. Six Bangladeshi individuals were called and requested to complete the surveys over the phone. The data were filtered using the Standard Deviation (SD) technique, and none of the responses were determined to be unengaged, which means that they were not indifferent. For maximal scales,

Cronbach's α was greater than 0.70. The survey scales were developed from well-known research journals published in the field of social research, namely on business and entrepreneurship, with a focus on TQM and innovation. Table 3.1 shows a summary of the scales used and their sources.

Table 3.1: Summary of scales used

No	Scale	Subscales
1	Organic Quality Management - OGQ	4
2	Mechanistic Quality Management - MCQ	4
3	Administrative Innovation - AD	3
4	Technological Innovation - TC	3
5	Financial Performance - F	3
6	Non-Financial Performance - NF	3

Therefore, from table 3.1 above, it is shown that a total of 20 subscales are available under 6 scales, with a maximum of 4 and a minimum of 3 subscales in each scale. Table 3.2 shows a summary of the total subscales under each respective scale and the number of items available in each subscale.

Table 3.2: scales and the number of items that are available in each subscale

No of Extracts	Scale	Accepted Subscales after EFA	Entities of Subscales	Number of Items
1	Organic Quality Management - OGQ	4	i. Top management Leadership –B1	• B1=6
			ii. Employee suggestion –B2	• B2=5
			iii. Small group problem solving--B3	• B3=5
			iv. Task-related training – B4	• B4=4
			v. Supplier quality management –B5	• B5=7
			vi. Customer relationship – B6	• B6=6
2	Mechanistic Quality Management - MCQ	4	i. Strategic quality planning –C1	• C1=6
			ii. Process management –C2	• C2=6
			iii. Preventive Maintenance –C3	• C3=5
			iv. Housekeeping–C4	• C4=7
			v. Quality information –C5	• C5=5
			vi. Marketing Benchmarking-C6	• C6=6
3	Administrative Innovation - AD	3	i. Internal organisational innovation –AD1	• AD1=3
			ii. Marketing Innovation—AD2	• AD2=3
			iii. Strategic Innovation—AD3	• AD3=3
4	Technological Innovation - TC	3	i. Product/Service Technology	• ET1=3
			ii. Process Technology	• ET2=3
			iii. Technological Technology	• ET3=4
5	Financial Performance - F	3	i. Inventory Management for Financial gain –F1	• F1=5
			ii. Benchmarking for Financial gain –F2	• F2=7
			iii. Average marketing and Financial performance –F3	• F3=4
6	Non-Financial Performance - NF	3	i. Social Responsibility--NF1	• NF1=5
			ii. Customers Perspective –NF2	• NF2=4
			iii. Innovation and Learning perspective—NF3	• NF3=5.

Compared to close-ended questions, open-ended questions provide respondents with more flexibility in answering them (Couper *et al.*, 2001; Dillman, 2011). Multiple-choice and scale questions are examples of structured questions, and Likert-scale questions are often employed in social scientific research due to their nature, simplicity, and composition (Malhotra, 2006). Respondents can convey the strength of their reaction using the Likert scale by selecting from a variety of options (DeVellis and Thorpe, 2021). Although Likert-scale inquiries can present several options, Malhotra (2017) argues that the nine-point Likert scale is difficult for respondents to answer owing to cognitive limits. This study employs a five-point Likert scale so respondents can more easily participate and score the ordinal categories along a continuum (Neuman, 2014). The questionnaire comprises three sections. The first section contains the organic and mechanistic aspects of TQM elements. The second section contains the administrative and technological innovation elements. The third section contains organisational financial and nonfinancial performance based on a balanced scorecard approach.

3.8 Measurement Scales

Several quality management researchers defined organic elements (Hoang *et al.*, 2006; Feng *et al.*, 2006; Prajogo and Sohal, 2004) or soft components (Lewis *et al.*, 2006; Rahman and Bullock, 2005; López-Mielgo *et al.*, 2009; Fotopoulos and Psomas, 2009) are methods which attempt to encourage the human aspects of a quality system. In light of the above references, Maistry *et al.* (2017) developed organic TQM features and related assessment criteria, which are accepted in this research work to select the indicators and assessment criteria. This study used five-point Likert scale assessment criteria for all measured variables. The following seven organic TQM features and associated assessment criteria are shown in Table 3.3 below.

Table 3.3: Questionnaires for Soft QM

B1. Top Management commitment in quality management:	
1	All major department heads within our plant accept their responsibility for Quality
2	Management gives top priority to evaluate quality performance
3	Top management sit together to set a comprehensive goal for quality process
4	In top management meetings, quality issues are reviewed as a top priority
5	Top management consider quality improvement as a way to increase profit
6	All manager/department head works toward encouraging Just in Time production (JIT).
Items	Sources: Flynn <i>et al.</i> (1994), Kaynak (2003), Ho <i>et al.</i> (1999), Anderson <i>et al.</i> (1995), Ahire <i>et al.</i> (1996), and Maistry <i>et al.</i> (2017).
B2. Employee suggestions:	
1	Management takes all product and process improvement suggestions seriously
2	We feel free to make suggestions for performance improvement at this plant
3	Management gives us feedback on our suggestions about work-related issues
4	Many useful suggestions are implemented at this plant
5	My suggestions are taken seriously in the organisation.
Items	Sources: Zeng <i>et al.</i> (2015).
B3. Small-Group Problem solving:	
1	Our plant forms teams to solve a problem
2	During problem-solving sessions, we make an effort to get all team members opinions and ideas before making a decision
3	Many problems have been solved in the past three years through small group problem-solving session
4	Problem-solving teams have helped improve the manufacturing process at this plant
5	Employee teams are encouraged to solve their problems as much as possible.
Items	Sources: Zeng <i>et al.</i> (2015), Flynn <i>et al.</i> (1995), and Maistry <i>et al.</i> (2017).
B4. Task-related training for employees:	
1	We receive training and development in workplace skills regularly
2	Management at this plant believes that continual training and upgrading of employee skills is important
3	We train up our employees for different units related task
4	Our employees regularly receive training to improve their skills.
Items	Sources: Maistry <i>et al.</i> (2017).
B5. Supplier quality management:	
1	We have a long term relationship with our suppliers
2	Our organisation has reduced the number of suppliers since implementing JIT purchasing
3	Our organisation selects suppliers based on quality
4	Our organisation selects suppliers based on price
5	Our organisation selects suppliers based on a flexible delivery schedule
6	Our organisation has a supplier rating system
7	Our suppliers are strongly involved in our product, process, and service development process
Items	Sources: Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2000) and Maistry <i>et al.</i> (2017).
B6. Customer relations:	
1	We frequently are in close contact with our customers
2	Our management knows our customers
3	Our customers often visit our office or workplace
4	Our customers often give us feedback on the quality and delivery performance
5	We note our customer's opinions and feedback.
Items	Sources: Maistry <i>et al.</i> (2017).
B7. Social Responsibility	
1	We recycle our factory waste
2	Noise levels caused by our firm is maintaining the optimal level
3	We don't dump the dyeing and washing dirty water into the river
4	Our firm is concerned about low carbon emission
5	We follow the standard government payment policy
6	We have more than one fire exit door on each floor for our employees.
Items	Sources: Maistry <i>et al.</i> (2017), Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2000).

Mechanistic/Hard Aspect

TQM is made up of many aspects that can be divided into mechanistic and organic components. According to researchers Lewis *et al.* (2006), Rahman and Bullock (2005), López-Mielgo *et al.* (2009), and Fotopoulos and Psomas (2009), the components of hard quality management or mechanistic elements also defined by Hoang *et al.* (2006), Hoang *et al.* (2010), Feng *et al.* (2006), Prajogo and Sohal (2004), are practice related to corporate planning, quality standards compliance, conformance to specification, and use of TQM tools such as statistical process control and Pareto analysis. Based on the discussion in the literature review (Chapter Two) and measurement scale Table 3.1 and Table 3.2, the following six subscales are pointed out to measure the mechanistic aspect of quality measurement using 5-point Likert scale assessment criteria.

Table 3.4: Questionnaires for Hard QM

C1. Strategic Quality Planning	
1	We have a mission and vision statement on Quality management
2	We develop our strategies considering customers' requirements.
3	We develop our strategies and plans considering the firm's capabilities
4	The management communicates its strategies and objectives to the staff
5	Customer needs are taken into account when establishing objectives
6	Our quality strategies affect all organisational areas.
Items	Sources: Maistry <i>et al.</i> (2017), Rao <i>et al.</i> (1999).
C2. Process Management:	
1	A large percentage of the processes on the shop floor is currently under statistical quality control
2	We make extensive use of statistical techniques to reduce variance in the process
3	We use charts to determine whether our manufacturing process is in control
4	We arrange training for basic statistical techniques (ex- histogram and control chart) in the organisation
5	We arrange training for advanced statistical techniques (ex-design of experiment and regression analysis) in the organization.
6	We meet our production schedule every day
7	We monitor our process using statistical process control.
Items	Sources: Zeng <i>et al.</i> (2015), Maistry <i>et al.</i> (2017).
C3. Preventive Maintenance:	
1	We upgrade inferior equipment, to prevent equipment problems
2	To improve equipment performance, we sometimes redesign equipment
3	We estimate the lifespan of our equipment so that repair or replacement can be planned
4	We use equipment diagnostic techniques to predict equipment lifespan
5	We conduct with the technical analyst of a major breakdown.
Items	Sources: Zeng <i>et al.</i> (2015), Maistry <i>et al.</i> (2017).
C4. Housekeeping:	
1	Our plant emphasises putting all tools and fixtures in their place
2	We give priority to keeping our plant neat and clean
3	Our plant is kept clean at all times
4	We have a special team to keep our plant clean frequently
5	Employees often have trouble finding the tools they need
6	We keep clear our floor fire exit doors at all time
7	We make ready our plant for next day work.
Items	Sources: Zeng <i>et al.</i> (2015). Prajogo and Sohal (2004).
C5. Quality Information:	
1	We note quality data such as defect rates, error rates, scrap, defects, errors in this organisation
2	Our quality data and information are regular and timely
3	Organisation pass information to the employees about a major emergency such as fire or building collapse
4	Management informs us of customers feedback regularly
5	We gather data from our buyers/suppliers to improve the quality of information.
Items	Zeng <i>et al.</i> (2015),
C6. Benchmarking:	
1	We compare relative cost positions with other firms
2	We compare our operating processes with other firms
3	We compare our technological capabilities with other firms
4	We compare our quality maintain procedures with other firms
5	We compare other firms human resource management practices and policies
6	We compare other firm's strategic decisions.
Items	Sources: Maistry <i>et al.</i> (2017), Rao <i>et al.</i> (1999).

Measurement Scale for Innovation

Administrative and technological innovation were the two main categories of innovation explored in this study following the measurement scale used by Chuang *et al.* (2010), Weerawardena (2003), Yonghong *et al.* (2005), Ling and Nasurdin (2010), and Maistry *et al.* (2017). Administrative innovation is the adoption of new working methods to increase organisational performance, structures, systems, and processes (Weerawardena, 2003). Technological innovation concerns an organisation's manufacturing process, products or services, and service delivery (Yonghong *et al.*, 2005). Chuang *et al.* (2010) and Maistry *et al.* (2017) used three subscales to measure innovation, such as internal organisational innovation, marketing innovation, and strategic innovation for administrative function. Similarly, technological products or services, technological technology, and technological process innovation are used to measure technological innovation. Following the previous study of Chuang *et al.* (2010) and Maistry *et al.* (2017), the indicators of administrative and technological innovation were used for the assessment criteria (see Table 2.1), have also employed in this research work (see Table 3.5) to develop the questionnaires considering the context of the Bangladesh garments industry.

Table 3.5: Questionnaires for Administrative innovation indicators

Adminstrative Innovation:	
Internal Organisational innovation	
1	Our organisation implemented new employee reward training schemes
2	Our organisation provides opportunities for staff to explore their talents.
3	Our organisation obtained new financing sources
Marketing innovation	
1	We have a strategy to involve buyers in the organisational innovation process to find new market
2	We have a strategy to involve suppliers in the organisational innovation practicing a process for existing market development
3	Our organisation has an appropriate marketing policy in response to its competitor's activities
Strategic Innovation	
1	Our organisation implemented improved computer-based administrative applications
2	Our organization promotes strategic alliance/partnership in response to changing economic environment
3	Our organisation has an appropriate policy in response to external stakeholders threats (ex-social issues, building clasped issues, fire, environmental issues).”
Items	Sources: Chuang <i>et al.</i> (2010), Maistry <i>et al.</i> (2017).
Technological Innovation:	
Technological Products	
1	We use innovative technology to develop new products
2	We use direct social media marketing to promote and sell the products
3	We have our own web-based online marketing platform
Technological Technology	
1	Our organisation is involved in adopting new technology for improving its R&Ds outputs.
2	We use smoke detectors or technological instruments to identify the cause of the fire
3	We introduced a technology-oriented new machine to increase productivity in this firm
Technological Process	
1	Our organisation's electronic mailing option is open and checked 24 hours for quick response to our buyers and suppliers.
2	Within the last 3 years, we have used upgraded technology in production sectors to reduce the delay of delivery days
3	We have a special online-based customer service team for 24 hours
4	We use a security camera to stop smoking in the factory by the employees.
Items	Sources Chuang <i>et al.</i> (2010), Maistry <i>et al.</i> (2017).

Organisational performance measurement

The balanced scorecard approach uses as a standard organisational performance measurement criterion (Banwet and Deshmukh, 2006; Bremser and Barsky, 2004), as defined that acceptable performance measurements should include both financial and non-financial indicators to evaluate operational results and processes (Maisel, 1992). Hence, organisational performance was evaluated from both a financial and non-financial aspect. In this research context, corporate social responsibilities (NF1), employee performance from the customer's perspective (NF2), and innovation and learning perspective (NF3) are considered as nonfinancial scales for assessment criteria. Conversely, Inventory management (F1), benchmarking for financial achievement (F2), and marketing & financial perspective (F3) are considered as financial scales for the assessment of organisational performance. This study followed the assessment scales that are used in the previous studies by Maisel (1992) and Maistry *et al.* (2017) (see Appendix 7) with 3-5 items each for financial and non-financial predictors under 5-point Likert scale assessment criteria, which is shown the Table 3.6 below.

Table 3.6: Assessment Scales for organization's financial and non-financial performance

Financial Performance:	
Inventory Management performance for financial achievement	
1	Purchase material turnover is high in our firm
2	Total inventory turnover is high in our firm
3	Financial benefit achieved as Supply chain cycle time has reduced
4	Our customer service system flexibility has increased for financial achievement
5	Financially benefited Product development cycle time has reduced
6	Financially benefited as Frequency of delivery time has increased.
Financial Achievement: As a result of benchmarking	
1	As a result of benchmarking, our unit production cost has increased
2	As a result of benchmarking, our products delivery rate became faster for financial achievement.
3	As a result of benchmarking, the online response became quicker
4	As a result of benchmarking, production cycle time increased
5	As a result of benchmarking, financial achievement increased as manufacturing quality is better to gain more orders from buyers.
6	As a result of benchmarking, our customer satisfaction is better than before and increased sales.
7	As a result of benchmarking, market share has increased
Market and financial performance	
1	Return on assets of the firm has increased
2	Market share of our firm has improved than before
3	Profits of our firm have grown than before
4	Sales of our firm have grown than before.
Items	Sources: Maisel (1992), Maistry <i>et al.</i> (2017).
Non-Financial Performance:	
Social Responsibility (Reputation and stakeholder concern)	
1	Water pollution caused by the waste of our firm has decreased
2	Noise levels caused by our firm have decreased
3	Carbon emission caused by our firm has decreased
4	Maintaining a standard payment policy, employee satisfaction has increased
5	Emergency fire exit door for each floor has brought a good reputation for this organisation
Employee performance for Customer satisfaction	
1	Customer satisfaction has improved
2	Our customer complaints have decreased over last three years
3	Our employee's organisational commitment is higher than before to meet the customer's product demands
4	Our employee's job performance is higher than before to keep the supply regularly
5	Our employee's morale is higher than before for serving the customers
Innovation performance	
1	The number of successful new product introduced of our firm is higher than other firms over last three years
2	The number of the successful process introduced of our firm is higher than other firms over last three years
3	The number of successful services introduced of our firm is higher than other firms over last three years
4	The use of the latest technological innovation in our new product has increased
5	The technological competitiveness in our firm has increased than before.
Items	Sources: Maisel (1992), Maistry <i>et al.</i> (2017).

3.9 Personal experiences during the survey process

Due to Bangladesh's social and cultural contexts, it is quite challenging to gather primary data (Saeed *et al.*, 2005). The researcher conferred with the Director of Studies (DoS) to overcome the difficulty while considering his personal experience. Following consultation, the researcher chose to visit several garment industries in Bangladesh to collect quantitative and qualitative primary data for this research study. During the first visit to the factory, the researcher handed over the quantitative questionnaires to the participants. Following the random purposive sampling, the researcher asked the specific participants for an interview. From those who agreed to participate, the researcher went a week after to conduct semi-structured interviews to collect the qualitative data. The researcher used to keep the consent form and questionnaires during the visit to the factory and politely asked the managers to join in the survey for this research work. Few selected candidates were invited to interview who showed their interest in participating in the survey. A week later, the researcher visited the factory to collect the handed-over survey questionnaires and conducted the interviews if they agreed.

Despite having permission to visit the factories, the researcher faced difficulties collecting data from a few factories. Due to the external stakeholder threat to the factory, maximum managers were initially seen as not cooperative to participate in an interview. However, after the consent letter, the researcher managed nineteen managers' consent to participate in the discussion. Two factories returned the unmarked questionnaires without participating though they accepted them on the first visit. In twenty-five factories, the researcher distributed 391 survey sample questionnaires. The data was then analysed to see if any hypotheses were correct. It took over one and a half months to complete this task (mid of March 2019-mid April 2019). Among many other factors, such as time, money, security, and considerable travel, the research culture (research and study gap) remained a major difficulty during the field study.

3.10 Data Analysis

This study uses Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to improve the components' validity and reliability. To increase the validity and reliability of the data, this study used exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). Based on the CFA results, this study used two different approaches, such as analyzing squared multiple correlations (R^2), measuring composite reliability, examining average variance extracted (AVE), and maximum shared value

(MSV) (Carr and Pearson, 1999; Boyer and Hult, 2005). The squared multiple correlations (R^2) on individual items were investigated in the first stage to measure the reliability.

The consistency of item-level errors within a single factor is referred to as reliability. The term "reliability" refers to the capacity of a set of variables to consistently load on the same component. The Cronbach's α test is used to complete the reliability test for each factor, which should have a value of at least 0.7 and at least three variables (Chang *et al.*, 2010). For unidimensionality, the extent to which the measurements in a scale reflect one underlying construct was investigated (Venkatraman and Grant, 1986). Prior to testing CFA, the factor loadings of each item were assessed using exploratory factor analysis (EFA). A factor loading under EFA greater than 0.40 or 0.45 is considered the minimal cut-off (Nunnally, 1975; Bhuian *et al.*, 2005; Kathuria, 2000; Terziovski *et al.*, 1997). The CFA method employs variance and covariance to investigate the causal relationship between observed and latent variables (Hoyle, 2012). As a result, the CFA method was employed to analyze the relationship between latent variables in this study. To explore the structure of the models, there are numerous commercial and free software tools available. Amos, Mplus, LISREL, EQS, and Stata are some examples (Byrne, 2012; Byrne, 2001; Kline, 2015). This study employed SPSS-Amos 26 for rigorous filtration (Kline, 2015). After the CFA was performed, the assumptions were statistically tested using structural equation modeling (SEM). Path analysis was carried out to find the direct and indirect impact among the variables (Bollen, 1989; Kaplan, 2008). To understand and explain their theoretical relationships, the variable's associations were estimated (Kline, 2015).

3.11 Qualitative Data Quality issues-validity, reliability

To ensure the validity of the semi-structured interviews, the research objectives, aims, and research questions would be considered and linked with the interview themes. For external validity and generalisability, two practical principles were followed, such as relevant subjects and increasing the sampling size or sub-samples representing different perspectives to emerge the new ideas. The standard sample size was made based on TQM, innovation, and business performance measurement tools to maintain generalisability and external validity. The same questions were asked with all respondents with the same tone and manner, avoiding the interviewer effect. If the explanation is needed for the respondents, it was followed so that it might not influence the respondents to answer being biased. It was highly followed the same protocol for all the respondents to avoid interviewer bias. This study has purposefully chosen managerial employees from the garments industry as study participants to get the real phenomena about

the TQM and innovation practices and their impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance (Saunders *et al.*, 2018). One of the potential issues that the researcher came upon was a linguistic barrier. Because not all respondents spoke English fluently, they were given the option of interviewing Bengali (the country's native language) or English (the country's official language) (Erling, 2017). As a result, all participants chose to speak Bengali. All 15 Interviewees (see Table 3.7) were first interviewed in Bengali, then translated and transcribed into English. Interviews were recorded in audio format with the interviewees' permission and a signed consent form. All interviews were carefully translated, so the researcher listened to the audio recordings carefully and frequently to guarantee that the transcripts were accurate. This study was completed with 15 interviews.

Table 3.7: Interviewee's Profile

	Interviewee	Business	Business Address
1	R01	Garments Industry	Dhaka, Bangladesh
2	R02	Garments Industry	Dhaka, Bangladesh
3	R03	Garments Industry	Dhaka, Bangladesh
4	R04	Garments Industry	Dhaka, Bangladesh
5	R05	Garments Industry	Dhaka, Bangladesh
6	R06	Garments Industry	Dhaka, Bangladesh
7	R07	Garments Industry	Dhaka, Bangladesh
8	R08	Garments Industry	Dhaka, Bangladesh
9	R09	Garments Industry	Dhaka, Bangladesh
10	R10	Garments Industry	Dhaka, Bangladesh
11	R11	Garments Industry	Dhaka, Bangladesh
12	R12	Garments Industry	Dhaka, Bangladesh
13	R13	Garments Industry	Dhaka, Bangladesh
14	R14	Garments Industry	Dhaka, Bangladesh
15	R15	Garments Industry	Dhaka, Bangladesh

3.12 Qualitative Data Analysis: Thematic Framework Matrix

According to O'Connor & Gibson (2002), the qualitative data analysis process should be started by first getting to know about the data. It is important to choose the right data analysis technique (Aronson, 1995). Data must be summarized and classified to make relevant inferences (Saunders *et al.*, 2011). There are a variety of research techniques for evaluating people's shared perspectives and experiences (Mahrer, 1988; SJ and Bogdan, 1984). One such approach is thematic analysis (Aronson, 1995), an important method of organising and summarising

interviews to examine meaningful patterns that may develop (Braun and Clarke, 2006). According to Braun and Clarke (2006), the thematic analysis goes through six steps (Figure 3.2) which are:

Figure 3.2: Strategy and Process of Thematic Analysis

In the thematic approach, the code creates the themes, then reviews, defines, and reports the themes by following the sequence of Braun and Clarke (2006). However, framework analysis does work differently where themes are generated during fieldwork and literature review, and then codes are placed into the relevant themes (Dixon-Woods, 2011). The purpose of codes is to understand the context of a response (R). The interviewee codes are denoted as R1 to R15, as indicated in Table 3.8 below:

Table 3.8: Participants in Qualitative Research

Interviewee No:	Interviewee code
1	R01
2	R02
3	R03
4	R04
5	R05
6	R06
7	R07
8	R08
9	R09
10	R10
11	R11
12	R12
13	R13
14	R14
15	R15.

The framework analysis can be undertaken during and after data collection (Ritchie et al., 2003). The UK researchers developed framework Analysis (FA) as a pragmatic approach for social

research based on existing ideas other than producing a new theory (Ritchie & Spencer, 1994; Ritchie *et al.*, 2003; Snape & Spencer, 2003), which involves a few distinct stages but is correlated (Rabiee, 2004). FA provides a clear track of how data moved from interview transcripts to themes, with summaries in charts ending researchers to discuss ideas (Furber *et al.*, 2009).

Therefore, following the framework analysis, the researcher has applied five main stages to analyse the primary qualitative data, such as:

1. Familiarization – through immersion in the data
2. Identifying a thematic framework
3. Indexing and pilot charting
4. Summarising data in an analytical framework
5. Synthesizing data by mapping and interpreting

First stage: Familiarization – through immersion in the data

In the first stage, the researcher listened to each interview several to be familiar with the collected data and transcribed them into a word file. This is how the researcher became familiar with the data and identified the emerging themes (Ritchie *et al.*, 2013). According to Braun Clarke (2006), the overall goal at this stage is to delve into the details of each transcribed interview copy, divide it into sections, and gain an idea of the whole interview before identifying recurring themes.

Second Stage: Identifying a thematic framework

Themes in framework analysis might be based on previous concerns' inquiries. As a result, the researcher began by generating overreaching categories using the interview topic guide, and several emergent themes from transcripts were coded as responses to each question. According to Pope *et al.* (2000), the outcome of this stage is a detailed index of the data into manageable chunks for subsequent retrieval and explanation. The recurring themes identified in the first stage have been added to a chart using NVIVO for this case. However, MS Excel, MS Word, or paper charts can be used for this work (Gale *et al.*, 2013). This stage is undertaken by the researcher and uses NVIVO-26 to bring out the outcomes. Table 3.9 shows the themes and sub-themes that formed the draft framework.

Table 3.9: Themes and Sub-Themes for Stage 2

Themes -Sub-themes	Files	References
ORGANIC QUALITY MANAGEMENT	15	379
<i>Top Management Commitment</i>	15	61
<i>Employee Suggestions</i>	14	56
<i>Group Problem Solving</i>	15	50
<i>Task Related Training</i>	14	53
<i>Supplier Quality Management</i>	15	47
<i>Customer Relationship</i>	12	48
<i>Social Responsibility</i>	7	26
<i>Political and cultural Impact</i>	10	38
MECHANISTIC QUALITY MANAGEMENT	15	385
<i>Strategic Quality Planning</i>	12	50
<i>Preventive Maintenance</i>	12	79
<i>Housekeeping</i>	15	61
<i>Benchmarking</i>	14	43
<i>Quality Information</i>	15	83
<i>Process Management</i>	15	69
Administrative Innovation	15	243
<i>Internal Organisation Innovation</i>	15	100
<i>Marketing Innovation</i>	14	55
<i>Strategic Innovation</i>	14	88
Technological Innovation	15	146
<i>Technological Products</i>	12	26
<i>Technological Process</i>	15	53
<i>Technological Technology</i>	15	67

Third Stage: Indexing and pilot charting

Themes and sub-themes were revised, merged, and a framework (Table 3.10) was built into this project. During this phase, the researcher read through the transcript data and noted the prototype framework about the recurring themes. At this phase, the decision was made based on the commonalities and variances between the first themes to reflect the data and emergent sub-themes more accurately. So, a refined framework (only one element from all nodes is shown in the figure) was developed below to ensure that data fit into only one subject and was not repeated in several places (Gale *et al.*, 2013).

Table 3.10: Refined themes and sub-themes

Name	Files	References
ORGANIC QUALITY MANAGEMENT		
Employee Suggestions	15	379
Business Performance	14	56
Financial	14	37
Nonfinancial Performance	2	2
Customers Perspective	14	35
Innovation and Learning Perspective	2	2
Internal Business Perspective	14	20
Practicing by organisation	11	13
Gap	13	19
	2	3
MECHANISTIC QUALITY MANAGEMENT		
Process Management	15	69
Business Performance	15	46
Financial	7	8
Nonfinancial Performance	15	38
Customers Perspective	6	8
Innovation and Learning Perspective	11	13
Internal Business Perspective	13	17
Practice by Management	14	23
Gap	1	2
ADMINISTRATIVE INNOVATION	15	243
Marketing Innovation	14	55
Business Performance	13	38
Financial Performance	9	15
Nonfinancial Performance	12	23
Customers Perspective	5	6
Innovation and Learning Perspective	5	5
Internal Business Perspective	9	12
Practice	11	17
Gap	10	13
TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION	15	146
Technological Process	15	53
Business Performance	13	37
Financial Performance	5	8
Nonfinancial Performance	13	29
Customers Perspective	2	2
Innovation and Learning Perspective	6	7
Internal Business Perspective	12	20
Practice	10	16
Gap	7	10
TQM and Innovation relationship	15	14

Stage 4: Summarizing data in an analytical framework

In this stage, the researcher condenses the data into concise explanations of what the respondents stated (Ritchie *et al.*, 2013), and using the software would expedite this process (Swallow *et al.*, 2003). In this research work, the researcher used NVIVO-26 to draw the analytical framework.

Stage-5: Synthesizing data by mapping and interpreting

Framework analysis is thought to contribute to the overall development of a conceptual framework by allowing the refinement of themes (Smith and Firth, 2011). At this point, a researcher can compare subjects and subtopics and examine original transcripts, live notes, and recordings for context. In this stage, no changes were made to the topic or subtopics, and the final theoretical framework was agreed upon. This stage proves the transparency of framework analysis because the analysis process can be compared with the original data at each phase,

thereby increasing the rigor (Swallow *et al.*, 2003). Hence, the data findings are discussed in Chapter Four below.

Chapter Four: Data Findings and Analysis

4.1 Findings and Results for Qualitative

The qualitative and quantitative data findings and analysis are covered in this chapter. The qualitative data was collected through fifteen face-to-face interviews with the managerial employees of the Bangladesh garments organisation. This chapter illustrates the qualitative data findings followed by a thematic framework matrix analysis. The variables developed, followed by fundamental research objectives, themes, and sub-themes, have been considered to bring out the research outcomes. The multi-dimensional view (Organic & Mechanistic) of TQM and innovation (administrative and Technological) practice's impact on organisational financial and non-financial contexts have been considered to find out by this research task. In addition, the relationship between TQM and innovation is examined. Therefore, the themes and sub-themes were developed during the literature review, data collection, and interpretation stages. The framework matrix analytical table was generated using the auto-create NVIVO-12 analytical software. The findings in the framework matrix table have been used to carry out the final qualitative analysis. An analysis plan shows in Figure 4.1, which includes all the themes and subthemes for this research task.

Figure 4.1: Research Project for thematic analysis

Therefore, the themes for this project are:

- Organic Quality Management
- Mechanistic Quality Management
- Administrative innovation and
- Technological Innovation
- Financial performance, and
- Non-financial performance

A total of twenty-six sub-themes were developed under the above six themes. This research validates several aspects of the initial conceptual framework created from the literature review. It provides an insight into the logic of the multi-dimensional view of TQM and Innovation practice and their impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance.

4.2 Organic Quality Management: Eight elements

Top Management's impact on performance

Organisational Financial Performance

Table 4.1 below shows eight participants out of 15, meaning more than 50% of participants acknowledged the financial impact of management leadership on organisational performance. All 15 participants made 45 references to top management's significant effect on organisational performance, with nine agreeing that top management commitment had a substantial impact on financial and non-financial perspectives.

Table 4.1: Files and references about management Leadership

Name	Files	References
Top Management Leadership	15	61
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	15	45
Name	Files	References
Financial	8	9
Non-Financial Performance	15	36
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	8	9
Innovation and Learning Perspective	9	11
Internal Business Perspective	13	16
Name	Files	References
Practicing by Organisation	15	16

The literature review defined management leadership as one of the principal matters of achieving organisational goals. Leadership decisions are directly involved and influence all the sectors in the organisation (Zhang *et al.*, 2000). For example, participant R10 has emphasised the financial impact on customers' perspectives, communication, and waste management perspectives. In addition, participants R3 and R7 also explained the same thing. For example, participant R03 said, *"We get in touch with top-level management if we can not figure out a problem, explain the circumstance, and ask for help. They come and fix the issues, which helps to increase the organisation's production capacities. It consequently enhances the financial performance."* participant R07 also said, *"When clothing is manufactured differently from how the buyer desires, a quality issue results and the buyer may claim to reproduce the entire goods or money back, which causes risk of losing money for the organization."* Participants R2, R5, R9, R11, and R12 also noted that the leadership gap might affect the quality of goods or services. They pointed out that the leadership gap negatively impacts the organisation in several ways because customers can cancel orders, claim financial loss, or even stop doing business with the organisation for improper communication. For instance, participant R02 said, *"Top management always suggests we ensure the quality, so buyers do not get an option to claim."* The above issues relate to the article of Zhang (2000), which defined that improving products and quality management issues is challenging if top management does not lead the participants. Quality improvement involves making decisions and creating something that did not exist before. As said by R12, *"A big sum of orders can be canceled if we cannot ensure the quality, so we should always ensure the quality to avoid financial loss."* Therefore, top management's commitment, participation, and decision about quality management in the organisation may save the financial loss and increase the business profit.

Non-Financial Perspective

The organisational non-financial performance measurement has been carried out based on the customer's perspective, innovation & learning perspective, and internal business perspective. Considering the present garments business flow and industrial production, the interdependence of buyers and suppliers has increased dramatically. To a certain extent, the supplier becomes an extension of the buyer's organisation. Therefore, a relationship emerged between buyers and suppliers in the flexible business environment (Juran, 1993) and a practice of TQM in the modern business environment (Anderson *et al.*, 1994). In the Bangladesh garments industry, buyers and suppliers are often considered customers. Hence, buyers are viewed as customers in this research context. There are 8 participants out of 15 who acknowledge that management

leadership impacts non-financial customer perspectives. Participants R02, R05, R9, R11, and R13 mentioned that poor quality causes customer dissatisfaction. For instance, participant R13 *“If the production quantity is good, but defective rates are higher, suppose 20 pieces defects found out from 100 pieces is not worthwhile for organization, which means we wasted our time, productivity, capacity as well dissatisfaction might be replied from buyers”*. The above information can relate to the articles as Juran (1993), and Deming (1986) stated that receiving customer complaint information is one way to find opportunities to improve product and service quality. Quality complaints always deal with different problems, and strategic leadership actions are needed to resolve the matters. Top management must identify, review, and resolve the issues when they get any customer complaints. A depth analysis demands discovering the primary causes to remedy those issues. In addition, R04, R06, and R07 have emphasised the buyer's (customer's) requirements, and they suggested the management have all kinds of strategic procedures to meet the customer's demands. As explained by participant R06, *“We always prioritize fulfilling the buyer's requirements.”* The above statements can relate that customer focus is on the degree to which a firm continuously needs to satisfy customer needs and expectations. As mentioned, a successful firm put prioritises the needs of the customer first in every decision the organization makes (Philips, 1995).

Innovation is the essential foundation for sustainable business performance. Innovation is the process of taking new ideas effectively and profitably to satisfy the organisational performance. It is a process of continuous improvement that involves the entire firm, and it is a vital component of corporate strategy and daily operations (Hoang, 2006). Quality management supports innovation by enabling effective identification of customer needs, training, idea sharing, and top management commitment and participation. Participant R14 said, *“This is very important to guide the work being done correctly, and new strategies are being implemented in the organisation.”* Participants R01 and R07 also made the same statement, saying that innovation helps to bring new ideas or helps to implement new strategies to bring organisational success. Top management's commitment to quality reflects the organisation's strategy for changing the culture and learning new things to meet the objectives or new goals (Juran, 1993; Bollen, 1989). However, TQM has defined a holistic management philosophy that strives for continuous learning and organisational improvement (Flynn *et al.*, 1995). Participants R14, R12, R04, R05, R06, and R01 stated that management commitment positively impacts on continuous learning and doing things accurately in the organisation. As an example: *R14 (a): “if we do not follow the strategy, then work will be done in the wrong way. They always guide us on how to do the work*

the right way and what to do exactly". Also, participant R12 said, "Top management also keeps us updated on quality assurance and what to do." Furthermore, the general data implication reveals (See above Table 4.1) that 9 out of 15 participants (60%) acknowledged the influence of top management quality implementation on non-financial performance nearly 11 times, followed by the perspective of 'innovation and learning.' As a result, managerial commitment significantly influences non-financial performance in terms of innovation and learning perspective in the Bangladesh garments industry.

The internal business perspective in TQM defines how QM helps to develop or progress an organization's internal performance, which could be in production, process, or service management. TQM practices in organizations effectively build and develop a range of capabilities that go beyond quality and maintain the flow of information (Prajogo and Hong, 2008). For instance, *R12 said, "Top management instruction is not to compromise with quality. We need to ensure quality for sustainable business performance"*. Similar statement made by R14, R15, R04, R06, and R11. However, few Participants have emphasised that monitoring the working procedures during production might be effective for a successful business. As said by participant *R03, "We constantly monitor our floor personnel to ensure that they are following management instructions. When we cannot solve an issue, I call the top-level managers or state that I cannot fix the problem and ask them how I should proceed. Later, they come and fix it to maintain the continuation of the production flow."* R05, R13, R09, and R01 made similar remarks concerning control and monitoring issues. In contrast, R10 and R14 have emphasised the need for teamwork and cooperation among employees and senior management to assure quality. An example, participant *R10 said: "We are four-person work in my department, and we also discuss the issues if we cannot solve by one person. In addition, we also discuss with the top managers"* Thus, the above statement can relate with Lascelles and Dale (1988), and Dale *et al.* (1999) as defined that the way of improving the firm's quality improvement efforts is to ensure top management engagement in different management sections. Management participation helps spread quality consciousness throughout a firm. Therefore, from the above discussion based on the analysis of primary and secondary data, it can be said that top management leadership has a substantial impact on the organisational internal business perspective.

The data findings in Table 4.1 showed that over 55% of participants (8 out of 15 participants) believe senior management leadership directly influences organisational financial success. In contrast, 15 participants (100%) mentioned 36 times (see Table 4.1) the influence of senior management leadership on the non-financial aspect of organisational success. Among the non-

financial viewpoints, 13 participants underlined the relevance of internal business perspectives, nine individuals emphasised innovation and learning, and 8 participants addressed the customer's perspective. For example, Participants R1, R3, R5, R7, R9, R10, R11, and R12 all agreed that top management influenced organisational performance, both financially and non-financially. In addition, participants R1, R4, R6, R8, R13, R14, and R15 have also acknowledged the top management impact from a non-financial standpoint. Thus, 8 participants (53% of 15 participants) acknowledged the impact on financial performance, and 15 (100%) responded that top management significantly impacts on non-financial performance. As a result of the analysis of this primary data, a conclusion can be drawn that the top management influence on the viewpoint (see Table 4.1) of organisational non-financial success is 47% greater than the financial performance (8 participants out of 15 = 53%).

Employee Suggestions impact on performance

Organisational Financial performance

Table 4.2 demonstrates that only two participants (R04 and R10) out of 15 acknowledged twice the financial impact of employee suggestions on organisational performance. According to Hackman and Wageman (1995), employee participation is exemplified by teamwork, employee suggestions, and employee commitment. Teamwork is a remarkable characteristic of employee participation, and it helps to improve input and output at any stage. Dean and Bowen (1994) define that employee participation helps develop the collaboration between managers and non-managers among the different functions. Participant R04 acknowledged, *"I may not be aware of certain things, but helpers might. For instance, I might perform a task in 30 seconds, but my assistants or operators might accomplish it more quickly and effectively because of their prior work experience from other factories. As a result, I prioritise their operations. It contributes to boosting manufacturing output, which is advantageous to financing."* Also, R10 said, *"Our goal is always to keep fewer defects rate so we can save expenses. We seek help from the manager if the issue is complicated. Otherwise, I will discuss it with my colleague to solve the issue."* From the above responses, it can be assessed that employees' suggestions do not have any strong impact on the organisational financial performance. However, discussing the non-financial perspective will make it clear to conclude the impact broadly.

Table 4.2: Files and references about employee suggestion

Name	Files	References
Employee Suggestions	14	56
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	14	37
Name	Files	References
Financial	2	2
NonFinancial Performance	14	35
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	2	2
Innovation and Learning Perspective	14	20
Internal Business Perspective	11	13
Name	Files	References
Gap of Practicing	2	3
Practicing by organisation	13	16

Source: Primary data

Organisational Non-Financial Performance

The customer's perspective meets customers' expectations, resulting in customer satisfaction which could be a compliant resolution (Ahire *et al.*, 1996). Only two participants (R04 and R08) recognised the influence of complaint resolutions on non-financial performance from the consumers' perspective. Therefore, employee engagement by accepting their suggestions has a moderate non-financial impact on organisational performance. Data shows 14 participants have referred 20 times (Table 4.2) about the impacts of innovation and learning on non-financial performance. The participants *R01, R02, R05, R07, R13, and R15* mostly talked about new ideas that come from employees' suggestions and lead to a successful business. The emergence of new ideas by people who, over time, engage in interactions with others within an organised order is characterised as innovation (Garud *et al.*, 2013), which brings drastic and incremental success to the organization (Ali *et al.*, 2010; Prajogo and Sohal, 2001; Bright and Cooper, 1993). For example, *R01* said, "The group meeting contributes to generating new and innovative ideas. When buyers inquire about new product needs, we instantly inform the new employees about work practices that satisfy the client's expectations." *R05* said, "New ideas can benefit the organisation to learn new things." *R02, R15, and R13* eventually agreed on the same thing. The above primary data can relate to the explanation of Feng (2006) and Feng *et al.* (2021) that employee participation is considered a vital asset in today's knowledge-based economy. Rahman (2002) defines that employee involvement is an essential part of any TQM effort, and the MBNQA has highlighted the significance of human resources (Bowen and Lawler, 1992). Conversely, Participants *R01 (b), R04 (a), R04 (b), R08, R09, R10 (a), (b), R11, R12 (a), R12 (b),*

R14 (a), R14 (b) have mentioned that employee participation help employees to learn and develop their confidence which effectively impacts on organisational non-financial performance. As acknowledged by participant R09, *“In the meeting, we discuss any new difficulties that have arisen. If I do not understand how to resolve a problem, others might be able to assist me.”* Therefore, it can be said from the above discussion, employee suggestions bring success to the organisation in many ways, such as developing a relationship with the customers and ensuring quality by sharing knowledge among the employees. According to Mele and Colurcio (2006) and Male and Polese (2011), innovation creates value among customers and thus improves the firm's performance, which the participants above acknowledged.

Table 4.2 shows that 11 people confirmed the importance of employee ideas on organisational performance 13 times. Employee participation by suggestion is vital in inspiring action on quality improvement (Juran, 1986), which is acknowledged by R12, *“If there is a problem with the pattern, it signifies that the initial quality was not correct, the measurement was incorrect, or the machining positioning was incorrect. In this case, we contact the manager in charge, present the sample, and request that the problem be resolved. They arrive and resolve the problem. We make every effort to rectify those products for as long as possible.”* However, participant R10 observed that a lack of staff participation in the meeting could indicate a lack of information exchange. Due to the knowledge gap, the employee may need additional time on the final task. Similarly, said by R08, *“If I do not pass the information immediately among the employees, products might be produced in the wrong way, and we must rework because of the gap of information.”* The statement shows that lack of engagement may cause a lack of confidence and develop negative attitudes among the employees. According to Zhang *et al.* (2000), employees' involvement may allay employees' negative attitudes. Participant R07 also supported and said, *“Employees even can feel stress-free during work if they have the freedom to say, which may increase the volume of productivity”* and encourage them to understand better about the importance of product quality (R07 and R11). Therefore, from the above discussion, the conclusion can be made that employee engagement substantially impacts organisational internal business perspective by the view of the literature and participant's statements.

Small Group Problem-solving impacts on performance

Organisational Financial Performance

Figure 4.2 displays five participant appreciation of the importance of group problem-solving in achieving organisational financial success. For example, participants R15, R13, and R2 have explained conflict mitigation helps the organisation to save financial loss. It also allows people to focus on their tasks more successfully. Participant R15 explained, “Employees believe they need an extra day off, but because of the extra day, we must cancel the shipment and reroute it from ship to air cargo, which might cost an extra 10,000 pounds. The bulk of employees is unwilling to realize this situation. As a result, we explain and mitigate it.” The above statement can be linked with the view of Forza and Filippini (1998), establishing and fostering a collaborative problem-solving strategy that takes use of employees' capacity to provide improvement suggestions. Participants R5 and R11 also acknowledged its strong impacts on financial performance. Therefore, group problem-solving strongly impacts on organisational financial performance.

Figure 4.2: Participants acknowledge financial performance for employee suggestions

Organisational Non-Financial Performance

Ensuring product quality, service quality, and maintaining processes are very important as all those processes lead to a quality task. Long-term customer relationships always bring a good reputation for the organization. Hence, delivering goods timely to customers and keeping production flow to meet the customer's needs and expectations is a significant organisational performance issue (Ahire *et al.*, 1996). The following statement is acknowledged by participant R5, “We determine how many employees will be required to complete the task successfully and on schedule.” Customers' perceptions of non-financial achievements have only been stated by participants R5 (a) and R5 (b) twice. However, 8 participants (See Table 4.3) said that solving

problems in a group has a non-financial impact on innovation and learning perspective in organisational performance (R1, R2, R10). As noted by participant R1, *“We frequently talk about the quality issues among our staff. The meeting helps to bring new innovative ideas”*. Sitting in a group to solve problems or sharing ideas empowering the employees, which helps develop confidence among them (Ahire *et al.*, 1996). Workers' regular participation in operational decisions such as planning, goal setting, situation handling, and monitoring performance encourages them to make the right decisions. It helps them take a high degree of responsibility for overall performance (Zeng *et al.*, 2015). A similar statement is defined by participants R5, R6, and R4. For example, participant R4 said, *“It is not that all I know as a manager always right; I can be wrong. I still learn a lot from helpers. There is learning from each other. There are some things I do not know, but helpers may know better than me”*. As a result, employee group problem-solving moderately influences organisational performance in terms of innovation and learning perspective, evidenced by both primary and secondary data in this discussion.

Table 4.3: Files and references about small group problem solving

Name	Files	References
Group Problem Solving	15	48
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	14	30
Name	Files	References
Financial	5	5
Non-Financial Performance	14	25
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	1	2
Innovation and Learning Perspective	8	8
Internal Business Perspective	14	15
Name	Files	References
gap of practice	0	0
Practicing by Management	15	18

Source: primary data

Eight participants stated that problem-solving in a group environment helps employees learn and generate ideas. Similarly, 14 participants indicated that group problem-solving positively influenced internal business, leading to increased nonfinancial performance. However, another six participants, R8, R11, R12, R13, R14, and R15 (See Table 4.3), brought the further value of solving problems to the internal business perspective, as said by R12, *“We discuss how we can solve the matter. This is how we mitigate the conflict so that we can work as a team to increase the firm’s productivity”*. The above statement shows that conflict mitigation increases work performance. Conversely, conflict reduces organisational productivity. As Cooke (1992) stated, solving problem setting in a group allays employees’ negative attitudes and encourages employees to have a better understanding of the importance of product quality. As acknowledged

by R13, “Sometimes employees misunderstand us by listening to others as a rumor.” According to Cooke (1992), the study also revealed that employee participation significantly affects product quality. As R6 and R9 commented, teamwork increases productivity and helps to learn continuously. Participant 8(b) said that a friendly manner allows the employees to concentrate on the work more but puts the employee under stress, which reduces productivity. The rest of the participants almost defined the same things. Therefore, a conclusion can be made that group problem-solving significantly impacts on organisational non-financial performance.

Task Related Training impacts on performance

Education and training are vital elements for the successful implementation of TQM. An organisation’s learning is promoted through training and development activities. So, organisation must be followed the training and development process (Noe *et al.*, 2014; Sung and Choi, 2014; Colquitt *et al.*, 2000). Table 4.4 shows that 11 participants acknowledged their organisation has a policy to practice task-related training.

Table 4.4: Participants and their references for task-related training

Name	Files	References
Task Related Training	14	53
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	14	39
Name	Files	References
Financial	4	6
Name	Files	References
unspecified financial and nonfinancial both	1	1
Name	Files	References
NonFinancial Performance	14	33
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	0	0
Innovation and Learning Perspective	12	17
Internal Business Perspective	13	15
Name	Files	References
Gap of Practice	2	3
Practicing by Management	11	11

Source: primary data

Organisational Financial Performance

Training and development activities pursue generating new skills and knowledge and transforming existing knowledge into new configurations that meet ongoing needs (Noe *et al.*, 2014). The statement was also acknowledged by R1 and R13, where participant R13 said, “I believe that by providing training, 40% of total employees, including less educated or uneducated

employees, can be taught to use technology. This type of training was not implemented in this organisation. Additionally, I believe that training can help to improve employee abilities and organisational financial performance.” Noe et al. (2014) also explained that training increases job skills and influence employee performance. For instance, participant R3 said, “Training helps the organisation. Employees can learn and work accurately, reducing defect rates, which protects the organisation from financial loss”. Training puts everyone on the same page (Billett, 2004). Participant R9 also acknowledged, “Even if an employee is absent, production will be continued by the substitute employee, resulting in no production loss.” The following participant, R1, R3, R5, and R13, has defined that training financially impacts on organisational performance. Hence it can be said that Task-related training significantly affects organisational financial performance.

Non-Financial Perspective

In this case, none of the participants said that training has a non-financial impact on customers' perspectives (see below Figure 4.3). However, participants R3.a, R4, R5, R7, R8, R9, R9.b), R10, R11, R12, R13, R14, and R15 have acknowledged that training has a significant impact on innovation and learning perspective. Participants R1, R2, R3, R7, R8 (a), R9, R11, R12, R14, and R15 acknowledged about the importance of training from an organisational internal business perspective. According to Birdi et al. (2012), training positively relates to idea generation but is unrelated to idea implementation. Therefore, factors influencing the generation of ideas may differ from those affecting the implementation of ideas. As R9 explained, “We discuss in the meeting any new issues arise. Others may help me and suggest how to solve the matter if I do not know something.” According to Chen & Huang (2009) and Chen and Huang (2012), learning enables work performance and eases the development of competencies. Participant R14 also acknowledges this by saying, “We sometimes ask the employees to work in the different lines and floors so that they can learn multiple works in this factory.” According to Hatch and Dyer (2004), training and learning activities contributes to the creation, exchange, and utilization of knowledge, which may impact on innovation and organisational performance. This is also acknowledged by participant R15, “We observe employees' performance and arrange training based on their requirements. Training helps to develop employees' skills and knowledge. It is a way of continuous learning which increases any organisation's productivity”. Almost all the participants (Figure 4.3) have mentioned the training impact on innovation and learning perspective. One of the critical challenges of organizations is to increase employees'

competencies by transforming the work environment into “learning by doing” places called task-related learning (Wielenga-Meijer *et al.*, 2010).

Figure 4.3: non-financial – customer and Innovation & Learning Perspective

Work-based learning is how employees acquire new or further develop their existing experiences and confidence (Nikolova *et al.*, 2014). The following statement can relate to the view of participant R1, “*Training benefits in a variety of ways, including increased product volume and easier identification of changes by staff. As a result, they can minimise the alteration.*” As training develops the staff’s confidence, multitasking abilities also grow among the employees. According to Carmeli and Azeroual (2009), knowledge combination capabilities facilitated the development of knowledge creation capability. As exemplified relates to R14, “*Employees may be transferred from one factory to another, which is an issue. We have a backup plan in place. Consider that the person who works in this place does the same thing as the person who works beside him and another employee who assists. The employee in this role is then brought in to fill the void.*” So, from the above discussion, it can be concluded that task-related training has a significant impact on the internal business perspective in organisational non-financial performance.

Supplier Quality Management impacts on performance

Organisational Financial Perspective

Developing partnerships with the supplier is one of the effective TQM implementation practices (Hackman and Wageman, 1995). External cooperation between a firm and its suppliers has merits in the just-in-time purchasing system (Anderson *et al.*, 1994a). However, participants argued that partnership is not always good for the organisation, which is explained by R2, *“Negotiating profit with suppliers or as a shareholder is not a good idea. I do not know much about franchises or mergers or whether any organisations in Bangladesh are doing so.”* Working collaboratively with suppliers on a long-term basis is truly beneficial (Anderson *et al.*, 1994a), which is also acknowledged by R9, *“Long-term relationships benefit the organisation. It is important to consider the quality and finance to select the suppliers.”* A similar financial impact on the long-term partnership was also described by participant R14. Deming (1986) explained that working with suppliers in a long-term relationship of loyalty and trust improves the quality of incoming materials and decreases costs. Participants R4, R5, R7, R8, R15, R12, and R14 addressed the importance of supplier quality management on financial performance. For example, participant R14 said, *“supplier quality management is significant for the business to gain sustainable competitive advantages.”* Deming (1986) also mentioned that a long-term relationship between purchaser and supplier is necessary for the best economy. Therefore, from the above discussion by the participants and quality management researchers, supplier quality management significantly impacts on organisational financial performance.

Non-Financial Perspective

Four participants agreed five times that supplier quality management impacts customers and the firm's non-financial performance. Participant R6 acknowledged that *“We should establish positive relationships with our suppliers. For example, the buyer will refuse the products if the buttons are defective. Therefore, the supplier's quality products benefit customers as well.”* Participant R14 also focused on good relationships with buyers. It is explained by Juran (1986), and Huang and Keskar (2007), customers' perceptions of non-financial success are greatly influenced by supplier quality. Participants R1 and R4 suggested delivering a quality service to the suppliers helps to develop goodwill with them. However, in terms of the “Innovation and learning perspective,” Participant R4 explained, *“It is preferable to conduct long-term business with suppliers. Otherwise, things could get worse if I keep taking it from different people. It might lead to financial issues and difficulties in forming new relationships.”* This indicates that the long-term relationship impacts innovation and learning perspectives in the organisation. As Zhang *et al.* (2000) explained, improving supplier quality management through training would enhance the firm's product quality. This is also defined by the participants R11, R7, and R2 as how suppliers

learning engagement works on organisations performance. Participant R7 said, “Suppliers visit us to fix machine-related problems or repair the machine itself. They also instruct us on how to handle smaller problems.” About 13 participants mentioned 19 times (see below Table 4.5) that supplier quality management has a non-financial impact on the internal business perspective of the organisation. The following participants, R2 (a), R2 (b), R1, R3, R7, R13 (b), and R14, suggested developing a long-term relationship with the suppliers brings good reputations and desired business. For example, participant R13(b) said, “Long-term relationship sustains the business growth and develops goodwill whereas short-term relationship can end up the business and goodwill.” Deming (1986) noted that collaborating with suppliers in a long-term partnership of loyalty and trust enhances the quality of incoming materials and lowers expenses. Deming (1986) also stated that a long-term collaboration between the buyer and the supplier is essential for the finest quality implementation and economy. Therefore, the above discussion shows that supplier quality management has a significant impact on the organisation’s non-financial performance.

Table 4.5: Participants and references for supplier quality management

Name	Files	References
Supplier Quality Management	15	47
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	15	41
Name	Files	References
Financial	9	12
NonFinancial Performance	14	29
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	4	5
Innovation and Learning Perspectiv	4	4
Internal Business Perspective	13	19
Name	Files	References
Gap of Practice	1	1
Practicing by Management	5	5

Source: Primary data

Customers Relationship impacts on performance

Organisational performance on Financial and Non-financial Perspective

The organisation needs to prioritise the customers for every decision to succeed. Customer relationship can be defined as how a firm continuously satisfies customer needs and expectations (Harrison *et al.*, 2010; Karsten *et al.*, 2009). There are 8 participants who defined that customer quality relationships substantially impact an organisation's financial performance. According to participant R12, the organisation does not put much emphasis on customer quality issues. However, it states that customer satisfaction has a direct financial influence on the organisation (Figure 4.4).

Figure 4.4: Financial and non-financial impact of customer's perspective.

For Instance, participant R4 said, *“First quality and then cost, and we precede long time relationship with customers.”* Also, participants R2, R14, R5, R7, R8, R11, and R12 defined that maintaining goodwill with the customers, satisfying quality products, and delivering prioritised services are important to sustain a successful business. Juran (1993) said that obtaining customer complaint information helps to seek opportunities to improve product and service quality. Participants R5, R7, and R1 also acknowledged this as a non-financial performance from the customer's perspective. It is noted by R1, *“Good feedback always brings good business for us. We can get frequent orders from the buyers for a good service.”* R7 said, *“Even if we partially fail to fulfill the requirements, we must negotiate with the customers. In this case, we must let the customer know about the matter.”* Hence, customer quality maintained in services, products, or processes has a financial impact on businesses and has a non-financial effect on customers' perspectives on organisational performance. Participants R2, R10, R11, and R13 also acknowledged a similar impact of customer relationships on non-financial performance in the organisation. In addition, customer focus has been considered a window through which the

organisation can look at the outside and get the necessary feedback (Jones and Grimshaw, 2012; Perdom-Ortiz *et al.*, 2006), which participants R4 and R7 also acknowledged. For example, R4 said, *“We prioritise quality before cost, and we prioritise long-term relationships with suppliers and customers.”* So, although we found that consumers substantially impact on non-financial performance, participants defined that customers have less impact on innovation and learning perspective. Furthermore, Jones and Grimshaw (2012) and Perdom-Ortiz *et al.* (2006) described that organisations keep developing their staff through systematic training programs that provide necessary competencies that can be shared within the organisation to build goodwill with the customers. R1, R5, R7, R8, and R14 all agreed on a similar remark, as R14 stated, *“They bring us the business, so we need to have a good relationship to develop the goodwill with them.”* Customer satisfaction substantially impacts the internal business perspective on non-financial organisational performance as defined by 10 participants (Table 4.6). The above participant’s statements are in line with the view of Wang (2004), Deming (1982), Garvin (2001), and Homburg and Fürst (2005), in a customer-oriented organisation, customer satisfaction drives all company actions. So, in conclusion, it is assessed that customer relationships significantly impact organisational financial and non-financial performance.

Table 4.6: Participants and references for supplier quality management

Name	Files	References
Customer Relationship	12	48
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	11	35
Name	Files	References
Financial	8	10
Non-Financial Performance	11	28
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	8	13
Innovation and Learning Perspective	2	2
Internal Business Perspective	10	13
Name	Files	References
Gap of Practice	3	3
Practicing by Management	6	6

Source: Primary Data

Social Responsibility impacts on performance

Organisational financial and nonfinancial Performance

CSR should be evaluated by comparing relative costs and benefits. Standards such as ISO 14001 have been developed; but have not attracted the same level of attention as ISO 9001 (Sharma and Kodali, 2011; Srinivasan and Singh, 2010)). However, three participants, R2, R5, and R10, acknowledge that CSR has a substantial financial impact on businesses to mitigate harm and improve reputation on the global market (Figure 4.5). Only a few participants specified the financial impacts of CSR on organisational performance.

Figure 4.5: financial and nonfinancial impact by participants (CSR)

Remarkably, none of the participants mentioned the CSR impact on the customer perspective and innovation & learning perspective on nonfinancial performance. However, participants R2, R3, R5, R6, R7, and R10 (Table 4.7) acknowledged that CSR significantly impacts an internal business perspective. For example, participant R5 said, “Fire and building collapses have damaged the reputation of the Bangladesh garments industry.” R7 said, “We lost a lot before. So, we are careful now.” Participants mainly mentioned that CSR practice developed goodwill between organisations and customers or even with third-party auditors. According to Sharma and Kodali (2008), social responsibilities have been highlighted by various quality gurus. It has not been given due attention in the existing TQM framework. However, in the Bangladesh garments sector, social responsibilities significantly influence business performance since their past image has damaged their corporate goodwill on the global market. Hence, the organization is much more concerned about social responsibilities.

Table 4.7: The value of Participants and references for CSR

Name	Files	References
Social Responsibility	7	26
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	7	15
Name	Files	References
Financial	3	3
NonFinancial Performance	7	12
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	0	0
Innovation and Learning Perspective	0	0
Internal Business Perspective	7	12
Name	Files	References
Gap of Practice	3	5
Practicing by management	5	6

Source: Primary Data

Political Culture Impact

According to Hofstede (1994), culture is the collective programming of the mind which distinguishes one group from another, but Kempner (1992) defines it as the sum of beliefs, knowledge, attitudes of the mind, and customers to which people are exposed during their social conditioning. So, the culture can be different based on the diverse society. 10 participants said that culture significantly impacts organisational performance, and 5 of 15 participants (Table 4.8) said it has a direct financial impact on organisational performance. Maximum participants talked about the delayed delivery of products, and employee movement can be minimized and controlled by the government as they mentioned that those problems are 'political culture' matters (R2, R5, R4, R9, R13, R15). As said by participant R4, *"The government laws favour the workers, yet they called for a strike since the owners are required by law to follow them. They called a strike because the owners did not enact the new law."* Also, participant R9 said, *"Employee disagreement against management results in financial loss. It has consequences for the company."*

National culture differs in the way the members view the world (Stewart and Bennett, 1991). According to participants R2, R5, and R13, political culture was to blame for the shipment delay imposed on by strikes and traffic congestion. Additionally, the garment association's poor planning is to blame for the delay in delivering this business. For instance, participant R5 said, *"In the city of Dhaka, this is a major issue. Moving the factory outside Dhaka would allow us to supply the items more quickly while avoiding the traffic jam, in my opinion."* R13 said, *"I am tired of talking about politics. There is a significant gap there. If we can resolve the political concerns, the delivery time will be lowered from 90 to 30 days."* Therefore, culture impacts on customers' perspectives on non-financial business performance. However, R5 and R10 acknowledged that culture impacts on innovation and learning perspectives. Nine participants 18 times referenced

(see Table 4.8) that culture significantly impacts internal business perspective. A few of them, such as participant R1, said, *“There is nothing we can do about it. In that instance, when we accept the order, we add a product delivery date that is little later than intended. As a result, it costs us both time and money.”* According to Ngowi (2000) and Naveh and Erez (2004), if different TQM practices are applied jointly, they positively impact business or values, such as control and monitoring to detail. As a result, in addition to financial success, political culture considerably influences on organisational nonfinancial performance.

Table 4.8: Numeric values for Participants and references for Political Culture

Name	Files	References
Political-cultural context	10	36
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	10	30
Name	Files	References
Financial	5	7
Name	Files	References
NonFinancial Performance	10	23
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	3	3
Innovation and Learning Perspective	2	2
Internal Business Perspective	9	18
Name	Files	References
Gap of Practice	2	2
Practicing by Management	4	4

Source: Primary Data

4.2 Mechanistic Quality Management Elements

Process Management

Process management helps build manufacturing capabilities. Process management practices focus on continuous improvement and preventing defects by transforming the data between the functional areas in the organisation (Perdome-Ortiz *et al.*, 2006). As acknowledged by R3, R4, R7, R13, R10, and a few others, like participant R1 said, *“We inspect every package of new cloths, and if there are any quality issues we found, we alert the staff by flashing a yellow signal. If things stay the same, transfer that individual to a different department. By doing this, we can keep the defect rates under control and prevent financial loss.”* R2 said, *“They show them how to work properly until the problem gets resolved and then ask to continue working in a productive way to save financial damage.”* Therefore, process management substantially impacts an organisation’s financial performance. Six participants (Table 4.9) acknowledged that process management impacts on organisational non-financial performance from the customer’s

perspective. For example, R3 said, *“We transfer the employee to another department to work in a regular manner if we constantly find issues with his job and no improvement is being made. Otherwise, if supplies are of worse quality, buyers would complain.”* where R8 and R13 both define the same. The almost similar statement defined by Perdome-Ortiz *et al.* (2006), effective process management transforms the output of a particular department into another department to determine the source of poor performance in producing the products, which in turn, affect positively builds the manufacturing capabilities within the organisation.

Customer satisfaction is one of the keys to the quality process. Therefore, process management impacts on customers' perspectives on non-financial organisational performance. Furthermore, following the recording procedures of process management, the failure and success record helps the employees learn capabilities and identify innovative ideas and ways to deal with the matters (Perdomo-Ortiz *et al.*, 200; Perdomo-Ortiz *et al.*, 2009). As acknowledged same by participant R1, *“We have a chart, and we make notes on it to help us determine what the problems are and which machine is causing them. If an issue arises during manufacturing, our specialist will continue to assist them.”* Other participants, like R3a, R3b, and R13, acknowledged the same. Eleven participants agreed with Perdome-Ortiz *et al.* (2009) that process management positively influences employees' capabilities and creativity. Hence process management has an impact on innovation and learning perspective. The design of a production process is also one of the essential practices affecting internal quality performance and competitive capabilities. In designing production processes, defect-proofing methods help eliminate employee errors (Gibson, 1990; Gilbert, 1990; Rao *et al.*, 1997). Several participants, such as R2, R3, R4, and R15, acknowledged it; for example, R2 said, *“If we discover two or three defective items, we take action. To tackle the problem, the operators are informed how to do the task but not how they do it, which solves the problem and benefits the business.”* Similarly, R6, R7, R8, R9, R10, R11, R12, and R13 acknowledged the same. According to Benner and Tushman (2002) and Cheng (1991), organisations that implement the ISO 9001:1994 standards suggest a purely technical and closed quality management focus with a quality assurance strategy. Hence, as a part of TQM, process management ensures quality products, employee capabilities, and organisational business performance. Thus, process management strongly impacts on organisational both financial and non-financial performance.

Table 4.9: Files and References about Process management

Name	Files	References
Process Management	15	69
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	15	46
Name	Files	References
Financial	7	8
NonFinancial Performance	15	38
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	6	8
Innovation and Learning Perspective	11	13
Internal Business Perspective	13	17
Name	Files	References
Gap of Practice	1	2
Practice by Management	13	21

Source: primary data

Preventive Maintenance impacts on performance

Good maintenance and plant engineering processes are fundamental to success in manufacturing (Hanson, 1995; Madu, 2000). Preventive maintenance practices aim to extend operational life, increase efficiency, and monitor business effectiveness in equipment, buildings, and machinery (Dale, 1994). Participants R2, R3a, R3b, and R11 acknowledged the financial impact of preventive maintenance. For example, *R1 said, "To produce the products, we invested money, time, and effort. Therefore, we need to be careful in limiting and regulating defective goods. If we cannot fulfill the buyer's request, it undermines our reputation and costs us money."* Baysinger and Hoskisson (1990) point out that maintenance is the largest aspect of terotechnology. Customer satisfaction is the prime goal for any organisation. An organisation needs to satisfy the customers' needs, create demand, and provide value to customers. The statement can be linked with R2, R4a and R4b, R6, R12, and R14, as acknowledged by *R14, "Because of poor manufacturing, we had to cancel a few shipments. If a product is faulty, we cannot deliver it. Instead, we bin them in the storehouse."* The quality management approach is to achieve continuous quality improvement and increase productivity. Knowledge sharing, learning, and innovativeness are part of continuous improvement (Lofsten, 2014; Lindelöf and Lofsten, 2004). Only 7 participants (Table 4.10) said that preventive maintenance has an impact on innovation and learning perspective. For example, *R6 said, "If the work is performed wrong, we advise staff to switch up their approach and do the task properly. Employees follow the guidelines if we assert that cutting the loop was incorrect."* Preventive maintenance activities train employees to appropriately clean, maintain and respond to machine breakdowns (Zeng et

al., 2015). However, 12 (Table 4.10) participants, such as R2a, R2b, R7, R12, R6, and a few others, said preventative maintenance impacts an internal business perspective. Examples can be taken as participant R6 said, *“If the products are truly rejected, we will discard them. Even after rewashing, rejected products cannot be flawless. Thus they are discarded in the warehouse.”* According to Lofsten (2014), the effect on the maintenance department since the consequences of maintenance actions may seriously affect other units of an organisation. Also, Lofsten (2004) and Lindelöf and Lofsten (2004) defined that managers must have the capability to conduct an economic analysis of alternative policies to plan and control the maintenance cost. Therefore, preventive maintenance has both financial and non-financial impacts on organisational performance.

Table 4.10: Files and References of Preventive Maintenance

Name	Files	References
Preventive Maintain	12	79
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	12	69
Name	Files	References
Financial	12	28
Non-Financial Performance	12	41
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	5	7
Innovation and Learning Perspective	7	8
Internal Business Perspective	12	26
Name	Files	References
Practicing by Management	7	10

Housekeeping

Housekeeping is not only the key to production purposes but also from the customer’s perspective. The audit team keeps checking many of the housekeeping activities to ensure employees are consistent in maintaining specified housekeeping standards considering its impact on business (Zeng *et al.*, 2014; Ahire and Dreyfus, 2000). 13 participants defined that housekeeping has a substantial financial impact on business (Table 4.11). For example, R3 said, *“Our cleanliness is very important to manage the defect rates.”* R4 said, *“Buyers do not accept spotted clothes,”* and R5 said, *“Dirty floor can cause the defect or reject products.”* Similarly, R6 said, *“If the floor is dirty, it will leave stains on the garments, which will be counted as waste.”* Housekeeping is advantageous for the premises to improve safety, improving the working atmosphere and surrounding environment (Arauz *et al.*, 2009; Rao *et al.*, 1999; Flynn *et al.*, 1995). In line with this statement, participants R4, R10, R2, R9, R12, R15, and R14 explained that an unclean environment causes financial damage to the organisation. As said by R15,

“Cleaning is essential to our enterprise. If buyers and third parties visit our factory and notice the dirty or unclean floor or the products, they will complain, which would impact our finances and reputation.” As the quality of the product is directly related to customer satisfaction, housekeeping significantly impacts customers' perspectives on organisational non-financial performance. However, none of the customers has mentioned about the impact on ‘the innovation and learning perspective.

According to Flynn *et al.* (1995), any leak or other abnormality can be detected faster in a clean environment. Working in a clean environment improves motivation and safety. As acknowledged by R8: “Housekeeping and keeping work organised always add extra value to work. The spotless floor is needed to reduce defective items and increase work abilities if place and goods are organised properly.” Also, R6 and R11a, 11b, and R13 explained acknowledged the same. Many others, such as R1, R7, R2, R3, R10, and R13, also said that a clean floor saves the products from being spot defective or rejected. The participants below noted that a clean floor increases productivity and improves the organisation’s reputation. As acknowledged by R1, “We must exercise caution when cleaning. In our factory, we receive extremely few spotted products. We always keep a calendar to keep track of our cleaning tasks.” Table 4.11 shows 14 participants referenced 18 times that housekeeping impact on the internal business perspective and 7 participants defined its impact on customer’s perspective. 13 participants acknowledged that housekeeping has an impact on organisation’s financial perspective and 15 considered for non-financial perspective. Hence, housekeeping substantially impacts both financial and non-financial perspectives on organisational performance.

Table 4.11: Files and References about Housekeeping

Name	Files	References
Housekeeping	15	61
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	15	43
Name	Files	References
Financial	13	17
NonFinancial Performance	15	25
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	7	7
Innovation and Learning Perspective	0	0
Internal Business Perspective	14	18
Name	Files	References
Gap of Practice	1	1
Practice by Management	14	17

Source: Primary Data

Organisational Performance

Quality information is part of knowledge management as the basic input-output transformation process. Information sharing refers to the extent to which a company distributes information to its employees regarding policies, its relation to the general environment, and work-related goals (Lawler, 1992; Gibson *et al.*, 2007). In this context, information sharing is a flow of messages (Nonaka, 1994; Ittner and Larcker, 1995). 13 participants (Table 4.12) acknowledge that correct information sharing at the right time can save the company's financial loss and increase profit. For example, a similar statement was made by R1, R2 and R3, saying that *Good feedback brings good business and helps to identify the customers' needs and gaps*. Information sharing can contribute to enhancing work-related learning. So, mistakes can be reduced (Huo *et al.*, 2021; Bontis *et al.*, 2011), which is also agreed by the participants R5, R7, R8, R10, and R11. In addition, R7 and R5 have defined that information sharing also mitigates conflicts between employees and organisations. As said by R8, *"We can promptly take advise and work in accordance with feedback or information."* Therefore, quality information has a significant impact on organisational financial performance. The perceived information sharing has recently been found to indirectly affect innovative work behaviour through a group environment for innovation (Hsu *et al.*, 2008; Odoardi *et al.*, 2015). Participant R2 said, *"New ideas are obviously good, and we need that. When we feel the problem, we talk to the top management and get advice on what to do if things do not work out"*. Similarly, participants R4, R12, and R9 define that *information adds dynamic to work*. Information sharing can also contribute to work-related learning (Cangialosi *et al.*, 2020; Bartunek *et al.*, 2008), which suggests that when management regularly communicates about goals and clarifies work-related expectations, employees develop a broader understanding of their role in the organisation, which utterly facilitate their work-based learning (R11, R5, R12, R14, and R15), as an example, R15 said: *"Feedback is a way of learning from the mistakes."* So, quality information significantly impacts organisational innovation and learning perspective. Continuous feedback and learning procedures bring goodwill to the customers (Juran, 1986; Zeng *et al.*, 2015), which supports the statement made by R5, R8, R9, R10, R12, R13, and R15. For example, participant R12 said, *"If the information is accurate, we can work without hesitation and have zero chance of order rejection by the buyers."* Also, R13 Said, *"Whenever we get feedback from customers, we call the employees and inform them about the issues."* Hence, discussion shows that quality information has a significant impact on customers' nonfinancial performance perspectives. Information sharing reflects on HRM practice generated by the organisation toward employees and knowledge sharing (Nonaka, 1994; Wang

& Noe, 2010; Zeng *et al.*, 2015). It is mentioned mainly by the participants (R1a, R3, R4, R8, R10, R15) about the feedback what they have learned after that also after the mistakes, how they have solved the problems, how they maintain the business flow with the customers and brought goodwill with them. For instance, participant R15 said, *“Information always has a role-play on the business performance.”* Therefore, the above discussion shows that quality information substantially impacts on organisational financial and nonfinancial performance, including internal business perspective.

Table 4.12: Files and References of Quality Information

Name	Files	References
Quality Information	15	83
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	15	64
Name	Files	References
Financial	9	13
Non-Financial Performance	15	51
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	9	14
Innovation and Learning Perspective	13	18
Internal Business Perspective	13	19
Name	Files	References
Gap of Practice	7	9
Practice by Management	9	10

Source: primary data

Strategic Quality Planning impacts on performance

Organisational financial and non-financial Performance

Strategic quality planning is generally viewed as a management quality function involving the quality activities of a plan designed to accomplish business objectives (Lisinski and Saruckij, 2006; Gray, 1986). Nine participants (see Table 4.13) defined organisation practice quality as a significant issue from the strategic level. However, three participants said they do not consider it, or the organisation does not inform them about it. Strategic planning directs the organisation to focus on the chosen objectives for financial and non-financial achievement (Choi and Eboch, 1998; Ooi *et al.*, 2012). Maximum participants acknowledge that managing defect rates impact on business. An example can be mentioned when R4 said, *“We can control the loss if we can promptly identify the defect rate. Otherwise, we are wasting both time and money.”* Also noted by R5, *“One cannot take the button off. These goods are therefore disregarded.”* Most of the above participants talked about the procedures that must be followed to ensure product quality. Participants also mentioned how lack of quality might impact on business economically.

Furthermore, a Lack of quality expertise could result in factories producing goods of lower quality. Conversely, quality planning enables employees to work accurately to produce quality products (Choi and Eboch, 1998). This statement is in line with the comments made by participants R4, R5, and R12. For example, *R12 said, "If you set 5,000 items, 300 become faulty. These are currently gradually declining, and it has an impact on the company."* Being innovative helps create value for customers and thus improves the firm's performance to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage over its competitors (Mele and Colurcio, 2006). Therefore, strategic quality planning significantly impacts innovation and learning perspectives. This statement shows that strategic quality planning has an impact on organisational all sectors. A well-designed and coordinated approach is more likely to guarantee tremendous success for the new product (Martin and Home, 1993; Ooi *et al.*, 2012), which is defined by the participants R3, R5, R7, R12, and a few others. For example, participant *R3 said, "We transfer the particular employee to another department to work in a regular manner if we constantly find issues with his job and no progress is being made. Otherwise, if products are of worse quality, the buyer will complain."* Participants *R10, R11, and R14 are explained the same in this context"*. Hence quality panning has a significant impact on the customer's perspective.

A complete business strategy should incorporate a systematic plan for new products, connect the new product to the corporate goals, determine which market and technology to select, and what transmission criteria to apply (Martensen and Dahlgard, 1999; Cooper, 2000). Therefore, quality planning also works with the strategy, as discussed before. Participant R3 also acknowledged, *"If I notice the employee repeating the same error over and over again, I will issue a last warning to let the employee know to fix the issue. Otherwise, the employee will run into difficulties. Following the procedure as you work makes it easier to ensure quality."* In line with the statement, participants *R5, R7, R12: b), R13, and R14 acknowledged the same. For example, R14 said, "Different buyers have different requirements. However, if the quality is poor, they will not accept the merchandise."* The above statement shows that quality matters for sustainable business and customer goodwill. Also, technological innovation and the introduction of technology have been mentioned in the quality strategy for the internal business perspective. Moreover, regarding the impact of quality planning, six participants directly mentioned financial implications, and eleven said non-financial to the organisational performance (Table 4.13). Therefore, considering the literature and participant's statement, it can be said that strategic quality planning significantly impacts the organisational financial and non-financial perspective.

Table 4.13: Files and References of Strategic Quality Planning

Name	Files	References
Strategic Quality Planning	12	50
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	11	35
Name	Files	References
Financial	6	9
NonFinancial Performance	11	26
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	7	8
Innovation and Learning Perspective	3	3
Internal Business Perspective	9	15
Name	Files	References
gap of practice	3	3
Practicing By management	9	12

Source: Primary Data

Benchmarking impacts on performance

Organisational financial and non-fianncial performance

The value management process is benchmarked using a systematic approach that includes both hard and soft criteria. The crucial success factors (CSFs) are choosing the elements to be benchmarked, generating quantifiable performance metrics, comparing the outcomes, and selecting the optimal technique for benchmarking. The CSFs basically deal with the value management process as an objective measure that works with hard analysis such as ‘time,’ ‘cost,’ and ‘quality’ (Fong *et al.*, 2001; Maistry *et al.*, 2017). Participants recognised the financial impact as well. For example, R2 stated, “Benchmarking competitors is vital when the business shrinks. We will eventually have fewer orders, resulting in financial losses, fewer job prospects, and lower unemployment in the country.” Other participants also noted that benchmarking helps identify the reason for losing business or other aspects of a business's healthy and unhealthy situation (R6, R7, R13, R14). According to Medori and Steple (2000) and Lin and Shen (2007), benchmarking establishes and adopts appropriate final performance measurement systems for competitiveness, such as profit, market share, and cost. So, benchmarking can bring out the actual state of a business situation to the management, and management can make the right decision by observing the context. According to Fong *et al.* (2001), the critical success factor deals with the subjective value measurement process with soft aspects such as facilitator skills,

teamwork, creativity, customer satisfaction, also benchmarking results that reflect the actual situation. Therefore, benchmarking significantly impacts non-financial organisational performance. Considering the customer's perspective from the participant's comments, it is acknowledged by participant R2, *"Benchmarking is necessary because if it deteriorates the market share slowly, at some point, we will get fewer orders from customers, jobs opportunities will decrease, and unemployment in the country will increase. So, we can work accordingly to maintain goodwill with customers"*. R7 said, *"Analysis helps to understand the real financial and other issues of customers and positions of our organisation."* Only two participants spoke about the impact of benchmarking on the customer's perspective. Respectively, ten and eight participants (Table 4.14) said that Benchmarking has an impact on internal business, as well as on innovation and learning perspective. Participants defined in terms of innovation and learning perspective, such as participant R2, said, *"New ideas are certainly beneficial, and we require them. When we face any issues, we talk to upper management and obtain guidance on what to do if things don't work out."* Also, R7 said, *"Analysis helps us understand our organization's current financial state as well as other difficulties and positions."* R13, R15, R4, R6, R5, and R14 also support the statement. Almost 60% (8 out of 15 participants) of participants have defined that benchmarking impacts innovation and learning perspectives. According to Medori and Steeple (2000), benchmarking establishes and adopts an appropriate non-financial performance measurement system for competitiveness, such as quality, flexibility, time, delivery, and growth. So, benchmarking substantially impact on nonfinancial performance from an internal business perspective. For instance, participant R1 said, *"We occasionally look at how the other company is performing and how much of a performance gap we have with them."* Also, R15 said, *"We contrast the efficacy and efficiency goals. In this example, we generally compare performance to Bangladeshi organisations first, then to the rest of the world."* In line with them participants R13, R14, R4, R5, R6, are defined same. R12 said, *"We must compare our performance with both foreign and Bangladeshi factories, but we do it primarily with Bangladeshi factories."* As a result, identifying issues and resolving them for increased business performance is a widespread phenomenon revealed by the primary data mentioned above. Therefore, benchmarking significantly impacts the internal business perspective of organisational non-financial performance. According to Fong *et al.* (2001), crucial success elements are soft factors that deal with the subjective value measuring process, such as staff skills, teamwork, creativity, customer happiness, and benchmarking results that accurately reflect the situation. As a result, benchmarking has a significant impact on non-financial organisational performance in addition to financial performance, considering its primary (Table 4.14) and secondary data analysis.

Table 4.14: Fines and References of Management Benchmarking

Name	Files	References
Benchmarking	14	43
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	11	27
Name	Files	References
Financial	5	5
Nonfinancial Performance	11	22
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	2	2
Innovation and Learning Perspective	8	8
Internal Business Perspective	10	12
Name	Files	References
Practicing by management	14	16
Name	Files	References
Gap of Practice	9	9

Source: Primary Data

4.3 Innovation Management

4.4 Administrative Innovation impacts on performance

Administrative innovation occurs in the administrative process and affects an organisation's social system. It deals with rules, procedures, and structures related to the communication and exchange between organisational members (Damanpour, 1991; Damanpour *et al.*, 1989). Hence, administrative innovation has been divided into three ways such as internal organisational innovation, marketing innovation, and strategic innovation (Figure 4.6).

Figure 4.6: themes and sub-themes of innovation practices

Internal Organisational Innovation impacts on performance

An organisation can internally foster innovation by encouraging, recognising, and rewarding creativity and allocating sufficient resources, including people, cash, and time (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990; Scot and Bruce, 1994; Woodman *et al.*, 1993). Employees' perceptions of such internal support in their work environment make up the psychological context of creativity, which can influence their creative work (Amabile *et al.*, 1996). Innovative work, team effort, and goodwill development with the customers are all linked with business success as a way of financial achievement. The following participants, R2, R7, R11, and R15, acknowledged that partnership improves quality and profit, as defined by participant R2, *“The profit will be shared between two (Partnership with the buyers). In this case, quality can be improved by a shared vision, and expenses may reduce”*. Only three participants acknowledged the financial impact on internal organisational innovation, even though they mentioned it indirectly (see below Table 4.15). The participants R2a, R2b, R5, and R14 defined that internal organisational innovation brings sustainable business performance. Also explained by participant R2, *“So using the computerised machine, we can save 3-4 days of production duration and similarly reduce the delay delivery days”*. Hence, from the above discussion, it can be summarised that innovation helps build continuous business performance and saves unexpected damages or threats to the organisation. According to Parajogo and Sohal (2001), innovative organisations foster a culture that prioritises sustaining core competitiveness and producing unique, innovative and appropriate solutions. As mentioned, the impact of new ideas on innovation and learning perspective in business from several participants, such as participant R1 said, *“A new idea can be beneficial to the organisation. We frequently notice how new ideas might inspire a new way of doing things*. In addition participant R2 said, *“New ideas are certainly beneficial, and we*

require them. When we encounter a problem, we consult with top management to determine what we should do if things do not work out.” Participants R4, R5, R6, R7, and R13 also acknowledged the same. However, besides the new ideas, a few participants also discussed the innovative way of doing things important in business performance (R8, R9, R12). Participants R1, R4, and R6 defined that internal organisational innovation directly impacts business. For example, participant R2 said, “In many circumstances, the information provided by floor-level staff is quite beneficial, and we accept it.” According to Parajogo and Sohal (2001), innovation in the 'internal organisational process' perspective works with customers and suppliers along with many other things. Hence, the above participant’s statement satisfies the innovation’s impact on the view of the internal business process. Similarly, the internal business process has a direct impact on process management. Hence organisational process implementation significantly impacts on business, including technological processes in administration (R14, R7, R9, and R11). For example, participant R7 said, “Employee suggestions are always appreciated as very significant to improve organisational performance while keeping the organisation safe from serious threats.” The primary data implication shows (Table 4.15) all the 15 participants describe that internal business process innovation has a significant impact on business. Only three participants acknowledged the customer's perspective, whereas 11 and 14 participants described innovation and learning, and the internal business perspective. Surprisingly, only 4 participants have brought up the effect of internal organisational innovation from a financial standpoint. Internal organisational innovation thus has a significant non-financial impact on business performance but a comparatively minor impact on financial performance.

Table 4. 15: numeric value of Participants and their references

Name		Files	References
Internal Organisation Innovation		15	100
Name		Files	References
Business Performance		15	66
Name		Files	References
Financial Performance		4	9
NonFinancial Performance		15	57
Name		Files	References
Customers Perspective		3	5
Innovation and Learning Perspective		11	14
Internal Business Perspective		14	38
Name		Files	References
Gap of Practice		12	19
Practice by Management		11	15

Source: primary data

Marketing Innovation impacts on performance

In today's globalized world, businesses must deal with quick changes in customer needs as well as the character of marketplaces. Companies must develop new products and tactics to attract new customers and satisfy existing ones to achieve a competitive advantage and improve performance (Ungerma *et al.*, 2018). The innovative modern market positively impacts increasing sales and decreasing expenses, hence improving competitiveness. (Kamp and Parry, 2017). Which is acknowledged by participants R2 and R4. For example, participant R2 said, *“Direct buyers are preferable for long-term business and lower product prices.”* Therefore, marketing strategy is a part of marketing innovation (Kotler, 2005). As explained by participant R5, *“One thing we can do for minor defective products, we can decrease the price and sell it for \$5 instead of \$10 to make up for the losses.”* In addition, participants R10, R11, R12, and R1 defined strategic innovation's financial impact on business. Identifying new innovative markets is always a chance to add extra value to the business, which participant R3 represents in line with the statement of Kotler (2005). Therefore, marketing innovation has a significant financial impact on business performance based on the above discussion.

The notion of innovation moves a company forward (Ungerma *et al.*, 2018; Kamp and Parry, 2017; Wang and Ahmed, 2002). Several participants, such as R1, R11, R13, and R14, noted about creative ideas, new policies, and strategies from the customer's perspective have a significant impact on business as participant R1 said, *“I believe an alliance is a good concept because the shareholder (foreign investor) will attempt to contribute well with the resources, and we will do same in order to have a long-term business plan.”* Also, participant R14 said, *“Perhaps the buyer will not buy the new brand at first (when it is introduced), but if they buy once and validate the quality, they will return to buy again.”* An innovative marketing strategy can help the organisation to sustain its business performance. Coming out from the usual marketing procedure, if the organisation does something different, it may add extra value to the market (Kotler, 2010). Participants R1, R7, and R2 also defied the same. R2 said, *“It is better to have direct buyers for sustainable business.”* According to Ungerma *et al.* (2018), applying marketing innovation to the market has positive effects on a company's internal operations in a number of ways, including 'creating a positive public image and brand through increasing output, which also acknowledged by the participants R3, R8, and R12. According to Kotler (2010) and Baba (2012), improving communication with customers helps to improve the quality of the products. Participants R1, R2, and R11 also acknowledged the same. For instance, participant R2 said, *“It is better to have direct buyers for sustainable business and better price of products. Some*

factories already have direct buyers". Kotler (2005) also defined that innovation-oriented firms increase competitiveness by changing strategic planning and finding new markets. As mentioned by participant R4, *"Consider the possibility that if a buyer rejects a product, we may still use it outdoors if we have a showroom."* 9 and 12 participants, respectively, agreed that marketing innovation has a direct impact on both the financial and non-financial success of an organisation. (Table 4.16). Therefore, from the above discussion, it can be said that marketing innovation has a significant impact on the organisational internal business perspective.

Table 4. 16: numeric value of Participants and their references

Name	Files	References
Marketing Innovation	14	55
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	13	38
Name	Files	References
Financial Performace	9	15
NonFinancial Performance	12	23
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	5	6
Innovation and Learning Perspective	5	5
Internal Business Perspective	9	12
Name	Files	References
Gap of Practice	10	13
Practice by Management	3	4

Source: Primary data

Strategic Innovation impacts on performance

Strategic innovation extends beyond product innovation to connect resources and efforts to a successful overall business strategy (Damanpour, 1991). Strategic alliances or doing business by sharing partnerships could be a promising approach for the garments industry, which participants R4 and R1 explained. *For instance, R1 said, "Strategic alliance is a good idea for having a long-time business plan by sharing profit, ensuring quality, and can reduce expenses."* Furthermore, innovative strategic decisions can be made on waste management, variance control, resource allocation, and marketing policies (Wang and Ahmed, 2002). R5, R9, R13, and R14 participants also highlighted that innovative planning as an illustration. For example, R5 said, *"We always produce 3% more products than necessary, but our goal is to reduce that to 1%. We want to produce fewer supplementary items to cut costs and improve quality."* According

to Kotler (2005), strategic innovation deals with management's new policies to enhance the business. Hence, from the following discussion, it can be said that strategic innovation significantly impacts organisational financial performance. Strategic accurate decisions can make the organisation competitive and ensure quality services (Teece, 1980). As explained by participant R4, *“Assume the government introduces a new higher-paying scheme for employees beginning this month. Many factories were forced to close for a day or 10 days after hearing this. This, however, has not occurred in our clothing.”* Participants R5, R12, R13, and R14 also noted a similar statement. For example, R14 said, *“Even if we may have a number of suppliers, it counts for the company if customers request a certain source.”* The participants' discussion above revealed that strategic innovation substantially affects business, and its use may affect the organization's competitiveness. Conversely, with a gap in strategic innovation, an organisation may lose better opportunities for a successful business.

Innovation and continuous improvement are vital dimensions for sustainable business performance. Strategic innovation can introduce new ideas and processes to make the organisation competitive (Damanpour & Evan, 1984). Participant R1 said, *“New ideas can be helpful for the organization. We frequently see that new ideas can give a new process to do the work,”* also agreed by other participants, such as R5, R12, R13, and R14. Strategic innovation has an impact on customers, markets, and the quality of goods and services, all of which influence internal organisational success. Participant R3 said, *“If we attempt, innovation might provide a new technique to help reduce delivery delays. Assume that having email availability 24 hours a day, seven days a week can increase service quality.”* R1 and R4 also defined the same way its impact on business. Damanpour & Evan (1984) explained that organisational strategic innovation improves efficiency and productivity, increases market share, and generates economic wealth for the organisation. Participants R5, R7, R12, R13, and R14 defined the same thing in response to this statement. For example, R7 said, *“To end the strike and traffic congestion, the government, the BGMEA, and the opposition political parties can come together and pass a new law. This could be beneficial for this company's operations.”* This remark is connected to Hage & Aiken (1967), Kleinknecht (1996), Cooper (2005), and Damanpour et al. (2018), who defined that organisation introduces strategic innovations to adapt to environmental change and achieve strategic intents for maintaining and improving performance. Table 4.17 reveals that 7 and 12 participants out of 15, respectively, acknowledged the effects of strategic innovation on organisational financial and nonfinancial performance. Therefore, based on the

primary and secondary evidence, organisational financial and nonfinancial performance is significantly impacted by strategic innovation.

Table 4.17: Numeric value of Participants and their references

Name	Files	References
Strategic Innovation	14	88
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	12	55
Name	Files	References
Financial Performance	7	14
NonFinancial Performance	12	41
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	6	6
Innovation and Learning Perspective	7	9
Internal Business Perspective	12	26
Name	Files	References
Gap of Practice	12	24
Practice by Management	7	9

Source: primary data

4.5 Technological Innovation

Technology is used to develop new goods and services, as well as to mediate between inputs and outputs (process technology). Physical technologies are represented by product and process technologies (Anzola-Román *et al.*, 2018; Damanpour, 1992; Wang and Kim, 2017; Kleinknecht, 1996). The technological change reflects significant advances in technological performance within a technological regime. So, technology impacts technology (Lawless and Anderson, 1996). In this research work, technological innovation is divided into three ways: technological products, technological processes, and technological technology.

Technological Process impacts on performance

Technological innovation can be defined as a process in which new technologies are integrated into developing new products or processes. Thus, it has a strong financial impact on business (Maistry *et al.*, 2017; Burgelman *et al.*, 2004). As acknowledged by the participants, the technological process helps the organisation by saving employee costs, production costs, and production duration (R1, R3, R5, R12). For example, participant R5 said, “There is a new machine that produces cotton from discarded textiles. New ideas are essential in this industry.” Participant R12 noted, “The positive side is that we used to have 12 helpers, but now we use only 8. Even we can make zero helpers if we can use upgraded technology. We are trying to do so.” Participants also argued that it is expensive to apply technology methods. Therefore, if the organisation cannot implement the technological procedure, it will negatively influence finances

(R13). As earlier, it is mentioned that technology innovation affects customers because quality products and services develop goodwill for better business (Damanpour, 1989). As acknowledged by participant R4, *“If we use hand Lay, the linkage may not be good.”* R11 said, *“We have software that converts Bengali/English to Chinese. As a result, anytime we need to place an order or bring something from China, we converse in Chinese.”* Therefore, providing quality service could be a way to build credibility in the Bangladeshi apparel industry. The technological process innovation is understood as the result of the emergence of dominant designs (Anderson and Tushman, 1990) and how appropriate opportunities change with firm size (Klepper, 1996). Therefore, the technological process impacts on the innovation and learning perspective of business. Participants R1, R5, and R8 acknowledged the effect, saying that the machines introduced currently are favourable for us because we have to relocate workers to learn how to run the upgraded machines, and so organisation lowering local workers, creating unemployment issues in Bangladesh. Hence, from the above discussion, it can be said that technological implementation helps the organisation follow innovative processes that increase productivity and competitiveness. According to Klepper (1996), early technological development is motivated by the drive to meet market requirements, which was also defined by the participants R1, R2, R3, R4, R12, and R14. For instance, participant R14 said, *“This is really a gap, and we can make much better-quality products if we get that machine (new technology).”* Depending on the initial functionality and cost of the technology, the introduction of technology may lead to an early emphasis on enhancing the technology's functionality to meet the users' requirements or on process technology to reduce the price to a level that corresponds to the consumer's willingness to pay. As acknowledged by R13 and R5, where R5 said, *“The absence of the production facilities, washing facility, and internal printing facility has an influence on business. Therefore, technology is significantly affecting business.”* So, process innovation has an impact on the production process and business. Tarafdar and Gordon (2007) also explain that process innovation is related to the production process's improvement, efficiency, and effectiveness. Therefore, process innovation has a direct financial and non-financial impact on business. Table 4.18 shows that 5 participants acknowledged the financial impact of process innovation in business, and 13 participants out of 15 acknowledged the nonfinancial effects on business. From the nonfinancial perspective, only 2 participants acknowledged the customers' perspective, 6 participants for innovation and learning perspective, but 12 participants acknowledged about the impact of process innovation on the internal business perspective. Hence, strategic innovation impacts both organisational financial and non-financial performance.

Table 4.18: numeric value of Participants and their references

Name	Files	References
Technological Process	15	53
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	13	37
Name	Files	References
Financial Performance	5	8
NonFinancial Performance	13	29
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	2	2
Innovation and Learning Perspective	6	7
Internal Business Perspective	12	20
Name	Files	References
Gap of Practice	7	10
Practice by Management	4	6

Technological Products impacts on performance

Product innovation is defined as the introduction of new products or services to suit the needs of an external user. Product innovation is primarily market-driven, and its technological impact may increase the production volume and ensure better quality products for a successful business perspective (Damanpour, 1991; Tidd and Bessant, 2005; Utterback and Afuah, 1995). The following participants defined that product innovation significantly impacts financial and nonfinancial perspectives in business (R5, R6, R4, and R11). For example, participant R6 said, *“The organisation will benefit financially if we use technology in production,”* and R4 said, *“Innovation can increase productivity, but unemployment in the country may increase simultaneously.”* Therefore, technological product innovation has a significant impact on business. The drivers of product innovations are customer needs and demand. So, the organisation desires to become competitive in the market and grow the business (Damanpur, 1991; Allen, 2000; Prajogo and Sohal, 2004). Only one participant (R1) acknowledged that technological product innovation impacts on customers, saying, *“Technology helps to ensure the quality of services and products both.”* However, three participants explained that product innovation significantly impacts on organisational innovation and learning perspective (R11, R12, and R5). So, from the following discussion, it is shown that introducing innovative technology in production significantly impacts quality and business. Participants R2, R5, R6a, R6b, R11, and R12 also defined that technological implementation in product innovation has an impact on the internal business perspective. For instance, R12 said, *“ We use leisure light to bind the pocket to the pants. Using this leisure light marking device instead of a chalk marker saves us both time*

and money.” Following the above discussion, it has been identified that technological innovation in production increases production volume and ensures better quality products. Similarly, a participant also criticized that the technological gap in production negatively impacts on product quality. As acknowledged by participant R14, “This is really a gap, and we can make much better-quality products if we get that machine.” Hence from the above discussion, the conclusion can be made that technological innovation in products has a significant impact on organisational non-financial performance. Table 4.19 shows that 4 participants acknowledged the financial impact of technological product innovation in business, and 9 out of 15 participants acknowledged the non-financial effects on business. From the non-financial perspective, Only one person acknowledged the perspective of the customer, three participants acknowledged the perspective of innovation and learning, and nine people acknowledged the perspective of the internal business. Hence, technological product innovation impacts on organisational both financial and non-financial performance. Only one participant out of 15 stated that their organisation practices technological product innovation, and four stated that their firm has a product-technology innovation gap. So, to increase organisational financial and non-financial performance, management in the Bangladeshi garment sector must use technological product innovation to introduce new products to the market.

Table 4.19: numeric value of Participants and their references

Name	Files	References
Technological Products	12	26
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	10	20
Name	Files	References
Financial Performance	4	4
NonFinancial Performance	9	16
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	1	1
Innovation and Learning Perspective	3	3
Internal Business Perspective	9	12
Name	Files	References
Gap of Practice	4	4
Practice by the Management	1	2

Source: Primary Data

Technological Technology impacts on performance

The common understanding of innovation links it with new technology or technical innovation, and it is understood that organisational innovation is also associated with technological innovation. This misunderstanding is exacerbated later by using the term innovation to portray technology-based products and process innovations while the importance of technology and technological innovation for organization adoption, competition, and performance is undeniable (Sotarauta *et al.*, 2006; Grubler *et al.*, 2012; Utterback, 1994). Acknowledging the technological impact on customers, participant R1 said, *“Using the computerise machine, we can save 3-4 days of production duration and reduce the delay delivery days”*. Also, R4 said, *“Time can also be saved, and the quality of the garments will also be better,”* participant R11 also defined the same. Technology is defined as tools, devices, and knowledge for products and processes that impact organisational efficiency, facilitate the conversion of inputs into outputs and reduce inefficiencies in product development, production, and delivery. Thus, technological innovation on organisational financial performance is related to products and processes (Sotarauta *et al.*, 2006; Grubler *et al.*, 2012). R1, R2, R6, R7, R10, R11, and R12 all recognized that an organisation might save money and time by integrating technology in the manufacturing and processing area. For example, participant R1 noted, *“In order to save time and money, we assume that the manufacturing will be completed in 10–12 days, although it may actually take up to 3–4 extra days.”* Similarly, participant R11 said, *“We are arranging for APE and FEW machines to be brought in so that we can quickly produce jackets and pants, which could help us cut down on manufacturing time and costs.”* Hence, new technology has an impact on organisational financial performance.

Technological advancements within a technological regime are reflected in changes in technology. The broader meaning of technology changes occurs due to the cumulative effects of multiple technologies and technological innovations over time, which impact the new organisation for its innovativeness (Lawless & Anderson, 1996; Lawless and Fisher, 1990), which is acknowledged by participants R15, R14, R4, R11, R13, and R8. *For example, R8 Said, “The new machines are advantageous for us because that allow us to minimise the number of personnel. However, we must train the staff to learn how to operate the improved machines.”* As was already noted, new technology assists in creating high-quality products, but employees can also get new knowledge, which empowers them to work creatively. Technological changes can impact the development of new initiatives, economic growth, level of employment, and social prosperity (Dahlman and Westphal, 1982; Chanaron and Jolly, 1999; Rosenzweig, 2017), which

is also acknowledged by the participants R1, R2, R4, R5, R6, R7, R9, R10, R12, R13, and R14. For instance, R1 said, “We believe that computerised equipment can help this factory manage its time and save time.” In addition, R2 stated, “Computerization can be advantageous to manage time and save time for this facility to minimise the delay in delivery days.” The above participants mainly acknowledged that technology effectively increases production volume and reduces time. It is further emphasised that by utilising technology procedures, the organisation may reduce delivery delays, which has an effect on gaining consumers' trust and improving organisational efficiency. Table 4.20 further reveals that 9 and 14 participants agreed that technological advances impact both financial and non-financial performance (Table 4.20). Therefore, it can be concluded from the main study and literature review that technology significantly affects the organization's financial and non-financial performance.

Table 4.20: Numeric value of Participants and their references

Name	Files	References
Technological Technology	15	62
Name	Files	References
Business Performance	14	45
Name	Files	References
Financial	9	14
NonFinancial Performance	14	31
Name	Files	References
Customers Perspective	3	3
Innovation and Learning Perspective	7	8
Internal Business Perspective	13	20
Name	Files	References
Gap of Practice	11	13
Practice by Management	4	4

Source: Primary Data

4.6 Relationship between TQM and Innovation

According to Prajogo and Sohal (2001), Quality management and innovation have a contradictory relationship. According to Imai (2007) and Oliver (2009), QM proponents believe in continuous improvement with the goal of simplifying or streamlining a process. To maintain control and stability, continuous emphasises incremental change and necessitates standardization or formalisation. This statement is in line with the few participants, such as defined by R2, “Training allows us to learn more about the job. We gain knowledge through training.” Also, participant R4 said, “Group work helps to do the job accurately.” R1 said, “Working with colleagues allows us to understand more about the job and do that more precisely. As a

result, we can reduce the number of defects and make fewer mistakes.” Innovation is the key foundation for sustainable business performance. Quality management supports innovation by enabling efficient detection of customer needs, training, idea sharing, and top management commitment and participation (Hoang *et al.*, 2006). Participants R14, R01, and R07 all stated the same. Top management’s commitment to quality reflects in the organisation’s strategy for changing the culture and learning new things to meet the objectives or new goals (Juran, 1993; Bollen, 1989). However, TQM is defined as a holistic management philosophy that strives for continuous learning and organisational improvement (Flynn *et al.*, 1995). A statement noted by participant R12, *“Top management also update us on how to ensure the quality and what to do.”* R01 said, *“Employees may know about the requirements. It makes communication easy among us and helps us perform well.”* Also, R08 said, *“We work the way they instruct me,”* and a similar discussion was concluded by participants R04, R05, and R06. The above information can relate to the articles as Juran (1993), and Deming (1986) stated that receiving customer complaint information is one way to find opportunities to improve product and service quality. R04, R06, and R07, on the other hand, emphasised the buyer's (customer's) requirements and urged following management's strategic procedures to meet the customer's expectations. For example, participant R06 said, *“We always prioritize fulfilling the buyer’s requirements.”* Participants R1 and R15 addressed that working in groups might help learners accomplish precise work and minimise errors. Participants R8, R12, and R15 also mentioned that training allows them to learn more about their jobs, and they learn things through training. According to participants R1, R3, R12, R13, and R15 QM process helps to reduce waste and variance. In addition, participants defined that waste and variance control directly save loss and bring a good reputation (R1, R3, R5, and R7). This statement is in line with the author Sadikohlu and Zehir (2010), the goal of process management strategies is to reject waste and increase efficiency. According to Oliver (2009), consumer focus is a source of creativity. Hence, TQM practices help to increase organisational innovativeness. So, from the above discussion, it can be said that TQM practices also influence innovation performance.

Furthermore, following the recording procedures of process management, the failure and success record helps the employees learn capabilities and identify innovative ideas and ways to deal with the matters (Perdomo-Ortiz *et al.*, 200; Perdomo-Ortiz *et al.*, 2009). In line with the statement, R1, R3, and R13 all shared similar comments. For example, R13 said, *“We continue to use our method for tracking our successes and failures.”* Only 7 participants noted that preventive maintenance has an impact on innovation and learning perspective. According to

McAdam *et al.* (1998), quality management can be viewed as the foundation of a culture that fosters innovation in many ways. Pfeifer *et al.* (1998) propose three important subject areas for innovation: customer-oriented and service, flexible organisational structures, and creative employees, all of which align with QM principles. Participant R13 said, *"We have a complaint department that meets with the staff once a month to exchange unique thoughts, problems, and suggestions across the groups. We also have a complaint box in each restroom, where staff can leave concerns, ideas, or thoughts to be collected later."* In addition, Participant R2 also defined the same. Therefore, sharing information and accepting suggestions based on people management is essential for any organisation. 13 out of 15 participants acknowledged the importance of employee suggestions in their organisation. For example participant R1 said, *"We frequently talk about the quality issues among our staffs. The meeting helps to bring new innovative ideas,"* which is also repeated by participants R10, R2, R5, R6, R9, and R4. For instance, R6 said, *"We always aim to operate as a team since we believe it boosts productivity and allows for mutual learning."* As a result, both primary and secondary data under this discussion admit that employee teamwork and group problem-solving have a moderate impact on innovation and learning perspectives on organisational success. In addition, 13 participants defined that QM practices help an organisation to be innovative in performance. R1, R2, R4, R5, and R6, described that quality management practices increase employees' knowledge. It enables the employees to be creative. In responses to the direct questions about the relationship between organic QM and mechanistic QM's impact on administrative and technological innovation, 13 out of 15 participants defined that both aspects of QM strongly impact administrative and technological innovation.

Therefore, Quality management practices strongly impact on innovation and organisational financial and non-financial performance. Fourteen participants have referred 20 times to the impact of innovation and learning perspectives on non-financial performance. The participants R01, R02, R05, R07, R13, and R15 mostly talked about the new ideas which come from employees' suggestions and lead to a successful business. Innovation is defined as the development of new ideas by people who, over time, engage in transactions with others within an institutional order (Garud *et al.*, 2013), which brings drastic and incremental success to the organization (Ali *et al.*, 2010; Prajogo and Sohal, 2001; Bright and Cooper, 1993). For example, participant R01 said, *"Meeting helps bring new innovative ideas. Sometimes buyers may ask for any new product requirement, so we immediately pass the information to the employees to let them know and understand more about the work procedures."* The above primary data can relate

to the explanation of Feng (2006), Feng *et al.* (2021), and Rahman (2002), who defined that employee involvement is a vital part of any TQM effort, which has emphasised the importance of human resources in line with the output of Bowen and Lawler (1992). However, eight participants said that solving problems in a group has a non-financial impact on innovation and learning perspective in organisational performance. As noted by participant R1, *“We frequently talk about the quality issues among our staff. The meeting helps to bring new innovative ideas.”* Sitting in a group to solve problems or sharing ideas empowering the employees, which helps develop confidence among them (Ahire *et al.*, 1996). In contrast, it is stated by a number of participants, including R3, R5, R7, R9, R10, R11, and R15, that not only do quality management techniques have an impact on innovation, but innovation methods also help ensure quality.

Participants, for instance, agreed that administrative innovation practice is important for the company, despite the fact that organisations are still not entirely technology-oriented (R4, R5, R10, R15). We need to use software to do the jobs accurately (R9, R10, R13). Therefore, the above statement indicates that innovation practices are also important to ensure the quality for several aspects in the context of Bangladesh garments organisation. Mazzola and Perrone (2013) define enlightening product quality as closely tied to strategic requirements aimed at learning knowledge. However, Prajogo and Sohal (2003) found a favourable association between QM and innovation success in Australian organisations. From a managerial standpoint, quality improvement, particularly in products, can be viewed as a means to meet strategic knowledge needs rather than as a means to meet the demands of efficiency and effectiveness. When a corporation wishes to boost productivity, it has long been recognised that process innovation is required, emphasizing a possible link between innovation and quality management (Martinez-Costa and Martinez-Lorente, 2008). After reviewing the current literature on the quality-innovation relationship in terms of the hard and soft dimensions of quality management, it was discovered that many studies empirically analyse single quality management and its impact on innovation outcomes rather than taking into account the soft and hard parts of the approach, such as Zeng *et al.* (2015) is a significant recent example. A small number of studies look at the links between Quality Certification (ISO9000) and innovation, focusing primarily on the hard QIMs and innovation (Zeng *et al.*, 2015). According to Maistry *et al.* (2017), Technological innovation impacts on effectiveness, which refers to embracing new technology and relates to production processes and products or services and service delivery that satisfies the mechanistic TQM elements (Prajogo, 2016). However, administrative innovation improves organizational performance, structures, systems, and processes by implementing a new working

process that satisfies the organic TQM elements (Weerawardena, 2003). Therefore, organic TQM elements are considered to measure administrative innovations. Similarly, to measure technological innovation, mechanistic TQM elements are considered (Maistry *et al.*, 2017). However, from the above discussion, it can be summarised that QM practices significantly impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Hence, Mechanistic Quality management practices have a significant direct impact on Administrative and Technological innovation. Similarly, Organic QM has a significant direct impact on Administrative and Technological innovation. Furthermore, chapter five includes a critical discussion of these topics.

4.7 Analysis and Results: Quantitative Study

4.7.0 Data Screening

Data screening is the process of cleaning the data to fit the statistical analysis. This process is needed to ensure the data is usable, reliable, and valid for testing for causal theory. A researcher must examine whether the primary data has a missing value, suspicious response patterns, outliers, and data distribution (Hair *et al.*, 2021). The primary data was loaded and coded into the SPSS file for the different screening tests.

Missing Value

Missing data can be problematic if the missing quantity exceeds 15% of an observation (Hair *et al.*, 2021). Simultaneously, a big number of responses missing might get attention on the pattern of missing value (Pallant, 2013). A strict filtration process has been used for this study, and nine responses (2, 128,137,142,171,251,253,320, and 367) were removed due to missing values greater than five percent of the response variable. Overall missing values are less than 5%, considered insignificant (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2019). In addition, if missing values are $\leq 5\%$, they can be imputed with an average mean score of the variable. However, this study deleted all the missing value responses to avoid complicity in further calculating EFA and CFA (Hair *et al.*, 2021).

Assessment of Outliers

The unusual and extreme response to a particular variable, such as a univariate or group of variables or multivariate, is defined as an outlier (Meyers *et al.*, 2016; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2019). This study used Mahalanobis distance (D2) to identify cases for multivariate outliers, which means the distance of the variable's mean value from the centroid point as the common point where the mean of all variables intersects. The Mahalanobis distance < .001 is considered an outlier, and this study detected 12 (13, 319, 294, 110, 179, 6, 12, 106, 328, 327, 322, and 155) cases of multivariate outliers (see Table 4.21), which are deleted from the data set to increase the accuracy and reliability of the results.

Table 4.21: Mahala Nobis distance (D2)-Cases of Multivariate Outliers

	ID	MAH_1	Prob_MD	Outlier	Filter_ \$
1	13	104.4411	0	1	0
2	319	82.54828	0	1	0
3	294	69.84239	0.00001	1	0
4	110	68.49205	0.00001	1	0
5	179	68.01088	0.00001	1	0
6	6	65.80901	0.00003	1	0
7	12	65.44411	0.00003	1	0
8	106	65.00476	0.00003	1	0
9	328	59.24604	0.00021	1	0
10	127	59.06368	0.00022	1	0
11	322	58.91953	0.00023	1	0
12	155	57.49179	0.00036	1	0

Multi-Collinearity Test

Collinearity is defined as a situation where two or more two independent or independent variables are correlated with each other in a regression model (Meyers *et al.*, 2016; Mason and Perreault Jr, 1991). A strong relationship among independent variables usually inflates the standard errors, which adversely affect the statistical insignificant of coefficients (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2019). The correlation matrix of the independent variables and the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) approaches were used in this study to detect multicollinearity among independent variables (Kaplan, 1994; Peng and Lai, 2012). Hair *et al.* (2011) proposed that correlation coefficients greater than 0.90 indicate the occurrence of multicollinearity among independent variables. The correlation Table 4.22 show that all matrix values are significantly below the specified threshold of 0.90 or more. This implies that all independent variables are independent of one another, effectively ruling out the possibility of multicollinearity.

Table 4.22: Correlation Matrix of the Independent Variables

Latent Variables		Respondents	B_av	C_av	D_av	E_av	F_av	NF_av
Pearson Correlation	Respondents	1						
	OGQ_avg	-.026**		1				
	MCQ_avg	-.040**	.081**		1			
	AD_avg	-.145**	.050**	.165**		1		
	TN_avg	-.157**	.014**	.054**	.079**	1**		
	F_avg	-.078**	.094**	.352**	.085**	.023**		1
	NF_avg	.016**	.045**	.168**	.045**	.289**	.099**	

Note: ** = correlation is significant at 0.01 percent (1-tailed)

Common Method Variance (CMV)

CMV is defined as the shared covariance among variables due to measurement error rather than variable constructs (Kave, 2003; Tehseen *et al.*, 2017). This issue also frequently arises in self-reporting data since social scientists have traditionally established relationships among explanatory variables, this could mislead due to systematic error (Jakobsen and Jensen, 2015) because CMV can either inflate or deflate the relationship among variables (Chang *et al.*, 2010). Harman's 'single factor test' was employed to inspect data for the common method bias (Podsakoff and Organ, 1986). The problem of common method bias is positive if the single factor accounts for the maximum variance in the model (Chang *et al.*, 2010). This study used principal component analysis and extracted six factors. Which cumulatively explained 74.530 % (Table 4.24). However, any single factor's highest explained variation is 19.5 % which is well below than a critical level of 50% (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2012). Therefore, this study rules out the probability of common method bias and its resulting impact on the variables.

4.7.1 Descriptive analysis for Variance

Table 4.23 below shows that none of the measured variable's variance values are greater than 10. Therefore, all the variables met the level of the threshold for statistical calculation. According to Chang *et al.* (2010), if any of the variances are greater than 10, have a negative impact on statistical analysis. The descriptive analysis of latent (Table 4.23) variables was used to perform a basic summary of various indicators to identify the impact of TQM and Innovation practices on organisational performance. This study used a five-point Likert scale to measure the latent variables. Moreover, to verify the result's of reliability, validity, and generalisability, this study used a pre-developed and tested scale for measuring the variables.

Table 4.23: Descriptive Statistics for Latent variables

Descriptive Statistics		
	Mean	Std. Deviation
Latent Variables	186.47	106.747
OGQ_avg	22.5414	2.35923
MCQ_avg	26.8464	2.36539
AD_avg	13.3867	1.3543
TN_avg	15.5305	1.56963
F_avg	23.6457	2.21975
NF_avg	24.1943	2.34613

Source: Primary Spss

4.7.2 Exploratory Factor Analysis

The primary goal of using EFA is to enable an understanding of how elements are placed in different dimensions, given that the first step in implementing an EFA is to determine whether the data matrix is factorisable (Pasquali, 1998). To do so, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) criterion and Bartlett's sphericity test are two often used criteria (Dziuban and Shirkey, 1974). The KMO index, also known as the data to sample adequacy index, displays the amount of adequacy of EFA application to the data set, with a value fluctuating between zero and one, and is a value that shows the proportion of item variance that is explained by a latent variable (Lorenzo-Seva *et al.*, 2011). The current study employed an EFA to extract factors using the principal component approach. The method based on the internal consistency of Cronbach α was employed to establish the consistency of the instrument that was used. Therefore, valid scales are used for this research work. This method assesses the reliability of a measurement instrument by using a set of items that are expected to measure the same construct or theoretical dimension, assuming that the items in the questionnaire (measured on a Likert scale from 1 to 5) measure the same constructs and are highly correlated (Venkatraman and Grant, 1986). The stronger the internal consistency of the items tested, the closer Cronbach's value is to 1. Cronbach's α coefficient (α), used in other studies, highlights that a value of 0.7 is a decent indicator, a value of 0.8 is a good indicator, and a value of 0.9 is an exceptional indicator. The proposed model has an associated value of KMO > 0.7 (see Appendix 4), which is greater than 0.5, indicating that there is a decent correlation between the items that compose the model (Hayton *et al.*, 2004). The Bartlett's test of sphericity is also a significant level of 0.000 (see Appendix 4), which means variables are strongly correlated. The principal components method

was employed to extract the factors. Table 4.24 demonstrates the presence of six components, and the value that remained up to level six is 1.474, which proves that there are six new constructs. The rotation sum of squared loadings cumulative percentages is > 50 and is accepted for further model fit analysis. In this case, it is 74.530 %, which shows that the model is a good fit for analysis following structural equational modelling.

Table 4.24: Total Variance Explained (Cumulative)

Total Variance Explained									
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.903	19.513	19.513	3.903	19.513	19.513	2.847	14.235	14.235
2	2.888	14.44	33.952	2.888	14.44	33.952	2.71	13.548	27.783
3	2.66	13.299	47.252	2.66	13.299	47.252	2.577	12.887	40.67
4	2.31	11.552	58.803	2.31	11.552	58.803	2.479	12.395	53.065
5	1.671	8.357	67.161	1.671	8.357	67.161	2.264	11.321	64.386
6	1.474	7.369	74.53	1.474	7.369	74.53	2.029	10.144	74.53

Source: Primary Data

4.7.3 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

The factorial validity of each dimension and the final model were determined based on a CFA using the software Amos (V.26, SPSS), which was utilised to generate the variance and covariance matrices, as well as to estimate the causal measurement model (see below Figure 4.7). The CFA approach entailed a multistep procedure and the estimation of each step's specific parameters. Each dimension was statistically accepted based on the value derived from the χ^2 and indices mentioned in Table 4.26, followed by the standard measurement threshold, such as chi-square (χ^2)/df < 3, P>0.05, CFI > 0.95, AGFI > 0.80, RMSEA < 0.05, and PCLOSE > 0.05 (Hu and Bentler, 1999). Given the research aims, the matrix of variances and covariance of the component items was utilised to look for a direct or indirect causal relationship between the items, or to determine if they interacted through correlated routes. Model fit refers to how well the proposed model is based on the correlation between variables in the data set. In order to have a good fit of the model, it has to account for all the major correlations inherent in the dataset. A few specific measures are carried out here to determine the goodness of fit. The

matrices and acceptable thresholds are listed below, defined by Hu and Bentler (1999). Therefore, following the standard threshold, this research threshold is shown well acceptable goodness of fit almost in every case in Table 4.25. Furthermore, the assessment of the path model, measurement models, model fit analysis, and model evaluation is carried out in section 4.8, where a broad analysis of CFA and EFA is carried out to test the reliability and validity of the data sets for this study.

Table 4.25: Goodness of Fit

Measures (using by AMOS and SPSS)	Threshold
CMIN/DF	1.942
GFI	0.923
AGFI	0.896
RMSEA	0.052
PCLOSE	0.348
CFI	0.958

Sources: Primary Data.

4.8 Path Analysis

Assessment of Path model results:

Structural equation modelling is very popular and one of the widely used methods to examine the relationship among the latent variables due to its strength of maximising the defined variance (Hair *et al.*, 2011; Ong and Puteh, 2017). According to Ong and Puteh (2017), and Henseler and Sarstedt (2013), two steps method are reliable and efficient for the assessment of measurement and structural model, which is discussed below.

Assessment of measurement Model

It is important to test a hypothesis without measuring biases such as reliability, unidimensionality, and validity (Shah and Goldstein, 2006; Henseler and Sarstedt, 2013). Structural equation modelling was employed in this study analysis to test the measurement model and proposed hypothesis. As a result, a three-stage procedure was used to confirm that the measurement items were reliable, unidimensional, and valid.

Internal consistency reliability and Individual item Reliability Test

Internal consistency reliability was tested in the first step to determine the degree to which measures are free of random measurement error (Kline, 2015). Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was performed using AMOS and manually calculated to investigate reliability. This study employed two distinct methodologies based on the CFA results, such as analyzing the squared multiple correlations (R^2) and measuring the composite reliability (CR) and the average variance extracted (AVE) (Carr and Pearson, 1999; Boyer and Hult, 2005). In the first stage, the squared multiple correlations (R^2) on individual items were analyzed to examine the reliability. The R^2 values in a measurement model were computed as 1 minus the ratio of the disturbance variance over the total variance (Weston and Gore, 2006; Kline, 2005). In the acceptable range of each item within the CFA setting, the R^2 value should be at least greater than 0.30 for the large set of data (Carr and Pearson, 1999). However, five measured variables' R^2 values were found lower than 0.30, which were dropped from this analysis at this stage (see Figure 4.7). As a result of the analysis report, the five following measured variables B5-Supplier.Qul.Mng, B6-Customer.Relations, B7-Social.Responsibility, C3-Preventive.Maintnce, and C6- Benchmarking were dropped from this stage.

Figure 4.7: CFA Model Value loading in each construct

Source: Primary Data

In addition, the composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE) were calculated using the complete standardized solution in the CFA results (Hult *et al.*, 2004). According to a rule of thumb, the acceptable composite reliability (CR) should be > 0.70, and the average variance extracted (AVE) should be > 0.5 (Fornell and Larcker, 1981; Kim, 2009). The following Table 4.26 shows the CR range from 0.752 to 0.911 and AVE from 0.503 to 0.773. So, the result reveals that all measures have a reasonable level of individual item and internal consistency reliability.

Table 4.26: CR, AVE, MSV, MaxR(H) Test using AMOS.

	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)	NF	OGQ	MCQ	TN	AD	F
NF	0.832	0.625	0.121	0.852	0.791					
OGQ	0.866	0.622	0.011	0.891	0.056	0.788				
MCQ	0.817	0.538	0.141	0.875	0.153	0.068	0.733			
TN	0.911	0.773	0.121	0.912	0.348	0.002	0.077	0.879		
AD	0.887	0.724	0.033	0.902	0.041	0.049	0.182	0.084	0.851	
F	0.752	0.503	0.141	0.755	0.084	0.104	0.375	0.029	0.066	0.709

Source: primary Data

Individual construct reliability

Furthermore, Reliability refers to the consistency of the item-level errors within a single factor. Reliability means a set of variables will consistently load on the same factor. The Cronbach's α test is the popular approach to complete the reliability test for each factor where a value should be above 0.7 is recommended, and each factor should have at least 3 variables (Chang *et al.*, 2010). The average Cronbach's (α) is 0.809 for all measured variables, and for individual latent constructs (Table 4.27), all the values are > 0.73 . Therefore, each construct is reliable for running the statistical test for the model. Hence the data qualify the individual reliability for statistical analysis, which means all measures have a reasonable level of reliability.

Table 4.27: Reliability Statistics Test (Cronbach's alpha)

Reliability Statistics	Constructs
0.861	OGQ_avg
0.783	MCQ_avg
0.904	AD_avg
0.885	TN_avg
0.829	F_avg
0.736	NF_avg

Unidimensionality Test

In the second stage, unidimensionality was tested, which refers to how the measures in a scale reflect one underlying construct (Venkatraman and Grant, 1986). The Unidimensionality of TQM and Innovation constructs was assessed using CFA by Sila and Ebrahimpour (2005). Therefore, prior to testing CFA, factor loadings of each item were checked by conducting an exploratory factor analysis (EFA). The importance of EFA is to identify the variables that do not load on primary factors and should be dropped from the study. A factor loading value of more than 0.40 or 0.45 is considered to be the minimum cut-off (Nunnally, 1975; Bhuian *et al.*, 2005; Kathuria, 2000; Terziovski *et al.*, 1997). Thus, based on the analysis report, the following five items B5-Supplier.Qul.Mng, B6-Customer.Relations, B7-Social.Responsibility, C3-Preventive.Maintnce and C6- Benchmarking were dropped at this stage. The examination of factor loading in Table QQ-5.4 shows that factor loadings of the remaining items ranged from 0.736 to 0.921, which loaded accurately to their respective factor. A total of 20 items were retained and used for CFA (Table 4.28). Then the CFA was run to assess unidimensionality.

Table 4.28: EFA- Rotated Component Matrix

Rotated Component Matrixa	Component					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
	B1.Mng.Commitment	0.751				
B2.Emp.Suggestion	0.899					
B3.Problem.Solving	0.885					
B4.Task.Rltd.Training	0.816					
C1.Strategic.Q.Planning		0.836				
C2.Process.Mngt		0.842				
C4.Housekeeping		0.79				
C5.Quality.Information		0.736				
ET1.Technological.Product			0.905			
ET2.Technological.Tcno			0.921			
ET3.Technological.Process			0.902			
DA1.Strategic.Innov				0.875		
DA2.Internal.Org.Innov				0.921		
DA3.Marketing.Innovation				0.892		
NF1.CSR.Perf					0.862	
NF2.EMP.Perf					0.823	
NF3.Innov.Lrn.Perf					0.852	
F1.Invtry.Mng.Perf						0.765
F2.Benchmarking.Perf						0.752
F3.Financial.Prspctv						0.872

Sources: Primary Data

(N.B: So, from Table 4.29 above, it is shown that construct 1st (B) is soft QM, Construct 2nd is hard QM (B), Construct 3rd is Technological Innovation (ET), construct 4th (DA) is administrative innovation, construct 5th (NF) non-financial performance, and construct 6th (F) is financial performance.

The model fit was assessed by reviewing a set of indices: Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), the ratio of X^2 to the degree of freedom (X^2/df), Normed Fit Index (NFI), and Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI). The use of a set of indices is superior to the application of a single index because each index has strengths and weaknesses (Kline, 2015; Hu and Bentler, 1999), while CFI is a relatively stable fit index (Gerbing and Anderson, 1992). The indices have different rules to determine excellent fit as follows: CFI, NFI, and NNFI > 0.9 (Bentler and Bonett, 1980; Byrne, 2012); RMSEA < 0.08 (Browne and Cudeck, 1993); and X^2/df < 3.0 (Cohen *et al.*, 1990; Bollen, 1989). To examine the measurement model of each construct, the CFA was conducted separately, and the highest value of each constraint was considered as value 1 for further goodness of fit analysis of the proposed model. The goodness of fit of each statistic revealed that all measurement models fit the data well. Following the testing of the measurement models for each construct, CFA was used to evaluate the final measurement

model. The result of CFA shows an acceptable fit for the final measurement model too, where CFI = 0.958, GFI = 0.923, AGFI = 0.896, PCLOSE = 0.348, RMSEA = 0.052 and $X^2/df = 1.942$ (see Table 4.25). The data result satisfies the reasonable fit for all values. Thus, it is concluded that all constructs are unidimensional.

Convergent and Discriminant Validity Test

In the third stage, the validity test was assessed considering convergent and discriminant validity. Convergent validity means whether the items loaded up well under the constructs. Whereas discriminant validity means the construct measuring different things, nomological validity is to justify the overall model considered valid (Cohen *et al.*, 1990; Bollen, 1989). The relationship between items and their construct, as well as other variables, is assessed using convergent validity (Hair *et al.*, 2006). The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) approach is commonly used to examine convergent validity (Fornell and Larcker, 1981; Mah *et al.*, 2018). The confirmatory factor analysis has been carried out to test all those validities. By taking the value of the estimate of the standardized regression weights from each construct, the CR and AVE have been calculated. There were two parts used to calculate convergent validity. The first one is by calculating average variance extracted (AVE) test statistics, and the value needs to be > 0.5 (Cohen *et al.*, 1990). Similarly, Chin (1998) proposed a minimum level of 0.50 to ensure a construct's convergent validity. Table 4.26 above proves that all measures have satisfactory evidence of convergent validity. The result brought out by AMOS shows a satisfactory AVE > 0.5 . This proves that the constructs do have acceptable convergent validity. It is also discussed that convergent validity means the variable within a single factor is highly correlated. Significant loading depends on the sample size of the dataset. If the sample size is 350, the recommended minimum sufficient factor loading of 0.35 is accepted (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2012; Kave, 2003). There are 350 sample sizes used for this research task for six factors, and all the factors are loaded more than 0.75. Hence, data meets the demands to satisfy the convergent validity.

Discriminate Validity

Discriminant validity assesses how one latent construct differs from another (Duarte and Raposo, 2010). The study used different approaches to test the discriminant validity. According to Fornell and Larcker (1981), discriminant validity can be assessed by comparing the correlations amongst constructs with the square root of AVE. In the first approach, the discriminant validity was tested through the AMOS-26, where the output is shown in Table 4.26. The bold diagonal values are

the value of the square root of average variance extracted showed greater than the correlations among constructs. As a result, the current study passes the discriminant validity test in line with the statement of Fornell and Larcker (1981). The second approach for testing discriminant validity was to compare Cronbach's α of a construct and its correlations with other constructs (Kaynak, 2003). It was found that the Cronbach α of constructs are within the range of 0.736 to 0.904 (see Table 4.27), which is greater than the value of correlations (see Appendix 6). According to the rule of thumb, the discriminant validity can be achieved if the Cronbach α values are greater than correlations (Sila and Ebrahimpour, 2005).

4.9 Hypothesis testing for structural model

The path analysis was carried out to test the hypothesis using the AMOS-26 programme, where multiple reflective indicators were used (Arrows) to determine the calculations. The residuals were utilised with the indigenous variables and covariance among the exogenous variables. A number of indices are used to determine the fit of the data to the model (see Figure 4.7). The model fit was assessed by reviewing a set of indices: Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), the ratio of X^2 to degrees of freedom (X^2/df), Normed Fit Index (NFI), and Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI). The use of a set of indices is superior to the application of a single index because each index has strengths and weaknesses (Kline, 2015; Hu and Bentler, 1999), while CFI is a relatively stable fit index (Gerbing and Anderson, 1992). The indices have different rules to determine excellent fit as follows: CFI, NFI, and NNFI > 0.9 (Bentler and Bonett, 1980; Byrne, 2001); RMSEA < 0.08 (Browne and Cudeck, 1993); and $X^2/df < 3.0$ (Cohen *et al.*, 1990; Bollen, 1989). The overall fit statistics for the hypothesis model (Figure 4.8) are $X^2 = 268.302$, $df = 155$, $X^2/df = 1.734$, GFI = 0.932, AGFI = 0.907, CFI = 0.967, NFI = 0.926, PCLOSE = 0.764 and RMSEA = 0.046. The index X^2/df ratio, which is below the threshold level of 3, indicates a good model fit. The CFI, AGFI, NFI, and GFI, which have a value greater than 0.9 (see Appendix 5), are optimal since the value must be > 0.9 for the model to be considered a good fit (Bentler, 1980). The NNFI should be higher than 0.5 for the model to be considered a good fit. The NNFI, in this case, is 0.756, which meets the requirement. RMSEA is another fit statistic that adjusts the sample discrepancy function by degrees of freedom (Byrne, 2001), and a value of 0.05 or less indicates a good fit. In this context, the RMSEA = 0.046 fits well into the criteria. Therefore, the overall model demonstrates a good model fit Figure 4.8 below from these fit statistics.

Figure 4.8: Theoretical Model Specification

The following regression Table 4.29, produced via path analysis using 'Amos-26,' allows to examine the link between the variables to see if it is significant. There are 12 paths that originated from mechanistic (MCQ) and organic (OGQ) QM practices, and administrative (AD) and technical innovation (TN) practices to have an influence on financial (F) and nonfinancial (NF) performance in organisation (see Table 4.29). The mechanistic (MCQ) QM aspect showed a significant impact

on both financial (F) and nonfinancial (NF) performance (H1 and H2 are significant). Conversely, the organic (OGQ) QM aspect showed a non-significant impact on both financial and non-financial performance (H3 and H4: not significant). However, In the case of Innovation, TC (Technological innovation) has no significant impact on financial (F) Performance (H5: not significant) but is significant on non-financial (NF) performance (H6: significant). Conversely, AD (Administrative Innovation) did not significantly impact on financial and non-financial performance. So, hypotheses H7 and H8 are non-significant. In the 2nd phase, a path analysis was carried out to identify the direct relationship between innovation and QM practices and found that mechanistic QM has a significant impact on administrative innovation (H9: MCQ→AD: significant). In addition, all the elements that are associated with organic QM (management commitment, employee suggestions, problem-solving, and task-related training), mechanistic QM (strategic quality planning, process management, housekeeping, and quality information), technological innovation (technological product innovation, technological technology innovation, and technological Process innovation), administrative innovation (strategic innovation, Internal organisational innovation, and marketing innovation), financial performance (inventory management performance, financial performance, and benchmarking performance), and non-financial performance (CSR performance, employee performance, and innovation & learning performance) are significant to their respective latent variables. Conversely, the remaining three routes, such as the mechanistic QM's (MCQ) impact on technical innovation (TN) (H10) and the organic QM's (OGQ) impact on administrative innovation (AD) (H11) and technological innovation (H12), are not significant. Hence, H10, H11, and H12 are not significant. Therefore, the regression weight that came from the initial models showed that it has enough room to work on non-significant paths. Hence, a model evaluation is carried out in the next stage to find the best possible results from the composite scale indicators by using the average value of indicators for each variable.

Table 4.29: Regression Weight for Hypothesis Testing

Regression	Flow	Variables	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
TN	<---	OGQ	-0.003	0.06	-0.048	0.961	Non-Significant
AD	<---	OGQ	0.029	0.046	0.63	0.528	Non-Significant
AD	<---	MCQ	0.091	0.03	2.992	0.003	***Significant
TN	<---	MCQ	0.053	0.04	1.312	0.19	Non-Significant
F	<---	MCQ	0.27	0.054	5.03	***	***Significant
F	<---	TN	0.002	0.071	0.029	0.977	Non-Significant
F	<---	AD	-0.006	0.096	-0.067	0.947	Non-Significant
F	<---	OGQ	0.094	0.073	1.285	0.199	Non-Significant
NF	<---	MCQ	0.08	0.039	2.025	0.043	***Significant
NF	<---	TN	0.329	0.06	5.479	***	***Significant
NF	<---	AD	-0.013	0.075	-0.179	0.858	Non-Significant
NF	<---	OGQ	0.047	0.058	0.817	0.414	Non-Significant

Source: Primary Data

4.10 Model evaluation

The composite scale indicators are used to analyse and evaluate the models to determine if they are a good fit or not. Therefore, the factor loading and error variance are calculated following the construct reliability (CR) value. The error variance is calculated by subtracting 1 from CR values (Bentler, 1980). Therefore, the Error Variance is equal to the value of 1 – CR. In the first stage of model evaluation, a composite scale model was drawn from a structural model. Only one construct is created following the average values of each construct. Therefore, six of the new variables (in SPSS) are made with their respective average values, which were denoted as OGQ_avg for soft quality management, MCQ_avg for hard quality management, AD_avg for administrative innovation, TN_avg for technological innovation, F_avg for financial performance, and NF_avg for nonfinancial performance (see Figure 4.9). The factor loading and error variance values are inserted into the composite scale model. The square root of CR values implies the factor loading value, and error variance is calculated by subtracting 1 from the CR, shown in Table 4.30.

Table 4.30: Model evaluation and Validity testing

Convergent Validity	OG	MC	AD	TN	F	NF
CR	0.866	0.817	0.887	0.911	0.752	0.832
Factor Loading						
Root CR	0.9305	0.903	0.941	0.995	0.867	0.912
Error Variance						
1-CR	0.134	0.183	0.113	0.089	0.248	0.168

Note: The values from the above Table YY-5.5 are loaded into the constructs which is in the below Figure Z-5.5.

Figure 4.9: Model Evaluation

Now, the second model fit (Figure 4.9) analysis has been taken to check the model fit. The following results showed the overall fit statistics for the hypothesis model where $X^2 = 2.279$, $df = 2$, $X^2/df = 1.139$, $GFI = 0.998$, $AGFI = 0.977$, $CFI = 0.997$, $NFI = 0.978$, $PCLOSE = 0.582$, and $RMSEA = 0.020$ (see Appendix 5). The index X^2/df ratio, which is below the threshold level of 3, indicates a good model fit. The CFI, AGFI, NFI, and GFI, which have a value greater than 0.9, also fit well with the criteria since it must be > 0.9 for the model to be considered a good fit (Bentler, 1980). Therefore, these fit statistics concluded that the overall composite scale indicator model demonstrates a good fit. The following standardized residual covariance estimation has also been taken to test whether the model can estimate the actual causal effect between the constructs. Table 4.31 shows that all 21 values are within the range, which is not greater than +2 or less than -2 (Hair *et al.*, 2014). Hence, this model can be considered to examine the causal

effect between the constructs and can be applied to the general populations or a much larger sample size by the view of Hair *et al.* (2014).

Table 4.31: Standardized Residual Covariance for fit statistics

	F_av	NF_av	D_av	E_av	C_av	B_av
F_avg	0					
NF_avg	0.658	-0.002				
AD_avg	0.002	0.36	0			
TN_avg	0.022	-0.006	1.289	0		
MCQ_avg	-0.004	-0.011	-0.002	-0.007	0	
OGQ_avg	-0.001	-0.002	0	-0.001	0	0

Source: Primary Data

Thus, it is possible to analyse the final results obtained for the different research hypotheses after appropriate adjustment is made to the structural model. The following regression Table 4.32 allows to test the relationship whether significant or not significant. The result supports precisely the same as the previous regression report in path analysis. Therefore, the intermediating impact has been calculated to identify further the innovation and QM relationship on organisational financial and non-financial performance.

Table 4.32: Regression Weights for hypothesis testing (avg_value)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
TN	<---	OGQ	0.006	0.034	0.185	0.853	Not significant
AD	<---	OGQ	0.021	0.031	0.693	0.488	Not significant
TN	<---	MCQ	0.033	0.033	0.993	0.321	Not significant
AD	<---	MCQ	0.092	0.03	3.059	0.002	***Significant
NF	<---	OGQ	0.03	0.053	0.564	0.573	Not significant
NF	<---	MCQ	0.154	0.052	2.93	0.003	***Significant
NF	<---	AD	-0.009	0.098	-0.088	0.93	Not significant
F	<---	AD	0.044	0.096	0.461	0.645	Not significant
NF	<---	TN	0.474	0.086	5.532	***	***Significant
F	<---	MCQ	0.347	0.052	6.723	***	***Significant
F	<---	OGQ	0.066	0.052	1.27	0.204	Not significant
F	<---	TN	0.003	0.084	0.035	0.972	Not significant

So, the path analysis (Table 4.32) showed that the organic aspect (OGQ) of QM practices does not have any significant direct impact on organisational financial (F) and non-financial (NF) performance in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry. Hence, hypothesis H3: Organic QM practices have a significant impact on organisational financial performance, is rejected as the probability of getting a critical ratio as large as 1.27 in absolute value is 0.204. In other words, the regression weight for OGQ (Organic QM) in the prediction of F (financial performance) is not

significantly different from zero at the 0.05 level (two-tailed). Similarly, hypothesis H4: Organic QM practices have a significant impact on organizational non-financial performance, is rejected as the probability of getting a critical ratio as large as 0.564 in absolute value is 0.573. In other words, the regression weight for OGQ (Organic QM) in the prediction of NF (nonfinancial performance) is not significantly different from zero at the 0.05 level (two-tailed). Hence H3 and H4 are rejected. In the case of Mechanistic QM (MCQ), Hypothesis H1: Mechanistic QM practices directly impact on organizational financial performance is significant as the probability of getting a critical ratio as large as 6.723 in absolute value is less than 0.001. In other words, the regression weight for MCQ (mechanistic QM) in the prediction of F (financial performance) is significantly different from zero at the 0.001 level (two-tailed). Similarly, hypothesis H2: Mechanistic QM practices significantly impact on organisational non-financial performance as the probability of getting a critical ratio as large as 2.93 in absolute value is 0.003. In other words, the regression weight for MCQ (mechanistic QM) in the prediction of NF (non-financial performance) is significantly different from zero at the 0.001 level (two-tailed). Hence, hypotheses H1 and H2 are accepted. So, in the Bangladesh garments industry, mechanistic quality management practices significantly impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. On the other hand, organic QM practices had no significant impact in the same context.

Similarly, in terms of innovation, it was found from the regression weight that technological innovation practices have a significant impact on organisational non-financial performance, but in the context of financial performance, the impact did not show significance. Hence, hypothesis H5: Technological innovation has a significant direct impact on organisational financial performance, is rejected as the probability of getting a critical ratio as large as 0.035 in absolute value is 0.972. In other words, the regression weight for TN in the prediction of F is not significantly different from zero at the 0.05 level (two-tailed). However, hypothesis H6: Technological innovation has a significant direct impact on organizational non-financial performance, is accepted as the probability of getting a critical ratio as large as 5.532 in absolute value is less than 0.001. In other words, the regression weight for TN (Technological innovation) in the prediction of NF (non-financial performance) is significantly different from zero at the 0.001 level (two-tailed). Therefore, it can be defined that technological innovation practices have a significant direct impact on organisational non-financial performance but did not have a significant impact on organisational financial performance in the context of Bangladesh garments industry as the outcome showed that hypothesis H5: TN → F is rejected and hypothesis H6: TN-

→ NF is accepted. Conversely, administrative innovation does not have any significant direct impact on organisational both financial and non-financial performance. Therefore, H5: administrative innovation practices have a significant impact on organisational financial performance, is rejected as the probability of getting a critical ratio as large as 0.461 in absolute value is 0.645. In other words, the regression weight for AD in the prediction of F is not significantly different from zero at the 0.05 level (two-tailed). Similarly, Hypothesis H6: Administrative innovation has a significant impact on organisational non-financial performance, is rejected as the probability of getting a critical ratio as large as 0.088 in absolute value is 0.930. In other words, the regression weight for AD in the prediction of NF is not significantly different from zero at the 0.05 level (two-tailed). So, H5 and H6 are rejected, meaning that administrative innovation practices did not directly impact on organisational non-financial and financial performance in the Bangladesh garments industry.

Furthermore, the direct relationship between quality management and innovation practices has been tested. Therefore, four direct paths were added to the proposed structural model where Mechanistic Quality Management (MCQ) has a direct impact on Administrative (AD) and Technological innovation (TN) (e.g., H9: MCQ - - - > AD; H10: MCQ - - - > TN), and Organic Quality Management (OGQ) has a direct impact on Administrative (AD) and Technological (TN) innovation (e.g., H11: OGQ - - - > AD; H12: OGQ - - - > TN). The regression weight showed that the MCQ in the prediction of AD is significantly different from zero at the 0.01 level (two-tailed), where the probability of getting a critical ratio as large as 3.059 in absolute value is 0.002. Hence, hypothesis H9: MCQ has a significant direct impact on administrative innovation. Therefore, hypothesis H9 is accepted. However, MCQ in the prediction of TN is not significantly different from zero at the 0.05 level (two-tailed), where the probability of getting a critical ratio as large as 0.993 in absolute value is 0.321. Hence, hypothesis H10: Mechanistic QM has a significant direct impact on Technological innovation, is not significant in the result. So, hypothesis H10 is rejected. In terms of Organic QM (OGQ), the output showed that the regression weight for OGQ in the prediction of AD is not significantly different from zero at the 0.05 level (two-tailed), where the probability of getting a critical ratio as long as 0.693 in absolute value is 0.488. So, hypothesis H11: Organic QM (OGQ) directly impacts administrative innovation, is not significant in the result. Similarly, the regression weight for OGQ in the prediction of TN is not significantly different from zero at the 0.05 level (two-tailed), where the probability of getting a critical ratio as long as 0.185 in absolute value is 0.853 (H12: OGQ-->TN = not significant). Hence, hypothesis H12: Organic QM (OGQ) directly impacts technological innovation is not significant in the result. Therefore,

hypotheses H11 and H12 are both rejected by the result. Consequently, it can be summarized that organic quality management (OGQ) practices did not have any significant direct impact on administrative (AD) and technological (TN) innovation in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry. Furthermore, though mechanistic quality management (MCQ) practices did not have any significant direct impact on technological (TN) innovation, but MCQ has a significant direct impact on administrative innovation in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry. So, the relationship noted that mechanistic QM practices directly influence an organisation's administrative innovation practices. Furthermore, A mediating impact is tested to understand more about the relationship among the variables.

4.11 Estimates of Mediating/Indirect Effect: – when Innovation (AD and TN) is a mediator

In order to understand the link between the variables of TQM and Innovation and their influence on organisational performance, the mediation impact was investigated using AMOS to see if any variable mediates other factors on non-financial and financial performance. The p test has been carried out using the AMOS-26 inbuilt estimands called “SpecificIndirectEffect_Path.” The output of P values in Table 4.33 shows that all the possible indirect paths OGQ --> TN --> NF, OGQ --> TN --> F, OGQ --> AD --> NF, OGQ --> AD --> F, and MCQ --> TN --> NF, MCQ --> TN --> F, MCQ --> AD --> NF, MCQ --> AD --> F are not significant in results. Hence, organic QM and mechanistic QM do not mediate administrative or technological innovation to impact organisational financial and non-financial performance significantly. On the other side, technological and administrative innovation does not work as mediators to significantly impact on quality management (OGQ and MCQ) and organisational performance (F and NF).

Table 4.33: Indirect Effect using AMOS

Parameter	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P
OGQ --> TN --> NF	0.003	-0.014	0.044	0.483
OGQ --> TN --> F	0	-0.003	0.002	0.862
OGQ --> AD --> NF	0	-0.011	0.003	0.662
OGQ --> AD --> F	0.001	-0.002	0.016	0.447
MCQ --> TN --> NF	0.016	-0.001	0.078	0.186
MCQ --> TN --> F	0	-0.004	0.006	0.854
MCQ --> AD --> NF	-0.001	-0.032	0.013	0.878
MCQ --> AD --> F	0.004	-0.009	0.034	0.696

A mediator is a variable between two other variables. The mediation has been carried out from the unstandardized regression weight of path analysis where ‘a’ is the value of regression estimate, and SEa is the standard error between the first variable and mediating variable. Conversely, b is the value of the regression estimate, and SEb is the value of standard error

between the second path of mediating variable and the end variable. Furthermore, the Z test was carried out manually to justify the P score results and find the significant mediating impact among the three variables. The following formula is used to identify the Z value. The value of the regression weight from Table 4.32 above has been accepted for the calculation.

$$SEab = \sqrt{(SEa)^2 * b^2 + (SEb)^2 * a^2}$$

Therefore, the mediating effect

$Z = \frac{(a*b)}{SEab}$, the indirect effect would be significant if the value of Z is $\geq \pm 1.96$ (See the mathematical calculation in Appendix Five).

Table 4.34: Z test for mediating effect

Parameter	Z
OGQ --> TN --> NF	0.176
OGQ --> TN --> F	0.035
OGQ --> AD --> NF	-0.091
OGQ --> AD --> F	0.379
MCQ --> TN --> NF	0.984
MCQ --> TN --> F	0.036
MCQ --> AD --> NF	-0.917
MCQ --> AD --> F	0.453

All Z values are shown in Table 4.34, not significant in the results. Therefore, it is identified by both Z and P tests that organic quality management (OGQ) and mechanistic quality management (MCQ) practices do not have any significant mediating effect through administrative (AD) and Technological innovation (TN) on organisational financial (F) and nonfinancial (NF) performance.

4.12 Summary of the qualitative and quantitative Findings

The qualitative data analysis revealed that the organic TQM elements such as management commitment, employee suggestions, small group problem solving, task-related training, supplier quality management, customer relationship, social responsibilities, and 'political culture' significantly impact on organisational financial non-financial performance. Simultaneously, the predictor of mechanistic quality management, such as strategic quality planning, process management, preventive maintenance, housekeeping, quality Information, and market benchmarking, has a significant impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. However, the financial and non-financial effects are not equal for all predictors. Two new predictors, such as social responsibilities and political culture, have a considerable

direct impact on financial performance. Simultaneously, they substantially impact on non-financial performance to 'internal business' and 'innovation and learning perspectives.' Hence, the qualitative outcome showed that all organic and mechanistic predictors significantly impact organisational financial and non-financial performance in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry. So, organic and mechanistic quality management has a significant impact on organisational performance. Hence, TQM has a substantial impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Conversely, quantitative output shows that organic QM does not have any significant direct impact on organisational financial and nonfinancial performance. But mechanistic TQM significantly impacts on both financial and non-financial perspectives. Hence, in organic aspects, the TQM's impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance differs based on the results of quantitative and qualitative studies. From the qualitative results, hypotheses H1 and H2 for mechanistic aspects and H3 and H4 for organic aspects support the statements that organic and mechanistic QM has a significant positive impact on organisational financial and nonfinancial performance. In contrast, from the result of the quantitative analysis, hypotheses H1 and H2 (mechanistic) show a significant impact on organisational performance, but H3 and H4 (organic) are insignificant from the financial and non-financial perspectives.

In the context of innovation, the predictor of administrative innovation, such as internal organisational innovation, marketing innovation, and strategic innovation, have a significant impact on the organization's financial and non-financial perspective. Similarly, it is found that all the predictors of technological innovation, such as product (service) innovation, process innovation, and technological-technology innovation, have a significant impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. However, in the case of innovation (Administrative and Technology), more than 60% of participants have said that all the predictors have less impact on the financial perspective. It is remarkable that approximately 60% of participants (8 participants out of 15) also mentioned a gap in innovation practices in the organisation. Similarly, it is also identified by more than 70 % of participants that all the predictors of administrative and technological innovation have less impact on the customer's perspective. As customers always have a direct influence on financial performance. Hence, innovation has less impact on financial perspective in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry, and innovation may not be practiced from the customer's perspective. However, the maximum number of participants found that innovation significantly impacts an internal business perspective, and almost 50 % (See Table 4.8) acknowledged the importance of 'innovation and learning.' Therefore, it can be said that innovation impacts on both financial and non-financial perspectives, but it is highly significant

to non-financial in the Bangladesh garments industry. Conversely, more than 70% of participants (10 out of 15 participants) said that organisations have a gap in practicing innovation. Hence, the identified gap in practicing innovation by the management resulted in less impact on financial performance. So, findings indicate that management's extra focus on the predictors of innovation practices in the organisation might be helpful to bring an extra positive financial impact on organisational performance. Thus, the qualitative results defined that technological and administrative innovation significantly impacts on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Therefore, H5, H6 (technological innovation), and H7, H8 (administrative innovation) are significant in results by the qualitative outcome. However, the quantitative development shows that only technological innovation significantly impacts on organisational non-financial performance (H6). So, hypothesis H6 is accepted, but H5, H7, and H8 are rejected by the quantitative results, which means that technological innovation does not significantly impact on organisational financial performance (H5). Similarly, Administrative innovation does not significantly impact on organisational Financial (H7) and nonfinancial (H8) performance. Thus, in mechanistic aspect of TQM's impact on organisational financial and nonfinancial performance differs based on the quantitative and qualitative data results.

The qualitative study demonstrates that both organic and mechanistic elements of TQM have a positive and significant impact on organisational financial and nonfinancial performance in order to establish the relationship between organic and mechanistic aspects of TQM and innovation. Simultaneously, mechanistic, and organic innovation practices positively influence technological and administrative innovation performances, which leads to a significant impact on financial and non-financial performance. Hence, the qualitative result shows that mechanistic QM significantly impacts on administrative (H9) and technological (H10) innovation performance. Similarly, organic or soft QM practice significantly impacts on administrative (H11) and technological (H12) innovation performance. Thus, hypotheses H9, H10, H11, and H12 are accepted for this model by the qualitative researcher outcome. Conversely, the quantitative result shows that only mechanistic QM practices have a positive and significant impact on administrative innovation (H9) but insignificant on technological innovation (H10). In the context of organic QM, the result shows that organic QM does not significantly impact on administrative (H11) and technological (H12) innovation. Hence, by the quantitative result, hypotheses H10, H11, and H12 do not support the proposed model, but H9 is accepted for the proposed model. Hence, it is identified by the qualitative and quantitative results that only the mechanistic aspect of TQM positively influences the organisation's administrative innovation practices (H9). So, hypothesis H9 is

accepted for qualitative and quantitative models both, but mechanistic QM impacts on technological innovation (H10), and organic QM impacts on administrative (H11) and technological innovation (H12) differ in the results. Hence, the qualitative research outcomes supported all the hypotheses of the proposed model. Conversely, by the results of the quantitative, hypotheses H1, H2, H6, and H9 support the proposed model, and others do not. Therefore, two different models are developed following the mixed method concurrent triangulation, where qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis are carried out independently (Saunders *et al.*, 2018).

Chapter Five: Analysis and Discussion

Introduction

This chapter addresses the following research question - what is the impact and relationship between TQM (Organic & Mechanistic) and Innovation (Administrative & Technological) on organisational performance? Therefore, data outcomes are discussed in this chapter, followed by the research objectives and the hypothesis developed under each objective (see chapter Two, paragraph 2.8). From Objective One, the H1, H2, H3, and H4 hypotheses are covered. The hypotheses that fall under the second objective are H5, H6, H7, and H8. The final set of hypotheses, H9, H10, H11, and H12, are all connected to objective three.

5.1 Quantitative Data Analysis and Discussion

The following Table 5.1 has been taken as a reference for the study sample and determines that the paths between the factor of the first order and second order are relevantly significant. Hence, management commitment, employee suggestions, problem-solving, and task-related training are revealed as significant independent variables of organic quality management. Similarly, strategic quality planning, process management, housekeeping, and quality information are significant to mechanistic quality management. Strategic innovation, internal organisational innovation, and marketing innovation are significant in line with administrative innovation. In addition, for technological innovation: technological products, technological technology, and technological process constructs are significant. Similarly, corporate social responsibility, employee and supplier performance, and innovation & learning perspective are revealed significant with nonfinancial performance, and for organisational financial performance: inventory management performance, benchmarking, and an average financial perspective are significant for the model and allowed to conclude that all the hypotheses H1, H2, H3, H4, H5, H6, H7, H8, H9, H10, H11, and H12 are verified to test their impact on each other. With regards to the standardized estimates of the path coefficient of the model, it is demonstrated that the estimated values between factors present greater than 0.5 as all significant for all 6 constructs.

Table 5.1: Regression Weights for all variables

B1.Mng.Commitment	<---	OGQ	1				significant
B2.Emp.Suggestion	<---	OGQ	1.421	0.11	12.941	***	significant
B3.Problem.Solving	<---	OGQ	1.421	0.11	12.936	***	significant
B4.Task.Rltd.Training	<---	OGQ	1.13	0.097	11.699	***	significant
C1.Strategic.Q.Planning	<---	MCQ	1				significant
C2.Process.Mngt	<---	MCQ	0.96	0.065	14.849	***	significant
C4.Housekeeping	<---	MCQ	0.655	0.061	10.77	***	significant
C5.Quality.Information	<---	MCQ	0.434	0.045	9.587	***	significant
ET1.Technologcl.Product	<---	TC	0.742	0.034	21.688	***	significant
ET2.Technological.Tcno	<---	TC	1				significant
ET3.Technlgcal.Process	<---	TC	0.763	0.035	21.961	***	significant
DA1.Strategic.Innov	<---	AD	0.88	0.049	17.961	***	significant
DA2.Internal.Org.Innov	<---	AD	1				significant
DA3.Marketing.Innovtn	<---	AD	0.923	0.049	18.741	***	significant
NF1.CSR.Perf	<---	NF	1.34	0.107	12.537	***	significant
NF2.EMP.Perf	<---	NF	1				significant
NF3.Innov.Lrn.Perf	<---	NF	1.348	0.107	12.54	***	significant
F1.Invtry.Mng.Perf	<---	F	0.972	0.102	9.562	***	significant
F2.Benchmarking.Per	<---	F	1				significant
F3.Financial.Prspctv	<---	F	0.821	0.085	9.603	***	significant

This study established three key objectives and questions based on the research's purpose, which was mentioned in Chapter One. The quantitative results are discussed below by following the hypotheses under three objectives and respective hypotheses under each.

5.1.1 Discussion Based on Objective One

Objective 1: To identify the impact of TQM (organic and mechanistic quality management) on organisational performance (financial and non-financial) in the Bangladesh Garments industry.

In order to achieve the 1st objective, this study tested four hypotheses from H1, H2, H3, and H4, where H3 and H4 are considered for the organic aspect of TQM practices, and H1, H2 are considered mechanistic aspects of TQM to identify the financial and nonfinancial impact on the Bangladesh garments industry. Thus, the hypotheses are:

H1: Mechanistic QM has a significant direct impact on organisational financial performance

H2: Mechanistic QM has a significant direct impact on organisational non-financial performance.

It is shown in the regression Table 4.33 the path between Mechanistic QM (MCQ), and financial performance (F) is significant, where P-value = 0.00 < α = 0.05 in the model where the estimated value (0.347) between the factors reveals higher than the marginal value 0.5. It can be said that mechanistic quality management has a significant direct impact on an organization's financial

performance. So, hypothesis H1 did support the proposed model. Similarly, the mechanistic QM impact on non-financial performance also revealed significance as $P\text{-value} = 0.003 < \alpha = 0.05$ and estimated value (0.154) between the factors, which is higher than the marginal value 0.5. Hence, H2 accepted, which means that mechanistic quality management has a significant direct impact on organisational non-financial performance. Therefore, the elements of mechanistic TQM in this research, such as strategic quality planning, process management, housekeeping, and quality Information, significantly impact directly in the elements of financial (Inventory management/Benchmarking/finance) and nonfinancial (CSR, Employee/customers/suppliers, and innovation and learning perspective) performance. So, practicing mechanistic QM in the organization actually influences organisational financial and non-financial performance. The BSC is used to measure organisational performance following four perspectives: customer's perspective, internal business perspective, innovation, and learning perspective, and financial perspective. Therefore, both aspects of TQM elements were considered for either financial, non-financial, or both aspects, as defined that quality is driven by non-financial elements such as product design, process design, rework, and on-time delivery. Researchers argue that non-financial performance measures are better indications of management effort and represent the root reasons for future financial performance (Ittner & Larcker, 1995; Ittner & Larcker, 1997; Ittner *et al.*, 1997, Banker *et al.*, 2000). As a result, non-financial measures must be used in conjunction with financial measures to promote TQM.

Though the results of mechanistic TQM practices brought out a significant direct impact on financial and non-financial performance but contradicted to the previous result of Powell (1995), Dow *et al.* (1999), and Samson and Terziovski (1999), who showed that there is no significant link between hard TQM aspects and organisational performance. Dow *et al.* (1999) stated that their restrictive definition of organisational performance caused non-significant connections between hard TQM and performance. It is advised that productivity and flexibility should be incorporated into a larger definition of performance. However, Rahman and Bullock (2005) and Zeng *et al.* (2015) found a significant direct impact of mechanistic TQM on financial and nonfinancial organizations' performance. In line with the findings of Rahman and Bullock (2005) and Zeng *et al.* (2015), this study reveals that hypotheses H1 and H2 are accepted for the proposed model in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry. Therefore, based on the above discussion, the mechanistic TQM (strategic quality planning, process management, housekeeping, and quality information) directly impact on the elements of financial and non-financial performance. On the other way, it can be said that mechanistic QM practices influence

the organisational financial and non-financial performance in the context of the Bangladesh Garments Industry.

Organic quality management:

The following two hypotheses are discussed to identify the direct impact of the organic aspect of TQM on organisational financial and non-financial performance.

H3: Organic QM has a significant direct impact on organisational financial performance.

H4: Organic QM has a significant direct impact on organisational non-financial performance.

It was found from table 4.33 above that the path between organic QM (OGQ) and financial performance (F) is not significant ($P\text{-value} = 0.204 > \alpha = 0.05$) in the model where the estimated value = 0.066 between the factors reveals lower than the marginal value 0.5. It can be said that organic quality management does not have any significant direct impact on organisational financial performance. So, hypothesis H3 did not support the proposed model. Similarly, the organic QM impact on non-financial performance also did not reveal significance as $P\text{-value} = 0.573 > \alpha = 0.05$, and the estimated value (0.030) between the factors showed lower than the marginal value of 0.5. Hence, H4 was rejected, which means that organic quality management did not have any significant direct impact on organisational non-financial performance. However, in both case of financial and nonfinancial, Powell (1995) found soft quality elements such as executive commitment, open organization, and staff empowerment strongly connected with overall business performance. Dow *et al.* (1999) discovered that out of a total of nine criteria, only the three elements of staff commitment, shared vision, and customer focus had a significant positive correlation with quality and performance in an Australian manufacturing company research. Ahire *et al.* (1996) found that performance (in terms of product quality) was highly connected with soft TQM characteristics such as staff empowerment, employee training, and employee involvement in the context of automobile manufacturing and component firms in the United States. It is noted that researchers used different sets of indicators as a comparison, Dow *et al.* (1999) and Ahire *et al.* (1996) have used relatively narrow quality-focused definitions of performance, whereas Powell (1995) included a variety of specific TQM performance indicators. Therefore, the selection of indicators influences each aspect of quality management and whether the constructs impact organisational performance. Rahman (2005) found that five out of six organic TQM elements have a positive relationship with organisational financial and non-financial performance. Workforce commitment, shared vision, customer focus, teamwork, and

cooperative supplier relationships are among them. These findings are in line with the results of Powell (1995) and Dow *et al.* (1999). However, neither Powell (1995) nor Dow *et al.* (1999) found a significant link between cooperative supplier relationships and performance, implying that it may be context-dependent. Therefore, Rahman and Bullock (2005) explained that this factor like supplier relationships might be more important for manufacturing companies than service companies.

The garments industry in Bangladesh is manufacturing-oriented and provides services to buyers. In this research, four measurement indicators (top management leadership, employee suggestions, problem-solving, and task-related training) of soft TQM are used to test financial and non-financial performance but did not find a significant impact on financial and non-financial performance in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry. However, a previous study shows that TQM is driven by senior management, and managerial commitment must be converted into particular plans. Companies may improve their organisational performance by incorporating quality into their products and services, insuring in-process quality through defect prevention methods and control tools, and judiciously utilising quality information such as customer feedback, benchmarking, and charts (Ahire *et al.*, 1996). Organizations must be customer-focused, maintain skilled, trustworthy, and reliable suppliers, and foster employee engagement in decision-making processes through training and empowerment to successfully apply any strategies for performing well (Ahire *et al.*, 1996). As defined, the four elements are used to identify the soft TQM performance, such as top management leadership, employee suggestions, problem-solving, and task-related training, closely linked with the soft QM elements used by Ahire *et al.* (1996) and Bowen and Lawler (1992). Ahire *et al.* (1996) also suggested that companies may improve organisational performance by incorporating quality into their products and services, insuring in-process quality through defect prevention methods and control tools, and sensibly utilising quality information such as customer feedback, benchmarking, and charts (Power *et al.*, 2001). The indicators used to identify the organisational financial and non-financial performance in this study were closely linked with the measurement indicators used by Ahire *et al.* (1996), which are mixed by financial and non-financial aspects in most cases following the BSC 5 indicators. Therefore, it is questionable why soft TQM does not directly impact organizational performance in the Bangladesh garments industry context. However, according to Power *et al.* (2001), successful organizations are those that use a mix of hard and soft TQM rules to respond to changing consumer demands. Underperforming businesses, on the other hand, view technology as a means of improving operational outcomes rather than

customer satisfaction (Power *et al.*, 2001). Rahman (2001) also found that soft QM positively affects organisational performance through hard quality management.

Therefore, considering the above discussion, the indirect effects of soft quality management via hard QM were tested, and soft quality management significantly impacts both organisational financial and non-financial performance via mechanistic quality management. Table 5.2 shows the significant results with p-values of 0.05 and 0.01 for non-financial and financial aspects, respectively.

Table 5.2: Regression Weights and mediating Impact

Parameter	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P	Results
OGQ --> MCQ --> NF	0.013	0.002	0.043	0.05	***Significant
OGQ --> MCQ --> F	0.029	0.006	0.129	0.011	***Significant

Although researchers such as Rahman and Bullock (2005) found that soft quality has a direct effect on performance, these findings are in line with the outcomes proposed by Ho *et al.* (2001) and Zeng *et al.* (2015). Many insightful empirical studies on the impact of QM practices on performance, such as Anderson *et al.* (1995), Flynn *et al.* (1995), Forza and Filippini (1998), and Kaynak (2003), have characterized the relationship between QM practices and performance in the sequence from soft QM to hard QM, then to organization's performance. Although Ho *et al.* (2001) claim that hard QM practices may partially moderate the link between soft QM practices and performance, these data give strong support for the premise of total mediation underlying these investigations. Studies at the firm level, such as Rahman and Bullock (2005), tend to imply that soft QM has a direct impact on performance. Hard QM, on the other hand, may significantly influence performance in terms of conformity at the plant level. As a result, hard QM serves as a perfect intermediary between soft QM and its performance. In turn, well-established soft QM is required for the successful application of hard QM. Therefore, a conclusion can be made that, in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry, organic TQM does not directly impact financial (H3) and non-financial (H4) organisational performance. However, organic QM mediates mechanistic QM to impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Hence, hypotheses H3 and H4, though directly did not support the model but indirectly supported it.

Therefore, based on the above discussion, the mechanistic TQM (strategic quality planning, process management, housekeeping, and quality information) directly impact on the elements of financial and non-financial performance. However, elements of organic TQM in this research, such as management commitment, employee suggestion, problem-solving, and task-related

training, mediate mechanistic TQM elements to significantly impact financial and non-financial performance. As the research followed mixed-method concurrent triangulation, an independent qualitative data collection and analysis was carried out to understand this topic's context in depth. Thus, these quantitative results are further compared and discussed with the qualitative results in chapter 6, following the research objectives.

5.1.2 Discussion Based on Objective Two

Objective 2: Administrative and Technological innovation’s impact on organisational performance (financial and non-financial)

Table 5.3: Regression Weight for Innovation

constructs	Flow	constructs	estimate	SE	CR	P	Results
NF	<---H5	TC	0.329	0.06	5.479	***	***Significant
F	<---H6	TC	0.002	0.071	0.029	0.977	Non-Significant
NF	<---H7	AD	-0.013	0.075	-0.179	0.858	Non-Significant
F	<---H8	AD	-0.006	0.096	-0.067	0.947	Non-Significant

It is shown in the regression Table 5.3 the path between administrative innovation (AD), and financial performance (F) is not significant where P-value = 0.947 > $\alpha = 0.05$ and for the non-financial p-value = 0.858 > $\alpha = 0.05$ in the model. It can be said then administrative innovation does not have any significant direct impact on organization’s financial and non-financial performance. So, hypotheses H7 and H8 did not support the prospective model. However, the direct impact of technological innovation practices on the organisational financial performance is not significant as the P-value = 0.977, but in a non-financial context, technological innovation practices have a significant direct impact on the Bangladesh garments industry where the P-value = 0.00 < $\alpha = 0.05$ two-tailed. Hence, though hypothesis H6 did not support the prospective model, H5 supported the result.

Administrative innovation is the adoption of new working methods with the goal of increasing organisational performance, structures, systems, and processes (Weerawardena, 2003). Chuang *et al.* (2010) and Maistry *et al.* (2017) used three more subscales to measure administrative innovation those are namely, internal organisational innovation, marketing innovation, and strategic innovation. Administrative and technical innovations indicate potentially diverse decision-making processes (Daft, 1978), and they represent changes in a wide variety of operations in an organization collectively. Therefore, the elements of administrative innovation, such as internal organisational innovation, marketing innovation, and strategic

innovation, do not directly impact the elements of organisational financial and non-financial performance. Similarly, technological innovation practices did not directly impact financial performance, but it has a non-financial impact through the measurement indicators of products, processes, and technological technology. In line with the findings, researchers such as Acheson and Ferris (1990) and Han *et al.* (1998) considered both administrative and technological innovation vital for organisational financial and non-financial performance. It is also found by innovation organizations' increasingly hostile market environment and not only works for market growth but also for survival (Han *et al.*, 1998; Oly Ndubisi and Agarwal, 2014). Administrative, product, and process innovations (technology) have all been linked to improved organisational performance (Parnaby, 1991; Bamberger *et al.*, 1989; Livingston and Berkes, 1989). In addition, several studies have found a relationship between research and development and sales growth (Franko, 1989; Lengnick-Hall, 1991); productivity growth (Chakrabarti, 1990; Chakrabarti and Halperin, 1990); and profitability (Moreby and Reithner, 1990) following the implementation of both administrative and technological innovation. Therefore, it is remarkable why administrative innovation doesn't directly impact financial and non-financial performance and technological innovation of financial performance in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry. However, studies showed that the proper use of technological resources contributes to developing a long-term competitive edge that improves a company's financial performance (Hambrick *et al.*, 1983; Kalish and Lillien, 1986; Porter, 2008; Schroeder, 1990). So, in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry, the technological products, technological processes, and technological technology (elements of Technological innovation) have a significant direct impact on non-financial performance to its aspects of the internal business, innovation, and learning, and customer (BSC performance indicators). Hence, an indirect impact of technological innovation on financial performance and an indirect impact of administrative innovation on financial and non-financial performance were tested, followed by TQM (organic and mechanistic) elements to identify the relationship between TQM and Innovation on organisational performance below to discuss objective 3.

5.1.3 Discussion Based on Objective Three

Objective 3: Relationship between TQM and innovation on organization performance.

The following outcomes found from the regression analysis that organic quality management does not have significant direct impact on administrative and technological innovation as the P-value = .961 and .528, respectively. Similarly, with a P-value of 0.190, mechanistic QM did not

directly impact technological innovation. However, mechanistic QM gained a significant direct impact on administrative innovation with the P-value = 0.003 < α = 0.05 (Table 5.4). So, H9 is accepted for the proposed model, but mechanistic QM impacts on non-financial performance (H10), and organic QM impacts on financial and non-financial performance (H11 and H12) are insignificant in the result. Therefore, hypotheses H10, H11, and H12 are rejected for the proposed model.

Table 5.4: Regression Weights for QM and Innovation Relationship

Regression Weight	Flow	Variables	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
TC	<---H12	OGQ	-0.003	0.06	-0.048	0.961	Non-Significant
AD	<---H11	OGQ	0.029	0.046	0.63	0.528	Non-Significant
AD	<---H9	MCQ	0.091	0.03	2.992	0.003	***Significant
TC	<---H10	MCQ	0.053	0.04	1.312	0.19	Non-Significant

So, mechanistic QM practices directly influence administrative innovation practices in the Bangladesh garments industry. Hence, practicing mechanistic QM in the organization is ultimately practicing administrative innovation. Similarly, it can be said that the elements of mechanistic TQM in this research, such as strategic quality planning, process management, housekeeping, and quality information, significantly enhance the performance of administrative innovation to its aspects of internal organisational innovation, marketing innovation, and strategic innovation. These findings align with the outcomes proposed by Kim *et al.* (2012), where the researcher found that only hard QM (role of process management) supported a significant impact on innovation. While some studies, such as Prajogo and Sohal (2003), Feng *et al.* (2006) claimed that only soft dimensions (leadership and people management) could foster innovation. Conversely, Perdomo-Ortiz *et al.* (2006) argue that both hard and soft QM dimensions (e.g., process management and human resource management) are important in developing the innovation process. The study found that hard QM has a significant direct impact on administrative innovation, but neither soft nor hard quality management practices mediate administrative and technological innovation on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Thus, these study outcomes differ from others, verifying the correlation between QM and innovation in the regional context. These findings support those of Kim *et al.* (2012), emphasizing the importance of hard QM in innovation and the role of soft QM as a compliment. The findings show that hard QM is essential in determining the administrative innovation process. Hard QM can influence administrative innovation directly and indirectly through the combined effect of organic and mechanistic QM, which has a significant indirect impact (Table 5.5) on financial and non-financial performance in the Bangladesh garments industry.

Table 5.5: Indirect effect of OGQ through Innovation on financial and non-financial performance

Parameter			Estimate	Lower	Upper	P
OGQ --> MCQ --> AD			0.008	0.001	0.026	0.046
OGQ --> MCQ --> NF			0.013	0.002	0.043	0.05
OGQ --> MCQ --> F			0.03	0.007	0.128	0.012

These findings can be related to the literature as hard QM practices help the organization reestablish processes by bringing the system under control through variance reduction. According to Spencer (1994), once the system is stable and under control, it is possible to learn how to enhance it, resulting in developing a learning basis. A set of routines established through the implementation of hard QM can support innovation activities because a routine-based organization pays more attention to vital processes and avoid activities that do not add value (Hoang *et al.*, 2006). However, this empirical evidence lacks support for the direct impact of organic QM on innovation practices. This could be due to the operations-focused scope, which emphasizes soft QM at the operational level rather than at the firm level. Soft QM techniques at the firm level, such as top management leadership for quality initiatives and organizational-wide training and learning, employee suggestions, and group problem solving, can quickly distribute knowledge across functions and drive innovative ideas, resulting in better creative performance. However, at the operational level, worthwhile human capacity through the implementation of organic quality management is first turned into productivity in the form of improved quality performance and then subsequently becomes a solid platform for fostering innovation (Flynn *et al.*, 1994). Therefore, though the organic QM does not have any significant direct impact on innovation, but its combined effort with mechanistic QM mediates administrative innovation to have a significant impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Hence, the cumulating impact of organic TQM elements (management commitment, employee suggestion, problem-solving, and task-related training) and mechanistic TQM elements (strategic quality planning, process management, housekeeping, and quality information) enhance the organization's financial and non-financial performance indirectly.

TQM and innovation share many similarities as both formed as partial responses to the intense competitive pressures that manufacturers are experiencing. TQM and innovation share some similar characteristics, for example, both emphasize continuous improvement. In addition, organic culture is also viewed as a key component of TQM and innovation. These similarities suggest that organizations that effectively apply TQM may also be more innovative than those that do not. If this assumption is correct, TQM can be a vehicle for organizations to become more innovative (Prajogo and Sohal, 2001). However, Singh and Smith (2004) reveal that the empirical

data does not fit the proposed model entirely. Therefore, the relationship between TQM and innovation due to its impact on organisational performance is still contradictory. Above all, it appears that, despite the objections made against TQM as a valuable instrument for innovation, TQM is capable of creating a favourable atmosphere that overcomes the potential challenges to innovation. As a result, firms that operate in sectors where continuous innovation is required should not view TQM as an excellent technique to improve quality and a handicap to innovation but rather should add the TQM advantages to the facilitation of the innovation process. TQM can be an effective corporate approach, but it must first be implemented correctly to achieve these results. Therefore, the organization must use TQM in its broadest definition rather than limiting it to technical aspects defined by Martínez-Costa and Martínez-Lorente (2008).

5.2 Discussion of Qualitative Research Findings

The qualitative data outcomes are discussed in this chapter following the research objectives and the hypothesis developed under each objective.

5.3 Discussion Based on Objective One: Impact of TQM (soft and hard) on Organisational Performance

In this research task, as previously defined, eight entities are used to identify the organic (soft) aspect of QM performance in the organization. Soft (organic) aspects of quality management are more concerned with establishing customer awareness and managing human resources. The Soft aspect mainly deals with training and learning, small-group problem-solving, and teamwork (Pragojo and Sohal, 2004). The following organic QM element's impact on organisational performance is discussed based on financial (H3) and non-financial (H4) perspectives.

H3: Soft QM has a significant direct impact on organisational financial performance.

Top management commitment as a part of organic QM plays a vital role in critical areas of management. The strategic direction comes from the top management to introduce the organic QM environment in the organization. Therefore, top management commitment is one of the fundamental elements in TQM (Senge, 2017; Huffman and Hegarty, 1993). It was found that all 15 participants practiced management commitment in their organization (Table 4.1). The following participants, R1, R3, R6, R8, R13, R14, and R15, mentioned that they receive reasonable cooperation from their management for their daily work activities. For example, *R1 said, "Top management always tries to cooperate with us about any issues. We follow the 7 Ps system and all our hourly reports for quality management, such as measurement reports, quality*

reports, loss systems, etc. Are monitored by the top management.” However, participants R5, R9, R10, R11, and R12 have emphasized practicing top management commitment to ensure quality in all organizational sectors. Also, participants R2, R4, R6 (a), and R7 mentioned that management always reminds them to follow the quality facts while working on the floor. The top management impacts on financial performance were referenced 9 times by 8 participants (Below Table 5.2). A maximum of the participants said that top management contribution helps the employees ensure the quality of products, processes, and services. As mentioned, the lack of quality products causes buyers to claim money back or return the products. Participants explained the same as *R07 said, “When clothing is manufactured differently from how the buyer desires, a quality issue results, thus the buyer may claim to reproduce the entire goods or money back, which causes risk of losing money for the organization.”* However, R10 mentioned that ensuring quality helps to meet financial goals. For example, participant R10 said, *“products should be prepared with consideration for our customers’ needs and continued business relationships with them in order to meet our financial objectives.”* Management leadership helps to ensure the organic QM culture in the organization. So, the leadership gap may negatively impact on business (Zhang, 2000), which participants R2, R9, R11, and R12 have also acknowledged. For instance, participant *R05 said, “A lapse in product quality could be detrimental to the company’s revenues and reputation. We also waste raw materials, time, and money to correct those items.”* According to Dale (1999), there is no way a manufacturing firm can implement quality improvement activities if the top managers are bystanders. As Zhang (2000) defined, it is always difficult to improve products and quality management without proper leadership by the top management. Thus, participant *R12 said, “A big sum of orders can be canceled if we cannot ensure the quality, so we should always ensure the quality to avoid the financial loss.”* Hence, Top management’s commitment, participation, and decision about quality management in each corporate sector may save the financial loss and increase the business. High levels of quality performance in an organization are always related to the top management’s commitment to the goals. High product quality exists when top management is firmly committed (Motwani *et al.*, 1994). So, leaders should develop quality policies that contribute to organisational business performance.

Employee participation helps to develop the collaboration between managers and non-managers among the different functions (Dean Jr and Bowen, 1994). Only two participants R4 and R10 (Below Table 5.2), acknowledged the impact of employee suggestions on financial performance. For instance, participant *R10 said, “Our goal is always to keep fewer defects rate so that we can*

save expenses, but if the problem is bigger, we call the manager. Otherwise, I discuss next to my colleague to sort out the issue.” From the above responses, it can be assessed that an employee’s suggestion does not have any substantial impact on the organization’s financial performance, but it may have an indirect impact on financial performance via non-financial aspects. Five participants agreed that small-group problem-solving has an effect on financial performance. Participants R2, R13, and R15 explained that dispute resolution with employees saves the company money. Garvin (2001), and Flynn *et al.* (1994) define group-problem solving is very much quality-oriented and job-specific to resolve any matter which contributes to gaining organizational success. Participants R5 and R11 said that group problem-solving also helps increase productivity. For example, participant R11 said, *“we pay three months’ payments if any employees want to leave the jobs, or we ask them to leave. We ask the staff to follow the management instruction, but if they do not, we have to talk to them to mitigate the issue.”* This statement can be linked with Forza and Filippini (1998), developing and encouraging team problem-solving approaches having advantages of employees’ ability to make proposals for improvements. Training and development activities help to generate new skills and knowledge, which has an impact on meeting the organization’s emerging needs (Noe *et al.*, 2014). Four participants (R1, R3, R9, and R13) acknowledged that task-related training significantly impacts the organization’s financial performance. The participants mostly acknowledged that task-related training helps increase production abilities and confidence to identify mistakes, which helps reduce the alteration (R1 and R3). Participant R13 said, *“I believe that by providing training, 40% of total employees, including less educated or uneducated employees, can be taught to use technology. This type of training was not implemented in this organisation. In addition, I believe that training can help to improve employee abilities and organisational financial performance.”* The multitasking training helps the organisation cover the employee’s uncertain gaps during business hours if anybody is absent (R9a and R9b). The literature review shows that multitasking training helps the organization to recover uncertainty absent avoidance. Training puts everyone on the same page (Billett, 2004). Therefore, based on the above discussion, the conclusion can be made that task-related training financially impacts organisational performance in the Bangladesh garments industry.

CSR should be evaluated by comparing relative costs and benefits. Standards such as ISO 14001 have been developed but have not attracted the same level of attention as ISO 9001 (Sharma and Kodali, 2008). However, three participants acknowledge that CSR has a significant financial impact on business to save the damage and reputation on the world market.

Organizational workplace safety and environment are facts to maintain a good reputation in the developed economic market (R2). Fire and building collapse also threaten financial damages (R5, R10). Therefore, social responsibility has a significant financial impact on business. This quality management element has been prioritized during the data collection stage. Hence, CSR is considered an organic QM element in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry. Kempner (1992) defined the total of beliefs, knowledge, attitudes of mind, and customers to which people are exposed during their social and social conditioning. So, the culture will be different based on the various societies. 10 participants said that culture significantly impacts organisational performance, and among them, 5 participants (see Table 4.8) noted, it has a direct financial impact on organisational performance. Maximum participants talked about the delayed delivery of products, and employee movement, which can be controlled by political initiation, as they mentioned that those problems are caused by political instability. One of the key reasons for employee strikes against management is the gap in education and improper knowledge about employee rights (R4), which brings financial loss (R9, R13). However, traffic jam or political strike also causes delayed delivery of products to customers (R2, R15). Therefore, political culture has a significant impact on financial performance. Nine participants, such as R2, R4, R5, R7, R8, R9, R12, R14, and R15, acknowledged about the financial impact of supplier relationships on organisational performance. The TQM implementation supports developing partnerships with suppliers (Hackman and Wageman, 1995). The supplier relationship helps to get the raw materials at the right time, which could link with the just-in-time purchasing system (Anderson *et al.*, 1994). However, R2 said business negotiation with suppliers is not an appropriate idea and said this is just an opinion without knowing the actual facts of whether any Bangladeshi organization is doing business based on negotiation with suppliers. Working collaboratively with suppliers on a long-term basis is truly beneficial (Anderson *et al.*, 1994). It is also acknowledged that long-term relationships can benefit organizations financially and improve quality (R9, R14, R4, R5, and R7). Acknowledgment made by Deming (1986), working with suppliers as a partner in a long-term relationship of loyalty and trust to improve the quality of incoming materials and decrease costs. Conversely, relationship gap with suppliers or supplier disruption increases production expenses and delivery expenses (R8, R12, R14a&b, and R15). So, an excellent sustainable relationship between purchaser and supplier is necessary for the best economy (Deming, 1986). Hence supplier relationship has a substantial impact on financial performance. The customer gets priority from the organization for every decision they make. Therefore, organizations always try to satisfy customer needs and expectations (Philips, 2003; Harrison *et al.*, 2010). The participants R2, R4, R5, R7, R8, R11, R12, and R14 said that customer quality

relationship significantly impacts an organization’s financial performance. In maintaining a good customer relationship, the fundamental priorities are quality and costs (R4). Fulfilling the customer's demand bring goodwill to the organization (R14). In case of failure to meet the customer’s expectations might have a negative impact on business, as customers can claim to get back the payments (R2, R7, R11, and R12). The above discussion shows that maintaining goodwill with the customers, satisfying quality products, and delivering prioritized services are essential to sustain a successful business. As explained by Juran (1993), the fundamental fact of quality management is maintaining a close relationship with the customer to fully determine the customer’s needs and observe that those needs are being met to achieve the organisational target. For example, participant *R8 said, “Maintaining customer relationships is essential to achieve the organisational budget.”* Table 5.6 below shows the financial impact on the organization mentioned by the participants. The tables showed that employees' suggestions and social responsibility have less impact on financial performance as only 2-3 participants discussed their importance. However, the rest of the other six elements show a strong impact on the organization’s financial performance. So, the conclusion can be made that *Organic QM significantly impacts an organisation’s financial performance. Hence hypothesis H3 is tested with a positive response.*

Table 5.6: Organic QM financial perspective

Organic QM elements (Financial Impact)	Participants	References
Top Management commitment	8	9
Employee suggestions	2	2
Group problem solving	5	5
Task Related training	4	6
Supplier QM	9	12
Customer Relationship	8	10
Social Responsibility	3	3
Political cultural context	5	7

Source: Primary data

H2: Hard QM has a significant direct impact on organisational non-financial performance.

Practicing TQM in an organization creates a modern business environment (Anderson *et al.*, 1994), and a relationship emerged between buyers and suppliers in the flexible business environment (Juran, 1993). There are 8 participants out of 15 who acknowledge that management leadership impacts non-financial customer's perspective; among them, R02, R05, R13, R9, and R11 defined that organisational lack of quality brings customer dissatisfaction. For instance, *R11 said, “If we make less quality products, then buyers will not accept that, so we need to reproduce those products again. Therefore, first of all, we must be very careful from the*

beginning of the production.” However, management strategic direction should be followed to fulfill the customer’s requirement, as acknowledged by R06, “*We always prioritize to fulfill the buyer’s requirements.*” R04 and R07 likewise underlined the importance of the customer’s requirements. The above statements can be related to the fact that the customer focuses on the degree to which a firm continuously needs to satisfy the customer’s needs and expectations. As mentioned, a successful firm recognizes the need to put the customer first in every decision made (Philips, 2003). High-quality performance levels are always related to the top management’s commitment to the goals, and high product quality exists when the top management is firmly committed. So, quality policies should be developed by the leaders that contribute to organisational business performance (Motwani *et al.*, 1994). In the context of employee suggestions, only 2 participants out of 15 (Table 5.7) have acknowledged the impact of employee suggestions on the customer perspective (R04 and R08). Therefore, employee engagement by accepting their suggestions has a moderate non-financial impact on an organization’s performance in the Bangladesh garments industry. Similarly, only one participant, R5, acknowledged the impact of group problem-solving on the customer’s perspective. None of the participants (0) conceded that task-related training had a nonfinancial effect on customers’ perspectives (Table 5.7). However, the literature review shows that training help employees to develop their confidence as well as increase productivity (Attiq *et al.*, 2017; Byrge, 2021; Rao *et al.*, 1999). Hence, task-related training and group problem-solving do not directly impact customers’ perspectives but might have an indirect impact on customers. Remarkably, none of the participants acknowledged the impact of social responsibility on the customer’s perspective. However, according to Haque (2011) and Chowdhury *et al.* (2007), the Bangladesh garments industry faces a threat from the WTO due to its vulnerable work environment and poor payment to the staff. National culture differs in the way the members view the world, such as how the people deal with uncertainty, the degree to which individuals are integrated into groups, and the extent to which the less powerful members of the organisations accept, how individuals establish relationships with others (Seidman, 2007; Blowfield and Murray, 2014). From the view of participants R2, R5, and R13 political culture cause shipment delays due to strikes and traffic jams. Also, the improper planning by the authority for this garment business caused delayed delivery (R2, R5, R13). Therefore, culture impacts customers’ perspectives on non-financial business performance. Developing partnerships with the supplier is one of the major TQM implementation practices (Hackman and Wageman, 1995). Four participants with five references have acknowledged that supplier quality management impacts customers’ perspectives. Participants R6 and R14 (a) and (b) emphasized more on quality as said by participant R6, “*We*

should have a good relationship with suppliers. For example, *If the buttons are defective, the buyer will not accept the products.*” However, others found that buyer's demand also matters for the organization. In this case, buyers find that suppliers and organizations should rely on buyers' demand for sustainable business. Juran (1993) defined that obtaining customer complaint information seeks opportunities to improve product and service quality. The participants R1, R2, R5, R7, R8, R10, R11, and R13 acknowledged same. For example, R1: *“Good feedback always brings good business for us. We can get frequent orders from the buyers for a good service.”* Conversely, participant R8 said that misunderstanding with customers negatively impacts business. Hence, customer quality maintained in service, products, or processes not only has a financial impact on business but also has a non-financial impact on customers' perspective on organisational performance. Therefore, customer relationship strongly impacts customers' perspective on non-financial performance. It is noted that a maximum number of floor-level employees in Bangladesh are uneducated. So, management does not want to involve them in the decision-making process, and this could be the reason for acknowledgment made by only two participants about the impact on employee's suggestions, one about the group problem-solving, none for task-related training, and none about the social responsibility in customer's perspective on nonfinancial performance. However, other elements have significantly impacted customers' perspectives (Table 5.7). Therefore, it can be said that Organic QM has a moderate effect on customers' aspects from a non-financial perspective.

Table 5.7: Organic QM customer's perspective

QM elements (Customer's Impact)	Participants	References
Top Management commitment	8	9
Employee suggestions	2	2
Group problem solving	1	2
Task Related training	0	0
Supplier QM	4	5
Customer Relationship	8	13
Social Responsibility	0	0
Political-cultural context	3	3

Source: Primary Data

Innovation and Learning Perspective

Innovation can help firms to create a new market segment to improve the production tools and methods to innovate new products and services to improve human daily lifestyle (Kanji and Wallace, 2000). It's a process of continuous renewal involving the whole company and an essential part of business strategy and everyday practices (DTI, CBI and National Manufacturing Council, 1993). Nine (Below Table 5.8) participants (R1, R4, R5, R6, R7, R8, R12, R13, and

R14) have defined top management leadership has a substantial impact on innovation and learning aspects. Management contribution helps the employees learn the correct procedures to ensure quality work. Top management direction works as a training for the employees and management appreciation to involve employees in the decision-making process, bring new ideas in the organization, and helps to solve the problems in the factory (R14.b, R1.a, and R7). Innovation is the key area foundation for sustainable business performance (Hoang *et al.*, 2006). Quality management supports innovation by enabling the efficient detection of customer needs, training, idea sharing, and commitment and participation of top management (Zang *et al.*, 2000). Top management guidance creates an innovative culture in the organization and works as a continuous learning procedure for the management employees (R4, R1b, R05, R14a, R12, and R08). Apparently, fourteen participants R 1, R2, R4, R5, R6, R 9, R10, R11, R7, R8, R15, R12, R13, and R14 have referenced 20 times (Below Table 5.8) and defined that employee suggestion significantly impacts on innovation and learning perspective in organisational performance. The participants *R01 (a), R02, R05, R07, R13, and R15* mostly talked about the 'new ideas which come from employees' suggestions and lead to a successful business. Innovation is defined as the development of new ideas by people who engage in transactions with others within an institutional order (van Der Aa, 2002), which brings drastic and incremental success to the organization (Cooper, 2000). Participants R01 (b), R04 (a), R04 (b), R08, R09, R10 (a), b, R11, R12 (a), R12 (b), R14 (a), R14 (b) have addressed the learning perspective on non-financial performance in the organisation, stating that meetings help to learn about new ideas or working methods. The suggestion is also useful in learning from one another and working continuously to satisfy production goals. For example, *R14 said, "Employees' suggestions help us to know what they (buyers) exactly want and what gap we have between us."* Therefore, it can be said from the above discussion, employees' suggestions bring success to the organization in many ways, such as developing a relationship with the customers and ensuring quality by sharing knowledge among the employees. According to Mele and Colurcio (2006), innovation creates value among customers and improves the firm's performance to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage over its competitors, which the participants above acknowledged. The following eight participants, R1, R2, R4, R5, R6, R7, R9, and R10, have acknowledged that group problem-solving significantly impacts innovation and learning perspectives. As the participant acknowledged *R2: "Sometimes we sat in a meeting to solve issues. I also sat with my employees and shared the ideas."* Also, participants R1 and R10 were defined the same. Literature can be linked that sitting in a group and solving problems or sharing ideas empowers employees, which helps develop confidence among them (Ahire *et al.*, 1996). Solving problems by sitting in a group

helps the employees work as a team, increasing productivity (R6, R9). As a result, employee group problem-solving has a substantial impact on organisational performance in terms of innovation and learning, and both primary and secondary data are acknowledged in this discussion.

According to Birdi *et al.* (2012), training positively relates to idea generation but is unrelated to idea implementation. This suggests that factors influencing the generation of ideas may differ from those influencing the implementation of ideas. Participant R9 said, *“Training helps to gain knowledge, and knowledge does not limit this garment sector. Variation of learning about different departments’ tasks may help the employees develop extra confidence in work, increasing productivity.”* According to Chen & Huang (2009), learning enables task performance and eases the development of competencies. For instance, R14 said, *“We sometimes ask the employees to work in the different lines and floors so that they can learn multiple works in this factory.”* According to Battistelli *et al.* (2019) and Hatch and Dyer (2004), training and learning activities contribute to creating, exchanging, and utilizing knowledge, which may increase organisational performance and innovation. Almost all the participants, about 12 out of 15 (Table 4.4), have mentioned the training impact on innovation and learning perspective. Participants R3a, R4, R5, R7, R8, R9.a, b, R10, R11, R12, R13, R14, and R15 have acknowledged that training has a reasonable impact on innovation and learning perspective. Remarkably, none of the participants mentioned the CSR impact on innovation & learning perspective on nonfinancial performance. Out of fifteen participants, only four (R3, R4, R11, and R7) define that supplier quality management significantly impacts innovation and learning perspectives. However, in terms of the “Innovation and learning perspective,” Participant R4 advised establishing long-term business relationships with suppliers because long-term partnerships foster goodwill, which leads to suppliers delivering high-quality goods. However, changing suppliers frequently may have the chance to get less quality products (R4). As explained by the participants, how suppliers learning engagement works on the organization’s performance, as said R11, R7 said that goodwill with suppliers even helps the organization learn the machinery works effectively. Thus, it has a moderate impact as only 4 participants acknowledged its impact on innovation and learning perspective. Only two participants (R5 and R10) noted that political culture significantly impacts innovation and learning (see Table 5.8). As suggested, train the employees to keep the floor clean and get used to maintaining cleanliness and tidiness in the workplace (R5). The friendly manner with the staff reduces the chances of employee movement against the management. Also, employees follow and learn from the management (R10). Just two

participants acknowledged the impact of ‘politics culture’ on innovation and learning perspectives. Hence, it has significantly less impact on it. Customer focus has been considered a window through which the organization looks at the outside and gets the necessary feedback related to customers, competitors which represents the primary source that builds the resource and development research and development capabilities, and this sort of information helps to develop the innovative strategic planning capability and learn the new things (Jones and Grimshaw, 2012; Perdomo-Ortiz *et al.*, 2006). As acknowledged, quality is always the first priority, and cost could be a concern. Long-term relationships help to understand the customers properly (R4). However, communication should be accurate and timely with the customers. Even accurate and timely contact by email can help meet the customers' demand if they want to change or modify their orders during production (R7). So, from the above discussion, even if we see that customers have a significant impact on nonfinancial performance, from the participant's view, customers have less impact on innovation and learning perspective. There is zero impact on social responsibility, and only 2 participants acknowledged customer relationships and political-cultural perspectives (Table 5.8). However, the others have a substantial impact on innovation and learning perspective on nonfinancial performance. Hence. Organic QM substantially impacts on innovation and learning perspective in organisational nonfinancial performance.

Table 5.8: Organic QM Innovation and Learning perspective

QM elements (Innovation and Learning Perspective)	Participants	References
Top Management commitment	9	11
Employee suggestions	14	20
Group problem solving	8	8
Task Related training	12	17
Supplier QM	4	5
Customer Relationship	2	2
Social Responsibility	0	0
Political-cultural context	2	2

Source: Primary Data

Internal Business Perspective

The internal business perspective in TQM defines as how QM helps to develop or progress organization’s internal performance, which could be in production, process, or services management. TQM practices in organizations effectively build and develop a range of capabilities that go beyond quality and maintain the flow of information (Prajogo and Hong, 2008). Top management instruction helps for sustainable business performance and helps to avoid mistakes (R12, R14.a, R15, R04, R06, and R11.a). However, participants also defined that

management control and monitoring system helps to increase productivity (R03, R5, R13, R09, and R01). Conversely, R10 and R14 (b) have explained the teamwork and cooperation issues (R14.b) among the employees and top management. As said by R10, *“We are four-person work in my department, and we also discuss the issues if we cannot solve by one person. If we can’t solve, then we discuss with the top managers”*. As a result, the following remark can be related to Dale (1999), Puer & McCarthy (1996), and Saraph et al. (1989) in terms of increasing the firm's quality improvement initiatives by ensuring top management engagement in a distinct section of management. Management participation helps spread quality consciousness throughout a firm. Therefore, from the above discussion based on the primary and secondary data, it can be said that top management leadership has a substantial impact on an organisational internal business perspective. Employee participation by suggestion is vital in inspiring action on quality improvement (Juran, 1993). Suggestions help to share ideas and develop job confidence to rectify the patterns or defective items (R12). However, a lack of engagement in work negatively impacts business (R10, R08). The statement shows that a lack of engagement may cause a lack of confidence and develop negative employee manners. According to Zhang *et al.* (2000), employees' involvement may also allay employee's negative attitudes, as acknowledged by participant R07, *“Employees even can feel stress-free during work if they have the freedom to say which may increase the volume of productivity,”* and encourage them to have a better understanding of the importance of product quality. Logical suggestion helps the organization to be more competitive (R07, R11). Eleven participants about 13 times defined that employees' suggestions significantly impact the organization's internal business perspective (see table 4.2 above). Therefore, from the above discussion, the conclusion can be made that employee engagement substantially impacts organizations' nonfinancial performance, justified by both literature and participant statements. The fourteen participants expect R3 have acknowledged that group problem-solving significantly impacts internal business aspects. Participants R12 and R14 defined that solving problems in a group increases the relationship among the employees, and employees work as a team, which helps increase productivity. It is said that solving problem setting in a group allays employees' negative attitudes and encourages them to have a better understanding of the importance of product quality (Cooke, 1992). For example, R13, R6, and R9 stated they sit together to mitigate employee conflict. Sometimes rumors may influence employees to move against the organization, but solving problems in a group helps minimize the conflict; thus, they concentrate on working. However, participant R8 said that a friendly attitude helps the employees focus on the work more but putting stress on them can reduce productivity in the organization. The rest

has made a similar opinion to other participants. Hence, group problem-solving significantly impacts the organization's internal business perspective.

Participants R1, R2, R3, R7, R8, R9, R11, R12, R14, and R15 mentioned the impact of task-related training on an internal business perspective. As training develops confidence among the staff, multi-tasking confidences also develop among the employees to increase productivity (R15, R2, R3, and R12). According to Carmeli and Azeroual (2009), knowledge combination capabilities facilitated the development of knowledge creation capability. An example relates to R14: "Employees may move from one factory to another, and it's a problem. We keep a backup plan against it. Think, the one who works on this side does the same thing as the one who works beside him and another employee as a helper. Then we bring him here to fill the gap". One of the key challenges for organizations is to increase employee's competencies by transforming the work environment into "learning by doing" places which are also called task-related learning (Wielenga-Meijer *et al.*, 2010). Work-based learning is a process in which employees acquire new or develop their existing experiences and develop confidence (Nikolova *et al.*, 2014). The following statement can relate to participant R1 acknowledging that weekly meetings help the employees develop their confidence in their work. Management follows them after the training on how they work and identified that training helps in many ways, as the volume of the products may increase. Also, employees can quickly identify the alteration. So, employees can reduce and limit the defects rates of products. So, from the above discussion, it can be concluded that task-related training significantly impacts the internal business perspective in an organization's non-financial performance. About 13 participants (except R8 and R11) 19 times mentioned that supplier quality management (see Table 4.5) has a nonfinancial impact on the internal business perspective in the organization, as many of them suggested developing a long-term relationship with the suppliers. As defined that long-term relationships develop goodwill (R2). Long-term relationships ensure the exchange of quality products between supplier and factory, so quality goods can be produced if the supplier's goods ensure quality. So, goodwill is vital for a successful business (R2.b, R1, R7, R14, R13.b). For example, R3 said, "Quality matters more. I mean, from my line, if the quality of raw materials is good, then the quality of the products will be good". Therefore, maintaining supplier quality is very important to ensure the quality organization. As mentioned before, Deming (1986) defined working with suppliers as a partner in a long-term relationship of loyalty and trust to improve the quality of incoming materials and decrease costs. Deming (1986) also mentioned that a long-term relationship between purchaser and supplier is necessary for the best quality implementation and for the best economy. Seven participants

(Table 5.9) acknowledged that organisational social responsibility significantly impacts an internal business perspective. It is argued by Deming (1992) about the significance of the social contribution that would emerge through the application of quality tools and techniques (Jacques, 1999). According to Sharma and Kodali (2008), social responsibilities have been highlighted by various quality gurus, and it has not been given due attention in the existing TQM framework. As mentioned, CSR practices developed goodwill between organizations and customers or third-party auditors and stakeholders. However, considering the Bangladesh garments industry, social responsibilities significantly impact business as the previous business reputation has damaged their goodwill on the world market. Hence, the organization is more concerned about social responsibilities such as workplace environment, health, and safety issues, fair payment, fire doors, and evacuation training (R2, R3, R5, R6, R7). Therefore, in the Bangladesh garments industry, corporate responsibility has a significant impact on the internal business perspective. Nine participants 18 times referenced that culture considerably impacts the internal business perspective. A few mentioned that traffic jams caused by the political strike reduce production speed and take extra delivery time. So, organizations lose both time and money (R1). The government, opposition political parties, and BGMEA can sit together to open a particular service for the garments business even on the strike day, which would have been better for this business. Otherwise, we lose the profit (R7, R15, R1, R4, R9, R13). Naveh and Erez (2004) pointed out that if different TQM practices are applied jointly, they have a positive impact not only on business or values such as control and attention to detail but also on creativity and experimentation. Therefore, it can be said that political and cultural impact significantly impacts the organization's internal business perspective on the organization's nonfinancial performance. Nine participants, R1, R4, R5, R7, R8, R11, R12, R13, and R14, acknowledged the impact of customer relationships on the internal business perspective. Customer feedback helps the organization to develop employee's knowledge and skills by introducing proper training programs that can be shared within the organization to build goodwill with the customers (Jones and Grimshaw, 2012; Perdom-Ortiz et al., 2006). This is acknowledged that Ensuring quality products and fulfilling the commitment to the customers (R1, R5), fulfilling customer demands (R8), and developing good relationships with the customers (R14), make the organization competitive in the market. The information from Hart et al. (1991), Deming (1982), Garvin (2001), and Zhang (2000), which describes a customer-oriented organisation in which customer pleasure drives all firm operations, is likewise relevant to the participant's statement from above. The organization must take to its customers first to determine what needs to do, such as using customer feedback in designing new products, monitoring customer satisfaction levels, responding to customer

complaints, and evaluating its success. Customer satisfaction strongly impacts the internal business perspective on non-financial organisational performance. None of the elements showed less than a 50% impact on the internal business perspective. Hence, organic QM has a significant impact on the internal business perspective. Although few elements have less impact on the customer’s perspective or innovation and learning perspective, they all substantially impact an internal business perspective. Hence, organic QM significantly impacts on organisational nonfinancial performance.

Table 5.9: Organic QM Internal business perspective

QM elements (Internal business perspective)	Participants	References
Top Management commitment	13	16
Employee suggestions	11	13
Group problem solving	14	15
Task Related training	13	16
Supplier QM	13	19
Customer Relationship	10	13
Social Responsibility	7	12
Political cultural context	9	18

Source: Primary Data

Evolving primary conceptual model for Organic QM aspect

There were 15 participants interviewed for this research task. If 7 to 15 participants acknowledged any element out of fifteen, it is considered a strong impact. But the participant’s acknowledgments responses 3 to 6 have been regarded as a moderate impact on the elements. Zero responses are considered not significant in context. However, if 5-6 participants acknowledged any nodes, more than seven references are also considered to have a substantial impact in context. Therefore, from the above discussion on the organic quality management aspect and following the above tables, Table 5.6, Table 5.7, Table 5.8, and Table 5.9, the below primary conceptual model (Figure 5.1) is drawn for organic QM impacts on performance by combining all four tables.

Figure 5.1: Evolving primary Conceptual model for Organic QM aspect

According to the researcher's interpretation of Figure 5.1, any node with less than two impacts on organisational performance would be deemed non-significant based on the primary data results. As a result, two to four arrows are thought to have an impact on organisational performance, including financial and nonfinancial aspects. The conceptual model shows that all nodes significantly impact the internal business perspective. Conversely, only 2 (Figure 5.1) nodes impact the customer's perspective, 'top management commitment' and 'customer's relationship.' Hence, top management decisions and customer relationships influence building goodwill with customers. However, task-related training, group problem-solving, and employee suggestions don't impact financial performance. Remarkably, all those three elements are the organization's internal soft aspects, though they do not have any direct impact on financial performance but have a substantial effect on the internal business perspective and innovation & Learning perspective. So, they have a significant impact on business. Conversely, from the participant's view, social responsibilities only impact the internal business perspective. Hence, in

the context of the Bangladesh garments industry, corporate social responsibilities do not have a substantial impact on organisational performance. Still, corporate social responsibility is a rising issue in Bangladesh due to the unhealthy environment in the workplace, low payment, and child labour in Bangladesh garments business is under threat by the trade organization. As a result, in-depth research on corporate social responsibility may be beneficial in clarifying the context of its impact on the Bangladesh garments industry. Thus, Soft QM significantly impacts organisational financial and non-financial performance. Therefore, H3 and H4 are accepted for the proposed model by the qualitative output.

H1: Hard QM has a significant direct impact on organisational financial performance.

The major contribution of process management is that it builds manufacturing capabilities, where process management practices focus on continuous improvement and preventing defects through transforming the data between the functional areas within the organization (Perdome-Ortiz *et al.*, 2006). *“Process management helps reduce the production cost by reducing defects rate as management monitors and follows up the quality level of products frequently” (R1)*. The participant defined that *“they (management) show them (employees) how to do work properly until the problem gets resolved and then asked to continue working in a productive way to save financial damage” (R2)*. Participant R10 said, *“Employees rectify the defective products to save the financial loss by following the process.”* Seven participants (R1, R4, R3, R2, R7, R10, and R13) acknowledged the process management's impact on financial performance. Hence, process management significantly impacts an organization's financial performance. There were twelve participants acknowledged that preventive maintenance significantly impacts on business. Preventative maintenance practice's motive is to extend the operational life, increase efficiency and monitor the effectiveness in business terms of equipment, buildings, and machinery (Dale, 1999). Preventive maintenance is related to equipment, building, and operational activities, so the financial impact is closely linked. Participants defined that *“defective products damaged reputation if management cannot fulfill the buyers demand and lose money (R1)”*. Participants explained that rectifying defective products kills time and money (R2, R3.a, R14, R5, R6, and R9). However, R11 said that following management's designated procedure helps the organization to save costs (R10, R11, and R12). However, Flynn *et al.* (1995), Mitchell *et al.* (2002), and Baysinger and Hoskisson (1990) point out that maintenance is the largest aspect of terotechnology and that many activities in the business cycle both affect and are affected by in terms of operational and business performance. So preventive maintenance has a significant impact on financial performance. Housekeeping is not only the key essential factor

for production purposes but also for the customer's perspective. The implementation of audit services to keep in check many of these housekeeping activities to ensure employees are consistent in maintaining specified housekeeping standards considering its impact on business (Zeng *et al.*, 2015; Flynn *et al.*, 1994; Schonberger, 2007). Table 5.10 shows that 13 participants defined that housekeeping has a strong financial impact on business. Several participants said, "R3: *Our cleanliness is very important to manage the defect rates. R4: b) Buyers do not accept spotted cloths. R5: Dirty floor can be the causes of defect or reject products.*" Also, participants R1, R6, R7 defined the same causes. Whereas, R9 and R15 defined that product orders can be canceled if the buyer reports a dirty or unclean floor during their factory visit. However, R10 said, "A clean floor also reduced fire risk in the organization." Therefore, housekeeping significantly impacts the financial perspective of the garment's organization.

Quality information is part of knowledge management as the basic input-output transformation process. Information sharing refers to the extent to which a company distributes information to its employees regarding policies, its relation to the general environment, and work-related goals (Lawler, 1992). In this context, information sharing is a flow of messages (Nonaka, 1994). As 9 participants 13 times acknowledged (See below Table 5.10), correct information sharing at the right time can save the company's financial loss and increase profit. Participants R1 and R3 said that good feedback brings good business by getting frequent orders from the buyers. Participant R2 said that quality information helps to understand the customer's expectations so management can resolve any matter that has a financial impact on business due to customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction brings a good reputation for the organization, which means its financial achievement. Information sharing can contribute to enhance work-related learning. So, mistakes can be reduced (van den Heuvel *et al.*, 2013; Rao *et al.*, 1997). Thus, acknowledged about the information sharing by R11 and R10 same as R10 said, "*This is how we can work accurately and meets buyer's demands. Otherwise, buyers will not accept the products that profit loss for the organization.*" In addition, R5 and R7 have defined that information sharing reduces employee conflict and develops better relationships among floor staff and management (R8). Therefore, quality information substantially impacts an organization's financial performance. Strategic planning guides the organization to stay focused on the chosen objectives for financial and non-financial achievement (Gray, 1986; Lisinski and Saruckij, 2006; Choi and Eboch, 1998). Table 5.10 shows that six participants acknowledged quality planning significantly impacts on organisational financial performance. Participants R8 and R14 and others defined that *Strategic quality planning helps manage defect rates during production. So, the organization can save*

time and product cost by applying strategic quality panning (R8, R14, R4, R5.a &b). The organization wants to ensure quality to hold goodwill with customers for sustainable business (R7, R8). Therefore, considering the above participant's statements and comparing them with the literature of Choi and Eboch (1998), it can be agreed that strategic quality planning significantly impacts organisational financial performance. The benchmarking process is systematic and consists of both hard and soft measures for benchmarking the value management process. Participants acknowledged the financial impact on the organisation's performance, as R2 said, "As business is declining and we eventually will receive fewer orders, market-benchmarking on competitors is essential for preventing financial loss." Participants also acknowledged that market analysis helps understand why others are doing better. So, benchmarking may help the organization to learn and progress for financial achievement (R6, R7, and R13). Conversely, participant R14 said, "We analyze those to understand what factors we need to follow to bring more value to the organization." As most participants said, benchmarking helps identify the reason for losing business or other aspects of a business's healthy and unhealthy situation. According to the benchmarking framework of Medori and Steeple (2000), benchmarking establishes and adopts an appropriate financial performance measurement system for competitiveness, such as profit, market share, and cost. So, benchmarking can bring out the actual state of the business situation to the management, and management can make the right decision by observing the context.

Table 5.10: Mechanistic QM Financial perspective

Mechanistic QM elements (Financial Impact)	Participants	References
Strategic Quality Planning	6	9
Preventive Maintenance	12	28
Housekeeping	13	17
Benchmarking	5	5
Quality Information	9	13
Process Management	7	8

Source: Primary Data

Table 5.10 above shows that more than 50% of participants acknowledged the impact of mechanistic QM on organisational financial performance. Hence, *Mechanistic QM significantly impacts an organization's financial performance as H1 is accepted for the proposed model.*

H2: Hard QM has a significant direct impact on organisational non-financial performance.

Six participants (see below Table 5.11) acknowledged that process management impacts organisational nonfinancial performance from the customer's perspective. Participants said they

transfer the employees to another department if the product quality does not meet the expected level or cannot meet the expected quantity (R3). Employees must follow the quality standard (R8) by checking five stages during production to ensure the desired level of quality so that customers can't complain (R9). Participants said they also use customer strategy to provide better quality products for a successful business (R13). The almost similar statement defined by Perdome-Ortiz *et al.* (2006), effective process management transforms the output of a certain department into another department to determine the source of poor performance in the process of producing the products, which in turn, affect positively builds the manufacturing capabilities within the organization. Customer satisfaction is key to the quality process, so process management impacts customers' perspectives on non-financial organisational performance. The organization's prime goal is to satisfy the customer's need, create the demand and provide value to customers. The statement can be linked with the participant's comments, "Failure to meet consumer expectations has a negative financial impact on an organization (R2, R4, and R12)". However, R14 said buyers refuse to accept the products due to defective products in the dispatched goods. So, the delivery was canceled. It shows that preventive maintenance has a significant positive and negative impact on business. Housekeeping is an advantage for the premises to improve safety and improve the working atmosphere and environment. The dirty floor could be the cause of damaged and spotted products. As explained by R10: "*Buyer representatives always follow this issue during their visit in the factory. Even they can cancel their orders if they see the unclean environment in the working place.*" Similarly, R4, R13, R14, R9, and R15 acknowledged the importance of housekeeping to satisfy the customer's demand. Most of them mentioned that unclean floor is the major cause of defective or damaged products. Buyers don't accept spotted products. Therefore, cleanliness and tidiness have a significant impact on customers' perspectives.

The key to quality management is maintaining a close relationship with the customers. Sharing customer feedback among the employees and working accordingly to meet the demands is continuous feedback and learning procedure that brings goodwill to the customers (Juran, 1993). Management received some claims due to missing the registration marks caused by inadequate sharing of information at the right time. Hence, sharing information on time can ensure quality products and brings customers satisfaction (R5, R8, R9, and R10). Participant R12 said that the right information helps to make zero defects during production. Similarly, R11 and R13 noted that the right information helps to bring goodwill to the organization. Hence, the discussion shows that quality information strongly impacts on non-financial performance perspectives.

A well-designed and coordinated process is more likely to guarantee tremendous success for the new product. As innovative quality strategies and plans are being formulated, communicating these to all employees involved is important and crucial to ensuring quality products, processes, and services (Martin and Home, 1993; Ooi *et al.*, 2012). This statement shows that strategic quality planning has an impact on organisational in all sectors, so for customers as well. The participants acknowledged that the strategic quality panning team tries to fit the right person for the right work. If employees repeat the same mistakes frequently to ensure product quality, management may change the position of the employees and bring in a new person (R4). Participant R5 said buyers do not compromise quality; 100% needs to be maintained because customer satisfaction is our main priority. Participant R7 said that organizations take zero tolerance for quality-related issues, as customer priority is the main (R3, R10). A participant said quality reputation increases the number of buyers R12, R11, and R14). Planning and execution of quality programs must include the component of customer focus. The aspect is maintaining a close relationship with the customers, thus needing to develop quality products, processes, and services to satisfy them (Flynn *et al.*, 1994). Hence quality panning has a significant impact on the customer’s perspective. However, critical success factors deal with the subjective value measurement process with soft aspects such as facilitator skills, teamwork, creativity, customer satisfaction, etc., and benchmarking results that reflect the actual situation. Therefore, benchmarking has a significant impact on non-financial organisational performance (Fong *et al.*, 2001). Considering the customer's perspective from the participant’s comments, it is acknowledged by R2 that Benchmarking helps understand the market condition, which allows to find the gap and work accordingly to maintain goodwill with customers. For example, participant R7 said, “*Analysis helps to understand the real financial and other issues of customers, also helps to understand the positions of our organization.*” Only two participants have spoken about the impact of benchmarking on customers' perspectives, so a moderate impact is assessed.

Table 5.11: Mechanistic QM Customer’s perspective

Mechanistic QM elements (Customer’s)	Participants	References
Strategic Quality Planning	7	8
Preventive Maintenance	5	7
Housekeeping	7	7
Benchmarking	2	2
Quality Information	9	14
Process Management	6	8

Source: Primary Data

Table 5.11 shows that benchmarking has less impact on customer's perspectives. Only 2 participants acknowledged about that. However, the rest others have shown a substantial impact on the customer's perspective. So, from the discussion, it can be said that mechanistic QM significantly affects customers' perspectives on business.

Innovation and Learning perspective

The number of defective and scarp products may be tracked using the process management technique. The employee's learning capacity, ability to recognise innovative ideas and ability to cope with issues are all aided by their failure and success records (Perdome-Ortiz *et al.*, 2006; Perdome-Ortiz *et al.*, 2009). As acknowledged, maintaining a chart for defects and error rates helps quickly identify the problems and which machine is creating the problem. In this case, the technician can efficiently resolve the matter (R1). *"Share the problem and resolving it with everyone helps the employees learn from their mistakes,"* said participant R3. Organizations also use their innovative process for better purposes (R13). So, process management helps to learn new things and share ideas. The researcher found that 11 participants acknowledged process management's significant impact on innovation and learning perspective (Below Table 5.12). The quality management approach is to achieve continuous quality improvement and increase productivity. Knowledge sharing, learning, and innovativeness are part of continuous improvement (Löfsten, 2014). Only 7 participants (See Table 4.10) said that preventive maintenance has an impact on innovation and learning perspectives. Participant R5 noted that new ideas could contribute to the business in this factory, as we can recycle the wastage products to reproduce thread from it (R5, R10). Management instruction also helps prevent wastage, as employees can learn from management instruction. Even employees R7 said they sell the wastage products to the local market below the price. This innovative marketing helps the organization to recover some sort of financial damage. Though none of the customers has said about the impact on innovation and learning perspective (Table 5.12), according to Baba (2012), factory systems have practical experiences and regular assessment to enable the employees to embed the techniques and new working practices.

Information sharing is rarely studied as an HRM practice. However, related constructs such as clarity of organisational goals (Patterson *et al.*, 2005), internal and external communication (Burke *et al.*, 2004), and diversity of information have been found to affect innovation processes. Perceived information sharing has recently been found to exert an indirect effect on innovative work behaviour through a group environment for innovation (Odoardi *et al.*, 2015). The above

statement is also acknowledged as - information helps identify the problems and helps learn the right path to get the job done (R2). According to participant R4, when a new problem emerges, the staff members share it with one another so that they can quickly resolve it. Information is, therefore, a creative means of learning new things. Participant R12 said, *"We collect information from other factories, and we also find information from google about garments trading and try to develop the new process if we like. For example, we used to mark on the cloths with chalk to join the pocket, but now we use leisure light which helps us to save an extra employee (helper)."* Hence, information sharing or collecting new information from outside impacts innovation and learning perspectives (R12, R9). Information sharing can also contribute to work-related learning (Bartunek *et al.*, 1999), which suggests that when management regularly communicates about goals and clarifies work-related expectations, employees develop a broader understanding of their role in the organization, which utterly facilitates their work-based learning. The above discussion can relate to the statement of participants R5, R11, R12, R15, and R14. For example, R11 said, *"We first speak with customers and wait until we receive clarity if we have any questions or become confused about something. We occasionally also produce several samples to show the customers, and if they are delighted with a certain product, we proceed with production."* So, quality information significantly impacts on organisational innovation and learning perspective. Participants characterised market benchmarking as a tool that helps identify the difference between below average and higher performance from the standpoint of innovation and learning. As a result, the organisation can genuinely understand the business context (R2, R7, R4, and R15). Participants defined that *benchmarking works as an innovative learning process*. Participant R6 said, *"The garments business depends on who can make the best product. If we know the system, we will be able to produce more products quickly."* Conversely, R13, R5, and R14 define that benchmarking is very important to understand the market condition and why factories are moving to other countries in the context of the Bangladesh garment industry. Almost 60% of participants (Table 5.12) defined benchmarking impacts on innovation and learning perspectives. Hence, benchmarking is significant. Firm competitiveness comes from the employee's specialized knowledge, the ability of the firm to create new knowledge and innovate, and the strategic action enabled by innovation (Carayannis *et al.*, 2000; Grant, 1996). Therefore, a lack of awareness regarding quality may result in the manufacturer producing products of lower quality. Conversely, quality planning enables employees to work accurately to produce quality products (Choi and Eboch, 1998). Organizations closely monitor the employees to maintain quality instruction (R4). Participants R5 said, *"Every trouser has a register in a specific place, and the design must be in that specific*

place which is a quality requirement. So, we explain the issues and ask them to follow the instruction so we can save the loss.” Following the quality planning structure, the organization saves costs. The organization does not need to produce an extra 5-10% of cloths to meet the total quantity for the orders (R12). Being innovative helps create value for customers and thus improves the firm's performance to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage over its competitors (Mele and Colurcio, 2006). Therefore, strategic quality planning significantly impacts innovation and learning perspectives. Only three participants acknowledged that strategic quality planning significantly impacts on innovation and learning perspectives. So, a moderate impact has been assessed.

Table 5.12: Mechanistic QM Innovation and Learning perspective

Mechanistic QM elements (Innovation & Learning Impact)	Participants	References
Strategic Quality Planning	3	3
Preventive Maintenance	7	8
Housekeeping	0	0
Benchmarking	8	8
Quality Information	13	18
Process Management	11	13

Source: Primary Data

Table 5.12 above shows that housekeeping has zero impact on innovation and learning perspective. Also, the participant demonstrated less than a 50% impact on strategic quality planning. However, the other has substantially impacted innovation and learning perspectives. Hence, Mechanistic QM has a substantial impact on innovation and learning perspective.

Internal business perspective

Process management emphasizes having systems and the effective use of all technical systems. The design of a production process is also one of the important practices affecting internal quality performance and competitive capabilities. In designing production processes, the error-proofing process helps to eliminate employee errors (Gibson, 1990; Gilbert, 1990). Several participants also acknowledge this as said organizations take action against the employees if they frequently make mistakes. In this case, management asks the employees to change the working process and monitor the previous procedure to avoid mistakes. This is how organizations resolve the problem to help the business (R2). However, if the employee repeats the same errors, employees will be noticed to follow the management guidance during work (R3). Organizations can save loss if they immediately identify the cause of defective products (R4.a, b). Therefore,

process management helps us observe management's working progression and know about defect or error rates. According to Benner and Tushman (2002) and Benner and Tushman (2003), firms that implement the ISO 9001:1994 standards imply a merely technical and closed quality management focus. Hence, TQM's process management ensures quality products, employees' capabilities, and organisational business performance. For instance, participant *R15* said, *"We also do lab tests following bio equipment activities. Suppose we frequently wash to check whether the colour quality is ensured or diminishing. If the colour does not meet the quality, then the system does not meet the quality requirements. So, we test it before going to the final production."* As well as *"R6, R7, R8, R9, R10, R11, R12, and R13* also acknowledged that process management has a significant impact on business. Thus, process management substantially impacts an organization's internal business perspective. Conversely, twelve participants said that preventive maintenance strongly influences the internal business perspective. In the participants' opinion, more defective products cause the cost of time and money for the organization (*R2*). Management tries to rectify the products, but products need to be thrown out if they are not rectifiable. In this case, if the organization cannot meet customers' product demands, it can negatively impact customer goodwill (*R7, R6, and R12*). According to Lofsten (1999) and Smith (2000), any default machine or other abnormality can be detected faster in a clean environment. Working in a clean environment improves motivation and safety. As acknowledged by participant *R13*, *"The unclean floor could be dangerous for us and our business. If 3rd party investigation fails us, we have to stop working for a certain time, and it's a reputation and financial loss for the organization."* *R1, R6, R11a, and R11.b* explained that housekeeping makes the working environment comfortable, and employees feel good about working in a clean place. However, many others also said that a clean floor saves the products from being spot defective or rejected. The participants below noted that a clean floor increases productivity and improves the organization's reputation. As acknowledged by *R2 and R3*, *"Our cleanliness is very important to manage the defect rates and ensure quality."* *R1, R7, and R2* have defined similar reasons. As an element of TQM, housekeeping also contributes to improving the overall quality of corporate activities. It also seeks to maximize the organization's competitiveness (Kotler and Keller, 2016), which could impact an internal business perspective. As explained by Nonaka (1994), information sharing reflects an HRM practice generated by the organization toward employees and knowledge sharing (Wang & Noe, 2010). 13 participants (see below Table 5.13) have acknowledged that information impacts internal business perspectives on organisational performance. A maximum of the participant has said feedback helps to understand what the buyers want from the organization. Hence, feedback develops

goodwill with customers (R1, R3, R4, R5, R11, R10, and R14). However, R4 said that the right information helps the organization mitigate many conflicts between employees and staff in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry (R4). Conversely, the right information sharing helps the management reduce defect rates, prevent financial loss, and increase productivity (R3). As acknowledged by participants R8 and R10, "if I do not pass the information immediately among the employees, products might be produced incorrectly, and we must rework because of the information gap." Similarly, participant R15 defined that information sharing directly relates to competitive business performance. Therefore, the above discussion shows that quality information strongly impacts the internal business perspective. According to Medori and Steeple (2000), benchmarking establishes and adopts an appropriate non-financial performance measurement system for competitiveness, such as quality, flexibility, time, delivery, and growth. So, benchmarking significantly impact on non-financial performance on an internal business perspective. As acknowledged by participant R5, *"We consider the financial performance, production, and quality performance as well. It helps us understand our organization's position and what to do to improve"*. Checking other companies' performance and finding out why our organization is not doing well actually help us to perform well (R1, R4, R6, R9, R12, and R14). Benchmarking also helps to understand the organisation's internal progression (R13, R15), comparing inside and outside organizational performance, identifying performance gaps, and why others are doing well (R12). The common phenomenon identified from the above primary data is identifying the problems and working on them for better business success. Therefore, benchmarking has a significant impact on the internal business perspective of organisational non-financial performance. Fong *et al.* (2001) also defined that critical success factors deal with facilitator skills, teamwork, creativity, customer satisfaction, and benchmarking results that reflect the actual situation. A complete business strategy should incorporate a systematic plan for new products, connect the new product to the corporate goals, determine which market and technology to select, and what transmission criteria to apply (Martensen and Dahlgard, 1999; Cooper, 2005). Therefore, quality planning also works with the strategy. The participants also acknowledged that ensuring 100% quality is the main target for the organisation as it brings goodwill to the market and makes the organisation competitive (R3, R5). Participants R7 and R12 said quality panning helps to reduce defect rates. So, it helps to increase productivity. Furthermore, participant R14 said, *"A positive reputation results from quality. A good reputation increases the number of customers, which boosts sales."* However, R13 defined different issues as said technological implementation is required to ensure quality and reduce workloads for progressive business. The above statement shows that quality plays a big role in sustainable

business with the customers and maintaining sustainable goodwill. Also, technological innovation and the introduction of technology have been mentioned in the quality strategy for the internal business perspective.

Table 5.13: Mechanistic QM Internal business perspective

Mechanistic QM elements (Internal Business Impact)	Participants	References
Strategic Quality Planning	9	15
Preventive Maintenance	12	26
Housekeeping	14	18
Benchmarking	10	12
Quality Information	13	19
Process Management	13	17

Source: Primary Data

The Table 5.13 above shows that all the mechanistic elements strongly impact on the internal business perspective. Hence, Mechanistic QM has a substantial impact on the internal business perspective. Therefore, considering the above financial and non-financial performance, Mechanistic QM strongly impacts the organisational non-financial performance.

Evolving Primary Conceptual Model for Mechanistic QM aspect

There were 15 participants interviewed for this research task. If 7 of 15 participants acknowledged about any variables out of fifteen, it is considered a significant impact. But the participant’s acknowledgments responses 3-6 have been regarded as having a moderate impact on the elements. Zero responses are considered not-significance in the context. However, if 5 to 6 participants acknowledged any nodes, more than 7 references are also considered significant. Therefore, from the above discussion on the mechanistic quality management aspect, the following Table 5.10, Table 5.11, Table 5.12, and Table 5.13 were integrated to find the primary conceptual model (Figure 5.2) for mechanistic QM is shown below.

Figure 5.2: Evolving conceptual model for Mechanistic QM

From the researcher's view, any node with less than two impacts on organisational performance is considered non-significant based on the primary data result. So, 2 to 4 arrows are regarded as a significant impact on organisational performance, including financial and nonfinancial perspectives. The conceptual model (Figure 5.2) shows that all nodes significantly impact internal business and financial perspective, except 'benchmarking' is not significant from a financial perspective. However, 5 participants acknowledged the financial impact of benchmarking on business performance. Conversely, benchmarking significantly impact the internal business and, innovation & learning perspective. Hence, benchmarking is considered for its significant impact on organisational performance. Other variables show 3 or more than 4 impact arrows in organisational performance. Therefore, Mechanistic QM significantly impacts organisational Financial (H1) and Non-Financial (H2) performance. Hence, hypotheses H1 and H2 are accepted for the proposed model based on the qualitative data outcomes.

5.3.1 Evolving primary Conceptual model for Multi-dimensional view of TQM.

The organic and mechanistic QM practices impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Hence, considering both primary and secondary data, it can be said that QM substantially impacts organisational performance in both financial and non-financial contexts. It is also shown that the organic and mechanic conceptual models, respectively, Figure 5.1 and Figure 5.2, significantly impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. The below conceptual model, Figure 5.3, has been developed by combining both organic and mechanistic aspects of quality elements. Therefore, hypotheses H1, H2, H3, and H4 support the proposed conceptual model, followed by the qualitative data outcomes.

Figure 5.3: Evolving Integrated Primary Conceptual model for Multi-dimensional TQM

Source: Primary

5.4 Discussion Based on Objective Two: Impact of Innovation on Organisational Performance

Four hypotheses, such as H5, H6, H7, and H8 developed under objective two to identify the impact of technological and administrative innovation.

H7: Administrative innovation has a significant impact on organisational financial performance.

Organizations may internally support innovation by encouraging, recognizing, and rewarding creativity and providing adequate amounts of such resources as personal, funding, and time (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990; Scot and Bruce, 1994; Woodman *et al.*, 1993). The psychological context of creativity is made up of employees' impressions of such internal support in their workplace, which might impact their creative work (Amabile *et al.*, 1996). Creative work, team effort, and goodwill development with the customers are all linked with business success as a financial achievement. Participants R2, R7, R2, and R11 acknowledged that strategic negotiation with buyers and suppliers benefits the business financially. The participant said that waste management in an innovative way helps the organisation save finance as waste can be recycled (R11). However, Participant R15 said that employee movement against the organisation causes delayed delivery of products to the customers, which is expensive. Participant R14 noted that foreign direct investment could be one of the innovative ideas. Still, limited finance and unknown foreign business policy are barriers for the organisation, but FDI can be a profitable strategy for the organisation. Only four participants have talked about the financial impact on internal organisational innovation, even indirectly. Therefore, a knowledge gap has been identified among the employees in the innovation context as 11 participants (Table 5.14) acknowledged that they do not practice internal innovation directly. In the globalized world, business faces rapid changes both in customer needs and the nature of markets. To gain a competitive edge and improve their performance, companies must develop new products and strategies to attract new customers and satisfy existing ones (Ungerma *et al.*, 2018; Ittner *et al.*, 1997). A participant said that marketing innovation brings financial business success. As said, direct business with buyers other than via a third party is profitable (R2). Participants also defined that they do not have any partnership business with buyers, but it could be better to gain more business opportunities and profits (R4, R12). Therefore, marketing strategy is a part of marketing innovation (Kotler, 2014). Even a cheaper price strategy for selling defective or rejected products in the local market also covers the loss (R5, R3). Also, participants defined that foreign direct investment will be profitable if the organization has sufficient production and marketing abilities (R10, R11). However, a big sum of investment is required for the FDI. Participants questioned

that whether the organisation could do so (R1). The innovative modern market has a beneficial impact on boosting sales and reducing costs, thus improving competitiveness (Kamp and Parry, 2017). Therefore, marketing innovation has a significant financial impact on business performance based on the above discussion.

Strategic innovation refers to making knowledge creation and innovative initiative a way of life, attempting to create and expand the market share instead of simply responding to customer demand, and redirecting resources from profitable but dwindling lines of business to support emerging lines of business that have the potential to be more commercially viable (Ungerma *et al.*, 2018). Strategic alliances or doing business by sharing partnerships could be profitable for the garments industry (R1). However, participants also acknowledged that having their showroom and direct investment in a foreign market is an even better idea for gaining profit than a partnership (R4, R9). Furthermore, innovative strategic decisions can be made on waste management, variance control, resource allocation, marketing policies. For instance, participant R5 said, *“We value creative ideas, like in this factory, even though our rule is to cut 3% extra, but our target is to bring it in 1%, and that’s what we want to do, actually. We want to reduce our extra products that save money and improve quality.”* Participants defined that having a transparent supply chain helps the business save excessive dispatch costs via air cargo (R13). Participants also described that selling products directly to the foreign market would be more profitable than producing for buyers (R14). According to Kotler (2014), strategic innovation deals with management's new policies to enhance the business. Hence, from the following discussion, it can be said that strategic innovation significantly impacts organisational financial performance.

Table 5.14: Administrative innovation financial perspective

Administrative Innovation (Financial Impact)	Participants	References
Internal organisational Innovation	4	9
Marketing Innovation	9	15
Strategic Innovation	7	13

Source: Primary Data

Table 5.14 above shows that more than 50 participants acknowledged that administrative innovation significantly impacts financial performance. However, only 4 participants defined that ‘internal organisational innovation’ substantially impacted financial performance. However, 9 references have been made by the four participants about its impact. So, on average, it can be said that administrative innovation has a significant impact on organisational financial performance. Hence hypothesis H7 is accepted for the proposed model.

H8: Administrative innovation has a significant direct impact on organisational non-financial performance.

Client-oriented firms greatly emphasize consumer orientation, which may lead to an overemphasis on incremental innovation as a result of the desire to constantly evaluate customer needs (Prajogo and Sohal, 2001). The participants also explained that partnership is an innovative idea for a long-term business plan to develop customer goodwill (R2). Also, R2 said, *"using the computerise machine, we can save 3-4 days of production duration, and similarly, we can reduce the delay delivery days."* The initiation was of administrative innovation helping to reduce the fire-related damaged. Fire damaged the reputation of the Bangladesh garments business (R5). Innovation helps avoid third parties threats in the garments business (R14). Hence, from the above discussion, it can be summarised that innovation helps to build continuous business performance. Also, innovation practices save the organisation from unexpected damages or threats from third parties. Jaworski and Kohli (1996) explained that innovative customer orientation implies obtaining information from current and future customer needs, considering all the environmental forces that could shape their expectations. Participants R1, R4, R11, R13, and R14 have talked about the creative ideas, new policies, and strategies from the customer's perspective have a significant impact on business as said following: Partnership with the buyers is suitable for a long-time business plan as the organisation can make sustainable business progression (R1). Management has the policy to find new buyers from online. We show sample products to the buyers. If they like, they order production (R4, R11). Email is not the first communication path in the context of Bangladesh. Employees need to train about it, and management needs to be sincere and responsible to reply to the buyers as quickly as possible (R13). One participant defined that introducing their brand in the market can be a way to get more customers for a successful business. According to Ungerman *et al.* (2018) and Ittner *et al.* (1997), the notion of innovation moves a company forward. Therefore, new strategies, marketing policies, and creating something innovative can potentially attract a customer's attention.

Strategic innovation is a way of achieving a successful business. Obtaining customers' information, understanding customer needs, fulfilling the customers' demand, providing exceptional facilities, ensuring quality services and innovative goods could be the organisation's target factors. Customer's oriented strategy brings goodwill and sustainable business to the organisation. Strategic right decisions can make the organisation competitive in the market and ensure quality services as defined that strategic innovation helps to reduce misunderstanding between management and employees. Employee's movement against management can stop

production, which negatively impacts customer relationships (R4). Customer satisfaction is the business's main priority, and strategic innovation positively impacts on it (R5) for sustainable business performance both with customers and suppliers (R12, R13). From the above discussion by the participants, it is identified that strategic innovation significantly impacts business. Its implementation may influence the organisation's competitiveness. Conversely, the gap of strategic innovation in an organisation may lose the better opportunities for a successful business.

Table 5.15: Administrative innovation Customer's perspective

Administrative Innovation (Customer's Impact)	Participants	References
Internal organisational Innovation	3	5
Marketing Innovation	5	6
Strategic Innovation	6	6

Source: Primary Data

From the customer's perspective, internal organisation innovation shows comparatively less impact on organisational performance. However, more than 50% of participants acknowledged the impact of Administration innovation on the customers' perspectives (Table 5.15). Hence, administrative innovation has a reasonable impact on organisational performance.

Innovation and Learning Perspective

According to Parajogo and Sohal (2001), innovation-oriented firms create an organisational climate focusing on maintaining competitive parity and providing novel, innovative and striking solutions. As mentioned about the new ideas, how does it impact innovation and learning perspective in business by several participants are as follows: new ideas bring the new process in the organisation (R1). Even new idea helps to resolve problems when employees face them in the workplace (R2, R4, R5, R6, and R7). A participant acknowledges that new ideas can come from any employee and impact business. For instance, participant *R13 said, "Idea can come from any position, even from the floor employees. We can learn from innovative information. It could be a way of implementing new ideas to do better in business."* However, besides the new ideas, a few participants also discussed the innovative way of doing things important in business performance. As acknowledged by *R8, "We promote the employee who is skillful. Also, few employees can do the same work differently, effectively, and quickly."* Therefore, innovative ideas need to be valued and implemented in the business to achieve the best outcomes (R9, R12). 11 participants acknowledged the impact of internal organisation innovation on innovation and learning perspective. Hence, it's significant in business. Innovative marketing can help the

organisation to sustain its business performance. Coming out from the usual marketing procedure, if the organisation does something different, it may add extra value to the market (Kotler, 2014). The participants also acknowledged that partnership with foreign buyers is innovation and can be a way for sustainable business progress. Management can also learn about the foreign market's environment (R1). A participant said that products with less quality could be sold to the local market to cover the loss (R4, R5). Participant R2 defined that direct marketing can gain benefits, and management also communicates quickly to the buyers (R7). Participant represents that quick communication always helps to work effectively and accurately as quickly can understand what buyers demand and what management is doing to meet the demands during production. Hence, marketing innovation has a moderate impact on innovation and learning perspectives.

Innovation and continuous improvement are key dimensions for sustainable business performance. Strategic innovation emphasis incremental changes, create an innovative climate in the organisation, and maintains competitive parity. Strategic innovation can introduce new ideas and processes to make the organisation competitive (Kotler, 2014O). New ideas help learn new innovative processes to do the work (R1, R5). *An online mailing service is essential to continue business with customers and suppliers (R12)*. Customers also defined that using an innovative strategy such as multitasking is helpful as management can use those skilled employees whenever we really need them for different sectors (R13). *Even employees' suggestions help the organisation identify the gap between management and employees. It positively impacts on business (R14)*. As strategic innovation impacts customers, it has an impact on markets, and it has an impact on quality goods and services that influence internal organisational performance. For example, participant R1 said, *"I think this is a good idea because the shareholder (foreign investor) will try to invest more, and we will try to give quality products too for having a long-time business plan. The profit will be shared between the two parties. In this case, quality can be improved, and expenses may be reduced."* Also, R3 said, *"24 hours email service can help to reduce the delayed delivery if we try."* In addition, R4 said, *"we did not have an engineering department before. But this department's primary responsibilities are planning, time management, and employee management, which is very effective for the organisation."* Hence strategic innovation has a significant impact on innovation and learning perspective.

Table 5.16: Administrative innovation, Innovation & learning perspective

Administrative Innovation (Innovation & Learning Impact)	Participants	References
Internal organisational Innovation	11	14
Marketing Innovation	5	5
Strategic Innovation	7	9

Source: Primary Data

Table 5.16 shows that all administrative innovation elements significantly impact innovation and learning perspectives. Hence, administrative innovation has a strong positive impact on nonfinancial performance.

Internal Business Perspective

The internal business process perspective describes the business process that must be mainly adopted to satisfy its shareholders and customers, including the supply chain, organisational climate, resource allocation, and implementation (Zeng *et al.*, 2015). As acknowledged by Participant R1, *“New ideas can be helpful for the organization. We frequently see that new ideas can give a new process to do the work.”* R2 said, *“In many cases, it is seen that the information that floor-level employees give us is very useful, and in that case, we accept.”* Innovative ideas help the organization accomplish the work faster, even increasing productivity (R4, R6). Parajogo and Sohal (2001) defined that innovation in the internal organisational process perspective deals with the customers and suppliers, among others. Hence the above participant’s statement satisfies the innovation’s impact on the internal business process perspective. However, the internal business process has a direct impact on process management. Hence organisational process implementation significantly impact on business, including technological process in administration, which is acknowledged by R14, *“We did not have that before, but after a certain time, we realized the demand for the database in the factory. It’s beneficial for organizing and monitoring the daily works”*. Participants defined that suggestions are helpful in finding an innovative way of doing things. It is important for an organisation’s business progression, so they collect suggestions from the employees (R7, R9, and R11). Fourteen participants out of 15 acknowledged that internal organisation innovation significantly impacts on the internal organisational business perspective. Therefore, in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry, internal organisational innovation has a significant impact on the internal business perspective (Table 5.17). According to Zeng *et al.* (2015), applying marketing innovation in the market has an internal business impact in several ways, such as ‘building public relationships and branding by increasing the productivity of the works. Thus, acknowledged by the

participants: introducing their brands in the market will be profitable, but the organization does not do that (R3, R8). As acknowledged by example R12, *“Beximco has their own brand name YELLOW, and it’s doing well in the market. The quality of this brand is well as well.”* According to Prajogo and Sohal (2004), improving communication with customers and improving the quality of the products. The participants also acknowledged R1, *“But I know we reply to the email as soon as possible, and that is very important for effective communication and building goodwill.”* So, accepting digitalized technological implementation to provide better customer service is a way to develop goodwill. Participant R11 also defined that multiple language expertise required successful communication with the buyers (R11). Participants expressed that direct buyers are preferable for sustainable business performance (R2, R10). As acknowledged by R13, *“Once the buyers have been doing business with us for 2-3 years, the trust can build up, and buyers can turn to direct order payers for us. So, building up trust is really important. We recently appointed two persons in 2 different countries to find the direct buyers.”* Kotler (2014) also defined that innovation-oriented firms increase competitiveness by changing strategic planning and finding new markets. For Instance, participant R4 said, *“If we have our showroom, we can use the products outdoors if a buyer rejects them.”* Therefore, from the above discussion, it can be said that marketing innovation significantly impacts on the organisational internal business perspective.

Furthermore, Damanpour *et al.* (2018) and Damanpour and Wischnevsky (2006) explained that organisational strategic innovation improves efficiency and productivity, increases market share and probability, and generates economic wealth for the organisation. For example, participant R7 said, *“The opposition parties, government, and the BGMEA can sit together and enact a new law to find a solution to the strike and traffic jam which may help this business.”* Participants also defined that they are trying to reduce extra product-making to cover the defective items from 3% to 1% by improving quality (R5). Strategic innovation for supplier management brings success to the business, said R12, *“It is essential to have a strong relationship with the suppliers. We can have alternative suppliers, but the owner’s involvement is required to do so.”* Participant R13 also defined that the local political conflict among the political parties significantly impacts business. One of the reasons for delayed delivery of the products is if the employee makes a move against the organisation and does not work for a few days. The traffic jam and political declaration of strike day cause supply disruption (R13). The organisation needs to identify those issues. The organisation has a team to deal with these issues, which is helpful in understanding the market condition through effective analysis. This process significantly impacts on the

business as we can realize the context of the business gap or why others are doing well (R14). It is also defined by Hage & Aiken (1967), Damanpour (2017), and Damanpour *et al.* (2018) organisations introduce strategic innovations to adapt to environmental change and achieve strategic intents for maintaining and improving performance. Hence, based on the primary and secondary data discussion, strategic innovation strongly impacts on the organisational internal business performance.

Table 5.17: Administrative innovation internal business perspective

Administrative Innovation (Internal Business Impact)	Participants	References
Internal organisational Innovation	14	38
Marketing Innovation	9	12
Strategic Innovation	12	25

Source: Primary Data

Table 5.17 shows that all administrative innovation elements significantly impact an internal business perspective. Hence, administrative innovation has a substantial impact on non-financial performance.

Evolving Conceptual model for Administrative Innovation.

There were 15 participants interviewed for this research task. If more than 7 participants acknowledged any nodes out of 15, it is considered a significant impact. But the participant’s acknowledgments responses 3 to 6 have been considered to have a moderate impact on the elements. Below three and Zero responses are considered not to substantially impact context. However, if 5-6 participants acknowledged any nodes, more than 7 references are also regarded as significant in context. As a result of the discussion above on organic quality management and Table 5.14, Table 5.15, Table 5.16, and Table 5.17 have considered to draw the evolving primary conceptual model for administrative innovation’s impact on the organisational financial and non-financial performance. The following Figure 5.4 is the desired conceptual model by the primary qualitative outcomes.

Figure 5.4: Evolving Conceptual model for Administrative Innovation

Source: Primary

The above conceptual model (Figure 5.4) shows that each node from administrative innovation focused on more than two significant impacts on the organisation's performance, including financial and non-financial aspects. Remarkably, internal organisational innovation does not impact on customer's perspective. Conversely, both marketing and strategic innovation significantly impact customers and financial views. Strategic innovation equally impacts on both financial and non-financial perspectives. Administrative innovation significantly impacts on organisational financial and non-financial perspectives. Hence, administrative innovation significantly impacts on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Thus, H7 and H8 are accepted for the proposed model.

H5: Technological innovation has a significant direct impact on organisational financial performance.

Technological innovation is just a part of innovation, including the application of new technologies urging the change of products, services, and methods to generate products and services (Damanpour, 1987). Therefore, technological innovation can be defined as a process in which new technologies are integrated into developing new products or processes. Thus, it has a strong financial impact on business (Ahire *et al.*, 1996; Rao *et al.*, 1999). As acknowledged by the participants, the technological process helps the organisation save employee and production costs by managing the production's time length (R1). It is said that an automatic machine takes more than 3-4 days extra time than the automatic machine. Hence, technology helps save time and decrease production costs (R3). Participants also said that new machine management removes the threads from the waste cloths (R5), saving expenses. Conversely, participant R13 said that technological implementation sometimes causes extra costs, such as providing internet facilities to all employees is costly for the organisation (R13). Participants also defined that implementing new technology organizations save employee costs, as acknowledged by R12, *"The benefit of technology is that instead of using 12 assistance as we did in the past, we now only need 8. If we have access to more advanced technology, even we do not need any assistants. We are attempting to achieve that."* Therefore, the technological process significantly impacts an organisation's financial performance. Product innovation is introducing new products or services to meet an external user's need. Product innovation is primarily market-driven, and its technological impact may increase the production volume and ensure better quality products for a successful business perspective (Damanpour, 2006; Utterback, 1994). According to the following participants, using technology in production has positive and negative financial impacts on business. As explained, eight hundred thousand products must be washed monthly. However, do not have sufficient washing-up facilities of goods. Hence, management needs to find washing plants from another factory which costs extra budget' (R5). Participant also defines that technological implementation in the goods production system increases productivity, which financially benefits the organisation (R6). However, the participant describes that though technology brings financial benefits for the organisation, it increases unemployment problems for the country (R4). Participants also defined that the variation of producing products in the factory is a matter of introducing the technology. For Instance, participant R11 said, *"We are a factory that only produces jackets, despite having this machine for pants and jackets. So, a little hesitant to bring this machine given that it will cost more."* Hence, technology significantly impacts business, but introducing technology is also a matter for the organisation. Technology is defined as tools, devices, and knowledge for products and processes that affect organizational efficiency,

facilitate the conversion of inputs into outputs and reduce inefficiencies in product development, production, and delivery. Thus, technological innovation on organisational financial performance relates to the products and processes. The following participants acknowledged that implementing the technology in the production and process department that's how the organisation may save time and cost. As acknowledged by the participants, the technological process helps the organisation save the employee expense and saves the production cost by saving the time length of the production (R1, R7). It is said that a manual machine takes more than 3-4 days extra time than an auto machine. R2 defined that auto-machine produces more products in a specific time and can save time and cost. The auto machine can help to make accurate number of products in a particular time so that the measurement can be worked accurately, and less workforce is required (R6). Participant R10 acknowledged, *"We have the lane cutting machine to cut the cloths, which saves employees cost and time."* Management needs APE and FEW machines for jackets and pants to bring in, which could also help us save production time and cost (R11, R12). Hence, new technological technology has a significant impact on organisational financial performance.

Table 5.18: Technological innovation financial perspective

Technological Innovation (Financial Impact)	Participants	References
Technological Process	5	8
Technological Products	4	4
Technological Technology	8	11

Source: Primary Data

Though technological products have less impact on financial performance, the other elements strongly impact organisational financial performance (Table 5.18). Hence, Technological innovation substantially impacts organisational financial performance. So, hypothesis H5 is accepted for the proposed model.

H6: Technological innovation has a significant direct impact on organisational non-financial performance.

As mentioned earlier, technological innovation impacts new products and services or methods of generating products or services, so it impacts customers because quality products and services develop goodwill with the customers for better business (Damanpour, 1989). For example, participant R4 said, *"process management such as using land lay process helps to ensure quality products."* Also, R11 noted, *"using language converter software helps effectively dealing with customers."* Thus, the technological process helps to develop goodwill with customers. Only two participants acknowledged the impact of technological processes on the

customer’s perspective. Hence, it is ambiguous whether the technological process has a significant impact on the technological process. The drivers of product innovations are customer needs and demand. So, the organisation desires to become competitive in the market and grow the business (Damanpur *et al.*, 2018; Utterback, 1994). Only one participant acknowledged that technological product innovation impacts the customer’s perspective, as the participant said that technological product innovation helps ensure the quality of service and products (R1). Simultaneously, the literature review shows that technological product innovation significantly impacts customers, but only one participant out of fifteen has acknowledged it. Hence, in the Bangladesh garments industry, technological product innovation does not directly impact on the customer’s perspective. The general perception of innovation equates innovation with new technology or technical innovation and understands innovation in organisations as technological innovation. This misunderstanding is exacerbated later by using the term innovation to portray technology-based products and process innovations. While the importance of technology and technological innovation for organisation adoption, competition, and performance is undeniable (Utterback, 1994). As acknowledged from the customer’s perspective, implementing new technology over technology helps reduce production duration. Even increasing computer implementation assists the organisation in saving time, so the organisation can deliver the products in due time other than being delayed (R1). Only three participants defined the impact on technology from the customer’s perspective, which means 12 participants (Table 5.19) did not say any direct impact on the customer’s perspective. Participant R4 defined that technology helps to make better quality products. Participants also noted that organisations must introduce new technology to improve production facilities and product quality (R11). Hence, technological technology significantly impacts organisational non-financial performance from a customer’s perspective.

Table 5.19: Technological innovation customer’s perspective

Technological Innovation (Customer’s Impact)	Participants	References
Technological Process	2	2
Technological Products	1	1
Technological Technology	3	3

Source: Primary Data

Remarkably, all technological innovation elements show less than a 50% impact on the customer’s perspective (Table 5.19). Hence, it can be said that technological innovation does not significantly impact on customers' perspectives.

The technological process innovation is understood as the result of the emergence of dominant designs (Anderson and Tushman, 1990) and how appropriate opportunities change with firm size (Klepper, 1996). Therefore, the technological process impacts the innovation and learning perspective on business. The following participants also acknowledged the impact as participants defined that technology such as automatic machines can help to produce accurate number of products in a particular time so the measurement can be worked accurately, and organisation can save time and cost both (R1, R11). Also, participants defined a machine that makes cotton from waste cloths. New ideas are essential for this business to save the wastages and reuse that for-profit (R5). The knowledge gap is a common factor in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry. So, participants defined that the organization needs high migrant employees to run a few new machines for its effective utilization (R8). Conversely, R15 described that giving employees training can be another way to fill the technological knowledge gap in the organisation (R15, R13). Hence, technological implementation helps the organization to follow an innovative process that increases the productivity and competitiveness of an organisation and helps to learn about new technological utilization. So, it has an impact on innovation and learning perspectives. Three participants have explained that product innovation significantly impacts organisational, innovation, and learning perspectives, so introducing innovative technology in production has a minor impact on the learning perspective in business. In the broader meaning of technology, changes occur due to the cumulative effects of multiple technologies and technological innovations over time, impacting the organisation for its new innovativeness (Lawless & Anderson, 1996). participants R15 and R13 noted that the machine's output shows the production capacity and how much the employees are producing per hour. Organisation can monitor the work progression by following the report. Participants also defined that the new machine is suitable for production but needs to hire a technician from abroad to learn its utilization correctly to bring the best output (R8, R1, and R5). The new automatic machine helps save time and produce better quality products (R4). The technological implementation also helps identify errors and improve product quality. For example, participant R11 said, *“Imagine that there are 60 steps that a pair of pants must go through to prepare for supply, but only five of those steps are challenging. By using this technique, we will then be able to quickly detect those issues.”* As mentioned above, new technology helps to develop quality products. Alternatively, new knowledge can be a way to learn new things for employees, which allows them to work innovatively. So, technological technology has a significant impact on innovation and learning perspectives.

Table 5.20: Technological innovation, Innovation & Learning perspective

Technological Innovation (Innovation & Learning Impact)	Participants	References
Technological Process	6	7
Technological Products	3	3
Technological Technology	7	8

Source: Primary Data

From the above Table 5.20, it is shown that only technological product innovation has less than fifty percent impact on innovation and learning perspective in business. However, the other two have almost fifty percent impact on innovation and learning perspectives. Hence, Technological innovation significantly impacts innovation and learning perspective in organisational performance.

Klepper (1996) defined that early technological development is motivated by the drive to meet market requirements. Participants explained that manually operated machine is time-consuming. However, the automatic process helps to save time (R1). Participants also defined that they work manually, but it would have been better to have an automated machine to save production time and cost (R3, R4). However, participants also defined that the technological process helps communicate faster among employees and customers (R12). Also, participants said that technological implementation helps make better-quality products (R14). Depending on the initial functionality and cost of the technology, the introduction of technology may lead to an early emphasis on enhancing the functionality of the technology to meet the demand requirements of users or on process technology to reduce the price to a level that corresponds to consumers' willingness to pay (R5, R13). Therefore, process innovation has an impact on the production process and business. Tarafdar and Gordon (2007) also explain that process innovation is related to the production process's improvement, efficiency, and effectiveness. Therefore, process innovation has a direct impact on the internal business perspective. According to Damanpour (2002) and Utterback (1994), product innovations are embodied in the outputs of an organisation and may result in product differentiation and market expansions. However, technological implementation in product innovation may influence the products in the market by changing components or features. Conversely, being related to the product, service innovation also increases effectiveness and quality of the organisational output by introducing new technological facilities for clients or customers (Damanpour *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, technological implementation in product innovation impacts the internal business perspective, as explained by: Participant defined that technology helps increase production volume. Hence technology can save time and cost. Participants said that an automatic machine takes to

complete the production by 7-8 days, but a nonautomated machine may take another 3-4 days extra (R2, R5, R6.a, R12). Technology can increase productivity. It also helps to utilize the goods properly for maximum output (R6.b). Participants defined that buyers also demand to use of specific technology to ensure the quality of products. Hence, the technologies impact cannot be avoided (R11). Following the above discussion, technological innovation in production has been identified, increasing the production volume of products and ensuring better quality products. However, a participant also criticised the technological gap in output negatively impacting product quality (R14). Hence from the above discussion, the conclusion can be made that technological product innovation significantly impacts organisational non-financial performance. Technological changes can impact the development of new initiatives, economic growth, level of employment, and social prosperity (Ahlstrom, 2010; Nelson, 1985). The following participants also acknowledged as a computerized machine helps the organisation to save time and cost. So, management can reduce the delay in delivery days (R1, R2, and R10). Participants acknowledged that technology is required to ensure better quality in the products cutting sector (R4, R9). In addition, participant R5 said that technology directly impacts business. Participant R6 noted that technology helps utilise the maximum amount of raw material to produce the products. Participants also defined that technology impacts supplying the products from one place to another in the factory (R6). Technology saves production costs, reduces the number of employees (R12) needed for production, and helps monitor the work progress (R13, R15). As acknowledged by participant R7, *“From completing through packing, loaders are used here, but the new facility can assist in reducing loader costs by using an autoloader machine, and it will also save us time.”* In addition, Participant R12 said, *“The job progression will be automatically reported to us via the RDIF system. By reviewing the report, we can closely monitor the work’s progress.”* Participant R14 defined technological implementation as strongly impacting product quality and a successful business. The above participants acknowledged that technology mainly effectively increases production volume and reduces time. As also explained, using technological processes, the organisation may save delayed delivery time to develop goodwill with the customers and improve organisational efficiency. Hence, from the primary and secondary data, it can be said that technology has a significant impact on the organisational internal business perspective.

Table 5.21: Technological innovation internal business perspective

Technological Innovation (Internal Business Impact)	Participants	References
Technological Process	12	20
Technological Products	9	12
Technological Technology	13	20

Source: Primary Data

Table 5.21 above shows that more than seventy percent (12 out of 15 participants) of participants said technological innovation strongly impacts the internal business perspective. Hence, Technological innovation significantly impacts on organisational nonfinancial performance. So, hypothesis H6 is accepted for the proposed model.

Evolving primary Conceptual model for Technological Innovation

Figure 5.5: Evolving Primary Conceptual model for Technological innovation

Source: Primary

The above Figure 5.5 shows that technological product innovation impacts internal business and financial perspectives but does not impact other innovation and customers aspect. Hence, technological products do not significantly impact customers' performance based on the primary

data in the Bangladesh garments industry. However, the technological product has a robust significant impact on financial and customers perspective (Zeng *et al.*, 2015). The technology substantially impacts the Bangladesh garments industry but not new innovative products. Most participants defined that they take orders from the buyers and make the products based on their demand. So, the organisation uses technology to develop the product's overall productive capacity. Hence, the technological product significantly impacts an internal business perspective. However, four participants acknowledged the impact of technological products from a financial perspective. Therefore, it can have a considerable impact. Process and technological technology equally impact organisational performance in financial and non-financial aspects. Thus, technological innovation significantly impacts organisational financial and non-financial performance. Therefore, hypotheses H5 and H6 are accepted for the proposed model.

5.4.1 Evolving Integrated Primary conceptual model for Administrative and Technological Innovation

As administrative and technological innovation shows their impact on both organisational financial and non-financial performance. Hence, considering both primary and secondary data, it can be said that Innovation substantially impacts organisational performance from both financial and nonfinancial perspectives. The administrative and technological conceptual models in Figures 5.4 and Figure 5.5 also show that they significantly impact organisational financial and non-financial performance. The below conceptual model for innovation (Figure 5.6) has developed, combining both primary conceptual models of administrative and technological aspects as defined above in Figure 5.4 and Figure 5.5.

Figure 5.6: Integrated Conceptual model for Innovation practices

The above innovation conceptual model (Figure 5.6) has developed, combining administrative and technological aspects of innovation elements. It was defined earlier that administrative and technological factors determine innovation. As both significantly impact organizational performance, innovation significantly impacts on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Therefore, hypotheses H5 and H6 are accepted for the proposed model.

5.5 Discussion Based on Objective Three: Relationship between TQM and Innovation

According to Imai (2007) and Oliver (2009), QM proponents believe in continuous improvement to simplify or streamline a process. To maintain control and stability, continuous learning emphasizes incremental change and necessitates standardisation or formalisation. This statement is in line with the few participants, such as R2, R4, R7, R8, R12, and R15, who defined that training helps us learn more about the work. Participants R1 and R15 described that group work is a way to reduce mistakes and learn accurate work. According to participants R1, R3, R12, R13, and R15, the following QM process helps minimize waste and variance. In addition, participants defined that waste and variance control directly save loss and bring a good reputation (R1, R3, R5, and R7). This statement is in line with the author Sadikohlu and Zehir (2010), the goal of process management strategies is to reject waste and increase efficiency. According to Oliver (2009), consumer focus is a source of creativity. Hence, TQM practices help to increase organisational innovativeness. So, from the above discussion, it can be said that TQM practices also influence innovation performance. Pfeifer *et al.* (1998) propose three important subject areas for innovation: customer-oriented and service, flexible organisational structures, and creative employees, all of which align with QM principles. Participant R13 said, *"We have the complaint department that meets with the staff monthly where personal ideas, problems, and suggestions can be shared between the groups."* Furthermore, Participant R2 said, *"If there is a problem in the workplace, we write it down in a diary and place that in the meetings. We value each opinion of employees."* Therefore, practicing people management in the organisation is essential, which is acknowledged by 13 participants out of 15 and 16 times they referenced the practicing of employee suggestion in their organisation. Employees may achieve new knowledge by involving with organisational quality improvement activities. They can see the benefit of the quality disciplines and achieve a sense of accomplishment by solving quality problems innovatively (Zhang *et al.*, 2000). Therefore, Quality management practices strongly impact innovation practices and organisational financial and non-financial performance. There are 14 participants who have been referred 20 times about innovation and learning perspectives on non-financial performance. The participants *R01, R02, R05, R07, R13, and R15*

mostly talked about the 'new ideas which come from employees' suggestions and lead to a successful business. According to Garud et al. (2013), innovation is the process through which individuals discover new ideas and gradually interact with others within an institutional framework to produce both drastic and gradual organisational success (Ali et al., 2010; Prajogo and Sohal, 2001; Bright and Cooper, 1993). For example, R01 said, *"The meeting contributes to generating new and innovative ideas. When customers want a new product, we promptly inform the employees so they may learn more about the work processes."* Similar statement made by R02, R05, R15, R07, and R13. Thus, the data can relate to the explanation of Feng (2006), and Feng et al. (2021) that employee participation is considered a vital asset in today's knowledge-based economy. Rahman (2002) said that employee involvement is a vital part of any TQM effort, and the MBNQA has emphasized the importance of human resources (Bowen and Lawler, 1992). Eight participants said that solving problems in a group has a non-financial impact on innovation and learning perspective in organisational performance. For instance participant R2 said, *"We frequently talk about the quality issues among our staff. The meeting helps to bring new innovative ideas"*. R10 said, *"group discussion helps to do things innovatively."* Sitting in a group, solving problems, or sharing ideas empowers the employees, which helps develop confidence among them (Ahire et al., 1996).

Furthermore, following the recording procedures of process management, the failure and success record helps the employee's learning capabilities and identify innovative ideas and ways to deal the matters (Perdomo-Ortiz et al., 200; Perdomo-Ortiz et al., 2009). Participants R3, R13, and R1 acknowledged the same as an example participant R1 said, *"We have a chart, and we note there which can help to identify the problems easily and which machine is creating the problem. If any problem identifies during production, our technician keeps helping them."* About 11 participants acknowledged the same as Perdome-Ortiz et al. (2009) defined in the above in this para. Hence, process management has an impact on innovation and learning perspectives. The quality management approach is to achieve continuous quality improvement and increase productivity. Knowledge sharing, learning, and innovativeness are part of continuous improvement (Lofsten, 2014; Lindelöf and Lofsten, 2004). Only 7 participants said that preventive maintenance has an impact on innovation and learning perspectives. For example, participant R5 said, *"That is what we do. There aren't many machines that can turn waste clothes into cotton. A mechanism exists that turns leftover cloth into cotton. The business needs fresh thinking."* Similarly, R7 and R10 also acknowledged the same. Teamwork, worker autonomy, and information transfer are important factors in supporting creativity defined by Molina et al.

(2007). The relationship between quality and innovation performance is also covered by opposing viewpoints, making the QM innovation relationship more ambiguous. The common wisdom has been that product innovation, and quality is mutually exclusive (Flynn *et al.*, 1994). As said by participant R1, *"We frequently talk about the quality issues among our staff. The meeting helps to bring new innovative ideas."* R10 said, *"Sometimes group discussion opens a new path to do the innovative work way."* And R2 said, *"Sometimes, we sat in a meeting to solve issues. I also sat with my employees and shared the ideas."* Solving problems in a group or sharing ideas empowers employees and develops confidence (Ahire *et al.*, 1996). Additionally, 13 participants defined that QM practices help the organisation be innovative on performance. R1, R2, R4, R5, and R6, defined that quality management practices increase employees' knowledge. It helps the employees to be creative. In responses to the direct questions about the relationship between organic TQM and mechanistic TQM impact on administrative and technological innovation, 13 out of 15 participants defined that both aspects of QM strongly impact administrative and technological innovation. Interestingly, it is defined by several participants, such as R3, R5, R7, R9, R10, R11, and R15, *"not only do quality management practices impact on innovation but also innovation practices help to ensure the quality."* As defined, administrative innovation practice is essential for business, but the organisation is not 100 % technologically oriented yet (R4, R5, R10, R15). Participants also noted that organisation must use software to do the jobs accurately (R9, R10, R13). Therefore, the above statement indicates that innovation practices are also important to ensure the quality for several aspects in the context of Bangladesh garments organisation. Mazzola and Perrone (2013) define enlightening product quality as closely tied to strategic requirements aimed at learning knowledge. Conversely, Prajogo and Sohal (2003) found a favourable association between QM and innovation success in Australian organisations. From a managerial standpoint, quality improvement, particularly in products, can be viewed as a means to meet strategic knowledge needs rather than as a means to meet the demands of efficiency and effectiveness. When a corporation wishes to boost productivity, it has long been recognised that process innovation is required (Martinez-Costa and Martinez-Lorente, 2008), emphasising a possible link between innovation and quality management. Reviewing the existing literature on the quality-innovation relationship in terms of quality management's hard and soft dimensions, the study of Zeng *et al.* (2015) found a significant relationship. A small number of studies look at the links between Quality Certification (ISO9000) and innovation, focusing primarily on the hard QIMs and innovation. According to Maistry *et al.* (2017), Technological innovation impacts on effectiveness which refers to embracing new technology and relates to production processes and products or

services, as well as service delivery which satisfies the mechanistic TQM elements (Prajogo, 2016). However, administrative innovation improves organisational performance, organisational structures, systems, and processes by implementing new working methodology which satisfies the organic TQM elements (Weerawardena 2003). Therefore, organic TQM elements are considered to measure administrative innovations. Conversely, to measure technological innovation, mechanistic TQM elements are considerable (Maistry *et al.*, 2017). However, from the above discussion, QM practices significantly impact organisational financial and non-financial performance. Hence, Mechanistic Quality management has a significant direct impact on Administrative and Technological innovation. Thus they are substantial in the result. So, hypotheses H9 and H10 are accepted for the proposed model. Similarly, Organic QM has a significant direct impact on Administrative and Technological innovation and is also significant in results. Hence, hypotheses H11 and H12 are accepted for the proposed model.

5.5.1 Evolving primary conceptual model between QM and innovation impact

The following evolving primary conceptual model Figure 5.7 was developed based on the discussion of objective three, where QM and Innovation both impact on organisational performance.

Figure 5.7: Primary conceptual framework between QM and Innovation impact

5.6 Evolving Conceptual Model by TQM and Innovation Outcomes to validate the initial conceptual Framework

The evolving conceptual model validates the initial conceptual framework. From the finding of the qualitative data in this section, the researcher has developed an evolving conceptual model, which is shown in Figure 5.8. The initial conceptual framework was formed after the literature

review based on the secondary information presented in chapter two (Figure 2.1). The evolving conceptual model has been considered with the previously developed conceptual model based on the hypothesis. Considering chapter seven's discussion above, the evolving primary conceptual model is used to test the final model. Figure 5.1 and Figure 5.2 are used to develop the primary conceptual model for organic and mechanistic QM impact on financial and non-financial performance, denoted as Figure 5.3. Similarly, Figure 5.4 and Figure 5.5 are used to create the primary conceptual model for administrative and technological innovation's impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance formed in Figure 5.6. Finally, followed by the 3rd objective, the evolving primary conceptual model Figure 5.7, is developed to find the relationship between quality management and innovation. Furthermore, the above three primary conceptual models, Figure 5.3, Figure 5.6, and Figure 5.7, are integrated as one final model, Figure 5.8, to test the pre-conceptual model followed by the hypothesis. Therefore, based on the chapter seven discussion, the following conceptual model has been drawn to test the pre-developed conceptual model, shown below in Figure 5.8.

Figure 5.8: Final model developed from Qualitative study

As shown in Figure 5.2, Hard QM has a significant impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Similarly, Figure 5.1 shows that soft QM significantly impacts organisational financial and non-financial performance. So, hypotheses H1, H2, H3, and H4 are significant in the context of qualitative primary data analysis. Similarly, the discussion can be made based on Figure 5.4 and Figure 5.5, technological innovation (H5, H6) and administrative innovation (H7, H8) have a significant impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry (Figure 5.6). Hence, H5, H6, H7, and H8 are accepted in the result for the final model. Furthermore, the primary conceptual Figure 5.7 showed that mechanistic and organic quality management significantly impacts both administrative and technological innovation. Therefore, H9, H10, H11, and H12 are significant in results and accepted for the final model (see Figure 5.7). Hence, all the primary developed hypotheses have tested significant results from the qualitative research outcomes. So, the final model, Figure 5.8, is the tested model developed from the qualitative results. In contrast, it is identified that not only the quality management impact on innovation but also innovation influences quality management practices to have the financial and nonfinancial impact on organization in the context of the Garments Industry of Bangladesh.

Chapter Six: Conclusion and Implication

6.1 Data results compared between qualitative and quantitative analysis

The mixed method concurrent triangulation is the chosen research method for this study. According to Tashakkori and Teddlie (2010), the mixed method concurrent triangulation research approach requires both qualitative and quantitative data to be collected and analysed separately. However, it is important to compare the data outcomes at the end. As a result, chapter six compares and discusses the qualitative and quantitative data results in light of three main research questions.

Question one: What is the impact of soft and hard TQM on organisational performance?

The outcomes from the quantitative study (see Table 4.33) brought out that the path between organic QM (OGQ) and financial performance (F) is not significant ($P\text{-value} = 0.204 > \alpha = 0.05$) in the model where the estimated value (0.066) between the factors reveals a lower than the marginal value 0.5. Similarly, the organic QM impact on non-financial performance did not reveal significance as $P\text{-value} = .573 > \alpha = 0.05$, and the estimated value (0.030) between the factors showed lower than the marginal value of 0.5. Hence, H3 and H4 are rejected, which means that organic quality management does not directly impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. However, Powell (1995) found soft quality elements such as top management commitment, open organisation, and staff empowerment strongly connected with overall business performance. Therefore, the qualitative study was discussed following the balanced scorecard approach (See Table 6.1 in Appendix 10) with the financial and non-financial context.

Table 6.1 (See Table 6.1 in Appendix 10) shows that eight participants out of 15, which means more than 50% acknowledged the financial impact of management leadership on business performance nine times. The 15 participants acknowledged 45 times on organisational performance, and nine specifically discussed top management's impact on financial performance. However, almost 55% (8 out of 15) of participants acknowledge that top management directly impacts on organisational financial performance. Conversely, in the non-financial perspective, 15 participants out of 15 (100%) acknowledged 36 times about the top management's impact on the non-financial perspective on organisational performance. Among the measurement variables of the non-financial perspectives, 13 participants talked about the

impact of the internal business perspective, 9 spoke about innovation and learning, and 8 acknowledged the customer's perspective. Therefore, more than 50% of all non-financial measurement scales are individually impacted by management leadership. In comparison, an internal business perspective has been used to evaluate almost 90% (13 out of 15 participants) of the performance impact on the organization's non-financial standpoint (see Table 6.1 in Appendix 10). Hence, from the qualitative results, hypotheses H3 and H4 for organic aspects support the statements that organic and mechanistic QM has a significant positive impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Furthermore, participants R2, R3, R5, R7, R9, R10, R11, and R12 have simultaneously acknowledged the top management impact on organisational financial and non-financial perspectives. However, R1, R4, R6, R8, R13, R14, and R15 have only acknowledged the top management impact on non-financial perspectives. Therefore, based on the analysis of this primary data, it can be said that top management has a 47% greater impact on the aspect of organisational non-financial performance (15 responses out of 15 = 100%) than on financial performance (8 responses out of 15 = 53%).

Nine participants mentioned the financial impact of supplier quality management on organisational performance. However, 14 out of 15 participants mentioned the significant impact on non-financial performance. The customer's perspective and 'innovation and learning' perspective of non-financial performance have been acknowledged by 4 participants (see Table 6.1 in Appendix 10). However, 14 participants noted that the internal business perspective significantly impacts organisational non-financial performance. Therefore, supplier quality management has the highest impact on the internal business perspective than the customers and innovation perspective. Similarly, customer relationship and group problem-solving impact on financial performance, which is mentioned by 8 and 5 participants, respectively, but these elements strongly impact non-financial performance. A few participants (3 and 2 participants, respectively) have spoken about social responsibility and employee suggestions about how it affects financial success. They may, however, have a potential impact on nonfinancial performance. Hence, the data results show that all elements of organic quality management strongly impact on organisational non-financial performance. Though, social responsibility, employee suggestion, and task-related training do not have any potential impact on financial performance. Dow *et al.* (1999) defined that out of a total of nine criteria, only the three elements, such as staff commitment, shared vision, and customer focus, had a significant positive correlation with quality and performance, based on the research outcome of the Australian manufacturing organisation. Ahire *et al.* (1996) observed that in the context of American

automobile manufacturing and component firms, performance (in terms of product quality) was strongly correlated with soft TQM features, such as staff empowerment, employee training, and employee involvement. It should be emphasised that researchers carried out their work by comparing different sets of indicators. Dow *et al.* (1999) and Ahire *et al.* (1996) have used relatively narrow quality-focused concepts of performance, whereas Powell (1995) included a variety of specific TQM performance indicators. As a result, the selection of indicators influences each aspect of quality management as well as whether the construct has an impact on organisational performance. Rahman (2005) found that five out of six organic TQM elements positively correlate with organisational financial and non-financial performance. Employee commitment, shared vision, customer focus, teamwork, and cooperative supplier relationships are among them. Although these findings are in line with the findings of Powell (1995) and Dow *et al.* (1999), neither Powell (1995) nor Dow *et al.* (1999) found a significant link between cooperative supplier relationships and performance. Therefore, the output may be context-dependent. Therefore, Rahman (2005) explained that supplier relationships might be more important for manufacturing companies than service companies. The garments industry in Bangladesh is manufacturing-oriented and provides services to buyers. In this research, four elements (top management leadership, employee suggestions, problem-solving, and task-related training) of soft TQM are used for quantitative analysis to test the impact on financial and non-financial performance but did not find any significant impact on financial and non-financial performance in the context of Bangladesh garments industry. However, a previous study shows that TQM is driven by senior management, and managerial commitment must be converted into particular plans. Companies may improve their organisational performance by incorporating quality into their products and services, ensuring process quality through defect prevention methods and control tools, and judiciously utilising quality information such as customer feedback, benchmarking, and charts (Ahire *et al.*, 1996). To successfully implement performance-enhancing strategies, organisations must be customer-focused, maintain capability, maintain reliable and flexible suppliers, and foster employee involvement in decision-making through training and empowerment (Ahire *et al.*, 1996). Although the qualitative primary data results indicate that soft QM has a significant impact on both financial and non-financial performance, the results of the primary quantitative data raise some doubts as to why soft TQM has no discernible effect on organisational performance in the Bangladesh garment industry. It is further defined by Powell (1995) that successful organisations use a mix of hard and soft TQM rules to respond to changing consumer demands. On the other hand, underperforming businesses view technology as a means of improving operational outcomes rather than customer

satisfaction. Rahman (2005) also found that soft QM positively affects organisational performance through hard quality management. Therefore, considering the above discussion, the indirect effects of soft quality management via hard QM were tested. The result found that soft quality management significantly impacts on organisational financial and non-financial performance via mechanistic quality management. The quantitative result showed significance with p values of 0.05 and 0.011 for non-financial and financial aspects, respectively (see Table 6.9 in Appendix 8). So, hypotheses H3 and H4 indirectly impact organisational financial and non-financial performance, respectively. Therefore, significant differences have been identified between qualitative and quantitative analysis, such as:

The number of soft quality management elements used in the quantitative analysis was four, including employee suggestions, top management leadership, problem-solving, and task-related training, which were employed in the quantitative analysis as a limit for statistical calculation. The outputs defined that soft QM has no significant direct impact on both organisational financial and non-financial performance, which means H3 is rejected for the proposed model. But soft QM mediates Hard QM to impact financial and non-financial performance significantly. However, qualitative analysis brought out that soft quality management has a substantial direct impact on both financial (H3) and non-financial (H4) performance, where the measurement elements covered four extra more measurement scales, such as supplier QM, customer relationship, social responsibility, and political-cultural context, besides the other four used for quantitative analysis (top management leadership, employee suggestions, problem-solving, and task-related training). Political culture has emerged from the participants' interviews as a new element in the soft quality management philosophy. Therefore, qualitative analysis accepts hypotheses H3 and H4 for the proposed model, but quantitative analysis rejects the hypotheses, which differs between the qualitative and quantitative analysis in this research outcomes. Thus, an independent framework developed by both quantitative and qualitative results on organic and mechanistic aspects of quality management impacts on the performance of the Bangladesh garments industry.

The output shows that the path between Mechanistic QM (MCQ) and financial performance (F) is significant where $P\text{-value} = 0.00 < \alpha = 0.05$ in the model with the estimated value (0.347) between the factor reveals higher than the marginal value 0.5. It can be said that mechanistic quality management directly impacts an organisational financial performance (See Table 6.8 in Appendix 8). So, hypothesis H1 did support the proposed model. Similarly, the mechanistic QM impact on non-financial performance also revealed significance as $P\text{-value} = 0.003 < \alpha = 0.05$

and estimated value (0.154) between the factors, which is higher than the marginal value 0.5. Hence, H2 is accepted, which means mechanistic quality management directly impacts organisational non-financial performance. Thus, hypotheses H1 and H2 both support the proposed model through its quantitative results. Therefore, the elements of mechanistic TQM in this research, such as strategic quality planning, process management, housekeeping, and quality information, directly impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. So, practicing mechanistic TQM in the organisation influences organisational financial and non-financial performance. In addition, the results of mechanistic TQM practices brought out a significant direct impact on financial and non-financial performance but contradicted the previous result of Powell (1995), Dow *et al.* (1999), and Samson and Terziovski (1999), who showed that there is no significant link between hard TQM aspects and organisational performance. Dow *et al.* (1999) stated that the restrictive concepts of organisational performance caused non-significant connections between hard TQM and performance and advised that productivity and flexibility should be incorporated into more extensive concepts of performance. Data results in Table 6.2 (see Table 6.2 in Appendix 10) shows the participant's responses to the hard QM element's impact on business performance is more than 50 % for each aspect. So, all the six hard QM factors in the Bangladesh garments sector are strongly related to organisational financial and non-financial performance. It is noted that the following four elements (strategic quality planning, process management, housekeeping, and quality information) were used in quantitative analysis to identify its impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. It is found that preventive maintenance and housekeeping are strongly correlated with the organisation's financial perspective. On the other hand, preventative maintenance and benchmarking have a low loading value and displacement sequence in the EFA stage. Hence, due to low loading values and displacement sequence in EFA, preventative maintenance and benchmarking were deducted from the CFA stages from the quantitative analysis.

Moreover, the qualitative analysis found that preventive maintenance and benchmarking strongly impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Similarly, mechanistic TQM practices brought out a significant direct impact on financial (H1) and non-financial (H2) performance, which means hypotheses H1 and H2 are accepted for the proposed models by both qualitative and quantitative results. Although the overall number of variables in the qualitative and quantitative analyses varied, they significantly impacted on the organisation's financial and non-financial performance. Conversely, this outcome is in contrast with other findings by Powell (1995), Dow *et al.* (1999), and Samson and Terziovski (1999), which indicated

that there is no significant link between hard TQM features and organisational success. According to Dow *et al.* (1999), a more thorough concept of organisational performance should include with its flexibility and productivity to avoid the non-significant correlations between hard TQM and performance. However, Rahman (2005) and Zeng *et al.* (2015) found a significant direct impact of mechanistic TQM on organisational financial and non-financial performance. In line with the findings of Rahman (2005) and Zeng *et al.* (2015), this study reveals mechanistic QM fit with the proposed theoretical model in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry. So, Hypothesis H1 (hard QM impacts on organisational financial performance) and H2 (hard QM impacts on organisational non-financial performance) are accepted for the proposed model. Therefore, from the above discussion, it can be concluded that mechanistic QM significantly impacts on organisational financial (H1) and non-financial (H) performance in terms of both qualitative and quantitative results. However, in the organic aspect, the results differ. The qualitative study finds that organic QM strongly impacts organisational financial (H3) and non-financial (H4) performance, which means H3 and H4 are accepted for the proposed model. Conversely, in quantitative results, organic quality management mediates mechanistic QM to impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance, which differs between the results. So, two independent models are developed by qualitative and quantitative research outcomes.

Question Two: what is the impact of innovation on organisational performance?

The quantitative outcomes by the path analysis between administrative innovation (AD) and financial performance (F) are shown not significant where P-value = 0.947 > α = 0.05, and for non-financial, p-value = 0.858 > α = 0.05 in the model (see Table 4.30). Therefore, administrative innovation does not directly impact on organisational financial (H7) and non-financial (H8) performance. Similarly, the direct impact of technological innovation practices on the organisational financial performance (H5) is not significant as the P value = 0.977, but in the non-financial (H6) context, technological innovation practices have a significant direct impact on the performance of Bangladesh garments industry where the P-value = 0.00 < α = 0.05 (see Table 4.30). So, the quantitative development shows that only technological innovation significantly impacts on organisational non-financial performance (H6). So, hypothesis H6 is accepted, but the quantitative results for the proposed model reject H5, H7, and H8.

In qualitative results, Table 6.3 (see Table 6.3 in Appendix 10) shows that marketing innovation has the highest impact on financial performance among the three financial measurement scales. Simultaneously, the qualitative analysis showed a strong positive impact of administrative and technological innovation on organisational financial and non-financial performance. In the context of non-financial performance, all three measurement scales equally impact on the organisational internal business perspective. Conversely, administrative innovation has less impact on customers' perspectives, with an average of five participants saying that administrative innovation has a positive impact on customers' perspectives on organisational non-financial performance. Hence, it can be said that administrative innovation has a strong financial (H7) and non-financial (H8) impact on organisational performance. The following participants, R2, R7, and R11, acknowledged strategic negotiation with buyers and suppliers brings economic benefit to the business. The participant noted that waste management in an innovative way helps the organisation to save finance by recycling the waste (R11). However, Participant R15 said, *"Employee protest (strike) against the company results in a delay in product delivery to buyers, which eventually results in a delay in delivery, lost sales, and the need to ship by expensive cargo."* Again, participant R15 noted that foreign direct investment could be innovative ideas, but limited finance and unknown foreign business policy are barriers for the organisation. But, FDI can be a profitable strategy for the organisation. Similarly, R1, R4, R5, R9, R12, R13, and R14 also agreed that administrative innovation practices impact on organisational financial performance (H7). Almost all participants defined that administrative innovation strongly impacts on non-financial performance (H8). The following are some of the ways that participants have addressed how new ideas impact innovation and learning in the workplace: new ideas bring new processes to the organisation (R1). Even new idea helps to resolve problems when employees confront them in the workplace (R2, R4, R5, R6, and R7). A participant acknowledges that new ideas can come from any employee, which impacts on business. For instance, participant R13 said, *"Ideas can come from any position, including floor employees. We can benefit from new information. It could be a strategy for accepting and practicing innovation in the organisation."* Similarly, the rest of the participants also noted its importance on non-financial organisational performance. Administrative innovation is adopting new working methods to increase organisational performance, structures, systems, and processes (Weerawardena, 2003). Chuang *et al.* (2010) and Maistry *et al.* (2017) used three meaningful subscales to measure administrative innovation those are namely, internal organisational innovation, marketing innovation, and strategic innovation. Administrative and technological innovations indicate potentially diverse decision-making processes, and they collectively represent changes in a wide

variety of operations in an organisation (Daft, 1978). Therefore, the elements of administrative innovation, such as internal organisational, marketing, and strategic innovation, do not directly impact on the organisational financial and non-financial performance.

In qualitative findings, technological innovation practices have a strong impact on the financial (H5) and non-financial (H6) performance of organisations, where participants emphasise on the non-financial perspective more than the financial aspect. On average, more than 70% (average 11 out of 15 participants) of participants indicated that technological innovation had a significant impact on non-financial (H6) perspectives across all measurement scales (see Table 6.4 in Appendix 10). Hence, Technological innovation significantly impacts on organisational financial (H5) and non-financial (H6) performance, which means hypotheses H5 and H6 are accepted for the proposed model by its qualitative results. Data results in Table 6.4 shows that technological product only impacts the internal business perspective but does not substantially impact the other three aspects. Hence, technological product innovation does not significantly impact on organisational performance in the Bangladesh garments industry. In line with the findings, researchers such as Acheson and Ferris (1990) and Han *et al.* (1998) noted that administrative and technological innovation are both important for organisational financial and non-financial performance. Innovation's increasingly hostile market environment works for market growth and acts for survival (Han *et al.*, 1998). Technology-related advances in management, products, and processes have been linked to improved organisational success (Parnaby, 1991; Bamberger *et al.*, 1989; Livingston and Berkes, 1989). In addition, several studies have found a relationship between R&D and sales growth (Franko, 1989; Lengnick-Hall, 1991); productivity growth (e.g., Chakrabarti, 1990; Chakrabarti and Halperin, 1990); and development of profitability (Moreby and Reithner, 1990) enhanced after the adaptation of both administrative and technological innovation. The clothing production in the garment industry in Bangladesh is considerably impacted by technology but not the development of new and innovative items. The majority of participants explained that they use technology to increase the organisation's capacity for production by taking orders from customers and manufacturing products in response to their needs (R1, R2, R3, R4, R7, R9, R10, R12, R13, R14, and R15). Hence, 'technological product innovation' significantly impacts on the organisational internal business perspective. However, four participants acknowledged about the impact of technological product innovation on the organisational financial perspective. The impact of 'technological process innovation' and 'technological technology innovation' on organisational finance aspects was also acknowledged by participants 8 and 11, respectively. Thus, it can be said that all measurement scales, including

those for process, product, and technological innovation, have an identical impact on the performance of organisations in both financial (H5) and non-financial (H6) aspects. Hence, Technological innovation significantly impacts organisational financial and non-financial performance, which means hypothesis H5 and H6 supports the proposed model. In contrast, the quantitative findings led to the question of why, in the case of the Bangladesh garment industry, administrative innovation had no direct impact on either financial and non-financial performance or technological innovation of financial performance. The previous studies showed that the proper use of technological resources contributes to developing a long-term competitive edge that improves a company's financial performance (Hambrick *et al.*, 1983; Kalish and Lillien, 1986; Porter, 2008; Schroeder, 1990). Hence, to determine the relationship between TQM and Innovation based on organisational performance, quantitative data analysis was used to test for an indirect influence of technological innovation on financial performance as well as an indirect impact of administrative innovation on organisational financial and non-financial performance, which is discussed below.

Objective 3: what is the relationship between TQM and innovation on organisational performance?

Outcomes from the quantitative regression analysis showed that organic quality management did not significantly impact on both administrative (H11) and technological (H12) innovation as the P-values = .961 and .528, respectively. Similarly, with the P-value of 0.190, mechanistic QM did not directly impact on technological (H10) innovation. However, mechanistic QM significantly impacted on administrative (H9) innovation with the P-value = 0.003 < α = 0.05 (See Table 6.10 in Appendix 8). The results showed that mechanistic QM practices directly influence administrative innovation practices (H9) in the Bangladesh garments industry. Hence, by the quantitative result, hypotheses H10, H11, and H12 do not support the proposed model, but H9 is accepted for the proposed model. So, practicing mechanistic QM in the organisation is ultimately practicing the administrative innovation process. Similarly, it can be said that the elements of mechanistic TQM in this research, such as strategic quality planning, process management, housekeeping, and quality information, significantly enhance the performance of administrative innovation elements, including internal organisational, marketing, and strategic innovation. These findings align with the outcomes proposed by Kim *et al.* (2012), where the researcher found that only hard QM (role of process management) supported a significant impact on innovation. While some studies, such as Prajogo and Sohal (2003), Feng *et al.* (2006) claimed that only soft dimensions (leadership and people management) could foster innovation. However, qualitative results show that both soft and hard QM influence administrative and

technological innovation practices, and their performance strongly impacts on organisational financial and non-financial perspectives. For instance, participant R2 said, *“Implementing quality management practices within the organisation is quite innovative and fosters the growth of the business.”* Participants R3, R5, R6, R7, R9, R12, R13, and R15 all responded similarly in this way. Over ten participants discovered that quality management procedures are innovative, meaning that both soft and hard quality management practices drive innovation practices and impact on organisational performance. Hence, from the above participant's view, the qualitative results show that mechanistic QM significantly impacts administrative (H9) and technological (H10) innovation performance. Similarly, organic or soft QM practice significantly impacts on administrative (H11) and technological (H12) innovation performance. Thus, hypotheses H9, H10, H11, and H12 are accepted by the qualitative researcher outcome for the proposed model. Thus, these findings align with the outcomes claimed by Perdomo-Ortiz *et al.* (2006), hard and soft dimensions (e.g., process management and human resource management) are important in developing innovation. The study found that hard QM has a significant direct impact on administrative innovation, but neither soft nor hard quality management practices mediate administrative and technological innovation on organisational financial and non-financial performance. However, participants such as R1, R4, R5, R11, R13, and R14 said that innovation practices impact on quality management practices and organisational performance. For example, participant R11 said, *“Independent innovation practices impact on quality management as well. Suppose technology helps ensure the quality of products and increase production flow.”* A nearly identical statement was made by participant R1, who said, *“Using software in the administrative job is very innovative and helps to ensure the quality work in the organisation.”* Therefore, qualitative findings defined that quality management and innovation both impact each other. So, they together impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Based on these issues, the research alternatively opened the option to justify the impact of innovation practices on TQM. In order to justify the qualitative result with the quantitative path analysis, an alternate path model was developed in quantitative analysis. The new model was created following the impact of the innovations on quality management. The following fit analysis (see Figure 6.1 in appendix 10) shows the statistical components of $X^2 = 2.398$, $df = 2$, $X^2/df = 1.199$, GFI = 0.998, AGFI = 0.976, CFI = 0.996, NFI = 0.977, PCLOSE = 0.564, and RMSEA = 0.024. The index X^2/df ratio, which is below the threshold level of 3, indicates a good model fit (Bentler, 1980). RMSEA is another fit statistic that adjusts the sample discrepancy function by degrees of freedom. Therefore, the overall composite scale indicator model (see Figure 6.1 in Appendix 10) demonstrates a good fit from these fit statistics.

The regression Table 6.5 (See Appendix 9) shows that technological innovation has a significant direct impact on non-financial performance and administrative innovation has a significant direct impact on mechanistic QM performance. Remain results are almost the same compared with the first model. However, the mediating effect is shown in Table 6.6 (see appendix 9) that administrative innovation mediates mechanistic quality management significantly impacts on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Conversely, technological innovation does not mediate TQM to impact organisational performance significantly. Based on the regression analysis (see Table 6.6 in Appendix 9), the P scores showed that organic and mechanistic QM does not mediate between technological innovation and organisational financial and non-financial performance. Also, organic QM does not mediate between administrative innovation and organisational financial and non-financial performance. Conversely, QMC (mechanistic QM) acts as a significant mediator between administrative innovation (AD) and organisational performance in terms of both financial (AD --> QMC --> F) and non-financial (AD --> QMC --> NF) aspects. In addition, it is identified by the Z test that administrative innovation (AD) practices have a mediating effect through Mechanistic quality management (QMC) on organisational Non-financial (NF) and financial (F) performance (see calculation in Appendix 3). However, it was noted that quality management practices do not individually mediate innovation practices to have a significant impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Conversely, researchers such as Prajogo and Sohal (2003), also Feng et al. (2006) claimed that only soft dimensions (leadership and people management) could foster innovation. In contrast, Perdomo-Ortiz *et al.* (2006) argue that hard and soft dimensions (e.g., process management and human resource management) are important in developing innovation. The study found that hard QM has a significant direct impact on administrative innovation, but neither soft nor hard quality management practices mediate administrative and technological innovation on organisational financial and non-financial performance. These findings support those of Kim *et al.* (2012), emphasising the importance of hard QM in innovation and the role of soft QM as a compliment. The findings show that hard QM is essential in determining the administrative innovation process. Hard QM can influence administrative innovation directly and indirectly through the combined effect of organic and mechanistic QM, which has a significant indirect impact (See Table 6.7 in Appendix 9) on financial and non-financial performance in the Bangladesh garments industry. Thus, this study's outcomes differ from others, verifying the correlation between QM and innovation in the regional context.

These findings are consistent with the literature that hard QM assists the organisation in restoring discipline and bringing the system under control through variance reduction. When the system is stable, and under control, it is possible to learn how to improve it, resulting in the development of a learning foundation (Spencer, 1994). A set of routines established through the implementation of hard QM can support innovation activities because routine-based organisations pay more attention to vital processes and avoid activities that do not add value (Hoang et al., 2006). Therefore, though the organic QM does not directly impact innovation, its combined effort with mechanistic QM mediates administrative innovation on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Hence, the cumulating impact of organic TQM elements (management commitment, employee suggestion, problem-solving, and task-related training) and mechanistic TQM elements (strategic quality planning, process management, housekeeping, and quality information) enhance the organisational financial and non-financial performance indirectly. According to Prajogo and Sohal (2001), TQM and innovation share many similarities. They both formed as partial responses to the intense competitive pressures that manufacturers are experiencing. In some cases, TQM and innovation share similar characteristics, as both aspects emphasize continuous improvement. In addition, organic culture is viewed as a key component of TQM and innovation as well. These similarities suggest that organisations that effectively apply TQM may also be more innovative than those do not. If this assumption is correct, it concludes that TQM can be a vehicle for organizations to become more creative. However, Singh and Smith (2004) reveal that the empirical data does not fit the proposed model entirely. Therefore, the relationship between TQM and innovation due to its impact on organisational performance is still contradictory based on the organisation's structure, size, types, and researcher's data collection strategy.

6.2 Contribution of Research

Business is one of the fundamental facts for the economic development of any country. Generally, manufacturing organization plays a vital role in developing the economy as it was mentioned earlier that 78% of export earnings for Bangladesh are carried by the RMG sector (Seddiqe and Basak, 2014). TQM was introduced and practiced before as a quality management tool in developed countries. Business competition among organizations is rising because of technological advancement and innovation practices. Therefore, due to technological advancement, Bangladesh is getting in touch with globalised business competition. Organisations are more aware of how to cope with global competition. In addition, the concept of TQM and innovation practices are not being practiced thoroughly for sustainable business

development (Mamun and Islam, 2002). It is argued by Denzin and Lincoln (2008) that the researcher's investigation of different themes in several contexts provides new perspectives, which is effective for enriching knowledge and understanding a particular phenomenon. Therefore, it is evident that different contexts are examined to understand more in-depth details of any topics by the researcher since the findings vary with settings. Based on this discussion, the researcher aims to contribute to the knowledge of TQM and innovation's impact on the business performance of the Bangladesh Garments industry. The relationship between TQM and innovation is examined in that context. This is one of the newest research projects to examine and identify TQM and innovation's impact and their relationship on organisational performance in the RMG industry of Bangladesh. Therefore, the findings of this research are novel and valuable to cover the research gaps identified by the literature review marked as theoretical, empirical, and methodological.

Contribution to theory

The research outcomes theoretically offer new insights with rich information about TQM and innovation performance on business and their relationship. The geographical location and context of the industry will add additional value to this research besides its dimension of developing economy. The study is conducted in the context of the Bangladesh Garments industry as a similar study has not been done before. However, a part of the impact of TQM practicing in RMG has been worked out by the following researchers Absar and Mahmood (2011), Akhter (2014), Akter *et al.* (2015), Goldstein *et al.* (2017), Haque *et al.* (2011), Huda *et al.* (2007), Islam and Shazali (2011), Mamun and Islam (2002), Mitaa *et al.* (2014), Rahman and Masud (2011), Syduzzaman *et al.* (2016), Syduzzaman *et al.* (2014), Uddin *et al.* (2014), and Yunus and Yamagata (2012). However, none of the research has been carried out on innovation or the relationship between TQM and innovation in the context of the Bangladesh RMG industry. According to Wright *et al.* (2005), developing economies are fertile grounds for testing the existing theory. It could modify the existing theory and develop richer ones. Therefore, the significance of this study demands special consideration due to the reality of the different economies and the industrial research context. Additionally, this research identified the TQM impact on innovation and organisational performance, it also identified the innovation practices impact on TQM and organisational performance. Interestingly, innovation does not mediate between TQM and organisational performance to significantly impact both financial and non-financial perspectives. However, TQM worked as a mediator between innovation and organisational performance to have a significant impact on financial and non-financial aspects.

Therefore, this research has a unique contribution to the theory of both TQM and innovation practicing impact and their relationship to them on organisational performance.

The outcomes from the qualitative study remind that practicing TQM and innovation in the context of a developed country and a developing country (such as Bangladesh) have differences based on management process, regional social, and 'political and cultural' aspects. This is acknowledged that some organizations do not welcome employee engagement. For example, participant *R11* said, *"We usually do not take employees' opinions or collect information from them."* Also, *R12* and *R05* acknowledged the same. But it is noted that employee participation is considered a vital asset in today's knowledge-based economy, so employee engagement positively impacts on the business (Feng, 2006; Feng *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, Rahman (2002) defined employee involvement is an essential part of any TQM effort, and the MBNQA has highlighted the significance of human resources (Bowen and Lawler, 1992).

It is also mentioned that the Bangladeshi organisation should consider the impact of 'political cultural' on organisational performance. Participants defined that political culture in the context of Bangladesh negatively impacts on business. For instance, participant *R9* said, *"Employee's movement against the management causes financial loss. It affects the company, and of course, the effect is negative for business."* *R13* said, *"If the third-party investigation yields unfavourable findings and is marked as failing by audit, we are required to halt operations for a predetermined period of time, which undermines the organization's reputation and costs money."* Also, *R12* and *R14* said, *"We have a team that tackles critical business issues. Only accurate information can enable us to understand the facts and act appropriately to attain success in business."* Therefore, the findings of this research suggest that the political culture, management leadership, social responsibilities, and employee engagement may add extra theoretical richness to the TQM measurement scales in the context of a developing economy.

Empirical and contextual contribution

As mentioned earlier, the researchers have worked out the impact of TQM practices on organisational performance. However, no research has been carried out on TQM and innovation practices and their relationship to business performance in the context of the Bangladesh RMG organisation. Additionally, research on the global context of the specific clothing sector has not been done. Therefore, the research results will add to the body of knowledge regarding TQM and innovation practices in addition to those of earlier studies conducted by Antunes *et al.* (2017),

Choi and Eboch (1998), Fernandes *et al.* (2014), Goldstein *et al.* (2017), Jung and Wang (2006), Maistry *et al.* (2017), McAdam *et al.* (1998), Molina (2007), Ooi *et al.* (2012), Pinho (2008), Prajogo (2016), Prajogo and Hong (2008), Prajogo and Sohal (2003), Prajogo and Sohal (2004), Rovira Nordman and Tolstoy (2011), Sila (2007), Singh and Smith (2004), Terziovski and Samson (1999), and Zeng *et al.* (2015). Therefore, based on the points made by Saunders *et al.* (2012), replicability does not undermine the richness of the research. Hence the study looks to reflect the reality at this point in time.

In the previous chapter, it was mentioned that several researchers had been carried out to identify the relationship between TQM and innovation in the context of developed countries by Fernandes *et al.* (2014), Goldstein *et al.* (2017), Molina *et al.* (2007), Ooi *et al.* (2012), Pinho (2008), Prajogo (2016), Prajogo and Hong (2008), Sila (2007), and Zeng *et al.* (2015). However, no substantial research has been carried out to examine the TQM and innovation practices and their relationship with business performance in the context of the Bangladesh RMG industry. In contrast, studies on the effects of TQM have been conducted by Akhter (2014), Akter *et al.* (2015), Goldstein *et al.* (2017), Huda *et al.* (2007), Yunus and Yamagata (2012), and Syduzzaman *et al.* (2016). However, the research did not take a multidimensional approach to identify the effects of TQM and innovation on organisational performance. In addition, the studies did not pinpoint how TQM and innovation are related due to organisational performance. As defined, developing economies are fertile grounds for testing existing theories and developing newer ones (Wright *et al.*, 2005). Therefore, the geographical location and this research on specific garments industries in developing economies added extra empirical value to this research area.

Similarly, as research has not been thoroughly carried out in the context of Bangladesh, also substantial similar studies have not been found in the context of garments industries globally, but previous studies on different contexts globally undertaken on TQM practices and organisational performance those report a mixed and ambiguous relationship (Anil and Satish, 2016; Jung and Wang, 2006; Zeng *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, there is insufficient theoretical and conceptual knowledge in this context, and this research output extends this domain's growing knowledge. Following the quantitative findings, this study concluded that organic quality management (QM) does not directly affect organizational performance but uses mechanistic QM as a conduit to impact on financial and non-financial performance. In addition, qualitative analysis defined that organic and mechanistic QM independently impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Furthermore, this research may add extra conceptual knowledge on

an organic aspect of TQM, such as political culture, employee engagement, and leadership in the developing economy. For instance, participant R13 noted, *“I am really fed up with the political matter. We have a real gap in the political field. If we can sort out the political issues, the delay delivery days can be reduced to 30 from 90 days.”* Also, R14 said, *“We have a team that deals with critical and political issues. Only accurate information can help us understand the facts and work accordingly for business success.”* In the same manner, participant R15 also defined that political issues cause delayed delivery of products to the buyers. Therefore, these research findings might be helpful to resolve that crucial management and political challenges in the context of organic quality management. Simultaneously, this research on the multidimensionality of TQM elements and innovation performance fills a gap in the existing literature and enables decision-makers to increase innovation performance levels in the manufacturing sector. So, this research outcome might fill this context's insufficient theoretical and conceptual knowledge, and the output extends this field's growing knowledge.

Methodological contribution

To carry out this research, the researcher did not literally identify common articles where analysis was carried out under the mixed method concurrent triangulation following qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis separately and independently to examine the impact of TQM and innovation on organisational performance. In the field of TQM and innovation, maximum researchers have used quantitative mono-method for data collection and analysis process in order to bring the research output. For instance, research carried out in this context by Anil and Satish (2016), Antunes *et al.* (2017), Choi and Eboch (1998), Fernandes, Lourenço and Silva (2014), Goldstein *et al.* (2017), Jung and Wang (2006), Maistry *et al.* (2017), McAdam *et al.* (1998), Molina *et al.* (2007), Ooi *et al.* (2012), Pinho (2008), Prajogo (2016), Prajogo and Hong (2008), Prajogo and Sohal (2003), Prajogo and Sohal (2004), Rovira Nordman and Tolstoy (2011), Sila (2007), Singh and Smith (2004), Terziovski and Samson (1999), and Zeng *et al.* (2015) have used mono method quantitative data collection and analysis process to reach to the results. Therefore, there was a gap in this area to explore a pragmatic phenomenon using mixed methods of concurrent triangulation. The primary data collection was conducted by quantitative survey and qualitative semi-structured interviews and analysed independently. The qualitative findings indicated a strong influence of both soft and hard QM on administrative and technological innovation practices on the financial and non-financial performance of the organisation. However, the quantitative data outcome differs from the qualitative outcome. It is shown that organic TQM does not directly impact on innovation and organisational performance,

but organic TQM mediates mechanistic QM practices to significantly impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance. So, two different models have developed from two independent methods. The results of this research, therefore, vary depending on methodological variances. In light of this, the mixed methods concurrent triangulation strategy might add extra value to enhance models, theories, organisation, and the literature around this research domain.

Managerial Implication

This study's findings have significant consequences for the Bangladesh garments organisation. Organization managers should be aware of the critical role that hard and soft TQM practices and innovation practices play in improving organisational financial and non-financial performance. Managers who are actively involved in quality initiatives and projects, resource allocation, production, HRM, and supply chain obstacle reduction may enable the adoption and acceptance of the TQM and innovation concept to make the business competitive. The garment sector depends on effective communication with foreign buyers. In addition, this sector also faces significant external stakeholders' pressure for violating issues, such as quality, health and safety, and corporate social responsibility. Hence, having a well-trained TQM and innovation practice-oriented team may significantly influence organisational financial and non-financial performance. Despite the fact brought out by quantitative results that soft TQM did not have any significant direct impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance than hard TQM, but managers should not avoid or underestimate the value of the soft TQM techniques as soft TQM mediated hard TQM elements to have an indirect impact on organisational performance. Conversely, qualitative data outcomes brought out that soft and hard TQM both have a significant direct impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance.

A few of the previous quantitative studies have shown that hard TQM practices directly impact on organisational performance, but soft TQM does not. Conversely, few studies have found that soft and hard TQM practices significantly impact organisational performance. Though the previous studies have also shown a mixed and ambiguous relationship between hard and soft TQM practices and their impact on organisational performance, this study has found a positive direct impact on organisational financial and nonfinancial performance and a positive relationship between soft and hard TQM as they combinedly influence organisational performance. Thus, the managers must create a balance between soft and hard elements practices in the organisation.

Based on the quantitative outcome of this study, garment industries in Bangladesh have concentrated more on hard TQM procedures than soft ones. In contrast, the findings of the exploratory qualitative research showed that soft and hard TQM both are equally significant. Hence, managers must remember that soft TQM techniques are primarily responsible for the quality and organisational performance based on HRM, customers, suppliers, external stakeholders, and social and cultural perspectives, besides the hard TQM techniques. Many quality initiatives fail when soft techniques are ignored (Singh *et al.*, 2018). The organizations have high expectations and high level of knowledge, quality Information, benchmarking capabilities, corporate social responsibilities, political and cultural context, and their views of soft quality performance have a substantial impact on organisational performance. Hence, managers must focus equally on both soft and hard aspects of TQM practices to improve the organisational core capabilities.

This study also improves Bangladeshi ISO 9000-certified garment organisation's perceptions of TQM and innovation practices and its role in organisational financial and non-financial performance. The findings may support strategists in reflecting on their organisation's present position. Only when everyone within the organisation understands where they stand can then they determine where to go next. Thus, findings will help the managers to implement the TQM and Innovation practicing process effectively among the employees in order to bring the best efficiency from it. Simultaneously, practitioners may benefit from better planning of their quality management systems. According to Abraham *et al.* (1999), quality transformation is a long-term process that necessitates a fundamental culture shift. This study supports Beer's claim that the failure of many quality implementation initiatives may be partly due to an inability to pay attention to the alignment between organisational culture and quality management practices (Kanapathy *et al.*, 2017). Hence, managers can put extra focus on the management culture and implementation of the TQM and innovation practices process in the Bangladesh garments industry.

The favourable correlations between TQM practices and organisational performance metrics can drive the firm's top management to participate in better planning of corporate objectives, as well as to allocate resources in time, effort, and capital to the implementation of TQM practices in pursuit of enhanced quality, employee performance, and firm performance. The results suggest that organisations can improve organisational performance by integrating strategic planning, supplier quality control, human resources, and customer satisfaction. Furthermore, survey techniques such as customer feedback and complaint analysis should be used on a regular basis

to verify that customer demands and expectations are met, which will improve corporate performance. Finally, the findings of this study give significant information about TQM procedures in the sector of Bangladesh garments industry. If an organisation effectively wants to improve product quality and compete in the global market, it must prioritize the implementation of TQM techniques (Singh *et al.*, 2018). The findings can specially assist BGMEA academics, policymakers, managers, and organisations in Bangladesh who wants to encourage and support innovation and TQM methods.

Model outcomes and publication perspective

The model created in this study may be used in any garment organisation or other organisation with a minor adjustment to improve service quality by combining soft and hard components to enhance quality and organisational performance. This study is aimed to arouse the interest of researchers by diving into the new concept of TQM and attempting to identify scenarios in which TQM might help to the development of innovative performance for garments organisations in Bangladesh. This study shows that the TQM instrument may have a strong relationship to organisational innovation performance because it was developed in industrialised environments. The data might help to achieve a balanced view of organisational cultures, such as whether a positive organisational culture is favourable to TQM and contributes to attaining desirable organisational results following the developed models. Similarly, practicing elements of administrative and technological innovation in organisation may improve their financial and non-financial performance. It is defined that TQM adoption is complicated and takes time (Zeng *et al.*, 2015), So team management needs extra training to implement this framework. Adoption of this framework may assist organisations in considering all factors for organisational success by accepting all elements of TQM and Innovation practicing processes. The current approach can be used for the Bangladesh Garments industry by considering the additional emerging parameters, such as political culture and corporate social responsibility for the soft aspect of TQM practices. Similarly, innovation practice influences TQM performance and combinedly impacts on organisational performance. Hence, this research thesis may add extra value to the literature on the TQM and Innovation impacts on organisational performance and their relationship perspective.

Contribution to the body of knowledge

The contribution to the body of knowledge is an important consideration for a research project, but its conceptualisation remains a shaded term. According to Phillips and Pugh (2010), the contribution to knowledge is not like an enormous breakthrough with the subject rocking on its foundation. However, according to Creswell (2011), research must demonstrate that the researcher has a good grasp of how such activities are done in the domain. Therefore, this study intends to contribute to the body of knowledge in the following ways:

In the last ten years, numerous textile workers in Bangladesh have died in fires and building collapses. A single factory known as Rana Plaza collapsed in the capital city of Bangladesh, Dhaka, killing about 1100 workers. Consequently, the external stakeholder pressure has reduced business volume in this sector. A number of western organisations stopped buying their products from Bangladesh after the incident (Siegle and Burke, 2014). Simultaneously, the World Trade Organization (WTO) and the media have raised concerns about the quality of the working environment, health and safety issues, infrastructures, employee rights, business processes, and services. Prajogo and Sohal (2003) state that the TQM and innovation practices help the organisation to ensure its quality products, processes, and services. Soft and hard quality management helps avoid organisational internal hazards, including employees' health and safety issues, workplace cleanliness, and interpersonal relationship between employees and management. The TQM philosophy also ensures the quality of products, processes, and services. Simultaneously, innovation practice helps to identify and find a creative way to succeed in business. Therefore, this research will contribute to the Bangladesh RMG manufacturers operating their business successfully.

Any country's ability to move from a lower to middle-income status depends heavily on the contribution of the industrial sector. The RMG sector has made a significant economic contribution to Bangladesh (Chowdhury and Quaddus, 2015). The RMG industry creates more than four million direct employment opportunities in Bangladesh. The export earnings from RMG are counted as 82.01 % of the national GDP and the value of the apparel exports on a fiscal year basis is \$28094.16 million as the second-largest garments exporter in the world (Ansary and Barua, 2015). Despite its vast potential in the country's economy, the industry is struggling to cope and survive with the changing business environment. Bangladesh's RMG industry is losing business regularly due to disruption in supply chain operations caused by political instability (Chowdhury and Quaddus, 2015). Thus, this research outcome may mitigate the supply chain

disruption issues. The participants acknowledged that 'political culture' is one of the reasons for the delayed delivery of the products (R13, R9, R11, and R15). For example, Participant R13 said, *"I have had enough of the political situation. There is a significant gap there. Political difficulties need to be resolved in order to lower the number of days for delayed deliveries from 90 to 30.."* A similar statement was made by participants R14, R9, R13, and R15, such as participant R15 said, *"Sometimes political influence and government unorganized decision cause employee's movement (strike) against the management. We really need to work on these issues for better business."* As a result, using the findings of this research, the concerns mentioned above, may assist organisations in discovering an appropriate solution.

The RMG industry is facing challenges of labour unrest for violation of human rights, power shortage, increased competition, employee dissatisfaction with poor wages, poor and hazardous working environment, insufficient operations, intensive competitive pressure, strict compliance code regarding social and environmental issues, higher technological competition, and lack of proper experts (Islam and Deegan, 2008). This is acknowledged by participant R9, *"In the last two to three years, I have not received enough training at this company, and I have been working in the same department since day one. Training is important, and I believe workers must receive multitasking training."* Participants such as R5, R8, and R14 defined that they mainly recruit experienced employees. However, participants also explained that they try to train their employees, which is still insufficient. For example, R7 said, *"The task being done here might be completed by one more person or someone else. To fill the employee deficit, we must train the staff to multitask. We are making an effort to do so, but not entirely."* Scholars defined employee involvement is an essential part of any TQM effort, and the MBNQA has highlighted the significance of human resources (Bowen and Lawler, 1992; Rahman, 2002; Rahman, 2002; Feng *et al.*, 2006; Ahire *et al.*, 1996). Organisations should therefore be concerned with the challenges identified by the data results and how to solve them to improve the way organisational processes are developed.

It is challenging for the RMG to remain competitive in the technology arena. In light of the situation, research on TQM and innovation's impact on business may help organisations address quality-related issues and point them in the direction of innovation to fill organisational gaps. For instance, participant R5 said, *"Technology has a big impact on business."* Also, R6 said, *"I believe that we can boost productivity while working with limited resources if we use technology."* Furthermore, participants R7, R11, and R12 made similar observations regarding the significance of technology within the company. Participants R1, R15, R14, and R12 stated that

technology might aid them in boosting productivity and adhering to the customer's product delivery timetable. As a result, management may perceive the value of technology through this research's output, which could lead to corporate success. So, these findings may contribute to the current literature in the domain of TQM and innovation by identifying the impact of TQM and Innovation on organisational performance and the performance correlation between TQM and innovation practices in the Bangladesh garments sector as well as garment organisations worldwide. Simultaneously, this research may provide an original theoretical and empirical contribution to the field of TQM and innovation from the perspective of the garment industry and in a developing economy.

6.3 Recommendations

There are various scientific studies that show how important innovation is for a company's survival. Numerous studies indicate that TQM can foster innovation by using various TQM elements. On the other hand, TQM has been demonstrated in multiple studies to be a successful management strategy that may assist organisations in gaining a competitive edge and improving their performance. However, the research identified some disagreement after evaluating a number of articles that looked for a relationship between the two systems. This study aimed to determine the significance of the TQM and innovation practice's impact on organisational performance and the correlation between them. After utilising structural equation modeling to analyse the innovation and quality management practices in a sample of 350 from the Bangladesh garments industry, the findings complement the literature as it indicates that TQM is a practical setting for fostering company innovation through qualitative investigation. In addition, quantitative analysis revealed that organic TQM significantly impacts organisational performance via mechanistic quality management.

Above all, it appears that, despite challenges to TQM as a valuable tool for innovation, TQM can create an environment favourable enough to overcome any possible barriers. Companies that operate in industries where constant innovation is required should not view TQM only as a good approach to improve quality and a hindrance to innovation, but instead of adding only the TQM benefits, the innovation process can be added simultaneously. In addition, organic innovation practices found a direct and indirect impact on TQM and the organisational financial and non-financial performance. Hence, it can be recommended that businesses adopt TQM in its broadest sense to achieve objectives rather than limiting its application to technical issues. TQM can be a

beneficial business strategy, but the corporation must first successfully implement TQM or practice TQM and innovation simultaneously to desire better outcomes.

The western market is the main buyer base for the Bangladesh garment industry. One of the emerging topics brought up by various participants in their interviews is corporate social responsibility. The demands placed on the organisation by external stakeholders are important to implementing CSR in the factory, and failure to practice CSR may lead threat to the organization. For example, participant R2 said, *“We all are concerned about the unsafe working conditions and workplace environment. In reality, since the Rana Plaza fell, the government and we have been worried. If a problem arises, we address it immediately because CSR influences how well customers see a company and its profitability.”* Participants R1, R3, R4, R5, R6, R8, and R11 also addressed that CSR is an essential issue for business. Therefore, Bangladesh RMG should perceive CSR as a significant component of TQM to counteract the danger posed by external stakeholders.

The use of administrative innovation and organic TQM techniques assists the organisation in being more innovative. Participants R1, R2, and R15 defined that administrative innovation, such as strategic decisions about mergers, alliances, and foreign direct investment, might be helpful in bringing success to the organisation in an innovative way. For example, participant R2 said, *“Along with superior financial results, strategic alliances will assist in building customer loyalty.”* Similarly, R7, R9, R10, and R14 noted that administrative innovation might positively impact on organisational performance. So, to attain commercial success innovatively in the current competitive environment, the researcher recommends management exercise administrative innovation broadly. The outcomes from both quantitative and qualitative studies mentioned that technology strongly impacts on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Implementing new technology may help the organisation to improve the quality of products and increase the production volume to meet the customer's demand and reduce the delayed delivery time (Koen *et al.*, 2001). Consequently, in order to obtain a competitive edge, TQM and innovation-related components must be widely applied. So, future research on only the organic aspects of TQM and Innovation to understand the issues in depth might be worthwhile.

To ascertain the relationship between TQM and innovation, the researcher collected data from managers focusing equally on both the soft and hard components of TQM and innovation. The researcher discovered that both aspects improve the performance of each other. The majority of the staff working on the floor lacks a formal education. As a result, extensive training and

development must be used to increase their skills and competence. The researcher believes that task-related training and group discussion will assist the organisation in setting expectations, which will result in success for the organisation. Simultaneously, proper cooperation, training, listening to employee problems, and sharing knowledge and information those organic components assist staff in efficiently managing the hard aspects such as waste and variance management, preventative maintenance, cleaning, and machinery operation. Several managers confirmed the effectiveness of seven pieces checking system in controlling the defect rates and variance. A small number of managers observed that management occasionally offers customers minorly defective goods. Some others said that defective products could not be sold in the market. The study advises against offering low-quality products on the market. Rather than doing so, the researchers recommend that the statistical quality control and monitoring system be maintained broadly to achieve zero defects. This would assist the organisation in saving money, increasing productivity, and increasing customer happiness by ensuring quality. It has been identified that sharing information and marketing benchmarking is very important for the business. However, almost all participants mentioned that they do not evaluate and contrast their organisation's marketing performance with that of other organisations. In fact, in the current globalised environment, firms must concentrate on benchmarking with external organisations to understand the competitive activities and close those gaps that hinder performance.

In this study, managers claimed that an organisational innovative culture makes workers more reticent and may occasionally cause them to depart from the strategic plan (R4, R11, R13, and R15). Even the most innovative organisations must allocate substantial resources to projects to achieve the desired outcomes. As a result, to assess whether the strategy is succeeding, this study recommends management integrate the control, monitor, and feedback systems correctly. The research also recommends that management should carefully justify whether a suggestion will result in a return on investment before putting it into action. Therefore, the garment organisation may pursue an open and organic approach to exchange and explore more innovative business concepts for success.

6.4 Suggestions for the Future Research

This study was conducted to identify the impact of TQM (Organic and Mechanistic QM) and innovation (administrative and technological) on the organizational financial and non-financial performance in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry. Suggestions can be made that

the following areas could further enhance the understanding of TQM and innovation's impact and their relationship based on the organisational financial and non-financial performance.

Earlier in this chapter, it is noted by participants R9, R7, R13, R15, R11, and R7 that organisations do not practice the organic aspect of TQM properly in the organization. Participants such as R9 said, *"I have been working for this company for around two to three years, and although I'm in the same field, I have not received adequate training."* Also, R11 said, *"we usually do not take employees' opinions nor collect information from them."* Participants R10, R2, and R5 noted similar arguments. Furthermore, this research has found from the quantitative data results that organic QM has no direct impact on the financial and non-financial performance of the organisation. However, qualitative data results found a substantial impact of organic TQM on organisational financial and non-financial performance. Therefore, future research can be conducted with a broad view of organic TQM's impact on financial and non-financial performance in the Bangladesh garments industry.

This study identified that organic QM elements, such as 'political culture,' strongly impact on organisational performance. For example, participant R15 said, *"Employee protests (strikes) against management are occasionally brought on by political influence and arbitrary government decisions. To enhance organisational effectiveness, we must work on these political issues."* Also, R13 and R14 defined *"We have a team that tackles critical political matters. Only information can assist us in understanding the facts and then working accordingly to attain greater commercial success."* So, future studies can be undertaken with a broad perspective on the 'political and cultural' context of RMG's organisational performance. It has been noted that organic QM and administrative innovation significantly relate to each other (Zeng *et al.*, 2014). This research outcome did not find any substantial direct relationship between them, but the study output discovered a strong indirect association. Several managers discussed that administrative innovation, such as mergers, strategic alliances, and foreign direct investment, substantially impact organisational performance. For example, participant R1 said, *"I believe mergers and alliances are a good concept because the shareholder (foreign investor) will strive to make positive contributions, while we will try to work together to develop a better long-term business plan to reach the success where the profit will be split equally between the two parties."* Similarly, participants R1, R7, R9, R10, R14, and R15 also defined that administrative innovation may positively impact on business performance. Thus, future studies can be undertaken broadly to identify the impact and relationship between administrative innovation technique and organic TQM in the context of the Bangladesh garment industry.

Similarly, the researcher suggests that the contingency components, such as environmental uncertainty, corporate culture, and strategic objectives, can be investigated to establish a relationship between organic and mechanistic quality management and innovation. In addition, a longitudinal study within the organisation might be carried out to track the realisation of performance due to the cumulative effect of TQM and innovation adoption. The qualitative research outcomes substantially impacted on TQM and innovation in organisational financial and non-financial performance. Hence, the researcher suggests undertaking further qualitative research broadly to find in-depth phenomena in the context of Bangladesh garment organisation. The outcome may help the organisation to grasp the TQM and innovation practices effectively for organisational success. Future research can also examine the TQM and Innovation relationship with a broader scope, such as strategic level, firm-level, or even inter-firm level, which may find more exciting results complementing this study.

This study employed a general narrative literature review but observed that the literature on the TQM and innovation impact on organisational financial and non-financial performance in the context of Bangladesh is minimal. Therefore, this study suggests a systematic literature review to combine the resources concentrating on TQM and innovations (multidimensional view) impact and their relationship regarding financial and non-financial performance in the Bangladesh garment organisation.

6.5 Research Limitations

Although the research has been successfully carried out to achieve the research aims by investigating the relationship between TQM and innovation and their impact on organisational performance in the context of the Bangladesh garments industry, but it is important to acknowledge its limitations. In some cases, the limitations were discussed in several places in different chapters of this thesis. However, this section is thoroughly summarized the research limitations.

Every research study has limitations regarding research objectives, methodology, and approaches to accomplish its goal and objectives, but by recognising these limitations, new study fields can be explored. The researcher used a narrative literature review where TQM and innovation and their impact on the garments industry in Bangladesh were the principal codes to identify the articles. Although many articles on TQM and Innovation are available, there are very few in the context of Bangladesh. This reason limits the researcher from finding suitable articles

to accomplish this research task conveniently. However, the research outcomes and developed conceptual framework will guide other researchers to explore different aspects of this research domain. Therefore, this study can be used as a guideline to compare and contrast the research findings in the future.

As noted earlier by several researchers, the research outcomes are highly context-specific. Therefore, the finding of this research may not be similar if the same study were carried out in another country. Mainly, TQM and innovation practices can be influenced by organic cultural practices, financial stability, and an educated social environment. Therefore, further empirical study can be carried out in South Asia or developing economic contexts to explore the role of TQM and innovation practices and their relationship based on organisational performance. However, this similar research may produce a different outcome in the context of a developed economy.

This study was carried out in the context of the garments industry only. Hence, the same research on different organisations or multiple organisations on TQM and innovation may produce different results in the same context of Bangladesh. Therefore, this research has contextual limitations in its outcome. The primary data for this research was collected from Bangladesh. The researcher had a time limit to collect the qualitative and quantitative data from outside the UK. Multiple visits to the organisations would have been better to enrich the primary data. However, due to covid-19 restrictions and limitations of finance, this research employed a cross-sectional approach. Therefore, future researchers may conduct a longitudinal study in this context to extensively understand the impact of TQM and innovations and their relationship with a broad view of financial and non-financial aspects in the Bangladesh garments industry.

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Appendices

Appendix 01: Ethics Approval Letter

19/02/2019

Dear Md-Hasan Sayed,

Your application 7685: TQM and Innovation , submission 6145, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean

Appendix 02: quantitative and Qualitative questionnaires

Dear Participant,

You are invited to participate in my survey for my Ph.D. thesis, “The Relationship and Impact of Multidimensionality TQM and Innovation on Organisational Performance: In the context of the Bangladesh Garments Industry.” Several employees will be asked to complete this survey that asks a set of questions in this survey. It will take approximately 30- 45 minutes to complete the questionnaires.

Your participation in this study is completely voluntary. There are no foreseeable risks associated with this project. However, if you feel uncomfortable answering any questions, you can withdraw from the survey at any point.

Your survey responses will be strictly confidential, and data from this research will be reported only in the aggregate. Your information will be stored and will remain confidential. If you have questions at any time about the survey or the procedures, you may contact Md. Hasan Sayed at [REDACTED] or by email at [REDACTED] or [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Thank you very much for your time and support. Please start the survey now by answering the questions below.

Section A

1. Please mark your position in the company at the moment.

- Owner
- General manager
- Plant manager
- Quality manager
- Production Manager
- Member of production department
- Member of quality department
- Floor manager
- Floor Supervisor
- HRM Manager
- Or Other _____

Section B: Organic (Soft) Total Quality Management

Please tick or write the number which accurately reflects your site's PRESENT position, where:

1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

<i>B1. Top Management commitment in quality management :</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	All major department heads within our plant accept their responsibility for Quality					
2	Management gives top priority to evaluate quality performance					
3	Top management sit together to set comprehensive goal for quality process					
4	In top management meetings, quality issues are reviewed as a top priority					
5	Top management consider quality improvement as a way to increase profit					
6	All manager/department head works toward encouraging Just in Time production (JIT).					

1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

<i>B2. Employee suggestions:</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	Management takes all product and process improvement suggestions seriously					
2	We feel free to make suggestions for performance improvement at this plant					
3	Management gives us feedback on our suggestions about work related issues					
4	Many useful suggestions are implemented at this plant					
5	My suggestions are taken seriously in the organisation					

1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

<i>B3. Small Group Problem solving:</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	Our plant forms teams to solve a problem					
2	During problem solving sessions we make an effort to get all team members opinions and ideas before making a decision					
3	Many problems have been solved in the past three years through small group problem solving session					
4	Problem solving teams have helped improve manufacturing process at this plant					
5	Employee teams are encouraged to solve their own problems as much as possible					

1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

<i>B4. Task related training for employees:</i>		1	2	3	4	5

1	We receive training and development in workplace skills on a regular basis					
2	Management at this plant believes that continual training and upgrading of employee skills is important					
3	We train up our employees for different units related task					
4	Our employees regularly receive training to improve their skills					

1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

<i>B5. Supplier quality management:</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	We have a long term relationship with our suppliers					
2	Our organisation has reduced number of suppliers since implementing JIT purchasing					
3	Our organisation select supplier based on quality					
4	Our organisation select supplier based on price					
5	Our organisation select supplier based on flexible delivery schedule					
6	Our organisation has a supplier rating system					
7	Our supplier are strongly involved in our product, process and service development process					

1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

<i>B6. Customer relations:</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	We frequently are in close contact with our customers					
2	Our management knows our customers					
3	Our customers often visit our office or workplace					
4	Our customers often give us feedback on quality and delivery performance					
5	We note our customers opinion and feedback					

1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

<i>B7. Social Responsibility</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	We recycle our factory waste					
2	Noise levels caused by our firm is maintaining the optimal level					
3	We don't dump the dyeing and washing dirty water to river					
4	Our firm is concern about low carbon emission					
5	We follow the standard government payment policy					

6	We have more than one fire exit door in each floor for our employees					
---	--	--	--	--	--	--

Section C: Mechanistic (Hard) Total Quality Management
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Please tick or write the number which accurately reflects your site's PRESENT position, where:

1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

C1. Strategic Quality Planning:		1	2	3	4	5
1	We have a mission and vision statement on Quality management					
2	We develop our strategies considering customers' requirement.					
3	We develop our strategies and plans considering firm's capabilities					
4	The management communicates its strategies and objectives to the staff					
5	Customer needs are taken into account when establishing objectives					
6	Our quality strategies affect all organisational areas					

1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

C2. Process Management:	
1	A large percentage of the processes on the shop floor are currently under statistical quality control
2	We make extensive use of statistical techniques to reduce variance in process
3	We use charts to determine whether our manufacturing process are in control
4	We arrange training for basic statistical techniques (ex- histogram and control chart) in the organisation
5	We arrange training for advanced statistical techniques (ex-design of experiment and regression analysis) in the organisation
6	We meet our production schedule everyday
7	We monitor our process using statistical process control

1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

C3. Preventive Maintenance:		1	2	3	4	5
1	We upgrade inferior equipment, in order to prevent equipment problems					

2	In order to improve equipment performance, we sometimes redesign equipment					
3	We estimate lifespan of our equipment so that repair or replacement can be planned					
4	We use equipment diagnostic techniques to predict equipment lifespan					
5	We conduct with technical analysis of a major breakdown					

1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

C4. Housekeeping:		1	2	3	4	5
1	Our plant emphasize putting all tools and fixtures in their place					
2	We give priority to keep our plant neat and clean					
3	Our plant is kept clean at all times					
4	We have a special team to keep our plant clean frequently					
5	Employees often have trouble finding the tools they need					
6	We keep clear our floor fire exit doors at all time					
7	We make ready our plant for next day work					

1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

C5. Quality Information:	
1	We note quality data such as: defect rates, error rates, scrap, defects, errors in this organisation
2	Our quality data and information are regular and timely
3	Organisation pass information to the employees about major emergency situation such as fire or building collapse
4	Management inform us customers feedback regularly
5	We gather data from our buyers/suppliers to improve the quality information

At this site, benchmarking has been undertaken at the following areas: Please Tick the accurate number position which accurately reflects your site's PRESENT position, where:

1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

C6. Benchmarking:	
1	We compare relative cost positions with other firms
2	We compare our operating processes with other firms
3	We compare our technological capabilities with other firms
4	We compare our quality maintain procedures with other firms
5	We compare other firm human resource management practices and policies
6	We compare other firms strategic decisions

Section D: Innovation indicators and assessment Criteria

Please Tick the accurate the number position which accurately reflects your site's PRESENT position, where:

1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = Agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

Administrative: Internal Organisational innovation		1	2	3	4	5
1	Our organisation implemented new employee reward training schemes					
2	Our organisation provides opportunities for staff to explore their talents.					
3	Our organisation innovative team involves buyers in the organisational innovation process for opening new markets.					

<i>Administrative: Marketing innovation</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	We have a strategy to involve buyers in the organisational innovation process to find new market					
2	We have a strategy to involve suppliers in the organisational innovation practicing process for existing market development					
3	Our organisation has appropriate marketing policy in response to its competitors activities					

<i>Administrative: Strategic Innovation</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	Our organisation implemented improved computer based administrative applications					
2	Our organization promotes strategic alliance/partnership in response to changing economic environment					
3	Our organisation has appropriate policy in response to external stakeholders threat (ex-social issues, building clasped issues, fire, environmental issues)					

1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

<i>Technological Products</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	We use innovative technology to develop new products					

2	We use direct social media marketing to promote and sale the products					
3	We have our own web based online marketing platform					

<i>Technological Technology</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	Our organisation is involved in adaptation of new technology for improving its R&Ds outputs.					
2	We use smoke detector or technological instruments to identify the cause of fire					
3	We introduced technology oriented new machine to increase productivity in this firm					

<i>Technological Process</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	Our organisation electronic mailing option is open and checked 24 hours for quick response to our buyers and suppliers.					
2	Within last 3 years we have used upgraded technology in production sectors to reduce the delay of delivery days					
3	We have a special online based customer service team for 24 hours					
4	We use security camera to stop smoking in the factory by the employees					

Section E: Balanced Score card approach for Business performance measurement

Please Tick the accurate the number position which accurately reflects your site's PRESENT position, where:
 1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

<i>Inventory Management performance for financial achievement</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	Purchase material turnover is high in our firm					
2	Total inventory turnover is high in our firm					
3	Financial benefit achieved as Supply chain cycle time has reduced					
4	Our customer service system flexibility has increased for financial achievement					
5	Financially benefited Product development cycle time has reduced					

6	Financially benefited as Frequency of delivery time has increased					
---	---	--	--	--	--	--

Please select in which competitive position is your company in comparison with its competitors relating to these performance measurements (where: 1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree)

Financial Achievement: As a result of benchmarking our		1	2	3	4	5
1	As a result of benchmarking our unit production cost has increased					
2	As a result of benchmarking our products delivery rate became faster for financial achievement.					
3	As a result of benchmarking online response became quicker					
4	As a result of benchmarking production cycle time increased					
5	As a result of benchmarking financial achievement increased as manufacturing quality is better to gain more order from buyers.					
6	As a result of benchmarking our customer satisfaction is better than before and increased sales.					
7	As a result of benchmarking market share has increased					

1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

<i>Social Responsibility</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	Water pollution caused by waste of our firm has decreased					
2	Noise levels caused by our firm have decreased					
3	Carbon emission caused by our firm has decreased					
4	Maintaining standard payment policy, employee satisfaction has increased					
5	Emergency fire exit door for each floor has brought good reputation for this organisation					

Please Tick the accurate the number position which accurately reflects your site's PRESENT position, where:

1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

Employee performance for customer satisfaction		1	2	3	4	5
	Customer satisfaction has improved					

	Our customer complaints have decreased over last 3 years					
	Our employees organisational commitment is higher than before to meet the customers product demands					
	Our employees job performance is higher than before to keep the supply regularly					
	Our employees moral is higher than before for serving the customers					

Please Tick the accurate the number position which accurately reflects your site's PRESENT position, where: 1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

<i>Market and financial performance</i>		1	2	3	4	5
1	Return on asset of firm has increased					
2	Market share of our firm has improved than before					
3	Profits of our firm has grown than before					
4	Sales of our firm have grown than before					

Please Tick the accurate the number position which accurately reflects your site's PRESENT position, where: 1 = strongly Disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = agree; 5 = Strongly Agree.

Innovation performance:		1	2	3	4	5
1	The number of successful new product introduced of our firm is higher than other firms over last 3 years					
2	The number of successful process introduced of our firm is higher than other firms over last 3 years					
3	The number of successful services introduced of our firm is higher than other firms over last 3 years					
4	The use of latest technological innovation in our new product has increased					
5	The technological competitiveness in our firm has increased than before					

Qualitative Interview guide:

Organic Quality Management:

Top Management decision:

- How does top management influence quality performance?
 - Probing: a) how do you maintain your quality improvement processes?
- How do management work to resolve any major issues around Buyers/suppliers?
- Do you have any policy that helps to find new innovative ideas in this organisation?

Employee suggestions:

- How important is the employee's suggestions for improving quality performance?
 - Probing: a) How do you collect the employee's suggestions?

Small Group problem solving:

- If any problem is identified in the organisation, how far do you think that team work is effective way to solve the problems by discussion?
 - Probing: a) From your experience, what are the benefits of team work in the organisation?

Task Related Training for employees:

- What do the organisation do to improve employee skills and confidence?
 - Probing: a) What activities do you follow to justify and upgrade the employee's knowledge?
 - Probing: b) How do employees enhanced skills help to improve organisational performance?

Customer Relation:

- What priority do you specially give to maintain customer relationship?
 - Probing: a) How willing are you to take buyers feedback and how do you handle it?

- For the reason of political instability, if buyers don't feel free to visit your plant, how do you tackle this situation to maintain sustainable business relationship with the buyers?
 - Probing: a) How does the buyer's relationship impact on your business?

Supplier Quality Management:

- Why long time relationship with suppliers is important for business?
 - Probing: a) How long has this organisation been working with the suppliers?
- How customers/ supplier's information contributes in business?

- What do you consider to select a supplier most?
 - Probing: a) Do you consider that supplier should be involved in product, process and services development process? If yes,
 - Probing: b) Why do you consider that supplier should engage?

Corporate Social Responsibility:

- How far do you think organisation need to think about the society?
- What do you consider to practice corporate social responsibilities in this organisaion?
- Do you think bothering social responsibilities helps the business? If yes,
- How does it help?

Mechanistic Quality Management:

Strategic quality planning:

- What objectives and vision are considered for quality performance in this organisation?
 - Probing: a) What organisational areas and managerial activities are covered by the present quality strategies?

Process Management:

- Do you use any statistical process control chart in the plant? If yes?
- Can you please explain to me how does it works practically?

Preventive maintenance:

- How important is waste and variance control for your organisation?
 - Probing: a) What are the activities or process that you follow to control the waste and variance in this plant?
- What do you do with the inferior or major damaged equipment in this plant?
 - Probing: a) Do you consider that preventive maintenance is beneficial for your organisation?
 - Probing: b) how does it contribute?

House Keeping:

- Do you think it's important to keep clean the plant? If yes ,
 - Why is it important?
 - How do you do that?
 - How does it contribute to the business?
- Do you have any special team to monitor the cleanliness and tidiness of the plant?
- Why do you consider housekeeping is important for this business?

Quality Information:

- Do you monitor and note the defect rates, error rates, and scrap in products, process or services?
 - Probing: a) How do you collect this information?
 - Probing: b) Do you consider quality information helps to review and market new products, process and services?
 - Probing: c) How does it contribute in business?

Benchmarking:

1. What are the major factors you consider to compare the competitive position with competitors?
Probing: a) How does it contribute to the organisational performance?

Administrative innovation:

- In what way do you think that innovation contributes to success in your business?

- Probing: a) Do you have a computer based administrative applications?
 - Do you consider that providing opportunities to all employees may help to explore their talents and competences? If yes,
 - What initiatives has the organisation taken to explore those competences?
 - Does the organisational innovative team, work with buyers/suppliers for market developments?
 - Why does marketing department have maximum foreign employees in garments business?
-
- Does the organisation have a future plan to introduce their own brand in world market by direct investment?
 - Do you have any special policy to tackle the emergency situations in the plant (ex: fire, building collapse) in response to external shareholder threats?
 - Do you have any strategic alliances/partnership for direct investment to enter into the western market with your own brand?

Technological Innovations:

- How does technology impact on Garments business?
- Is there any technology you have introduced within the last couple of years to improve the business performance. if yes,
- What is that and how has it contributed to your business?
- Do you have any gaps in technology that has been identified? If yes,
- What is that and how has it impact on your business?
- Do you have any plan to fill the gap that's been identified?
- Do you consider that security camera/fire alarm may help to avoid unexpected damages of this company?
- Do you consider that technological innovation may help to reduce the delay of delivery days? If yes,
- How does it may help to reduce the delay delivery days?

TQM and Innovation Relationship:

- Do you consider TQM and innovation both are important for this business? If yes/no

- a. Why do you think both are important?
- b. Why do you think both are not important
- Do you find any relationship between TQM and innovation practices due to its impact on business?

Appendix 03: statistical calculation for quantitative analysis

Mediating Effect/Indirect Effect: innovation mediates TQM Z test

$$SEab = \sqrt{(SEa)^2 * b^2 + (SEb)^2 * a^2}$$

Therefore the mediating effect

$Z = \frac{(a*b)}{SEab}$, the indirect effect would be significant if the value of Z is $\geq \pm 1.96$

When the possible Mediator OOG between TN and NF there are two possible paths directed such as TN --->>> OOG and OOG --->>> NF. Now following the above regression weight table, the value of a, b, SEa and SEb have placed into the equation to bring out the value of SEab.

$$SEab = \sqrt{(SEa)^2 * b^2 + (SEb)^2 * a^2}$$

$$SEab = \sqrt{(0.09)^2 * (0.03)^2 + (0.053)^2 * (0.017)^2}$$

$$= 0.002846366$$

Therefore, mediating effect (via OOG between TN and NF) = $Z = \frac{(a*b)}{SEab} =$

$$Z = \frac{(0.017 * 0.03)}{0.002846366}$$

$$Z = 0.1791 \text{ (not-significant)}$$

Path not-significant: TN---->>>OOG and OOG---->>>F

$$SEab = \sqrt{(SEa)^2 * b^2 + (SEb)^2 * a^2}$$

$$SEab = \sqrt{(0.09)^2 * (0.067)^2 + (0.052)^2 * (0.017)^2}$$

$$SEab = 0.006094453$$

Therefore, mediating effect (via OOG between TN and F) = $Z = \frac{(a*b)}{SEab}$

$$Z = \frac{(0.017 * 0.067)}{0.006094453}$$

$$Z = 0.186891263$$

Path not-Significant: TN--->>>QMC and QMC---->>>NF

$$SEab = \sqrt{(SEa)^2 * b^2 + (SEb)^2 * a^2}$$

$$SEab = \sqrt{(0.091)^2 * (0.154)^2 + (0.052)^2 * (0.069)^2}$$

$$SEab = 0.014466027$$

Therefore, mediating effect (via OOG between TN and F) = $Z = \frac{(a*b)}{SEab}$

$$Z = \frac{(0.069 * 0.154)}{0.014466027}$$

$$Z = 0.734548603$$

Path non-significant: TN---->>>QMC and QMC---->>>F

$$SEab = \sqrt{(0.091)^2 * (0.347)^2 + (0.051)^2 * (0.069)^2}$$

$$SEab = 0.031772477$$

Therefore, mediating effect (via OOG between TN and F) = $Z = \frac{(a * b)}{SEab}$

$$Z = \frac{(0.069 * 0.347)}{0.031772477}$$

$$Z = 0.753576753$$

Not-significant path: AD--->>> OOG and OOG--->>>NF

$$SEab = \sqrt{(0.101)^2 * (0.03)^2 + (0.053)^2 * (0.094)^2}$$

$$SEab = 0.005831057$$

Therefore, mediating effect (via OOG between TN and F) = $Z = \frac{(a * b)}{SEab}$

$$Z = \frac{(0.094 * 0.03)}{0.005831057}$$

$$Z = 0.483617305$$

Significant path: AD--->>> OOG and OOG--->>>F

$$SEab = \sqrt{(0.101)^2 * (0.067)^2 + (0.052)^2 * (0.094)^2}$$

$$SEab = 0.008347744$$

Therefore, mediating effect (via OOG between TN and F) = $Z = \frac{(a * b)}{SEab}$

$$Z = \frac{(0.094 * 0.067)}{0.0083477}$$

$$Z = 0.754455319$$

AD --->>>QMC and QMC --->>>NF

$$SEab = \sqrt{(0.103)^2 * (0.154)^2 + (0.052)^2 * (0.314)^2}$$

$$SEab = 0.022764152$$

Therefore, mediating effect (via OOG between TN and F) = $Z = \frac{(a * b)}{SEab}$

$$Z = \frac{(0.314 * 0.154)}{0.022764152}$$

$$Z = 2.124217034$$

Significant path: AD--->>>QMC and QMC--->>>F

$$SEab = \sqrt{(0.103)^2 * (0.347)^2 + (0.051)^2 * (0.314)^2}$$

$$SEab = 0.039164618$$

Therefore, mediating effect (via OOG between TN and F) = $Z = \frac{(a * b)}{SEab}$

$$Z = \frac{(0.314 * 0.347)}{0.039164618}$$

$$Z = 2.782051926$$

Mediating Effect/Indirect Effect: innovation mediates TQM P-test using Amos:

Parameter (AxB)	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P	Results
TN --> OOG --> NF	.001	-.003	.009	.695	Non-Significant
TN --> OOG --> F	.001	-.006	.013	.672	Non-Significant
TN --> QMC --> NF	.011	-.007	.041	.345	Non-Significant
TN --> QMC --> F	.024	-.004	.104	.160	Non-Significant
AD --> OOG --> NF	.003	-.002	.020	.304	Non-Significant
AD --> OOG --> F	.006	-.001	.034	.195	Non-Significant
AD --> QMC --> NF	.048	.014	.132	.002	*** Significant
AD --> QMC --> F	.109	.039	.265	.000	*** Significant

Coefficients^a

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
B1.Mng.Commitment	.575	1.739
B2.Emp.Suggestion	.327	3.062
B3.Problem.Solving	.318	3.147
B4.Task.Rltd.Training	.445	2.245
B5.Supplier.Qul.Mng	.803	1.246
B6.Customer.Relations	.691	1.447
B7.Social.Responsibility	.697	1.435
C1.Strategic.Q.Planning	.368	2.719
C2.Process.Mngt	.393	2.542
C3.Preventive.Maintnce	.620	1.613
C4.Housekeeping	.449	2.225
C5.Quality.Information	.398	2.514
C6.Benchmarking	.713	1.403
DA1.Strategic.Innov	.403	2.482
DA2.Internal.Org.Innov	.301	3.322
DA3.Marketing.Innovation	.364	2.748
ET1.Technological.Product	.315	3.175
ET2.Technological.Tcno	.286	3.499
ET3.Technological.Process	.306	3.265
F1.Invtry.Mng.Perf	.535	1.869
F2.Benchmarking.Perf	.583	1.714

F3.Financial.Prspctv	.491	2.036
NF1.CSR.Perf	.421	2.374
NF2.EMP.Perf	.576	1.736
NF3.Innov.Lrn.Perf	.428	2.336

a. Dependent Variable: Respondents

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Variance
B1.Mng.Commitment	350	27.9200	7.587
B2.Emp.Suggestion	350	22.3800	8.385
B3.Problem.Solving	350	22.2171	8.394
B4.Task.Rltd.Training	350	17.6486	7.151
C1.Strategic.Q.Planning	350	31.0400	8.400
C2.Process.Mngt	350	27.3857	7.172
C4.Housekeeping	350	27.4743	9.895
C5.Quality.Information	350	26.5714	9.214
DA1.Strategic.Innov	350	26.7343	9.531
DA2.Internal.Org.Innov	350	21.5429	4.392
DA3.Marketing.Innovation	350	31.1800	9.340
ET1.Technological.Product	350	22.9000	5.517
ET2.Technological.Tcno	350	26.6400	4.363
ET3.Technological.Process	350	13.2171	2.245
F1.Invtry.Mng.Perf	350	13.4200	2.221
F2.Benchmarking.Perf	350	13.5229	2.302
F3.Financial.Prspctv	350	13.9629	2.368
NF1.CSR.Perf	350	18.6400	3.985
NF2.EMP.Perf	350	13.9886	2.464
NF3.Innov.Lrn.Perf	350	21.9171	8.036
B1.Mng.Commitment	350	31.1029	9.491
B2.Emp.Suggestion	350	17.9171	5.073
B3.Problem.Solving	350	22.7114	7.719
B4.Task.Rltd.Training	350	27.3257	6.725
C1.Strategic.Q.Planning	350	22.5457	7.710
Valid N (listwise)	350		

2nd Part: mediating effect TQM----> Innovation--->Organisational Performance

When the possible Mediator TN between OGQ and NF there are two possible paths directed such as OGQ --->>> TN and TN --->>> NF. Following the above regression weight table, the value of a, b, SEa and SEb have been placed into the equation to bring out the value of SEab.

$$SEab = \sqrt{(SEa)^2 * b^2 + (SEb)^2 * a^2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} SEab &= \sqrt{(0.034)^2 * (0.474)^2 + (0.086)^2 * (0.006)^2} \\ &= 0.0161243 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, mediating effect (via OOG between TN and NF) = $Z = \frac{(a*b)}{SEab} =$

$$Z = \frac{(0.006 * 0.474)}{0.0161243}$$

$$Z = 0.1764$$

This means that the Standard deviation is not above the mean as the Z score doesn't fall in the significant level of $\geq (\pm 1.96)$.

Therefore, Organic QM (OGQ) practices do not have any mediating effect through TN on organisational Non-financial (NF) performance.

Now following the same manner, the mediating effect of TN between OGQ and financial performance (F) is shown below:

OGQ---->>>TN and TN---->>>F

$$SEab = \sqrt{(SEa)^2 * b^2 + (SEb)^2 * a^2}$$

$$SEab = \sqrt{(0.034)^2 * (0.003)^2 + (0.084)^2 * (0.006)^2}$$

$$SEab = 0.0005142$$

Therefore, mediating effect (via TN between OGQ and F) = $Z = \frac{(a*b)}{SEab}$

$$Z = \frac{(0.006 * 0.003)}{0.0005142}$$

$$Z = 0.0350046$$

Which means that the Standard deviation is not above the mean as the Z score doesn't fall in the significant level of $\geq (\pm 1.96)$.

Therefore, Organic QM (OGQ) practices don't have any mediating effect through TN on organisational financial (F) performance.

Now, considering the possible Mediator AD (Administrative innovation) between OGQ and NF, there are two possible paths directed such as OGQ --->>> AD and AD --->>> NF. Following the above regression weight Table DDD-5.5, the value of a, b, SEa and SEb have been placed into the equation to bring out the value of $SEab$.

OGQ--->>>AD and AD---->>>NF

$$SEab = \sqrt{(SEa)^2 * b^2 + (SEb)^2 * a^2}$$

$$SEab = \sqrt{(0.031)^2 * (-0.009)^2 + (0.098)^2 * (0.021)^2}$$

$$SEab = 0.0020768$$

Therefore, mediating effect (via AD between OGQ and F) = $Z = \frac{(a*b)}{SEab}$

$$Z = \frac{((0.021)*(-0.009))}{0.0020768}$$

$$Z = - 0.091$$

Which means that the Standard deviation is not above the mean as the Z score doesn't fall in the significant level of $\geq (\pm 1.96)$.

Therefore, OGQ practices don't have any mediating effect through AD innovation on organisational non-financial (NF) performance.

Similarly, the financial impact has been calculated below:

OGQ---->>>AD and AD---->>>F

$$SEab = \sqrt{(0.031)^2 * (0.044)^2 + (0.096)^2 * (0.021)^2}$$

$$SEab = 0.0024341$$

Therefore, mediating effect (via OOG between TN and F) = $Z = \frac{(a * b)}{SEab}$

$$Z = \frac{(0.021 * 0.044)}{0.0024341}$$

$$Z = 0.3796093$$

Which means that the Standard deviation is not above the mean as the Z score doesn't fall in the significant level of $\geq (\pm 1.96)$.

Therefore, OGQ practices don't have any mediating effect through AD innovation on organisational financial (F) performance.

Now the mediating effect between MCQ and NF (nonfinancial performance) via TN is calculated below:

MCQ--->>> TN and TN--->>>NF

$$SEab = \sqrt{(0.033)^2 * (0.474)^2 + (0.086)^2 * (0.033)^2}$$

$$SEab = 0.0158974$$

Therefore, mediating effect (via TN between MCQ and NF) = $Z = \frac{(a * b)}{SEab}$

$$Z = \frac{(0.033 * 0.474)}{0.0158974}$$

$$Z = 0.9839$$

Which means that the Standard deviation is not above the mean as the Z score doesn't fall in the significant level of $\geq (\pm 1.96)$.

Therefore, MCQ practices don't have any mediating effect through TN innovation on organisational non-financial (NF) performance.

Now the mediating effect between MCQ and F (financial performance) via TN is calculated below: MCQ--->>> TN and TN--->>>F

$$SEab = \sqrt{(0.033)^2 * (0.003)^2 + (0.084)^2 * (0.033)^2}$$

$$SEab = 0.0027738$$

Therefore, mediating effect (via TN between MCQ and F) = $Z = \frac{(a * b)}{SEab}$

$$Z = \frac{(0.003 * 0.033)}{0.0027738}$$

$$Z = 0.03569$$

Which means that the Standard deviation is not above the mean as the Z score doesn't fall in the significant level of $\geq (\pm 1.96)$.

Therefore, MCQ practices don't have any mediating effect through TN innovation on organisational financial (F) performance.

Considering the AD as a mediator, the impact between MCQ and NF is calculated below:

MCQ --->>>AD and AD --->>>NF

$$SEab = \sqrt{(0.03)^2 * (-0.009)^2 + (0.098)^2 * (0.092)^2}$$

$$SEab = 0.00902$$

Therefore, mediating effect (via AD between MCQ and NF) = $Z = \frac{(a * b)}{SEab}$

$$Z = \frac{(0.092 * -0.009)}{0.00902}$$

$$Z = -0.9179$$

Which means that the Standard deviation is not above the mean as the Z score doesn't fall in the significant level of $\geq (\pm 1.96)$.

Therefore, MCQ practices don't have any mediating effect through AD innovation on organisational financial (NF) performance

MCQ--->>>AD and AD--->>>F

$$SEab = \sqrt{(0.03)^2 * (0.044)^2 + (0.096)^2 * (0.092)^2}$$

$$SEab = 0.0089301$$

Therefore, mediating effect (via OOG between TN and F) = $Z = \frac{(a * b)}{SEab}$

$$Z = \frac{(0.092 * 0.044)}{0.0089301}$$

$$Z = 0.4533$$

Which means that the Standard deviation is not above the mean as the Z score does not fall in the significant level of $Z \geq (\pm 1.96) < 0.4533$.

Therefore, Mechanistic quality management (MCQ) practices don't have a mediating effect through Administrative innovation (AD) on organisational financial (F) performance.

Appendix 04: KMO

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.735
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3576.631
	df	190
	Sig.	.000

Appendix 5: GFI, AGFI, RMSEA, PCLOSE

Model	RMR	GFI	AGFI	PGFI	
Default model	.286	.932	.907	.688	
Saturated model	.000	1.000			
Independence model	1.539	.463	.406	.419	
Model	NFI Delta1	RFI rho1	IFI Delta2	TLI rho2	CFI
Default model	.926	.910	.967	.960	.967
Saturated model	1.000		1.000		1.000
Independence model	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Model	RMSEA	LO 90	HI 90	PCLOSE	
Default model	.046	.037	.055	.762	
Independence model	.229	.222	.235	.000	

Appendix 6: Correlation for Discriminant validity test

			correlation	Squared Correlation (R ²)	AVE should be > (R ²)		
Discriminant validity			Estimate		AVE1	AVE2	Discriminant Validity
OGQ	<-->	MCQ	0.068	0.004624	0.622	0.538	Established
OGQ	<-->	TN	0.002	0.000004	0.622	0.773	Established

OGQ	<-->	AD	0.049	0.002401	0.622	0.724	Established
OGQ	<-->	NF	0.056	0.003136	0.622	0.625	Established
OGQ	<-->	F	0.104	0.010816	0.622	0.503	Established
MCQ	<-->	TN	0.077	0.005929	0.538	0.773	Established
MCQ	<-->	AD	0.182	0.033124	0.538	0.724	Established
MCQ	<-->	NF	0.153	0.023409	0.538	0.625	Established
MCQ	<-->	F	0.375	0.140625	0.538	0.503	Established
TN	<-->	AD	0.084	0.007056	0.773	0.724	Established
TN	<-->	NF	0.348	0.121104	0.773	0.625	Established
TN	<-->	F	0.029	0.000841	0.773	0.503	Established
AD	<-->	NF	0.041	0.001681	0.724	0.625	Established
AD	<-->	F	0.066	0.004356	0.724	0.503	Established
NF	<-->	F	0.084	0.007056	0.625	0.503	Established

Appendix 7: Performance Measurement Criteria

Performance Scales	Used Assessment Criteria
Financial aspect	Return on investment, profitability, shareholders' funds, loyalties, and fund generation to build the capabilities are considered for financial assessment (Kaplan and Norton, 2000; Bhagwat and Sharma, 2007).
Internal organisational aspect	To assess the internal organizational performance, inventory management, impact on profitability, management benchmarking, and organisational initiatives to accept change are considered (Maisel, 1992; Maistry <i>et al.</i> , 2017).
Customer/(CSR) aspect	Considered the social-economic and environmental factors while operating the activities or agenda. Considered the aptitude to match the market's demands and ability to generate new market demands. In addition, it is considered the ability to gain customer and stakeholders satisfaction (Maisel, 1992).
Innovation and Learning aspect	Considered the innovative way of utilizing resources and business processes such as mergers, acquisitions, or licensing. Also, considered the ability to develop new ideas, technologies implementations in goods, services, communications, transportation, etc. The ability to publish research findings or advertisements in international business. In addition, task monitoring skills, abilities, and capacity to meet delivery deadlines or improve the delivery frequency have been considered (Maisel, 1992; Maistry <i>et al.</i> , 2017).
Human resource/employee aspect.	To assess employee performance, capacity-building and programmes' effectiveness are considered. Simultaneously, motivation to recruit and retain highly competent employees, job satisfaction, and health and safety issues are considered (Maistry <i>et al.</i> , 2017).

Appendix 8: several Mediating Effects

Table 6.8

Construct	Flow	construct	Hypo	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Results
F	<---	MCQ	H3	.347	.052	6.723	***	***Significant
NF	<---	MCQ	H4	.154	.052	2.930	.003	***Significant

Table 6.9

Parameter	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P	Results
OGQ --> MCQ --> NF	.013	.002	.043	.050	***Significant
OGQ --> MCQ --> F	.029	.006	.129	.011	***Significant

Table 6.10

Regression Weight	Flow	Variables	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
TC	<---H10	OGQ	-.003	.060	-.048	.961	Non-Significant
AD	<---H9	OGQ	.029	.046	.630	.528	Non-Significant
AD	<---H11	MCQ	.091	.030	2.992	.003	***Significant
TC	<---H12	MCQ	.053	.040	1.312	.190	Non-Significant

Appendix 9: Regression Analysis

Table 6.5: Innovation impact on TQM

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Results
OOG	<---	TN	.017	.090	.190	.849	Non-Significant
QMC	<---	TN	.069	.091	.759	.448	Non-Significant
OOG	<---	AD	.094	.101	.935	.350	Non-Significant
QMC	<---	AD	.314	.103	3.057	.002	***Significant
NF	<---	OOG	.030	.053	.573	.566	non-Significant
NF	<---	QMC	.154	.052	2.944	.003	***Significant
NF	<---	AD	-.010	.098	-.103	.918	Non-Significant
F	<---	AD	.044	.097	.459	.646	Non-Significant
NF	<---	TN	.474	.086	5.518	***	***Significant
F	<---	QMC	.347	.051	6.748	***	***Significant
F	<---	OOG	.067	.052	1.290	.197	Non-Significant
F	<---	TN	.003	.085	.035	.972	Non-Significant

Table 6.6: Indirect impact of Innovation on F and NF

Parameter (AxB)	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P	Results
TN --> OOG --> NF	.001	-.003	.009	.695	Non-Significant
TN --> OOG --> F	.001	-.006	.013	.672	Non-Significant
TN --> QMC --> NF	.011	-.007	.041	.345	Non-Significant
TN --> QMC --> F	.024	-.004	.104	.160	Non-Significant
AD --> OOG --> NF	.003	-.002	.020	.304	Non-Significant
AD --> OOG --> F	.006	-.001	.034	.195	Non-Significant
AD --> QMC --> NF	.048	.014	.132	.002	*** Significant
AD --> QMC --> F	.109	.039	.265	.000	*** Significant

Table 6.7: Indirect impact of OGQ on F and NF

Parameter	Estimate	Lower	Upper	P
OGQ --> MCQ --> AD	.008	.001	.026	.046
OGQ --> MCQ --> NF	.013	.002	.043	.050
OGQ --> MCQ --> F	.030	.007	.128	.012

Appendix 10: performance analysis tables for qualitative analysis

Table 6.1: Combination of financial and non-financial performance of Organic QM

Organic Q.M	Financial Impact		Non-Financial Impact on organisation's Performance					
	Multiple elements impact on finance		Customers perspective		Innovation and Learning Perspective		Internal business perspective	
Numbers	Participants	References	Participants	References	Participants	References	Participants	References
Top Management commitment	8	9	8	9	9	11	13	16
Employee suggestions	2	2	2	2	14	20	11	13
Group problem solving	5	5	1	2	8	8	14	15
Task Related training	4	6	0	0	12	17	13	16
Supplier QM	9	12	4	5	4	5	13	19
Customer Relationship	8	10	8	13	2	2	10	13
Social Responsibility	3	3	0	0	0	0	7	12
Political cultural context	5	7	3	3	2	2	9	18

Table 6.2: combination impact of Mechanistic QM on F and NF

Mechanistic QM	Financial Impact		Non-Financial Impact on organisation's Performance					
	Multiple elements impact on finance		Customers perspective		Innovation and Learning Perspective		Internal business perspective	
Numbers	Participants	References	Participants	References	Participants	References	Participants	References
Strategic Quality Planning	6	8	7	8	3	3	9	15
Preventive Maintenance	12	7	5	7	7	8	12	26
Housekeeping	13	7	7	7	0	0	14	18
Benchmarking	5	2	2	2	8	8	10	12
Quality Information	9	14	9	14	13	18	13	19
Process Management	7	8	6	8	11	13	13	17

Table 6.3: Combination impact on administrative innovation on F and NF

Administrative Innovation	Financial Impact		Non-Financial Impact on organisation's Performance					
	Multiple elements impact on finance		Customers perspective		Innovation and Learning Perspective		Internal business perspective	
Numbers	Participants	References	Participants	References	Participants	References	Participants	References
Internal organisational Innovation	4	9	3	5	11	14	14	38
Marketing Innovation	9	15	5	6	5	5	9	12
Strategic Innovation	7	13	6	6	7	9	12	25

Table 6.4: Combination impact on Technological innovation on F and NF

Technological Innovation	Financial Impact		Non-Financial Impact on organisation's Performance					
	Multiple elements impact on finance		Customers perspective		Innovation and Learning Perspective		Internal business perspective	
Numbers	Participants	References	Participants	References	Participants	References	Participants	References
Technological Process	5	8	2	2	6	7	12	20
Technological Products	4	4	1	1	3	3	9	12
Technological Technology	8	11	3	3	7	8	13	20

Figure 6.1: Alternative Conceptual Model for innovations impact on TQM

